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INTERNATIONAL UNION
OF PURE AND APPLIED PHYSICS

GENERAL INFORMATION

AND

REPORT
ON THE XIIIth GENERAL ASSEMBLY
(DUBROVNIK, 1969)

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I - ADMINISTRATION

The history of the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics is described in eight previous publications (documents IUPAP 1, 2, 4, 5, 7, 8, 10 and 14).

Essentially, the Union is composed of the National Physics Committees or groups of physicists in the various countries adhering to the Union (see center pages). Delegates from these committees meet in the General Assemblies of the Union which are held every three years. The General Assembly appoints the members of the Executive Committee, and various special committees, and nominates representatives on various interunion committees.

General Assemblies were held in Brussels (1923 and 1925), Paris (1931 and 1947), London (1934 and 1954), Amsterdam (1948), Copenhagen (1951), Rome (1957), Ottawa (1960), Warsaw (1963), Basle (1966), and Dubrovnik (1969). The Executive Committee usually meets once each year.

The Physics Union adheres to the International Council of Scientific Unions (I.C.S.U.). This Council is at present composed of 14 unions and more than 50 national members. The President of ICSU is Prof. V.A. Ambartsumian (USSR), and the Secretary-General is Prof. K. Chandrasekharan (India). The administrative office is in Rome (7 Via Cornelio Celso, Rome 00161, ITALY).

The General Assembly of ICSU consists of union representatives, together with national delegates. In the future, the Assembly will meet in alternate years.

In 1946, ICSU concluded an agreement with the United Nations Economic, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNES-

CO) which enables the Union to receive, through ICSU, special financial grants specifically to support international conferences. This important source of financial support enabled IUPAP to support about sixty conferences in the period 1966-1969.

The use of funds from UNESCO for conference expenses is subject to the following conditions:

- i) UNESCO may wish to send a representative to the meeting;
- ii) UNESCO would like mention of its support in all relevant publications. The following wording is suggested: "Published with the financial support of UNESCO";
- iii) UNESCO would like to receive ten copies of all conference reports.

Conferences and meetings of commissions are also supported from funds derived from the national members of IUPAP. These funds are also used to meet the administration expenses of the Union.

Correspondence concerning the general business of the Union and its various commissions should be sent to the Secretary-General.

Correspondence on financial questions and the payment of subscriptions from national committees should be sent to the Associate Secretary-General.

II – STATUTES

(adopted by the General Assembly of 1931 and modified by those of 1948, 1954, and 1960. The 1960 modifications are in italics).

I. Aims of the Union and Conditions of Membership

1. The aims of the Union are :
 - (i) the stimulation and promotion of international co-operation in Physics ;
 - (ii) the co-ordination of the work of preparing and publishing abstracts of papers and tables of physical constants ;
 - (iii) the promotion of international agreements on the use of symbols, units, nomenclature, and standards ;
 - (iv) the encouragement of interesting research.

The Union may organize international meetings.

Individual nations may join the Union through their National Academies, their National Research Councils, equivalent national societies or groups of societies, or, if suitable ones do not exist, through their Governments.

Membership of a given nation through several distinct organizations is not permitted, unless these several organizations have previously agreed to share Union dues and voting rights.

The word “nation” includes dominions, diplomatic protectorates, or other territories which have an independent scientific community.

II. National Committees

2. The body responsible for initiating its country's membership in the Union will set up a National Committee, which will maintain liaison with the Union.

3. The National Committees will, in their respective countries, encourage and co-ordinate study in various fields of Physics, with emphasis on international aspects. Every National Committee may, of itself or in collaboration with other National Committees, submit to the Union for discussion problems which are within its competence.

The National Committee elect their delegates to Union assemblies. They also elect a Delegation Head who votes on the delegation's behalf on questions of administration as laid down in Articles 14 and 16.

III. Administration of the Union

4. The work of the Union is directed by the General Assembly of delegates.

5. *The Executive Committee of the Union comprises: the President, the Past President, the first Vice-President, the Vice-Presidents, and the Secretary-General. With the exception of the Past-President, the members of the Executive Committee are elected by the General Assembly; they remain in office up to the end of the ordinary General Assembly following their election. The first Vice-President replaces the President if the latter is unable to officiate.*

With the exception of the Secretary-General, the elected members of the Executive Committee may not continually occupy the same office for more than two intervals between ordinary General Assemblies.

The Executive Committee may appoint members to vacancies which may occur in the Committee. Members named in this fashion will complete the term of the member whom they are replacing.

There is also set up an *administrative office* under the direction of the Secretary-General of the Union. This office deals with Union correspondence, administers Union funds, maintains archives, and organizes the preparation and distribution of those publications approved by the General Assembly.

IV. Commissions

6. The General Assembly and, subject to the approval of the next General Assembly, the Executive Committee may set up commissions pertinent to the work of the Union and may also decide to participate in joint commissions together with one or more other unions.

Union commissions include *affiliated commissions* whose activities concern certain wide fields of Physics, and *specialized commissions* which concern themselves with more specialized subjects.

Each commission must submit, through its Secretary, a report of its work to each General Assembly.

7. The constitution, statutes, activities, and financial statements of affiliated commissions must be submitted for approval to the Executive Committee of the Union. The latter has the particular responsibility of seeing that the commission's field of interest be well defined.

The Executive Committee delegates one or more of its members to represent the Union on each affiliated commission.

Affiliated commissions may, in addition to funds voted to them by the Union, collect special dues and receive grants from other sources.

8. The members of specialized commissions and the delegates of the Union to joint commissions are elected by the General Assembly which takes into consideration the suggestions of the Executive Committee. These members and delegates remain in office up to the end of the next General Assembly, and are eligible for re-election.

Specialized commissions may add members to their number subject to the approval of the Executive Committee.

The designation of members of affiliated commissions other than those delegates of the Executive Committee of the Union provided for under Article 7, is determined by the statutes of each commission.

Activities of joint commissions are governed by the International Council of Scientific Unions.

V. General Assemblies

9. Ordinary General Assemblies of the Union are held, in principle, every three years. If the date and site of a meeting have not been decided by the previous General Assembly, they are set by the Executive Committee and announced, at least four months in advance, to all members and affiliates.

10. In special cases, the President may, with the approval of the Executive Committee, convene an extraordinary General Assembly ; he is obliged to do so at the request of one-third of the votes of member nations.

11. All members of National Committees may attend the meetings of the General Assembly and take part in the deliberations. However, they may not vote.

The President of the Union may invite scientists who are not delegates to attend meetings of the General Assembly as consultants.

Members of affiliated commissions mentioned in Article 7 who are not delegates to the General Assembly may nevertheless take part in meetings of the General Assembly when matters concerning their commission are discussed. However, they may not vote.

12. The Agenda of Meetings is determined by the Executive Committee and issued at least four months before the opening of the Meeting. Subjects not on the Agenda may not be debated at the Assembly without the consent of half of the votes of nations represented at the Assembly.

VI. International Congresses

13. International Congresses are organized by the Executive Committee of the Union.

VII. Budget and Voting Rights

14. The Executive Committee will draft a budget estimate for each year for the period between sessions of the General Assembly. A financial commission, set up by the General Assembly, is appointed to examine each year the financial statement of the preceeding year, and to study the draft budget for the next. It prepares separate reports on these two matters for submission to the General Assembly.

Following consideration of these reports, the General Assembly sets the value of one share of Union dues *. Members' annual dues are then determined by the number of shares of each country. This number is determined by the Executive Committee which takes into account the suggestions of the country's National Committee, and may subsequently be modified by agreement between the Executive Committee and the said National Committee.

The establishment or modification of the number of shares assigned to a country must be ratified by the next General Assembly.

The number of official delegates (and votes) is fixed according to the following scale :

Number of shares : 1, 2 or 3, 4 to 6, 7 to 9, 10 and more

Number of official
delegates (and votes) : 1, 2, 3, 4, 5

The Academy or other group responsible for a country's membership in IUPAP is also responsible for the payment of annual dues.

15. All dues which the Union receives from its member countries must be used :

(i) to pay for the cost of publications and incidental administrative expenses ;

(ii) to carry out the aims outlined in Article 1.

*One share was fixed at U.S. \$300. from January 1st 1971.

Gifts received by the Union must be used in accordance with the wishes of the donors.

Any country withdrawing from the Union forfeits its rights to Union assets.

16. In the course of General Assemblies, motions concerning scientific questions are carried by a majority of votes of all delegates present.

Motions concerning the administration of the Union or motions of a mixed nature will be carried by a majority of votes cast by heads of National Delegations according to Article 14.

Any doubts as to the category of the motion will be decided by the President.

At the meetings of commissions, motions are decided by majority votes of delegates and not by countries.

In all cases of tied votes, the President will cast the deciding vote.

17. A member country whose delegation will not attend a given General Assembly but wishes to vote on an appropriate matter appearing on the Agenda may send its vote in writing to the President. To be valid, it must be received before the votes on that motion be counted.

VIII. By-Laws

18. The General Assembly may pass by-laws regulating the conduct of its work, the duties incumbent on the members of the Executive Committee, or, in general, anything not provided by these statutes.

Each commission may also set up by-laws governing its own activities. Such by-laws may not however contravene the Union's statutes.

IX. Duration of the Union and Modification of its Statutes

19. The life of the Union is not limited.

20. No change may be made in the present statutes without the approval of two-thirds of the votes of member countries.

21. In the event of the dissolution of the Union by a vote of the General Assembly receiving a majority of two-thirds of the votes of the member countries, its assets will be allocated by the General Assembly to one or more scientific organizations.

22. In the case of discussion as to the interpretation of the articles of the Statutes, the French text will be used exclusively.

III — Minutes of the XIIIth General Assembly Dubrovnik, Yugoslavia, September 1969.

The Assembly met at Trade Union Hall in the old city of Dubrovnik on Thursday, Friday, and Saturday, 11-13 September 1969. The President, Prof. D. I. Blokhintsev, was in the Chair for all sessions.

About 120 delegates had registered for the General Assembly. The list, by country, is given in Appendix V.

The S.U.N. Commission had held meetings in Dubrovnik prior to the General Assembly.

Arrangements for the meetings were organized by the Yugoslav National Committee for Physics, under the direction of Prof. Dr. A. Milojevic. Comfortable facilities for the Assembly had been provided in the picturesque old city of Dubrovnik. Between sessions, delegates had the opportunity to hear an excellent lecture by Prof. N. Kurti of the Clarendon Laboratory of Oxford, as well as a remarkable guitar concert given by Dr. J. Jovicic of the University of Belgrade. Arrangements had also been made for delegates to attend a dinner and an excursion to Kotar and St. Stefan if they so desired. A ladies' programme had also been arranged.

THE FIRST SESSION, Thursday, September 11th, 1969

10:00 a.m.

1 — The President of the Yugoslav National Committee for Physics, Prof. Dr. A. Milojevic, welcomed the delegates to Dubrovnik. Mentioning the coming 50th anniversary of the Union, he pointed out its coincidence with the development of Physics in Yugoslavia; he related the contribution that several scientists such as Professor Boskovic from Dubrovnik itself had made to Physics over the centuries, and expressed the conviction that delegates would find much to interest them in various spheres during their visit.

II – President Blokhintsev thanked Prof. Milojevic for his remarks and for having arranged the programme which the delegates were enjoying. The Secretary-General, Prof. C. C. Butler, then outlined the programme of business which lay before the General Assembly.

III – New Members :

The Secretary-General announced the request of Cuba to join IUPAP. This has been agreed to by the Executive Committee and, in accordance with the Statutes, was presented for ratification to the General Assembly. Cuba would hold 1 share. The Assembly agreed unanimously to the admission of Cuba.

The Secretary-General then submitted the request for membership by South Korea. Its application was recommended by the Executive Committee. The Assembly unanimously agreed that South Korea be admitted. South Korea would hold 1 share.

IV – Agenda :

The Secretary-General submitted the agenda for approval. This was unanimously accepted. He invited commissions and national delegates to submit texts of resolutions which they wish to propose so that they might be circulated to delegates.

V – Secretary-General's report :

The Secretary-General submitted a brief report. The routine but important business of the Union had been carried out, mostly by the Commissions. There had been four Executive meetings, and the Secretariat had distributed considerably more publicity and information about the Union (its book of general information, its News-Bulletin, trimestrial Newsheet, as well as articles in the Australian Journal of Physics and Physics Today). He reported that the financial position of the Union was good, that its annual reports had been audited and would be discussed later. The Secretary-General emphasized the importance of the elections to be held at the third session, and explained the nature of the slate of nominees that was being circulated to the delegates. He explained the possibility of further nominations from the floor and the voting procedure that would be followed.

VI – Commissions' reports :

The various international commissions then submitted reports of their work since the General Assembly at Basle in 1966. In Appendix II will be found a summary of these reports. Specific resolutions proposed by commissions were deferred until the second session of the Assembly. Particular points raised by various commissions were :

1. *Finance Commission* : See item X.

2. *SUN Commission* :

The report was presented by the Secretary, Prof. J. deBoer ; he mentioned the adoption of the new unit the "Pascal" (Newtons/m²) and the adoption of "K" as the symbol for absolute temperature degrees. An exchange took place between Prof. deBoer and Dr. G. Herzberg of Canada concerning the opportunity of certain SUN recommendations such as the dropping of the circle index before the absolute temperature symbol K. Prof. deBoer stated that the best circles had been consulted on the matter. He also reported that having served as secretary of the International Commission since 1948, he had submitted his resignation. The Assembly warmly applauded Prof. deBoer in recognition of his valuable work on behalf of the Union.

3. *Thermodynamics and Statistical Mechanics* :

The report was presented by Prof. P. Mazur. In addition to commenting on international conferences, Prof. Mazur reported that the President of the Commission, Dr. Kubo, has submitted his resignation.

4. *Cosmic Rays* :

The report was presented by Prof. Wilson. Concerning international conferences, he mentioned that the Commission was tending to a policy of one major conference every three years. The Commission still considered that an international conference lasting ten days was necessary in its particular field. This particular view had not been mentioned in the report submitted. He also

mentioned the useful tradition of the Commission's maintaining a library of reports and pertinent documents operating during the 10 days of its international conferences.

5. *Low Temperature* :

The report was presented by Prof. Allen. He mentioned that the Commission intended to freeze its cycle at three years and hoped that this might be synchronized with similar cycles of the Magnetism and Semiconductors Commissions. He also described the nature of the Fritz-London Award administered by the Very Low Temperature Commission. This was the most prestigious international award in this field and was now subsidized by the I.B.M. Company. The Assembly delegates indicated their gratification at this Union sponsored award.

6. *Publications* :

The report was presented by Dr. Stickland. Miss Stickland pointed out that a meeting of the editors of Physics journals had decided that there was no need for an association of such editors inasmuch as the International Commission could play the useful role of such an association.

7. *Acoustics* :

The report was presented by Prof. Malecki. He emphasized the importance of the Acoustics Commission collaborating with other unions and associations since the subject had ramifications in the biological and even sociological spheres. The Commission expected to play an important role in the current study being undertaken on the general theme of man and his environment. It was widely recognized that noise was a form of pollution of the environment which must be as rigourously controlled as other types of pollution.

8. *Semiconductors* :

The report was presented by the Secretary. Prof. Mitchell considered it useful to redefine for the delegates the scope of the Semiconductors Commission. Its field excluded such topics

as alkali halides, etc. (Solid State); mechanical problems (Solid State); magnetism (Magnetism Commission); but included problems of materials having bound gaps of from a few electron-volts to about 0 electron-volt (excluding metals). He mentioned that the Commission considered a two-year sequence of meetings most useful for its purposes. Dr. Brattain was retiring as President of the Commission; all were very grateful to him for the work he had accomplished.

Dr. Boas of the Solid State Commission exchanged views with Prof. Mitchell on the possible joint sponsorship of certain conferences which bordered on the fields of interest of the two Commissions.

9. *Magnetism* :

The report was presented by Prof. Marshall. The Commission agreed to the synchronisation of a three-year cycle with that of the Very Low Temperature Commission.

10. *Solid State* :

The report was presented by Dr. Boas. He explained the nature of the work of the Commission which resulted in a rather large number of international conference.

11. *High Energy Nuclear Physics* :

The report was presented by Prof. Lanius. He mentioned the Commission's conference policy which tended to recommend one very large conference per three-year cycle, and several small topical conferences.

12. *Low Energy Nuclear Physics* :

The report was presented by Prof. Huber. He expressed the great regret of the Commission at the recent death of Prof. Amos deShalit, and read a short eulogy about this distinguished physicist. (The Assembly rose and stood for a minute in silence to the memory of Prof. deShalit).

Prof. Huber discussed the conference policy of the Commission which seeks to reduce the number of conferences. He

raised the question of the visa problem which, although greatly reduced, still occurred. A case in point was the refusal of a visa to Prof. deShalit to attend a recent international conference in the USSR. Suggested action is contained in the body of his report. Prof. Huber also expressed his Commission's concern over the fact that the organizers of some conferences made the buying of the conference's abstracts compulsory.

13. *Atomic Masses and Related Constants :*

The report was presented by Prof. Duckworth. He mentioned the improvement in the least squared values based on ^{12}C which had been obtained since 1966. Following the second adjustment of the initial values which had appeared in 1964-65, a third adjustment or "1969 Atom Mass Standards" would appear shortly in the review "Nuclear Data". Concerning fundamental constants, the last critical review had been in 1963 with some additions in 1965 and in 1967. It now appeared that there were errors as large as 100 parts in 10^6 which appear in such fundamental constants as e, h, etc.

An exchange took place between Prof. Duckworth and Prof. Terrien (France) concerning possible overlap between the 4th International Conference on Atomic Masses and Related Constants and the proposed National Bureau of Standards Meeting. It was pointed out that the latter meeting sought to emphasize to young physicists that precision measurements now always involve fundamental constants, and therefore were of renewed interest.

14. *Physics Education :*

The report was presented by Prof. Staub. Prof. Staub mentioned the great interest that Prof. deShalit had had in the Physics Education Commission work. He gave notice of a resolution to be presented concerning teaching and research.

15. *Atomic and Molecular Physics and Spectroscopy :*

The report was presented by Dr. Herzberg. He mentioned the support of the Commission for the proposed new Plasma Commission.

VII – International Commission for Optics :

The report was presented by Prof. Toraldo. He explained the special nature of I.C.O. which, as an affiliated commission, now had national committees in 17 countries. In fact, the only country making a major contribution to the study of Optics which was not a member of I.C.O. was the USSR. He reported that they were in excellent financial circumstances, and tabled a booklet recently prepared on the nature and work of I.C.O.

VIII – Miscellaneous Commissions :

The Secretary-General reported on the activities of the various interunion and other commissions and committees. A summary of the reports received is to be found in Appendix II. In particular, the Secretary-General noted :

1. *Joint Commission on Applied Radioactivity :*
Following the recommendation of IUPAP, ICSU had now abolished this Joint Commission.
2. *Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research (SCOR):*
Report tabled.
3. *Special Commission for Space Research (COSPAR):*
No report had been received to date.
4. *International Geophysical Commission (CIG):*
This Commission had now been wound up. However there continued the former CIG's Upper Mantle Committee whose report was tabled.
5. *ICSU Abstracting Board :*
No report had been received as yet.
6. *Atmospheric Sciences Commission :*
No report had been received as yet.
7. *ICSU Committee on Data for Science and Technology (CODATA) :*
The report was tabled. Sir Gordon Sutherland reported in addition that CODATA would soon publish a compendium

of sources of data on pure substances. Four countries had joined the six original members of CODATA.

8. *ICSU Spectroscopy Commission :*

No report had been received as yet.

9. *IUPAC Polymer Commission :*

No report had been received. However, IUPAC was being re-organized and had accepted Dr. Wolf as IUPAP representative on this Commission.

10. *ICSU Solar-Terrestrial Physics Commission.:*

Report was tabled.

IX – ICSU Matters :

President Blokhintsev reported on IUPAP's relations with ICSU. He had found that the General Assembly of ICSU in Paris had devoted much time to the discussion of finances and relatively less to the discussion of scientific matters. His own request to ICSU for an increase in their financial allotment to IUPAP as the result of the increase in Physics activity over the past decade had been sympathically received. (Note : in 1969, ICSU increased its grant to IUPAP from \$13,125 to \$16,125.).

Brief discussion on ICSU relations ensued. Prof. Robson (Canada) requested information concerning ICSU's activities on Symbols, Units, and Nomenclature. Secretary-General Butler informed the delegates that ICSU had no such commission of its own, but that IUPAP's SUN Commission collaborated with other unions such as IUPAC directly, as well as with organizations outside of ICSU, such as ISO.

THE SECOND SESSION, Friday, September 12th, 1969

10:00 a.m.

X – Report of the Financial Commission :

Sir Gordon Sutherland, President of the Commission, reported that Prof. deBoer and he had examined the audited

reports of the Union each year since 1966, and that the consolidation of these three reports could be found in the literature distributed to delegates. Prof. deBoer and he had found the Union finances in general to be in good order.

Financial Position :

The Associate Secretary-General reviewed the financial position of the Union. Its current operating budget was about \$55,000. per year while its reserve account had slowly built up to about \$45,000., not quite one year's operating cost. Since the last increase in the unit fee in 1966, the cost of living increases had eaten considerably into the Union's ability to support international conferences on a suitable scale. He reminded the delegates that several commissions in their reports had insisted on the need for increased financial support for such international conferences.

The Executive's decision to request the General Assembly to raise the unit fee from \$250 to \$300 US had been circulated to all national Committees. Only a minority of these had indicated their position on the matter, but this minority was heavily in favor of the move. Prof. Dobrotin of the Soviet Union explained in detail the arrangements made in his country when an international conference was held there. He pointed out that on the one hand the cost of such conferences was greatly in excess of any financial aid that IUPAP bring to it, and that on the other hand it was very difficult for some countries to obtain convertible currency to pay the increasing dues of the numerous international unions. His delegation therefore did not propose to support the proposition. President Blokhintsev called for a straw vote to indicate the feeling of the Assembly on the matter. A show of hands indicated that of the 86 votes present, 8 were against the motion (USSR, East Germany); 18 abstained and 60 were in favor. In view of this indication, the Assembly agreed that a formal ballot was not necessary, and President Blokhintsev declared the motion passed.

To wit : that the increase in the unit fee to the Union be raised from US \$250. to US \$300. effective in 1971.

XI – Recommendations of Commissions :

Several commissions proposed resolutions to the General Assembly. These were briefly discussed at the second session, and then reconsidered at the third session. The results of both deliberations are considered here.

a) *Physics Education* :

Reading was given of a resolution concerning teaching and research. This resolution was modeled on that adopted by I.U.B.S. in 1967 and sought to discourage the tendency to divorce teaching and research activities in the universities. Sir Gordon Sutherland objected to the clause concerning mentors to advanced students. He felt that recognition of this activity as formal teaching might be used as an excuse to further dissociate research directors from undergraduate teaching. Dr. Havens of the US delegation pointed out the need for giving greater recognition to those physicists who act as reviewers and render the work of advanced research more accessible to non-specialists and students. At the third session, the following resolution was unanimously adopted :

Considering that :

1. advances in the rapidly growing fields of pure and applied physics not only deepen mankind's understanding of the universe, but through their applications have profound implications for human welfare and destiny ;
2. discoveries in Physics, the most basic of the natural sciences, strongly affect all of the basic and applied sciences and the professions related to them ;
3. the teaching of Physics to advanced students of Physics, to students in related scientific and professional fields, and to those who will become part of an enlightened citizenry can only be done well by those who are themselves active in creating or in using new knowledge ; and
4. research reaches its culmination in the communication of new knowledge to others, and employers should re-

cognize the importance of evaluation and synthesis of existing knowledge which often require depth of insight and creativity at least as great as primary research,

the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics resolves that :

1. research and education be carried on in the closest possible association ;
2. any tendencies toward divergence between the activities of advancing and of disseminating knowledge be vigorously counteracted and efforts to improve the teaching of Physics be encouraged ;
3. excellence in teaching and in the dissemination of knowledge about Physics should receive the same recognition as excellence in research. In this connexion, all sponsoring agencies and foundations should give financial support for the preparation of critical reviews of current developments and for the compilation of critical data ;
4. talented research workers be expected to teach, and their exemption from teaching occur only in special circumstances and not as a reward for excellence ;
5. teachers be encouraged to maintain their intellectual vitality and participation in the advancement of knowledge by being given time for research or for closely related scholarly activities ; and
6. research workers in Research Institutes and Industrial Laboratories should collaborate with Academic Institutions in the training and education of advanced students in Physics.

b) *Atomic and Molecular Physics and Spectroscopy Commission :*

Dr. Gerhard Herzberg of Canada presented a resolution aimed against the use of compulsion by editors of scientific journals

and directors of laboratories to induce authors of scientific papers to use a particular system of units or symbols. Commenting on this resolution, Prof. deBoer expressed the concern about the Union taking a stand concerning the prerogatives of laboratory directors. Prof. Kurti of the U.K. delegation did not wish the Union to become schizophrenic, setting up standards on the one hand and deploring the enforcing of them on the other hand. Prof. deBoer pointed out that freedom for authors should also entail freedom for editors. He pointed out that authors have the duty of presenting their work in intelligible way. Given time, the problem will no doubt solve itself. Dr. Wolfe of the US delegation agreed that editors also have the responsibility that published papers be understood, and therefore must encourage uniformity. Particularly must they insist on the recognized system of symbols for units. Prof. Toraldo of the Italian delegation reminded the Assembly that the Union should not enforce anything. However, it should show unity on this one. At the third session, the following modified resolution was passed unanimously :

“ that authors be encouraged to adopt the SI units for data in Physics journals as recommended by the SUN Commission, the Conférence générale des poids et mesures and the International Organization for Standardization and by other international unions closely related to Physics. Editors are urged to use persuasion rather than stronger measures to secure the cooperation of authors in the choice of symbols for physical quantities and of units but should require that standard symbols for units be used when the names of the units are written out in full ”.

XII – Recommendation of the Executive and National Committees :

The Executive and several of the National Committees proposed resolutions to the General Assembly. These were discussed in a preliminary fashion and then presented for final consideration at the third session. The results of both deliberations are summarized as follows :

a) **Executive :**

Liaison with the European Physical Society :

Secretary-General Butler pointed out that the European Physical Society wished to have a member of IUPAP on its Executive Committee. This person should be already a member of the European Physical Society. The Executive recommended Prof. Butler, the Secretary-General. The General Assembly gave unanimous agreement to this.

b) **Executive :**

Criteria for international conferences :

The Associate Secretary-General reported that, following submissions from several of the international commissions, the Executive had circulated proposed criteria for evaluating international conferences. These took into consideration the scientific value of the conference, the international character of the conference, and its organization.

Dr. Havens of the US delegation proposed as an amendment to the resolution the addition of a section whereby proposed conferences would be designated by categories : full meetings, topical conferences, and highly specialized conferences. Some discussion as to precise wording took place ; it being agreed to leave the editing to the Executive Committee.

At the third session, the amended resolution was adopted unanimously and will be found in Appendix III of this document.

c) **Canada :**

Concerning the SUN Commission :

Prof. Robson presented a resolution recommending that ICSU set up a SUN Commission. Prof. deBoer of the IUPAP SUN Commission pointed out that there was already very extensive liaison between IUPAP's Commission and other bodies in the field including those such as ISO which were

not connected with ICSU. He feared that the setting up of yet another commission would complicate matters unnecessarily. Dr. Kurti of the UK delegation said that his delegation would support the resolution if it implied the abolishing of the IUPAP Commission as well as similar commissions in other unions, so as to have only one overall inter-union commission. However, if the resolution implied that Union SUN Commission should remain, then his delegation would oppose the resolution. Prof. Robson stated that the intent of the resolution did not include abolishing the present Union SUN Commission.

At the third session, the Canadian delegation requested and was given permission to withdraw its resolution.

d) Poland :

Liaison between Commissions and National Committees :

Prof. Pal explained the need for greatly increased efforts to disseminate information from the Executive and from the International Commissions to physicists in general and National Committees of IUPAP, EPS and APS. His delegation proposed :

1. that IUPAP contact APS and EPS concerning a greater exchange of information, and
2. that each international commission send copies of all correspondence and documents to all national committees.

Prof. Kurti of the UK delegation and Secretary-General Butler pointed out that this would entail great difficulty for the international commissions' secretariats to get copies of all their correspondence into the hands of the national committees. On the other hand, Prof. Auger of France emphasized the need for administrators to be aware of information in science, giving the examples of UNESCO and OCDE. The General Assembly agreed with the need for information and greater liaison between physicists and other groups, but took no formal action on the resolution.

e) **United States :**

Names of Commissions :

Dr. Havens introduced a resolution whereby the name of the Low Energy Nuclear Physics Commission would be changed to that of the International Nuclear Physics Commission, and also whereby the name of the High Energy Nuclear Physics Commission would be changed to that of the International Commission on Particles and Fields.

The General Assembly adopted this resolution unanimously

XIII – New Commission :

The Secretary-General reviewed the history of the Atomic and Molecular Physics and Spectroscopy Commission. This had been set up at the General Assembly in Basle in 1966 with the expectancy that modifications would have to be made in its structure as the result of a three-year trial. The Commission had been set up in 1966 with three divisions : Spectroscopy, Atomic Collisions, and Plasmas. One of its mandates had been to contact the organizing group of the international conferences on ionized gases with a view to inviting them to collaborate with IUPAP. This has been done and the organizing committee of these international conferences (which were sponsored by IUPAP) had unanimously agreed to request the Union to form a Plasma Commission. The International Commission on Atomic and Molecular Physics and Spectroscopy, which had initiated this matter, had reviewed this recommendation and endorsed it. The Executive now proposed to the General Assembly that it proceed with the creation of the new International Commission on Plasma Physics. The General Assembly agreed to this unanimously.

THE THIRD SESSION, Saturday, September 13th, 1969

10:00 a.m.

President Blokhintsev presided the General Assembly and before resuming regular business, invited several delegates to address the Assembly.

Prof. Dobrotin of the Soviet delegation commented on the recent death of Prof. Powell, the discoverer of the π -meson. He requested the Assembly to pay tribute to the memory of Prof. Powell whereupon the Assembly stood in silence for a minute.

Prof. Allen made a moving tribute to the memory of Dr. Lewis Weil, a member of the Very Low Temperature Commission, who had recently past away. The Assembly rose to stand for a minute in silence in tribute to this indefatigable worker.

Prof. Auger of France rose on a question of privilege to inform the delegates that he would presently be meeting the Committee of UNESCO which was in turn charged with meeting the ministers of science of various countries. He would see that the teaching-research problem discussed previously be raised at this committee, and that the Union resolution be brought to their attention.

XIV – Conferences for 1970 :

The Secretary-General presented a list of conferences which the Executive recommended for Union sponsorship in 1970. To guide the discussion of delegates on the coming resolution concerning categories of conferences, proposed categories had been indicated on the list of conferences as an experiment (See XII b). He then reviewed the various proposed conferences dwelling in particular on those which had not been recommended by International Commissions. He also commented on the recent awarding of Union grants to conferences, a list of this distribution by commissions having been given to the delegates. After some further discussion, the list of conferences, as found in Appendix IV, was extended the patronage of the Union by the General Assembly.

XV – Elections :

The Secretary-General commented on the procedure to be followed. Any nominations for positions on the Executive and on International Commissions received during the summer both from National Committees and from Commissions had been incor-

porated in a complete list circulated to the delegates on their arrival in Dubrovnik. From this list, the Executive Committee had prepared a proposed slate which had also been distributed to the delegates. This slate was formerly proposed by the Executive but could be amended by resolutions from the floor.

Some such resolutions were received and, as a result, members of the Executive Committee and of the various international commissions were elected to office as per the list given in the center pages of this document (IUPAP 16). No formal vote was taken.

In the case of the Atomic and Molecular Physics and Spectroscopy Commission, only members of the Commission were named, and it was decided to request the advice of the Commission concerning the need for sub-divisions now that the Plasma Sub-Division had become an International Commission.

In the course of the elections, particular mention was made of Prof. Bacher succeeding to the presidency and of Prof. Maier-Leibnitz who was to become First Vice-President. Particular mention was also made of Prof. deBoer who, having rendered great service to the Union over a period of over 20 years, was resigning as secretary of the International Commission on Symbols, Units and Nomenclature.

XVI – Resolutions from Commissions :

See XI.

XVII – Resolutions from the Executive and National Delegations :

See XII.

XVIII – 1972 General Assembly :

Delegates were informed that invitations for the 1972 General Assembly had been received from Washington, U.S.A.; Madrid, Spain; Stockholm, Sweden; and East Germany.

These invitations were gratefully acknowledged by the General Assembly, which requested the Executive to take the final decision, at its meeting in 1970.

XIX – Other business :

Dr. Gerhard Herzberg of Canada rose to speak of the outstanding work of President Blokhintsev during his term of office. He had accomplished his task with much tact, care, and imagination, and lend great dignity to his position. Dr. Herzberg also mentioned that three of the vice-presidents were now completing their terms of office : Prof. M. Danysz, from Poland ; Prof. J.M. Jauch, from Switzerland ; and Sir Gordon Sutherland of the United Kingdom. They had all given much time and energy to the Union affairs and made a real contribution to our science. He also paid personal tribute to the extraordinary work of Prof. deBoer for the SUN Commission over so many years.

XX – Adjournment of the Assembly :

President Blokhintsev addressed the Assembly briefly. The text of President Blokhintsev's address is to be found in Appendix I.

The President then declared the Assembly adjourned.

Annexe I Appendix I

President Blokhintsev's final address to the General Assembly

As I leave the president's post I would like, first of all, to express my gratitude to the Secretary-General, Professor Clifford Butler, and to the Treasurer, Professor Larkin Kerwin, for their benevolent work for our Union during the last three years.

I am also much indebted to my colleagues, members of the Executive Committee, for their efficient activity.

Our Union has considerable experience and good traditions in international collaboration. It is a pleasure for me to note that we have succeeded in conserving these traditions during these years in our unquiet world.

Of course, the activity of the Union is a small contribution to the enormous efforts which peoples make to reach a better understanding of the unity of the goals of all humanity.

However, it is very important that these efforts be not weakened in any of the links.

Encouraging the development of Physics, the science which has made the people of our generation much more powerful, we would wish that this power would mean not only the growth of technical possibilities, but also the growth of social consciousness of humanity.

I am happy that it is just in my country that the idea of the international fraternity of peoples was enunciated 50 years ago.

In 1962, speaking at the Conference on High Energy Physics in Rochester, I compared the Earth with a small space ship with the difference that nobody knows from which cosmodrome it was launched and in what direction it is flying.

Is it not a real madness in such a situation to settle disagreement between peoples by using force and weapons ?

The cosmic era was opened by Yuri Gagarin's flight in 1961. Now we rejoice at the success of the men who stepped onto the surface of the Moon. It seems to me that the captain of the space ship Apollo-10, Frank Borman, was justly moved by the idea of the smallness of the Earth :

“ It is small enough to be covered with a finger-nail ”.

I am convinced that the development of cosmonautics and its applications will lead to a fundamental change in people's psychology and to a new level of understanding of the ideas of internationalism.

Therefore it would be extremely important for our Union to conserve, in this period, its traditions which till now have been expressed in an explicit aspiration to support the spirit of internationalism among physicists.

To Professor Bacher, my successor, I would like to extend sincere wishes for every success in leading our Union and furthering its activities.

Annexe II

Appendix II

Reports prepared by IUPAP Commissions and IUPAP Representatives on ICSU Organizations

(these reports have been edited in the Secretariat)

Specialized Commissions :

1. Financial Commission (no written report)
2. Commission for Symbols, Units and Nomenclature (SUN)
3. Commission on Thermodynamics and Statistical Mechanics
4. Cosmic Ray Commission
5. Very Low Temperature Commission
6. Publications Commission
7. Acoustics Commission
8. Semiconductors Commission
9. Magnetism Commission
10. Solid State Commission
11. High Energy Nuclear Physics Commission
12. Low Energy Nuclear Physics Commission
13. Commission on Atomic Masses and Related Constants
14. Commission on Physics Education
15. Commission on Atomic and Molecular Physics and Spectroscopy and Plasma Physics

Affiliated Commissions :

16. International Commission for Optics (ICO)

Some Commissions and Organizations on which IUPAP has representation :

SCOR
Upper Mantle Project
CODATA
CIG

1. **Financial Commission** (no written report)
2. **Commission for Symbols, Units and Nomenclature (SUN)**

A. *SUN Recommendations*

The document UIP 11 (Doc. SUN 65-3), of which 5000 copies were printed is now out of print. The National Committees obtained about 1200 copies and 200 copies were distributed amongst all committees of IUPAP. Free copies went to the members of all relevant committees of IEC, IUPAC, ISO/TC 12 and of the International Committee of Weights and Measures. About 200 copies went in bulk to about 25 universities and institutions and about 1500 copies were distributed free upon individual requests of 1 up to 5 copies each. As requests for further copies, in particular bulk requests are still received, 500 copies of the document have been reprinted by photo offset. About 400 copies are still available to cover the time needed to prepare a new edition.

The SUN Commission has not had any formal meeting in the period following the meeting in Basle in 1966, but correspondence and personal contact between the various members of the Commission have given ample opportunity to continue our work and to co-ordinate activities of IUPAP with those of other international organisations. A new list of recommended symbols for Solid State Physics and for Plasma Physics is in preparation. These will be sent for comments to the members of the relevant IUPAP Commissions. Other sections will be added and the whole document now urgently needs a critical revision in order to make it up to date. The SUN Commission will meet during the General Assembly of IUPAP in 1969, where the document UIP 11 will be reconsidered in view of the various new developments which have taken place since its publication in 1965.

Many of the SUN Commission's recent activities were concentrated on presenting the views of IUPAP in the collaboration with other international organisations. These are presented in subsequent sections.

B. *The ISO/TC 12-project*

The SUN Commission continued the collaboration with the Technical Committee 12 of the International Organisation for Standardisation : ISO/TC 12. The present status of the various sections of the ISO Recommendation R31, named "Quantities, Units, Symbols, Conversion Factors and Conversion Tables", is as follows :

ISO-R 31, I	I	Basic Quantities and Units
ISO-R 31, II	II	Periodic and Related Phenomena
ISO-R 31, III	III	Mechanics
ISO-R 31, IV	IV	Heat
ISO-R 31, V	V	Electricity and Magnetism
Draft ISO-Rec. 1778	VI	Radiation and Light
ISO-R 31, VII	VII	Acoustics
Draft ISO-Rec. 1777	VIII	Physical Chemistry and Molecular Physics
Draft ISO-Rec. 838	IX	Atomic and Nuclear Physics
Draft ISO-Rec. 839	X	Nuclear Reactions and Ionizing Radiations
ISO-R 31, XI	XI	Mathematical Signs and Symbols to be used in Physical Science and Technology
Draft Proposal	XIII	Rules for Rounding of Numbers
Draft Proposal	XIV	General Principles concerning Quantities, Units and Symbols
Draft Proposal	XV	Dimensionless Parameters
Draft Proposal	XVI	Procedures for Interconversion of Values
ISO-Rec.	XVII	General Rules for the use of SI-Units, their Multiples and Submultiples in the various Industries

Remarks: "ISO-R 31, I", etc. are accepted ISO-Recommendations of the Series R 31.

"Draft Proposals" are approved by a majority of the memberbodies of ISO/TC 12.

"Draft ISO-Recommendations" are approved by a majority and submitted for final approval to all memberbodies of ISO.

At the last meeting of the Advisory Panel with the Secretariat of ISO/TC 12 in Copenhagen (June 1968) the remarks received from the various member bodies of ISO and ISO/TC 12 on the various Drafts and new questions which have come up in the work were discussed. At this meeting and also on various occasions later on, much attention has been given to a Draft Proposal of ISO/TC 97 on "Abbreviations for Names of Units to be used in Systems with limited character Sets" e.g. in the case of information processing and use of computers when not all characters needed for making the unit indications unique (e.g. capital *and* lower case letters) are available. Developments in this field need much attention because they may influence the general practice in physics in an unfortunate way.

Sub-Committee 2 of ISO/TC 12 has finished its recommendations "General Rules for the Use of SI-Units, their multiples and submultiples in the various industries".

The importance of all these ISO-Recommendations lies in the fact that they usually have an important influence on the national recommendations, which find their way in education and industry. Therefore the SUN Commission considers its collaboration with ISO/TC 12 on an international level and the further completion of this project one of its most important tasks.

C. *International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC)*

Most of the activities of IEC, which are of interest for IUPAP took place in, or are co-ordinated by the "Working Group I" of Technical Committee 25 (Secretary: C.H. Page, N. B. S. Washington), which prepares recommendations for symbols for quantities. In the period of this report six meetings have been held: in London (November 1966), Den Haag (June 1967),

Praha (August 1967), Bad Nauheim (February 1968), Stockholm (November 1968) and Paris (March 1969), in which Mr. Stille always represented the SUN Commission. The working group has prepared a document containing rules for subscripts and a first list of recommended subscripts circulated in the SUN Commission (Doc. SUN 67-5/6). The discussions concentrated on symbols for time varying quantities, for singularities and distributions, for logarithmic measures and for the electric and magnetic constants.

D. Commission on Symbols, Terminology and Units (IUPAC)

The STU Commission (President : M. L. McGlashan, Exeter, England) of IUPAC keeps close contact with the SUN Commission. A regular exchange of documents and mutual representation at the meetings of both commissions is provided for. The IUPAC has completed in 1968 a new tentative version of the IUPAC Manual on Symbols and Terminology for Physicochemical Quantities and Units. This document is published in the IUPAC bulletin No. 32, Aug. 1968.

E. International Committee for Weights and Measures and Consultative Committee for Units

The International Committee for Weights and Measures (CIPM) acting for the "Conference Internationale des Poids et Mesures" of the international treaty, the "convention du mètre" has created a Consultative Committee for Units (CCU), which has to advise the CIPM on matters of units, symbols and nomenclature. In this CCU, active representatives of all international organisations working in this field are present together with interested physicists of the various national standardizing laboratories and other experts.

The first meeting of the CCU was held in April 1967 in the Bureau International des Poids et Mesures in Paris. Several members of the SUN Commission are also members of the CCU and were present at this meeting : Rudberg (representing SUN), Stille (representing the PTB), Terrien (director BIPM) and de Boer (president of CCU). The CCU made various recommend-

ations to the CIPM about the new definition of the second as a unit of time, about the wording of the definitions for the units of temperature and luminous intensity, and recommended the change of the name and symbol for unit of temperature into kelvin with symbol: K. The CCU also considered various requests to introduce new names for more or less complicated derived SI-units (such as Pascal for Newton per square meter), but no recommendations were made. As an alternative a proposal was studied to use the general symbol SI for *any* SI-unit. Finally the CCU recommended the introduction of the mole as a basic unit for quantity of matter to be added to the six other basic units of the International System.

The 13^{ème} *Conférence Générale des Poids et Mesures* in October 1967 accepted many of the proposals: in particular the name of the unit for thermodynamic temperature was changed into kelvin, symbol K, but the inclusion of the mole as an independent basic unit in the International System did not get sufficient support.

The *second meeting of the CCU* was held in June 1969 in Paris. The recommendation to the CIPM to introduce the mole as an additional basic unit of the International System of Units was reconfirmed: all relevant international organisations such as IUPAP, IUPAC and ISO/TC 12 have accepted the mole as a basic unit for many years and in particular the IUPAC representative (Prof. McGlashan) has stressed also very much the importance of the adoption on the mole by the next *Conférence Générale*. The CCU has recommended the CIPM to add the unit siemens, symbol S, to the list of SI units, this being a unit which from the beginning has been recommended and used by the IEC. An international inquiry has been made by ISO/TC 12 to investigate the feasibility of using the symbol SI for any SI-unit for which no special symbol exists, but which is too complicated to write out explicitly every time: the advantage would be that prefixes could be added such as in SI and kSI. The majority, however, was against such an abbreviated notation. In view of the urgent need for a special name for the unit of pressure of which prefixes can be added, the CCU recommended to CIPM the adoption of the pascal, symbol Pa.

The CCU also made new recommendation to the CIPM concerning those units which are incoherent with the SI-units but which have to be used together with the SI-units because of the fact that they are generally used and cannot be eliminated. These are the time units : minute (min), hour (h), day (d) ; the units of angles : second ("), minute ('), degree (°) ; the energy unit : electron volt (eV) ; and the units litre (l) and tonne (t). The CCU also recommended the CIPM to admit a number of other noncoherent units temporarily for use together with SI units. These were : angstrom (Å), seamile, knot, are (are), hectare (hare), barn (b), bar (bar), (normal) atmosphere (atm), gal (Gal), curie (Ci) and röntgen (R). The use of special names of C.G.S. units, such as erg, dyne, poise, stoker, gauss, oersted and maxwell was deprecated as well as the use of other units incoherent with the SI units.

July 1969.

3. Commission on Thermodynamics and Statistical Mechanics

The Commission met during the conferences in the summer of 1966 at Copenhagen, and in September 1968 in Kyoto. It also sponsored two conferences on Theoretical Physics and Biology, in July 1967 and July 1969.

Report on the International Conference "From Theoretical Physics to Biology":

This conference which took place in Versailles between June 30th and July 5th was attended by about 100 invited delegates from seventeen countries. They were theoretical and experimental physicists, mathematicians and various branches of biologists. Various sessions dealt with the following subjects :

- Order in physical systems
- Structure and maintenance of life
- Generation of biological molecules
- Structure of dissipative systems
- Mutation and evolution
- Information and biological systems.

Plenty of time was available for discussions and it appears that both physicists and biologists were greatly stimulated. The proceedings will be published in due course.

July 1969.

4. Cosmic Ray Commission

A. Meetings

The Commission met in Calgary in June 1967 and also in Budapest at the end of August 1969.

B. Conferences

The Tenth IUPAP Conference on Cosmic Rays was held at Calgary 19-30 June 1967 at the invitation of the National Research Council of Canada during Canada's Centennial Year. It was attended by participants from 24 countries, and fully attained the high effectiveness which has been a characteristic of this long standing series of conferences, of which the first took place in Cracow in 1947. The Eleventh Conference will take place in Budapest from 25 August to 4 September 1969 at the invitation of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences.

C. Conference Proceedings

The Proceedings of the Ninth (London) Conference were published in two volumes by the Institute of Physics and the Physical Society in May 1966; those of the Tenth (Calgary) Conference were published in two sections: invited and rapporteur papers were issued at an early date from original typescripts by the Organising Committee, the original contributions were published in May 1968, as supplementary issues of Volume 46 of the Canadian Journal of Physics.

D. Location of Future Conferences

At its meeting in Calgary the Commission noted difficulties of timing which have arisen because the location of a coming conference in the series has in the past been formally designated only at the time of the previous conference, that is to say with two years' notice, more or less. It resolved that it would be more appropriate were conferences to be designated four years ahead. Preliminary steps to secure this position were taken and the proposal will be taken further at the meeting in Budapest.

E. *Finance of Conferences*

A request under this heading of a general rather than specific nature may come forward after the meeting of the commission in Budapest.

F. *Nature and Effectiveness of the Biennial Conferences*

Discussions at the Calgary meeting on this topic lead the Commission to reaffirm the view that this series of conferences with a limited number of participants offered the effective normal procedure for maintaining a general consensus of the development of the subject and the significance of its major points of growth. The Commission did not plan to support other conferences.

However, the appropriate duration and organisation of these conferences was a matter which the Commission thought in need of discussion, and the Secretary was asked to secure and to summarise the views of a representative group of regular participants. This was done, and the summary circulated to members of the Commission.

July 1969.

5. **Very Low Temperature Commission**

A. Membership of the Commission with dates of initial appointment is as follows:

J. F. Allen (Chairman)	Great Britain	1960
J. Bardeen (Secretary)	USA	1963
N. E. Alekseevskii	USSR	1966
*W. Buckel	W. Germany	1966
*N. Kurti	Great Britain	1963
*J. L. Olsen	Switzerland	1963
S. Safrata	Czechoslovakia	1966
T. Sugawara	Japan	1966
K. W. Taconis	Netherlands	1966
§L. Weil	France	1963
*Corresponding Members	§ Deceased, 1968.	

- B. The main purpose of the Commission is to help plan and sponsor a series of conferences on low temperature physics. The tenth of the series, LT-10, was held in Moscow, 31 August – 6 September 1966. The next, LT-11, was held at St. Andrews, Scotland, 21 August – 28 August 1968. It is planned to hold LT-12 in Kyoto, Japan, 4 September – 10 September 1970.
- C. Proceedings of the Moscow conference, LT-10 were published in a series of four volumes by Viniti, Moscow, 1967. Proceedings of LT-11 were published by the Organising Committee and printed by the St. Andrew Printing Department in two volumes, edited by J. F. Allen, D. M. Finlayson and D. M. McCall.
- D. Two satellite conferences were held in connection with LT-11 and sponsored by IUPAP. One on "A. C. Properties and Applications of Superconductors" was held at the School of Engineering Science, University of Warwick, England, August 1968, with Professor R. G. Rhodes as Secretary. A second, "Electron Mean Free Paths in Metals", was held at the Institut für Kalorische Apparate und Kältetechnike, Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule, Zurich, 3-4 September 1968, with Professor J. L. Olsen as Secretary.
- E. A meeting of the VLT Commission was held at St. Andrews, 24 August 1968. Recommendations for action at the General Assembly at Dubrownik 11-13 September 1969, will be summarized later in this report.
- F. A conference on the Science of Superconductivity is to be held at Stanford University, Stanford, California, 26-29 August 1969. It is being sponsored by IUPAP, by Stanford University, and by the United States Air Force Office of Scientific Research. Co-chairmen are T. Geballe and W. Fairbank of Stanford University. Secretary is W. Goree, Stanford Research Institute. An attendance of about 400 is expected. Proceedings will be published by the North-Holland Publishing Company.

- G. Plans have been announced in the scientific press for LT-12 to be held in Kyoto, Japan, 4-10 September 1970. The conference will be sponsored by the Japan Science Council and the Physical Society of Japan as well as by IUPAP. Information : T. Sugawara, Institute for Solid State Physics, University of Tokyo, 7-21-1 Roppongi, Minato-ku, Tokyo, Japan.
- H. Tentative plans have been made for a satellite conference to LT-12 on Transport Properties of Solids, to be held at the University of Sydney, Australia, 27-29 August, 1970. Sponsors are the Australian Institute of Physics with support from CSIRO Division of Pure and Applied Physics : Information : G. K. White, CSIRO Division of Physics, Sydney University Grounds, Chippendale NSW 2008, Australia.
- I. At its 24 August 1968 meeting the Commission discussed possible sites for LT-13 in 1972. The West Coast of the U.S.A. or Canada was favoured by the majority and inquiries have been made regarding the University of California, San Diego, at La Jolla, and Simon Frazer University in British Columbia. An invitation has been received for Grenoble, France. A decision will be made by the VLT Commission in 1970.
- J. The Commission favours going to a three-year cycle of LT Conferences after 1972, and to coordinate with the Magnetism and Semiconductor Conferences so that one would be given each year in the cycle. A Magnetism Conference has been scheduled for 1973, so that the Semiconductor Conference could fit into the cycle by meeting in 1974 and the Low Temperature Conference in 1975. An invitation has been received from the University of Helsinki for 1975.
- K. In order to coordinate activities of the VLT Commission with international bodies in related areas, N. Kurti was appointed to serve as liaison with Commission 1 of the International Institute of Refrigeration and S. Safrata was appointed to serve as liaison with the Board of the Cryogenic Engineering Conference.

- L. An important feature of LT Conferences in recent years has been the presentation of the Fritz London award for distinguished work in Low Temperature Physics. The VLT Commission requests that the General Assembly give suitable recognition to the international status of the award and its association with the VLT Commission.

August 1969.

6. Publications Commission

The Publications Commission has met twice since the General Assembly in 1966, and much useful work has also been accomplished between meetings. There are no specific recommendations to the 1969 General Assembly, but the following matters of interest are reported.

A. *Standardization of Journal Style*

1.1 *Guide for the Preparation of Scientific Papers for Publication.*

Guide for the Preparation of Author's Abstracts for Publication.

At the 1966 General Assembly, the redrafting of the original UNESCO Guides for the preparation of scientific papers and abstracts was approved subject to final modifications to satisfy the requirements of UNESCO. This was achieved early in 1967 and the Guides have now been widely circulated by UNESCO, in six different languages; members of the Publications Commission arranged for them to be published in a number of national physics journals, and they were reproduced in the IUPAP Report of the XIIth General Assembly.

1.2 *Journal Title Abbreviations*

The International Standards Organisation (ISO) is in process of agreeing a new Standard for journal title abbreviations compiled by coordination of the US and UK standards.

B. *Conference of Editors of Primary Journals in Physics*

At the suggestion of, and with financial support from UNESCO a meeting of editors of physics journals was held in May 1967. There was an attendance of about 40, from 9 countries; two commercial publishing houses were represented.

The major subjects discussed were the Guides for preparation of scientific material (see 1.1 above), the essential function of the referee of the scientific paper; the dangers of the proliferation of pre-print exchange; the development of mechanised information systems; the value of cooperation of editors of primary journals with the abstracting journals; the feasibility of setting up an association of editors of primary journals in physics, either international or regional (e.g. European, Latin American, etc.).

On this latter point, the conference considered that the Publications Commission itself could well be the basis of such an association and it was agreed to develop this aspect by the institution of a news letter.

C. *IUPAP Publications Commission News Letter*

A Publications Commission News Letter has been started and the first issue appeared in August 1968. It contained items of interest such as those included in this report, and a comprehensive list of names and addresses of editors of some 200 physics journals, which has been found most useful. The next issue should be ready shortly.

D. *Liaison with European Physical Society*

The formation of the European Physical Society was welcomed and the Commission noted with interest that its publications policy had as its primary aim the rationalisation of physics journals. The Commission agreed the following resolution:

“We welcome the establishment of the European Physical Society and hope for close liaison with it through Professor B. R. Coles.”

August 1969.

7. Acoustics Commission

A. *Composition of the Commission*

Chairman	I. Malecki (Poland)
Secretary	F. Ingerslev (Denmark)
Members	L.M. Brehkovskih (USSR) J. Frenkiel (Belgium) R. Lindsay (USA) Yu Saneyoshi (Japan) D. Sette (Italy) E. Zwiker (W. Germany)
Corresponding Members	F. Kolner (Czechoslovakia) R. Lehmann (France) D.W. Robinson (UK) T. Tarnoczy (Hungary)

There were no changes in the composition of the Commission during the last term of office. All the Members have taken an active part in its work.

B. *Meetings of the Commission*

Four meetings of the Commission were held : 12-13 September 1967 (Warsaw), 22 and 27 August 1968 (Tokyo) and 26-27 May 1969 (Rome) and one joint meeting of ICA with the representatives of acoustical societies 24 August 1968 (Tokyo). A considerable number of matters has been settled and arranged by correspondence. Apart from that, members of ICA took part in a number of international congresses and symposia and particularly in the standardisation works which have been carried out within the framework of ISO-TC 43 and IEC-TC 29.

C. *The Sixth International Congress of Acoustics*

The Sixth ICA Congress was the most important event during the current term of office. The Congress was held from 21 to 28 August 1968 in Tokyo. The Congress included the Symposium on Acoustoelectronics (Sondai, 19-20 August 1968) and Speech Symposium (Kyoto, 29-31 August 1968). The Congress was at-

tended by 712 participants from 19 countries and 124 family members, 843 persons in all. The debates of the Congress covered plenary sessions at which 8 reports were presented, and work in 13 sections. 424 papers were submitted at the section meetings. Additional meetings of specialists in various fields with representatives of the Japanese industry were held in the evenings. A technical exhibition gave a review of the new achievements in equipment and electroacoustic devices. Technical excursions were a valuable supplement in the Congress. The total cost of organising the Congress amounted to about US \$65,000 — 60% covered by Japanese enterprises and 12% from the reserve fund of the Acoustical Society of Japan. The remaining part was obtained from the registration fee and ICA contribution. The President of the Congress was Prof. Yu Saneyoshi, President of the Acoustical Society of Japan ; Chairman of the Executive Committee — Prof. K. Awaya ; Secretary-General — Prof. J. Igarashi.

It is worth emphasizing the excellent organization of the Congress and great contribution of the Japanese hosts to its arrangement. The abstract of the papers were circulated among the participants before the Congress ; upon arrival the participants received proceedings including full texts of the papers of about 2000 pages. The proceedings are now available for sale in book stores through Elsevier and Co.

For two years prior to the Congress the ICA was in close contact with the Organizing Committee giving advice in many essential scientific matters and those concerned with the arrangements to the Congress.

D. Preparations for Future ICA Congresses

In the activities of ICA, particular attention has been drawn to the philosophy of acoustical congresses, whose size and range of problems has been constantly increasing. Various ideas for raising the efficiency of the congresses have been put forward. Future congresses will provide an opportunity for testing these new ideas.

ICA has discussed the organization and scientific programme of the 7th Acoustical Congress, which is to be held in Budapest in 1971. The main sponsor of the Congress will be the Hungarian

Academy of Sciences. ICA has carried some negotiations dealing with the future congresses, and took part in setting up the organizing committee for the 8th Acoustical Congress planned to be held in London under the auspices of the Royal Society in 1974.

E. *Symposia and other events*

The number of international events in the field of acoustics has been constantly growing. Since there is some overlapping of meetings, ICA has taken some steps to co-ordinate them to some degree, or at least to inform all acoustics experts about them. The dates concerning acoustical meetings which were to be held in 1968-1969 had been collected and rendered accessible to the acoustic societies. At present, data on symposia and other international events to be held in 1970-1971 are being compiled.

F. *Co-operation with acoustical societies*

ICA has attached great importance to having close links with committees of acoustics effects all over the world. The first necessary step was obtaining data about the existing acoustical societies and of other forms of acoustical activities. In December 1967 ICA sent a questionnaire to 23 existing national and regional organizations throughout the world. Detailed replies have been received from 19 organizations. The information has provided a basis of a general quantitative appraisal and evaluation of the organizational development of acoustics, which was presented by the Chairman of ICA at the 6th Congress and was the beginning of establishing regular contacts with the societies.

On the occasion of the Congress in Tokyo a meeting of representatives of acoustical societies was held on the initiative of ICA. The meeting was attended by representatives of 18 organizations. Background papers prepared by ICA as a result of analyzing answers to a questionnaire were the basis of the discussion. Particular attention was devoted to forecasting acoustical developments and the best forms of its representation. It was agreed that the fragmentation of acoustics should be avoided ; it is rather necessary to aim at its integration and the co-operation of various branches of acoustics as an interdisciplinary field of science although basically connected with physics.

G. *The problem of an European Acoustical Society*

At the meetings in Tokyo, a group of acoustics experts made a proposal to set up an European Acoustical Society or association of acoustical societies and approached ICA for support. ICA being unauthorized to take any steps decided to act only as "a clearing house". In November 1968 ICA sent European acoustical societies a questionnaire asking what they think of establishing an European Acoustical Society. The majority of answers was positive though some reservations were expressed concerning the administrative arrangements. Opinions on the relations between the planned society and the European Physical Society varied. Replies to the questionnaire have been collected, summarized in abridged form and distributed to all the European societies. Further initiatives will depend on the societies themselves.

H. *Co-operation with other organizations*

Acoustics has some close connections with other scientific disciplines other than physics, and that is why, following the views shared by all the ICA Members, it was resolved that co-operation with other unions should be extended. After getting IUPAP's approval ICA approached three unions with proposals of co-operation : International Union of Theoretical and Applied Mechanics (IUTAM), International Union of Physiological Sciences (IUPS) and International Union of Biological Sciences (IUBS). All the unions mentioned above have accepted the initiative of ICA. IUTAM and IUPS have nominated their permanent representatives to ICA who took part as observers in the last ICA meeting. IUBS intends to discuss the nomination of its representatives to ICA at the forthcoming meeting of its Executive Committee. At the ICA meeting the possibilities and the scope of co-operation with the unions concerned were defined, and particularly the prospects in exchanging information about symposia and other international events arranged by the unions and concerned with acoustical problems, as well as co-operation in selecting the topics of world congresses. The co-operation in bio-acoustics and infrasounds is considered to be particularly promising.

Another problem is covered by the plans of co-operation between ICA and the research project "Man and his Environment" to be launched by UNESCO. The UN Economic Commission for Europe will be concerned with a part of that Project. Assuming that noise is one of the most important components of the environment of contemporary man, ICA supports the initiative of including the problem of noise in the above-mentioned project.

July 1969.

8. Semiconductors Commission

A. Membership

Dr. W.H. Brattain, U.S.A., Chairman (1957)
Professor E.W.J. Mitchell, U.K., Secretary (1963)
Professor G. Busch, Switzerland (1963). resigned 1968.
Dr. G.M. Hatoyama, Japan (1963)
Professor V.S. Vavilov, U.S.S.R. (1966)
Professor J. Bok, France (1966)
Dr. H. Welker, Fed. Germany (1966)

Corresponding members :

Dr. J. Tauc, Czechoslovakia
Professor L. Soshowski, Poland
Dr. J. Auth, D.D.R.

B. Conferences have been held in:

Kyoto	1966
Moscow	1968

A report in the Kyoto meeting was given at the 1969 General Assembly in Basle.

C. The Moscow Conference, 1968

This was attended by about 800 scientists. The Conference was scientifically most successful and the U.S.S.R. Programme Committee achieved a very good balance of high quality papers over the whole semiconductor field.

A number of new experiments using laser light were reported, including the scattering by free carriers both in and out of magnetic fields, and this technique is likely to be more widely applied in the future. There was also a useful session on liquid and amorphous semiconductors and also polaron states in magnetic fields.

Immediately before the Conference, a one day symposium on semiconductor lasers was held and was well attended. Other informal sessions were held during the main Conference, including one on lattice defects in semiconductors.

The mechanics of the Conference worked very smoothly and the hospitality was most impressive. At the sessions themselves the U.S.S.R. organisers (Acad. Vul, Professors Bonch-Bruевич, Kalashnikov, Regel and Vavilov) had arranged that the translators were all scientists and it was generally agreed that the simultaneous translation arrangement were better than members of the Conference had previously experienced.

The proceedings have been published.

D. The Commission met in Moscow in July 1968 and at other times conducted business by post.

(a) *Topical Conferences*

The Commission has been effectively operating for some time the criteria to be satisfied, if IUPAP recognition is to be recommended, as now laid down by the Executive of IUPAP.

The following Topical Conferences have been held, are about to be, or are being recommended for approval :

1967 II/VI Semiconducting Compounds.

Held in Brown University, U.S.A. Proceedings published, W.A. Benjamin 1967, New York, Amsterdam.

1969 International Conference on Photoconductivity, August 12-15th, 1969, Stanford, U.S.A.

1969 Amorphous Semiconductors, September 1969, Cambridge, U.K.

1970 Recognition has been agreed for Radiation Damage in Semiconductors, July, Albany, N.Y., U.S.A. (timed in sequence for the Boston, U.S.A. Semiconductor Conference).

A request has been received by the Semiconductors Commission for IUPAP recognition for an International Conference on "Heterojunctions and Layer Structures" being organised by Dr. G. Szigeti in Budapest in October 1970 (11-17th).

(b) *Main Conference*

(i) The Commission takes the view that regular international meetings on the Physics of Semiconductors play a vital role in the semiconductor field and that in the range 500-1000 participants the meetings are not unreasonably large. The programme of smaller international topical meetings which the Commission recommends is seen as complementary to the main meeting.

(ii) At its 1968 meeting the Commission received a report from representatives of the Planning Committee for a Conference in Boston in 1970 (August 17-21). The Commission has approved the arrangements and has recommended to IUPAP that this meeting be recognized and sponsored with financial support from IUPAP.

(iii) The Commission has agreed to hold a Conference in 1972 and will make a recommendation to IUPAP after the meeting in 1970. Preliminary discussion of the venue of the 1972 Conference indicated Poland as being most likely although the U.K. and Switzerland have also been mentioned.

(iv) Since the meeting of the Commission, the question has been raised by the Low Temperature Commission of operating the Low Temperature, the Magnetism and the Semiconductor Conferences on a phased 3-year cycle.

On the surface this sounds attractive but in a collection of postal opinion the Semiconductors Commission would wish to discuss this in detail at its next meeting with representatives of the other Commissions present. The Commission emphatically does not wish to modify its present proposals for Conferences in 1970 and 1972.

The Physics of Semiconductors continues to be a flourishing field and it was the Commission's very considered view when it discussed this subject in 1966 (quite apart from the Low Temperature Commission's suggestion) that the 2-year period was required to keep pace with developments. This has certainly been brought out by the Tokyo (1966) and Moscow (1968) meetings. The Commission feel at present that it exercises a useful, if light control over the international conference sequence in the semiconductor field. The pace of the subject and demand is such that, if the period were three years, the Commission would be acting against its better judgement if requests in intervening years had to be turned down.

"Low temperature" is a technique which is important in many parts of solid state physics — including magnetism and the physics of semiconductors. When this technique primarily furthers the individual subject the topic will naturally gravitate to the subject meetings. The low temperature phenomena "par excellence" are those of quantum fluids. The Semiconductors Commission welcomes the closer liaison between Commissions and looks forward to having a member of the Low Temperature Commission present at the Semiconductors Commission in 1970 to discuss this further.

E. The Commission recommends that IUPAP sponsorship should be provided without financial support for a conference on "The Physics and Chemistry of Semiconductor Heterojunctions and Layer Structures" being organized by Dr. G. Szigeti in Budapest.

F. The Commission is asking the International Organizing Committee of the 1969 Conference on Amorphous Semiconductors, Cambridge, U.K. to advise it whether and when a further conference should be held and where it should be held.

July 1969.

9. Magnetism Commission

The IUPAP Commission on Magnetism met in Boston, on 12th September 1967, during the International Conference on Magnetism.

Following our usual custom, the next formal meeting of the Commission will be held in Grenoble in September 1970, during the International Conference which will be held there. In the meantime, the work of the Commission is done through a lively correspondence and by informal talks between the Commission Members.

A. *General Information*

The main activity of the Commission is to oversee those Conferences on Magnetism which are of an international character and deserve recognition from IUPAP and we have spent some time reviewing our general policy in this area. The subject of magnetism is growing in size and popularity and, as a result, the international conferences tend to be larger. Because of the growing pressure, we have therefore considered whether we should hold the large International Conferences more frequently and whether we should encourage smaller, more specialised, Conferences. After some debate we have concluded that the large International Conference fulfils a very valuable need for the advancement of high quality science in this area, because it enables the leading people in the subject to make presentations of their work to a wide audience and informally discuss all matters of research in a lively fashion. We also decided that we were happy with the quality of the papers and the quality of the discussions which took place at the large meetings and we would not wish to prejudice this under any circumstances whatever. We came to the conclusion that if we held Conferences more frequently, then inevitably the average scientific quality of each must decrease. We therefore agreed quite firmly that we would retain our present tradition of holding a large International Conference at intervals of three years. We are, of course, quite conscious of the value of the smaller, more specialised, Conferences which, when they are truly international in character, we wish to encourage, but we decided not to do so to the financial disadvantage of the major triennial Conference.

B. *Conferences*

(i) *Conferences on Magnet Technology*

Oxford, Great Britain, 11th-14th July, 1967.

This conference was orientated mainly toward technological applications; recent results were also presented and disclosed a rapidly advancing understanding of problems. The number of participants was about 250; the number of communications was 90. The Commission on Magnetism regretted that the communications have not been published either in a journal or as a book, even though many preprints were distributed at the Conference. Sponsorship, but no financial support, was given by IUPAP.

(ii) *International Conference on Magnetism*

Boston and Cambridge, Massachusetts, U.S.A.,
11th-15th September, 1967.

This was the main event in the magnetism calendar for the period under review, and as such, received IUPAP financial support. The organisation and the scientific level of this conference we judged to be very good. The number of participants was 1325 of which about 300 were from outside the U.S. More than half of the papers were presented by the non-American participants. The Communications have been published in the *Journal of Applied Physics*, Vol. 39, No. 2, Parts I and II, 1968. The budget available imposed a strict control of the expenses; the number of registrations was just sufficient to balance the budget. Because general reports of the large conference have already appeared in the physics literature, we shall not say anything further here.

(iii) *Colloque Ampere*

Grenoble, France, 16th-20th September, 1968.

The number of participants was 500, of which 300 came from 24 different foreign countries. The proceedings of the Conference have been published as a book, in May 1969, by North-Holland. This book, entitled 'Magnetic Resonance and Radiofrequency Spectroscopy', has 550 pages of which 230 are dedicated to the invited communications.

C. *Information about future Conferences for which sponsorship has been given by IUPAP*

(i) *Conference on High Magnetic Fields and their Applications*

Nottingham, Great Britain, 1969.

This conference is being organised under the auspices of the Institute of Physics and the Physical Society. It will take place at the University of Nottingham from 17th to 19th September 1969. The Chairman of the Organising Committee is Prof. N. Kurti, University of Oxford, Clarendon Laboratory, Parks Road, Oxford.

The scope of this conference will be concerned with the use of high magnetic fields in the study of electrons in metals, electrons in semiconductors and dielectrics, electronics and nuclear paramagnetism, magnetic ordering in solids, magneto-optics, type II superconductors and techniques for the production and measurement of high magnetic fields.

(ii) *International Conference on Magnetism*
Grenoble, France, 1970.

This conference has also received sponsorship of the French Physical Society. The conference will open on Monday, 14th September 1970 and will close on the following Friday or Saturday, depending on the size of the programme.

The Chairman of the Organising Committee is Prof. Néel, Laboratoire d'Electrostatique et de Physique du Métal, Cedex No. 166, 38-Grenoble-Gare, France.

All the sessions will take place in the amphitheatres of the University of Grenoble. Topics will be concerned with theoretical and experimental investigations of magnetism, magnetic materials and their properties, and certain new and important applications of magnetism. Papers will be presented in French or in English. The proceedings of the conference will be published in a French scientific journal — 'Le Journal de Physique'.

The first announcement of this conference has been mailed during the month of June 1969; a large distribution of this announcement has been assured. The mailing list of possible participants has been supplied by the representatives of the National Commissions of IUPAP.

It can be estimated that the number of participants will be about 1000, which would be a smaller number than in Boston. The reason for the smaller number is that as the meeting is

being held in Europe, there will be a smaller number of Americans. Furthermore, it seems that in many countries there is a decrease of funds for travelling abroad.

The International Conference will be preceded and followed by two conferences :

- : Conference Sagamore on the density of electronic charge and spin which will be held in Aussois (France) from 7th-12th September 1970. The Chairman of the Organising committee is Dr. E.F. Bertaut, Laboratoire d'Electrostatique et de Physique du Métal, Cedex No. 166, 38-Grenoble-Gare.
- : International Colloquium on Magnetic Thin Films, in Prague (Czechoslovakia), 21-23rd September 1970. The Chairman of the Organising Committee is Prof. L. Valenta, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, of the Charles University, Department of Theoretical Physics, Prague 2, Ke Karlovu 3, Czechoslovakia.

(iii) *The 1973 Conference*

During its meeting in Boston, the Commission on Magnetism proceeded to a classification of the countries applying for the organisation of the 1973 Conference on Magnetism. Moscow's candidature was settled as the first priority. By letters dated November 1st, 1967 and February 21st, 1969, Dr. Marshall, Chairman of the Commission on Magnetism asked Academician N.V. Keldish, President of U.S.S.R. Academy of Sciences, the views of the Academy upon the advisability of holding a large international conference on magnetism in Moscow in 1973.

The answer was given in a telegram dated March 20th, 1969. "In name of Prezidium U.S.S.R. Academy of Sciences have honour to invite IUPAP hold its Magnetism Conference September 1973 in Moscow. Academy shall render any possible assistance make Conference most success and representative. Regards, Academician Peive, General Secretary, U.S.S.R. Academy of Sciences."

The formal decision will be reached during the meeting of the Commission on Magnetism on September 1970 in Grenoble.

(iv) *Conferences in 1976 and later*

Proposals have been received for holding the 1976 Conference, or alternatively the 1979 Conference in Czechoslovakia, Netherlands, Japan and Australia. A preliminary view on these alternatives will be taken during the next meeting of the Commission to be held in Grenoble in 1970.

July 1969.

10. Solid State Commission

A. The Commission consists of 8 Members (including the Chairman and the Secretary) and 6 Corresponding Members, one of whom is specifically representative of the field of ferroelectricity and another one of the field of luminescence.

B. During the three years covered by this report, no meeting of the Commission was held. All matters were dealt with by correspondence.

C. The following conferences sponsored by the Commission were held (most but not all with financial support).

- June/July 1966 — Prague — International Meeting on Ferroelectricity.
- August 1966 — Budapest — International Conference on Luminescence.
- September 1966 — Ljubliana — 14th Colloque Ampere, Conference on Magnetic Resonance and Relaxation.
- March 1968 — San Francisco — International Conference on the Metal-Nonmetal Transition.
- July 1968 — Birmingham, U.K. — 2nd International Conference on Crystal Growth.
- September 1968 — Rome — 5th International Symposium on Colour Centres in Alkali Halides.
- September 1968 — Julich — International Conference on Vacancies and Interstitials in Metals.

- January 1969 — Delhi — International Conference on Science and Technology of Non-metallic Crystals.
- April 1969 — Brighton — 2nd International Conference on Fracture.
- April/May 1969 — Boston — International Conference on Thin Films.

Reports received indicate that Conferences recommended by the Solid State Commission were highly successful.

D. Sponsorship of the following conferences has been granted by IUPAP :

- August 1969 — Delaware — International Conference on Luminescence.
- September 1969 — Kyoto — 2nd International Meeting on Ferroelectricity.
- September 1969 — Providence, R.I. — International Conference on Ultrasonic Attenuation and Internal Friction in Crystalline Solids.

E. Considerable discussion took place, by correspondence, on the principles of the policy which IUPAP may adopt regarding sponsorship of conferences. A summary of the opinions of this Commission has been sent to the Secretariat as a basis for further discussion. The memorandum deals with the mechanics of requesting sponsorship (with or without financial support) and with the criteria for granting sponsorship based on the scientific value of the proposed conference, its international character and the availability of organizational manpower and financial resources.

May 1969.

11. High Energy Nuclear Physics Commission

The Commission held each year one or two meetings during one of the regular International Conferences which it sponsors. One meeting was held in Cambridge, Massachusetts (11 Septem-

ber 1967), two meetings in Vienna, Austria (30 August and 4 September 1968). The 1969 meeting will be held in Liverpool, U.K., between 14-20 September.

The main business of the Commission was to discuss IUPAP sponsorship and financial support of conferences in the field of high energy physics. The regular International Conferences on High Energy Physics, held every even year, and the regular International Conferences on High Energy Accelerators, held every odd year, were prepared in detail. In addition, various more specialised meetings were discussed and IUPAP sponsorship was recommended for four conferences held in 1967, for three conferences in 1968, and for five conferences in 1969. In view of the large number of requests for sponsorship which reached the Commission in 1968, the general problem of reducing the number of meetings at IUPAP level was discussed. The number of requests fell to one in 1969.

A list of high energy conferences sponsored by IUPAP follows :

International Conference on High Energy Physics:

Vienna (Austria), September 1968.

International Conference on High Energy Accelerators:

Cambridge (Mass./U.S.A.), September 1967.

Yerevan (Armenia/U.S.S.R.), August/September 1969.

Specialized Conferences:

International Conference on High Energy Physics and Nuclear Structure (Rehovoth/Israel), February/March 1967.

International Theoretical Physics Conference on Particles and Fields (Rochester/U.S.A.), June 1967.

International Symposium on Electron and Photon Interactions at High Energies (Stanford/U.S.A.), September 1967.

Topical Conference on High Energy Collisions of Hadrons (CERN, Geneva/Switzerland), January 1968.

International Colloquium on Nuclear Electronics (Versailles/France), September 1968.

Topical Conference on Weak Interactions (CERN, Geneva/Switzerland), January 1969.

Third International Conference on High Energy Reactions (Stony Brook, N.Y./U.S.A.), September 1969.

International Symposium on Electron and Photon Interactions at High Energies (Liverpool/U.K.), September 1969.

International Conference on High Energy Physics and Nuclear Structure (Columbia University, New York/U.S.A.), September 1969.

July 1969.

12. Low Energy Nuclear Physics Commission

On the occasion of the 12th Annual Assembly in Basle, 1966, the following members were elected :

P. Huber, Basle, Chairman
J. Teillac, Paris, Secretary
G.R. Bishop, Glasgow
A. Bohr, Copenhagen
P.A. Cerenkov, Moscow
T. Lauritsen, Pasadena
R. Ramanna, Bombay.

For reasons of health, Prof. Cerenkov resigned and Prof. I.M. Frank, Moscow, was elected in his place.

The corresponding members were :

R.E. Bell, Montreal
J. Fowler, Oak Ridge
I. Nonaka, Tokyo
H. Schopper, Karlsruhe
A. Szalay, Debrecen.

We should like to express our gratitude to the former members Prof. B.H. Flowers, Manchester and P.M. Endt, Utrecht, for the work done in the interest of our Committee.

The Commission held meetings on the occasion of the symposia in Tokyo (1967) and Dubna (1968). The following topics of general interest were discussed :

A. *General Policy of the Commission*

The Commission recommends that an International General Conference should be held at least every two years. This Conference should be very open and should cover the main topics of nuclear physics.

In between such General Conferences there are :

- a) restricted conferences, where the number of participants is limited and where a wide region of interest is treated (e.g. Dubna 1968);
- b) topical conferences on a special subject, where the number of participants is not limited (e.g. Montreal 1969);
- c) restricted conferences on limited subjects.

B. *High Energy Physics and Nuclear Structure*

The High Energy Physics Commission has already suggested holding joint meetings on high energy physics and nuclear structure (e.g. CERN 1963, Rehovoth 1967 and New York 1969). Such conferences are of special interest to nuclear physicists. We consider it therefore desirable as a general rule, to establish close collaboration between the High Energy Physics Commission and our Commission. We propose to do this by means of common meetings of a number of members of one commission participating in a meeting of the other.

C. *Admission of members to IUPAP-conferences*

A regrettable aspect of the Dubna conference was the fact that one of the members of our commission did not receive a visa. Since we found out about this problem only a short time before the conference, we were unable, despite the efforts of Prof. Blokhintsev and Prof. Frank, to settle this matter.

In its meeting at Dubna, our Commission has discussed this affair. The Commission considered as unacceptable the fact that visas are denied to members of IUPAP - commissions. Therefore we submit our serious concern to the Executive Committee and propose that in the future international conferences should only

be supported by IUPAP if the permit to enter the country is granted to all members of the corresponding commission and to everybody interested in attending the symposium.

Another matter arose in connection with the conference on the Three Body Problem in Birmingham. The organizing committee levied — which is often customary — from all participants a fee of £12.-.-. Furthermore they proposed to declare the purchase of the Proceedings as compulsory. We do not consider this procedure as a good solution, since the purchase of proceedings should be left to the individual participant.

D. The following symposia have been arranged during the period of report:

1967 International Seminar on Low Energy Nuclear Physics, Dacca (Pakistan).

International Conference on Nuclear Structure, Tokyo (Japan).

1968 International Symposium on Nuclear Structure, Dubna (USSR).

Conference on Electron Capture and on High Order Processes in Nuclear Decays, Debrecen (Hungary).

International Symposium on Nuclear Electronics, Versailles (France).

1969 International Conference on the Three Body Problem, Birmingham (UK).

Nuclear Reactions Induced by Heavy Ions, Heidelberg (Germany).

Properties of Nuclear States, Montreal (Canada).

International Cyclotron Conference, Oxford (UK).

International Conference on Experimental Electron and Gamma Ray Spectroscopy, Nashville, Tenn. (USA).

June 1969.

13. Commission on Atomic Masses and and Related Constants

Activities

i) The principal formal activity of the Commission since the 1966 General Assembly was the Third International Conference on Atomic Masses held in Winnipeg, Canada, 28 August - 1 September 1967. The Conference was attended by about eighty persons representing eleven different countries and the 901-page Proceedings were published in March 1968 by the University of Manitoba Press.

ii) The Commission has met as follows :

- a) Winnipeg, Canada 30 August 1967
- b) Teddington, England 2 August 1968
- c) Montréal, Canada 30 August 1969 (informal meeting of members attending Conference in Montreal).

iii) Members of the Commission have continued their efforts to improve our knowledge of atomic masses and the fundamental constants. In particular, in the former area, Professor A. Wapstra will soon be publishing the results of his latest least-squares adjustment and, in the latter area, one member, E.R. Cohen and corresponding member, J.W.M. DuMond, have continued their authoritative work.

iv) Preliminary plans have been made for the Fourth International Conference on Atomic Masses and Related Constants to be held in London, England during the summer of 1971.

July 1969.

14. Commission on Physics Education

A. Commission Membership

Members: H. H. Staub (Switzerland), Chairman; William C. Kelly (U.S.A.), Secretary; D. Sette (Italy); P. Fleury (France); A. S. Akhmatov (U.S.S.R.); H. B. G. Casimir (Netherlands); and W. Schaffer (South Africa).

Corresponding Members: A. Harashima (Japan); W. Kroebel (West Germany); M. Pihl (Denmark); J. Lewis (United Kingdom); M. Valouch (Czechoslovakia); and L. Pal (Hungary).

B. *Meetings of the Commission*

The Commission met at Zurich, Switzerland, on April 3-5, 1967; at Eindhoven, The Netherlands, on January 9-10, 1968; and again in Eindhoven on December 6, 1968. At least five of the members of the Commission attended each of these meetings, and several corresponding members were also able to attend. Representatives from UNESCO and other interested organisations also participated. The minutes of these meetings have been circulated. A meeting is planned in Rome on July 11-13, 1969.

C. *Seminar on the Education of Physicists for Work in Industry*

The Seminar was held in Eindhoven, The Netherlands, December 2-6, 1968, under the Sponsorship of the Commission and the Technical University of Eindhoven. The Organising Committee consisted of H.B.G. Casimir, Chairman; G. Diemer, Secretary; and P. van der Leeden. The Philips Company was most helpful in the organisation of the Seminar, and the Technical University provided pleasant surroundings and efficient assistance.

Sixty persons took part in the Seminar. Twenty-four were representatives of industry, 27 were from universities, and 8 others represented national and international scientific organisations. Eighteen different countries were represented.

The five-day program consisted of general sessions and discussion-group meetings, the latter devoted to the following topics: the situation in and the requirements of industry, possibilities for improvement in university work, optimum of specialist versus generalist education, cooperation between university and industry, and extramural courses.

The Proceedings of the Seminar, edited by G. Diemer and J. H. Emck, were published by the Centrex Publishing Company and given prompt world-wide distribution. *A Source Book of Papers Prepared for the Seminar*, also compiled by Diemer and

Emck and published by Centrex, will be given somewhat more limited circulation.

A lower limit of the cost of the Seminar was \$7,730, not including the full subsidy from Philips or the support of travel for some of the participants. Major contributors were Philips, Gevaert-Agfa, Unilever, Shell, the Dutch Ministry of Education and Science, UNESCO, IUPAP, IBM, and the National Science Foundation of the United States.

D. Conferences scheduled for 1970

The Commission has made plans for two international meetings on physics education to be held in 1970. An International Working Seminar on the Role of History of Physics in Physics Education will be held at Massachusetts Institute of Technology on July 13-17, 1970. The number of invited participants will be about thirty. The purpose of the Seminar is to stimulate and extend cooperation among physicists, historians of science, and others interested in the humanistic teaching of physics. The working sessions will include discussion and the preparation of pedagogical materials that illustrate the use of historical content. The chairman of the Organising Committee is Allen L. King of Dartmouth College and the other members are Sanborn C. Brown (MIT), Gerald Holton (Harvard), William C. Kelly (National Research Council), and Charles Weiner (American Institute of Physics).

An International Congress on the Education of Teachers of Physics in Secondary Schools will be held in Eger, Hungary, on September 11-17, 1970. The number of national delegates and other participants will be about one hundred. The purpose of the Congress is to review problems connected with the education of secondary-school physics teachers and to develop recommendations to governmental groups and universities for improved pre-service education, motivation, and continuing education of teachers. The chairman of the local Organising Committee is E. Nagy of Eötvös University. The membership of the international Program Committee includes D. Sette (Italy), Chairman; Roberto B. Da Costa (Brazil); A. Harashima (Japan); Ruud L. Krans (Netherlands); E. Nagy (Hungary); J.A.O. Sofolahan (Nigeria);

Fletcher G. Watson (U.S.A.); and a representative of the U.S.S.R. to be named.

E. *Other proposed conferences and seminars*

The Commission is considering the following international meetings as possibilities for the next two or three years: an open meeting of university physics teachers, a congress on the teaching of physics to students in related fields (engineering, life sciences, etc.), and a working seminar on physics and mathematics. Each of these has attracted interest to some extent, but sites and dates have not yet been arranged.

F. *Cooperation with UNESCO*

The Commission has continued to consult with UNESCO and provide assistance in several UNESCO projects. Professor Schaffer has assisted in the pilot project on the teaching of crystallography. Professor Sette has consulted with UNESCO in the preparation of the book "Mathematics for Physicists". Professor Pihl took part in a UNESCO conference in Bangkok on the teaching of nuclear sciences in secondary schools. Professor Fleury has been helpful to the UNESCO staff on many occasions.

In addition, the Commission is working with UNESCO on two writing projects. One is to prepare a "UNESCO Source Book on the Teaching of Physics in Secondary Schools". John L. Lewis (United Kingdom) is the editor-in-chief, and the other members of the editorial board include A.S. Akhmatov (with the collaboration of D.M. Tolstoi) (U.R.S.S.) and Thomas D. Miner (U.S.A.). A tentative outline for the book has been reviewed by the Commission, and invitations are now being extended to prospective authors of articles.

The second writing project with UNESCO is the preparation of a college-level "Source Book on the Teaching of Physics". E. Nagy (Hungary) is editor-in-chief, and the other members of the editorial board include P. Lorrain (Canada) and J.H. Emck (Netherlands). An outline for the book and a list of authors are now being developed.

G. *Other activities*

The Secretary served as a member of the Organising Committee for the Congress on the Integration of Science Teaching, Varna, Bulgaria, September 11-19, 1968, sponsored by the International Commission on Science Teaching (CIES) of ICSU and by UNESCO. The Congress made some notable contributions to international cooperation in this area. Its Proceedings have been published. Professor Fleury is the Executive Secretary of CIES.

The Commission considered whether it would be desirable to continue the circulation of the International Newsletter on Physics Education, which the American Institute of Physics published in 1964-65 at the suggestion of the Commission. It was decided that, although communication was a serious problem in international education, the Newsletter was not reaching a wide enough audience for it to be effective. A better plan would be to stimulate the interest of the editors of physics journals in international-educational news, and some tentative plans for this were made. Little has been done on this problem, however, and it remains an item of unfinished business.

July 1969.

15. Commission on Atomic and Molecular Physics and Spectroscopy and Plasma Physics

A. *General*

The Commission on Atomic and Molecular Physics and Spectroscopy was established at the IUPAP General Assembly in Basle in 1966. It was also decided at that time to include plasma physics, at least temporarily, in the Commission. Dr. G. Herzberg (Canada) was named Chairman of the Commission and Professor W.L. Fite (U.S.A.) was named Secretary. Professors S.C. Brown (U.S.A.) and W.C. Price (U.K.) were also named Commissioners.

The first meeting of the Commission was held on December 19, 1966, in Montreal, Canada, and was attended by the aforementioned individuals. Professor Larkin Kerwin kindly met with us to give general guidance in consideration of the organisation and operation of the Commission.

At that meeting, it was recognized that the major activities over which the Commission would have cognizance were (1) Spectroscopy, (2) Atomic Collisions and (3) Plasma Physics. It was decided to have six commissioners (in addition to the chairman) whose make up of scientific interests would be such that each of the three subfields in the Commission would be loosely represented by two commissioners. To this end Professor A. Kastler (France) was invited to be a commissioner and join with Professor Price in representing Spectroscopy, Acad. L.A. Artsimovitch (U.S.S.R.) joined Professor Brown representing Plasma Physics and Professor J. Kistemaker (Netherlands) agreed to serve with Professor Fite in representing atomic collisions.

At the same meeting it was decided to establish sub-commissions for each of the three sub-fields to advise the Commission as a whole. Each sub-commission has a total of six members.

Other general considerations of future Commission activities occupied most of the remainder of the first Commission meeting.

The second Commission meeting was held in New York on June 6, 1968. The members of all sub-commissions were invited to meet with the Commission. Although the meeting was scheduled to coincide with the International Conference on Atomic Physics, in hopes of getting good attendance at the Commission meeting, very few of the members were able to attend the Conference and the Commission meeting. While urgent Commission business was acted upon by those present, the meeting was very limited with respect to planning future Commission activities.

While Commission meetings have been very difficult to arrange and poorly attended, the majority of commissioners and sub-commissioners are to be commended for their participation in Commission activities via the mails.

It is understood that the Executive of IUPAP intends to establish a separate Commission on Plasma Physics. The members of the Commission on Atomic and Molecular Physics and Spectroscopy are entirely in favour of such a move, since it would tend to make our Commission more viable.

B. Meetings

The principal activity of the Commission has been to recommend certain conferences for IUPAP support and sponsorship. The meetings sponsored were :

1967 : Vth International Conference on the Physics of Electronic and Atomic Collisions, Leningrad, USSR.

VIIIth International Conference on Ionization Phenomena in Gases, Vienna, Austria.

9th European Congress of Molecular Spectroscopy, Madrid, Spain.

1968 : International Conference on Atomic Physics, New York, U.S.A.

International Conference on Laboratory Astrophysics, Lunteren, Netherlands.

Arnold Sommerfeld Centennial Memorial Meeting and the International Symposium on the Physics of One- and Two-Electron Atoms, Munich, Germany.

International Conference on Optical Pumping and Atomic Line Shapes, Warsaw, Poland.

1969 : VIth International Conference on the Physics of Electronic and Atomic Collisions, Cambridge, Mass., USA.

IXth International Conference on Phenomena in Ionized Gases, Bucharest, Romania.

C. Other Activities

The Commission has been concerned with some matters in addition to arrangement of meetings, the principal ones of which are summarized below :

Units. After considerable correspondence and discussion, the Commission adopted at its New York meeting a resolution in strong opposition to rigid enforcement of the International System of Units (S.I. Units) and urged that units now in common usage in Atomic and Molecular Physics and Spectroscopy (among which are included the inverse centimeter (cm^{-1}) the Angstrom (\AA) and atomic units) not be excluded in publications and other commu-

nications. It was widely felt that while rigid enforcement of such arbitrary systems might have some merit in newly developing fields, to impose a new unit scheme in a field of such long standing as atomic physics would only confuse and hinder the development of the field and tend to make obsolete many of the classical works on the eyes of present and future scientists.

Definition of International Character of Scientific Meetings.

At the New York Commission Meeting three criteria were adopted for determining whether a meeting was sufficiently international to warrant consideration for IUPAP sponsorship and support. The three, all of which should be met, are :

- i) The meeting must have significant participation by persons from outside the host nation.
- ii) Significant international participation in the planning and organizing of the meeting must precede the meeting. It is recommended that a member of the cognizant IUPAP Commission (or a sub-commission) be a member of the organizing committee.
- iii) International meetings may either be "open" or "by invitation only". Open meetings must be open to all qualified scientists from IUPAP member nations. Meetings where the size is to be limited and where participation is to be by invitation only must not discriminate against scientists from IUPAP member nations except on the grounds of scientific qualifications.

D. Data Collection and Evaluation

A subject on which no action has as yet been taken but which has received extensive discussion among commissioners has been the position that IUPAP should take with respect to the matters of data collection and dissemination and of critical reviews of the literature.

It is widely believed that at a time when scientific literature is increasing exponentially, the position of critical reviews, summarizing and evaluating recent data and theories, will assume an ever-increasing importance in making the literature usable. It has been noted that some of the critical reviews now appearing are prepared by authors whose youth and relative inexperience leaves

some doubts as to validity of their judgements on the merits and short comings of given pieces of research. At present data are collected and critical reviews are prepared (1) spontaneously by an inspired author, (2) within the framework of one of the data collection and reviewing programs within a single nation (for example the U.S. National Standard Data Reference System) and (3) by private companies.

It is felt that IUPAP should inject itself in some manner into the data collection and critical review picture. Among the suggestions as to how this might occur are the following :

A. Commissioning the collection of data and the writing of critical reviews for publication by IUPAP or in recognized journals.

B. Seeking to have existing organisations and individuals submit reviews to the cognizant IUPAP Commission for approval of the work prior to publication.

C. Reviewing published reviews and re-publishing them in a IUPAP document or publishing a list of IUPAP-approved reviews.

The problem of both the politics and the fiscal aspects of these sources have not been fully resolved. The matter is still under active discussion within our Commission and it is suggested that consideration of this problem would be appropriate for consideration by broader segments of the Union.

June 1969.

16. International Commission for Optics (ICO)

A. *Minutes of 1966 Commission Meeting:*

These were published in JOSA, Vol. 56, No. 9, 1966, and in *Optica Acta*, Oct. 1966.

B. *Publications:*

(a) Proceedings of Conference on Recent Progress in Physical Optics, Paris, 1966, *Optica Acta*, Oct. 1966.

- (b) Proceedings of the First International Conference on Electrophotography, Rochester, Sept. 1968, Applied Optics, Supplement #3, 1969.
- (c) The invited papers of the Symposium on Applications of Coherent Light will be published by Optica Acta.
- (d) Booklet ICO4, completing the 20 years history of the Commission and including its Constitution and Statutes.

C. Conferences and Colloquia:

- (a) Following their successful meeting in 1965, the Hungarian National Committee for Optics sponsored a 2nd Colloquium on Thin Films in Budapest, June 27 — July 2, 1967.
- (b) The First International Conference on Electrophotography was held in Rochester, Sept. 4-6, 1968. It was attended by some 500 delegates from the United States and 7 other countries. Approximately 40 papers were presented. Seven contributing corporations provided the original funds, which were supplemented by the fees collected. The conference was considered a great success.
- (c) A symposium on Applications of Coherent Light was held in Florence, Sept. 23-27, 1968. There were 168 participants at the meeting, representing 20 countries. Fifty-eight papers were presented.
- (d) The summer school on the Optical Processing of Information planned by the Institute of Optics in Paris for 1968 was postponed and will be held July 7-12, in Orsay.

D. Finance:

ICO funds are currently held in 2 accounts, a checking account at the Lincoln Rochester Trust Company, Rochester, New York and a savings account held by the O.S.A.

As of June 30, 1969, there was subscription outstanding for 1967. Seven subscription for 1969 have already been received.

Financial statements covering the period from June 30, 1966 to June 30, 1969 show the ICO to be in good financial condition. The current cash balance is slightly more than \$9000, with over \$2000 in subscriptions expected by the end of 1969. \$6000 was contributed towards ICO 8 and, due to a refund from the 1968 Symposium on Coherent Light, we were able to make a grant of \$1500 to the Summer School being held this month in Orsay. Booklet ICO4, bringing the history of the Commission up to date, will cost about \$550. There are ample funds for the planning of future conferences.

May 1969.

ICSU Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research (SCOR)

(IUPAP representative : Sir Edward Ballard)

SCOR issues annual volumes of "Proceedings" and there seems no object in trying to summarise these in detail for IUPAP. Instead, it seems more useful to pick out the aspect of SCOR's work that are related to that of IUPAP.

SCOR is a group of experts covering all branches of oceanography whose object is to encourage international collaboration in those parts of the subject where it is appropriate. This is done partly by the holding of conferences, often in conjunction with the business meetings of the committee (e.g. the *Symposium on the Scientific Exploration of the South Pacific* held in La Jolla in June 1968), partly by the setting up of working groups in particular topics and the adoption of resolutions asking for action by national and international oceanographic bodies.

A large part of the work of SCOR is on biological, chemical and geological topics of little interest to IUPAP. Perhaps the main fields of joint interest are the determination and tabulation of the physical properties of materials of oceanographic interest and the unification and calibration of measuring instruments. In both these fields the SCOR working groups have been active and have

not only collected information about work done by individuals and national organisations but have carried out work themselves.

Working group 10, on Oceanographic Tables and Standards, has been particularly active in collecting and publishing data on the physical properties of sea water as a function of temperature and salinity. A knowledge of the thermodynamic properties is fundamental to a study of stability and motion in the oceans. For this purpose density, the coefficient of expansion, compressibility and specific heat are required to an accuracy which is difficult to reach.

Working group 15 recommends apparatus and procedures for measuring radiant energy in the sea in a way that is meaningful for biological studies.

Working group 21 is concerned with the intercomparison at sea of the numerous devices for the continuous measurement of ocean currents.

Working group 27 is concerned with the measurement and analysis of deep sea tides.

Working group 28 studies interaction between the ocean and the atmosphere. This is a matter of fundamental importance to meteorology and is for the most part a hydrodynamic and thermodynamic problem and therefore a part of physics.

The rest of the working groups are concerned with matters of no direct interest to IUPAP.

The present arrangements for liaison between IUPAP and SCOR seem adequate.

June 1969.

Upper Mantle Project

(IUPAP representative : S.K. Runcorn)

The Upper Mantle project which formally comes to an end on December 31st, 1970 has encouraged the development of two important aspects in the study of the Earth's interior.

Firstly, the static model of the Earth, which seemed, a few years ago, adequate to explain the geophysical data (mainly seismological) has given way to a dynamic model of the interior. The older geological evidence for continental drift was powerfully reinforced by the paleomagnetic data and this has stimulated new tests of the continental drift hypothesis, such as the radioactive dating of geological provinces in South America and Africa. The interpretation of the magnetic surveys over the oceans has led to the hypothesis of sea floor spreading which neatly compliments continental drift. To satisfactorily incorporate this new evidence in a theory of the Earth's mantle, convection must be postulated in the Earth's interior and solid state creep must be assumed to occur beneath the crust. Thus hydrodynamics and solid state physics have been brought into Upper Mantle studies and the hydrodynamicist and solid state physicist presented with interesting new problems.

The second important direction in which Upper Mantle studies have developed concerns the property of solids at high pressures. The refinement of seismological studies, through development in instrumentation and the use of computers, have revealed discontinuities in the mechanical properties of the Earth with depth which have strongly suggested the presence of phase changes in the Mantle. The application of Bridgman "experimental methods" have shown that phase changes occur in the silicate minerals at temperatures and pressures which correspond to the depths at which discontinuities are found. Particularly the transition to spinel form of olivine has been experimentally studied and provides an explanation of the 20° discontinuity.

It will be seen that these new developments in Upper Mantle studies have brought the theoretical and experimental physicist very much to the forefront in his work. This has been reflected particularly in the symposia which the Upper Mantle Committee has run, especially the series on "Geophysical theory and computers" which has been held each year during the period of the project, and which have greatly contributed to the growing sophistication of theoretical studies in geophysics. The symposium on the "Non-elastic processes in the Mantle" held in the School of

Physics, University of Newcastle, was also notable in the number of solid state physicists who came and contributed.

I have attended the Upper Mantle Committee meetings at the International Union Meeting in Zurich 1967, and I was appointed a member of the Bureau. I also attended the Upper Mantle Committee in Canberra in January 1969 and the symposium on "Phase changes in the Mantle". There will also be a meeting in Madrid of the International Associations of Seismology and Physics of the Earth's Interior and Geomagnetism and Aeronomy. Special symposia organised by the Upper Mantle Committee have a feature of all the International Union and Association Meetings especially on the three topics, the world rift system, continental margins and deep boring, which have been selected for special attention during UMP.

At Canberra and Madrid the Upper Mantle Committee is making recommendations on post Upper Mantle activities to the Working Party under the Chairmanship of Professor Drake, which has been set up jointly by the International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics and the International Geological Union. During the Upper Mantle project a more fruitful dialogue between geophysicists and geologists has begun, particularly through the development of palaeogeophysics and round the discussions of continental drift, and this is to be further advanced in the post Upper Mantle activities. But I have also urged that now, for the first time, geophysical theories can be tested against data obtained from the study of the Moon and Planets. Therefore, I consider that the International Union of Astronomy should be closely associated with these further developments.

The continued interest of the IUPAP on the Upper Mantle project and its successor is very desirable.

June 1969.

Comité International de Géophysique

(IUPAP representative : M. Pomerantz)

The International Geophysics Committee (CIG) was established by ICSU in 1959 as the successor to the IGY committee.

CIG was organized, much as had been the latter, as an inter-Union, inter-disciplinary body. Four Unions — IUGG, URSI, IAU and IUPAP — were involved, and their representatives formed the CIG Bureau. The Unions also nominated discipline members for the Committee and thus the IUGG was heavily represented while the IUPAP needed but one such member, in the field of cosmic rays.

The functions of CIG were essentially two. First, to complete certain tasks of the IGY : (i) to guide the flow of IGY data to the three World Data Centers and the dissemination of catalogues relevant thereto and (ii) to supervise the completion of the *Annals of the IGY*. The interchange of data was completed several years ago. The publication of the final volumes of the *Annals* is expected this year.

Second, the CIG was also to look to the interests and needs of the scientific community vis-à-vis international programs along the lines of the IGY. The ICSU had, as a result of the IGY, created committees to cope with continuity in international programming for Antarctic investigations (SCAR), oceanographic research (SCOR), and space studies (COSPAR). CIG was thus to be largely receptive to interests in solid-earth geophysics and in solar-terrestrial research. CIG did lend support to IUGG interests in the former area, which led to the formation of the Upper Mantle Committee, an inter-union body administered by the IUGG which is now completing its most significant seven-year effort.

The single most important program planned by the CIG was the International Years of the Quiet Sun (IQSY). Once the initial planning had been completed, IQSY was established as a separate ICSU inter-union committee. Scientists of some 70 nations co-operated in this highly successful venture of 1964-65, and it was possible for the IQSY to disband itself by 1968. CIG itself voted its own dissolution by the end of 1968. The ongoing data center activities were turned over to a new ICSU panel on this topic while solar-terrestrial research were assigned by ICSU to the Inter-union Commission on Solar-Terrestrial Physics (IUCSTP).

All in all the CIG served scientists and nations with distinction, both in completion of the IGY, in initiating such efforts as the IQSY, in co-operating with the Unions and such ICSU committees as COSPAR, and in looking ahead through its recommendations for mechanisms and structures to carry on the data centers and international programming in solar-terrestrial research. Having fostered the Upper Mantle effort and in its very early days actively led by the IQSY, the last three years have been primarily concerned with completion tasks of the IGY, the world data centers, and the wind-up of its own administrative and fiscal affairs in 1968. Much is owed to the many scientists from various Unions for this record of accomplishment. An especial debt is owed to Professor W.J.G. Beynon, who served brilliantly and modestly as the President of Both CIG and IQSY. Our community is also in debt to Dr. C.M. Minnis, who served so well as Secretary for both of these groups.

July 1969.

Appendix III

CONCERNING INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES

The following criteria and rules received tentative approval by the XIIIth General Assembly at Dubrovnik. They will be reviewed by the Executive Committee, and any changes dictated by experience will be proposed to the XIVth General Assembly.

1. Categories

A. *General Conferences*

These would be designed to provide an overview of the entire field of interest to a Commission, and would normally occur at three-year intervals if advances in the field warrant. Attendance in the range of 750-1500 would be anticipated.

B. *Topical Conferences*

These would concentrate on broad sub-fields in the area of the particular Commission's interest (e.g. nuclear spectroscopy, nuclear reaction mechanisms, heavy ion physics in the case of the Nuclear Physics Commission). They would normally be scheduled in the years between the type A General Conferences, if the latter have been held. Attendance in the range of 300-600 would be anticipated.

C. *Special Conferences*

These would concentrate on much more restricted specialized topics than in the case of type B Conferences (e.g. angular correlations, lifetime measurements, neutron resonance studies in the case of the Nuclear Physics Commission). These would be scheduled in the years between the type A General Conferences, if the latter are held. Attendance in the range of 50-200 would be anticipated.

2. Criteria

A. *Scientific Value*

- a) There should be a clearly demonstrated need for the proposed conference, i.e. new and important advances to be discussed since the last conference of a similar type took place ;
- b) the invited speakers and the papers accepted for discussion should be of high caliber ;
- c) the accepting of papers should be based on some sort of refereeing system which assures a level comparable with that of papers in the regular journals. If the proceedings of the Conference are published, every effort should be made to have them published as a special issue of a regular journal in order to make them widely and easily available to the scientific community.

B. *International Character*

- a) There should be an international committee advising on the scientific programme ;
- b) the participation should be genuinely international, and not constitute effectively a national conference to which a few physicists from outside the country are invited. Such national conferences are necessary and valuable, but do not come within the mandate of I.U.P.A.P. . Organizers of conferences seeking Union sponsorship should make every effort to ensure that the attendance from outside the host country be not less than 30% and preferably be more than 50% ;
- c) open conferences should admit physicists of any I.U.P.A.P. member country. For a "closed" conference, the invitation list should include potential contributors from all I.U.P.A.P. member countries which have active programmes in the field ;
- d) I.U.P.A.P. will not sponsor a conference if visas are refused for travel to it purely on grounds of nationality

or citizenship. It is understood that request for sponsorship implies that the host country makes timely entrance possible for every scientist recommended for participation by the international committee (a).

C. *Organization*

- a) The Conference should have the approval of the relevant international Commission of I.U.P.A.P., and thus pertinent details should be submitted by the month of April of the year prior to that in which the conference is to be held ;
- b) it is important that the precise dates, address of the Conference and name and address of the Conference Secretary or Chief Organizer be submitted to the Commission, which can sometimes then help to avoid conflicts of dates, etc. ;
- c) the proposed Conference would benefit by having the approval of the National Committee for I.U.P.A.P. of the host country ;
- d) it is very helpful to the International Commission to have as much detail as possible about the organization and budget of the proposed Conference.

3. **Other**

The Union Executive meets in late September of each year, at which meeting sponsorship of conferences is decided and grants, if any, are made. Commissions should forward their recommendations to the Secretary-General by August 15th, including all of the information mentioned above (2-C : Organization). The Commission's recommendations should be based on the criteria of 2-A and 2-B, and should include a classification as to category (1). Therefore, organizers of Conferences should apply to Commissions by April, in order to allow the Commission to meet (often by letter) and study the request. Requests for sponsorship of conferences not falling within the domain of a Commission should be sent directly to the Secretary-General.

Annexe IV
Appendix IV

LISTE DES CONGRÈS APPROUVÉS EN 1970
CONFERENCE APPROVED FOR 1970

	Où Where	Quand When
1. Second International Conference on ATOMIC PHYSICS Organized by : Dr. G.K. Woodgate, Department of Physics, Clarendon Laboratory, Parks Road, Oxford, ENGLAND.	Oxford U.K.	July 21-24
2. Symposium on POLARISATION PHENOMENA in NUCLEAR REACTIONS Chairman : Prof. Barshall Information : (Low Energy) Nuclear Physics Commission c/o Prof. J. Teillac, secretary, Laboratoire Joliot-Curie, Faculté des Sciences d'Orsay, Orsay 91, FRANCE.	Madison Wisconsin U.S.A.	August 31- Sept. 4
3. HYPERFINE INTERACTIONS DETECTED by NUCLEAR RADIATION Information : (Low Energy) Nuclear Physics Commission	Rehovoth Israel	
4. AUGULAR CORRELATIONS in NUCLEAR PHYSICS Organized by : Dr. B. van Nooijen, Technische Hogeschool Delft, Dept. of Experimental and Nuclear Physics, Berlageweg 15, Delft, HOLLAND.	Delft Holland	1st week Sept.

5. International Conference on
MAGNETISM
Chairman :
Professor L. Néel,
Laboratoire d'Électrostatique et
de Physique du Métal,
Casier postal no 166,
Grenoble-Gare 38, FRANCE.
- Grenoble
France
- Sept.
14-19
- 5a. The DENSITY of ELECTRONIC
CHARGE SPIN and MOMENTA
Chairman :
Dr E.F. Bertaut,
Laboratoire d'Électrostatique et
de Physique du Métal,
Cedex no 166,
Grenoble-Gare 38, FRANCE.
- Aussois
France
- Sept.
9-12
- 5b. MAGNETIC THIN FILMS
Chairman :
Prof. L. Valenta,
Department of Theoretical
Physics,
Charles University,
Ke Karlovu 3, Prague 2,
CZECHOSLOVAKIA.
- Prague
Czechoslovakia
- Sept.
21-23
6. International Working Seminar on
the ROLE of HISTORY of
PHYSICS in EDUCATION
Chairman :
Prof. A.L. King,
Dartmouth College,
Hanover, New Hampshire 03755,
U.S.A.
- MIT - Cambridge
Mass. U.S.A.
- July
13-17
7. Int. Congress on the EDUCATION
of TEACHERS of PHYSICS in
SECONDARY SCHOOLS
Chairman :
Prof. E. Nagy,
Institute for Experimental
Physics,
Eötvös University,
Muzeum Körút 6-8,
Budapest VIII, HUNGARY.
- Eger
Hungary
- Sept.
11-17

8. XVth International Conference on HIGH ENERGY PHYSICS Kiev USSR Aug. 26-Sept. 4
- Organized by :
 Prof. N.N. Bogolubov,
 Joint Institute for Nuclear Research,
 Head Post Office, Box No. 79,
 Moscow, USSR.
9. STATISTICAL MECHANICS Mexico October 19-24
- Organized by :
 Dr. E. Braun and Dr. A. Morales,
 Comision Nacional de Energia Nuclear,
 Av. Insurgentes Sur 1079,
 Apartado Postal no. 27-190,
 Mexico 18 D. F.
10. 12th International on LOW TEMPERATURE PHYSICS LT-12 Kyoto Japan Sept. 4-10
- Organized by :
 Dr. T. Sugawara,
 Institute for Solid State Physics,
 University of Tokyo,
 7-21-1 Roppongi, Minato-ku,
 Tokyo, JAPAN.
- 10a. TRANSPORT PROPERTIES of SOLIDS Sydney Australia August 27-29
- Organized by :
 Dr. G.K. White,
 CSIRO - Division of Physics,
 Sydney University Grounds,
 Chippendale, NSW 2008,
 AUSTRALIA.
11. DÉCHARGES et ISOLEMENT ÉLECTRIQUES dans le VIDE Waterloo Canada Sept.
- Information :
 Dr. Max Goldman,
 Laboratoire de Synthèse atomique et d'Optique protonique,
 67, rue Maurice-Günsbourg,
 Ivry-sur-Seine 94, FRANCE.

12. IVth International Congress on RADIATION RESEARCH Évian France June 28 July 4

Information :

Secrétariat du IVe Congrès de Radiologie,
c/o Wagon-Lits Cook,
16 rue du Mont-Blanc,
Casier postal 230,
CH-Genève, SWITZERLAND.
(Secretary of International Association for Radiation Research :
Dr. R.F. Kimball, Biology Division, Oak Ridge National Laboratory, P.O. Box Y, Oak Ridge, Tennessee 37830, U.S.A.)

13. SEMICONDUCTORS Boston Mass, U.S.A. August 17-21

Information :

Semiconductors Commission,
c/o Prof. E.W.J. Mitchell,
secretary,
J.J. Thomson Physical Laboratory,
Whiteknights Park, Reading,
Berkshire, ENGLAND.

- 13a. RADIATION EFFECTS in SEMICONDUCTORS Albany New York, U.S.A. August 24-26

Information :

Prof. James W. Corbett,
Organizing Secretary,
Department of Physics,
State University of New York at Albany,
Albany, N.Y. 12203.

14. PRECISION MEASUREMENTS and FUNDAMENTAL CONSTANTS Gaithersburg Maryland, U.S.A. August 3-7

Organized by :

Dr. L. M. Branscomb,
A-363 Physics Building,
National Bureau of Standards,
Washington, D.C. 20234, U.S.A.

15. The PHYSICS and CHEMISTRY of SEMICONDUCTOR HETEROJUNCTIONS
 Budapest Hungary October 11-17
 Organized by
 Dr. G. Szigeti
 Ujpest 1,
 P.O. Box 76,
 Budapest IV, HUNGARY
16. PHYSICS of METASTABLE ALLOYS
 Brela Yugoslavia Sept.
 Information :
 Prof. M. Paic,
 Institute of Physics,
 University of Zagreb,
 P.O. Box 02-816,
 Zagreb, YUGOSLAVIA.
17. X-RAY SPECTROSCOPY
 Paris France
 Information :
 Mlle Yvette Cauchois,
 Laboratoire de Chimie physique,
 11, rue Pierre et Marie Curie,
 Paris Ve, FRANCE.
18. International Conference on THERMODYNAMICS
 Cardiff Wales, U.K. April 1-4
 Organized by :
 Professor P.T. Landsberg,
 Dept. of Applied Mathematics and
 Mathematical Physics, University
 College of South Wales and
 Monmouthshire,
 Cathays Park, Cardiff CF1 3NR,
 UNITED KINGDOM.
19. HOLOGRAPHY
 Besançon France July
 CIO Conference organized by :
 Prof. J. Viénot,
 Département de Physique,
 Université de Besançon,
 8, rue de la Convention,
 Besançon, FRANCE.

20. INSTRUMENTATION
Inf.: Prof. V.P. Dzhelepov,
Joint Institute for
Nuclear Research,
Head Post Office Box 79,
Moscow, USSR.

Dubna
USSR

Sept.
8-12

Annexe V
Appendix V

**Delegates to the XIIIth General Assembly, Dubrovnik,
Yugoslavia, 11th-13th September, 1969**

(Where known, the names of Heads of Delegations are in bold type).

ARGENTINA	J.J. Giambiagi
AUSTRALIA	J.S. Dryden , W. Boas
AUSTRIA	F. Regler
BELGIUM	W. Dekeyser
BOLIVIA	—
BRAZIL	—
BULGARIA	E. Djakov, E. Nadjakov
CANADA	J.M. Robson , G. Herzberg, H.E. Duckworth, R.E. Bell, I.M. Templeton.
CHINA (Formosa)	—
CUBA	—
CZECHOSLOVAKIA	M. Blazek, J. Krutel, M. Matyas, M. Trlifaj
DENMARK	S. Rozental , F. Ingerslev
FINLAND	L. Simons
FRANCE	A. Kastler, L. Néel, P. Auger, A. Blanc-Lapierre, E.F. Bertaut, J. Bok, G.A. Boutry, P. Cüer, P. Fleury, G. Fournet, Ch. Guillaud, A. Guinier, R. Pauthenet, J. Teillac, J. Terrien, J. Badoz
EAST GERMANY	K. Lanius , J. Auth, A. Büchner

WEST GERMANY	M. Kersten , F. Bopp, W. Buchel, H. Maier-Leibnitz, K.-H. Riewe, U. Stille, F. Trendelenburg, W. Kroebel
GREAT BRITAIN	N. Kurti , J.F. Allen, W.C. Marshall, E.W.J. Mitchell, R.S. Pearse, Miss A.C. Stickland, Sir Gordon Sutherland, J.G. Wilson
HOLLAND	J. de Boer, P. Mazur
HUNGARY	L. Pal , Z. Bodo, A. Budo, E. Fenyves, A. Konya, I. Kovacs, Gy Marx, Gy Szigeti, S. Szalay, Gy Turchanyi, T. Tarnoczy
INDIA	S. Bhagavantam , B.D. Nag Chaudhuri, A.R. Verma, S. Ramaseshan
IRELAND	C. O'Ceallaigh
ISRAEL	—
ITALY	G. Toraldo , D. Sette, G. Occhialini
JAPAN	M. Kotani , S. Yokokawa
MEXICO	—
NORWAY	—
PAKISTAN	G. Murtaza, K. Ahmad
POLAND	L. Sosnowski, M. Danysz, I. Malecki, J. Weysenhoff, Mrs. K. Leibler
ROMANIA	I. Agarbiceanu
SOUTH AFRICA	—
SOUTH KOREA	—
SPAIN	L. Villena , A. Lara, L. Plaza
SWEDEN	E. Rudberg, G. Ekspong, L. Huldt
SWITZERLAND	P. Huber , J. Rossel, H.H. Staub
UNITED ARAB REPUBLIC	—

UNITED STATES OF
AMERICA

W.W. Havens, Jr, D.A. Bromley, C.
Herring, H.W. Koch, H. Wolfe, R.F.
Bacher

U.S.S.R.

B.M. Vul, plus other delegates, D.I.
Blokhintsev

YUGOSLAVIA

A. Milojevic, G. Alaga, M. Paic, A.
Moljk, B. Galek, O. Peciare, M. Mlad-
jenovic, M. Opredkar, I. Slaus, P.
Tomas, D. Ivanovic, I. Supek

**Annexe VI
Appendix VI**

**ÉTATS FINANCIERS
FINANCIAL STATEMENTS**

1 jan. 1966 — 31 déc. 1968

**Bilan au 31 décembre 1968
Balance Sheet as at December 31, 1968**

**ACTIF
ASSETS**

En CAISSE et DÉPÔT
CASH and DEPOSIT

	taux rate	U.S. Dollars	
4,274.05 dollars canadiens	1.07¼	\$ 3,985.13	
33,236.87 dollars américains		33,236.87	\$ 37,222.00
COTISATIONS à RECEVOIR DUES RECEIVABLE			4,900.00
INTÉRÊTS COURUS ACCRUED INTEREST			500.00
			<u>\$ 42,622.00</u>

**AVOIRS
SURPLUS**

Solde au 31 décembre 1965 Balance as at December 31st, 1965	\$ 35,786.45
Ajouter : Revenu net des années 66-68 Add : Net income for the years 66-68	\$ 6,835.55
Solde au 31 décembre 1968 Balance as at December 31st, 1968	\$ 42,622.00
	<u>\$ 42,622.00</u>

État des recettes et déboursés
Statement of Receipts and Disbursements

RECETTES RECEIPTS	1966	1967	1968	Total
Subventions de I.C.S.U.	\$13,125.00	\$13,125.00	\$13,125.00	\$39,375.00
Grants from U.N.E.S.C.O.				
Cotisations des pays membres	24,000.00	41,500.00	42,000.00	107,500.00
Dues from member countries				
Divers Miscellaneous	—	1,093.80	1,421.15	2,514.95
	<u>\$37,125.00</u>	<u>\$55,718.80</u>	<u>\$56,546.15</u>	<u>\$149,389.95</u>
DÉBOURSÉS				
DISBURSEMENTS				
Conférences - I.C.S.U. UNESCO	\$13,125.00	\$13,125.00	\$13,125.00	\$ 39,375.00
Conférences I.U.P.A.P.	14,158.10	22,875.00	28,450.00	65,483.10
Frais de déplacement — Commissions	8,283.69	3,000.00	5,410.00	16,693.69
Travelling expenses — Commissions				
Frais de déplacement — Exécutif	4,323.38	4,204.28	4,371.82	12,899.48
Travelling expenses — Executive Com.				
Secrétariat	1,498.40	1,617.63	1,305.17	4,421.20
Impression	897.80	328.68	273.68	1,500.16
Printing				
Frais de banque, échange	226.74	26.75	285.78	539.27
Bank charges, exchange				
Cotisations Subscriptions	1,067.50	680.00	1,030.00	2,777.50
Cotisations des pays membres annulées	(2,335.00)	—	1,200.00	1,200.00
Dues from member countries cancelled				
	<u>\$41,245.61</u>	<u>\$45,857.34</u>	<u>\$55,451.45</u>	<u>\$144,889.40</u>
Surplus (Déficit)	(\$4,120.61)	\$ 9,861.46	\$ 1,094.70	\$ 6,835.55

IV – SOME RESOLUTIONS PASSED BY GENERAL ASSEMBLIES

International Conferences :

«For the patronage of the Union to be granted to a Conference, which implies, in principle, a subsidy from the Union fixed according to needs and available funds, it is necessary :

1. that the Executive Committee should have approved this subsidy, taking into account the future interest of the subject and other subjects proposed for Conferences ;
2. that the organizers of the Conference should have, beforehand, undertaken to submit to the President of the Union the precise date, scientific programme, place of meeting, and choice of people to be invited to present the principal papers. The choice of the speakers should be made in such a way as to ensure the greatest possible **international** participation at the Conference. »

(London, 1954)

Visas

«The International Union of Pure and Applied Physics, considering that free travel possibilities of all scientists for the participation in international scientific conferences form an indispensable basis for successful international co-operation, and considering further that this question not only touches the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics, but all scientific Unions, requests the International Council of Scientific Unions :

1. to encourage its national members to take appropriate steps with their respective governments for arranging facilities for granting exit and entry visas to all scientists attending international scientific conferences;
2. to bring the problem to the notice of the United Nations with the request that a way be found for the free movement of scientists attending scientific conferences and meetings. »

(Warsaw, 1963)

Elections

« The Assembly then discussed the procedure to be adopted in future for the selection of names to fill vacancies. It was decided that all proposals should be sent by National Committees to the Secretary-General well before the next Assembly. All of the proposals would then be given to delegates on arrival at the Assembly. The Executive Committee would have the right to add names to this list. It would, however, make its choice just before the opening of the Assembly, and a paper with the Executive Committee's proposals would be available at the beginning of the Assembly. Thus, the delegates would see all the proposals and know the Executive Committee's recommendations one or two days before the final vote is taken. It was agreed that additional names could be proposed from the floor of the Assembly before the final vote. »

(Warsaw, 1963)

Young Scientists

« In view of the desirability of providing continuity in the growth of close international contacts between physicists, the General Assembly of IUPAP considers it highly desirable to include some younger scientists among delegations to large international conferences sponsored by IUPAP in addition to leading scientists in the particular field. »

(Warsaw, 1963)

I.C.S.U.

« The General Assembly of the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics approves in principle the proposals of the reorganizing committee of ICSU, but makes the following recommendation :

In order to safeguard the scientific character implied in ICSU's name, it is highly desirable to prevent the voting power of the unions being outbalanced by the voting power of the national members in the General Assembly of ICSU. Balance could be achieved by increasing the vote of the unions and by giving each general union more votes than each specialized union. It is

realized that, as the number of unions and nations adhering to ICSU increases, the voting procedure will need modification ».

(Warsaw, 1963)

Scientific Papers

« Every scientific paper, with the possible exception of short letters, should be published with a synopsis (or abstract) in English, French or Russian. It is desirable to print it also in a second language. »

(Warsaw, 1963)

Publications

« The General Assembly approves :

1. The Guide for the Preparation of Authors' Abstracts for Publication with authorization to make some modifications in order to achieve accord with UNESCO ;
2. The Guide for the Preparation of Scientific Papers for Publication with authorization to make some modifications in order to achieve accord with UNESCO ;
3. The statement on Bibliographic References on the second page of the Commission report ;
4. The following statement on publication of conference proceedings : The assembly of collections of preprints for the participants does not constitute satisfactory publication of the proceedings of a conference. It is highly desirable that conference proceedings should be refereed in the same way as journal articles. When the proceedings are published as a unit, rather than by separate submission of the papers to appropriate journals, publication should be in a regular or special issue of a journal or in a book which will be made widely available through established channels.

A paper may be included in the proceedings of a conference, even though it may have been published first as a journal article. In this case, the bibliographic reference should be given. The published proceedings should be covered by the abstracting

services, and conference secretaries should assume responsibility for bringing them to the attention of the abstract journals.

The General Assembly recommends :

5. The adoption of a single standard for Journal Title Abbreviations and, to that effect, draws the attention of ISO to the work of Committee Z-29 of the American Standards Association. »

(Basle, 1966)

Physics Education

« Considering that :

1. advances in the rapidly growing fields of pure and applied Physics not only deepen mankind's understanding of the universe, but through their applications have profound implications for human welfare and destiny ;
2. discoveries in Physics, the most basic of the natural sciences, strongly affect all of the basic and applied sciences and the professions related to them ;
3. the teaching of Physics to advanced students of physics, to students in related scientific and professional fields, and to those who will become part of an enlightened citizenry can only be done well by those who are themselves active in creating or in using new knowledge ; and
4. research reaches its culmination in the communication of new knowledge to others, and employers should recognize the importance of evaluation and synthesis of existing knowledge which often require depth of insight and creativity at least as great as primary research :

the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics resolves that :

1. Research and education be carried on in the closest possible association ;
2. Any tendencies toward divergence between the activities of advancing and of disseminating knowledge be vigorously

counteracted and efforts to improve the teaching of Physics be encouraged ;

3. Excellence in teaching and in the dissemination of knowledge about Physics should receive the same recognition as excellence in research. In this connexion, all sponsoring agencies and foundations should give financial support for the preparation of critical reviews of current developments and for the compilation of critical data ;
4. Talented research workers be expected to teach, and their exemption from teaching occur only in special circumstances and not as a reward for excellence ;
5. Teachers be encouraged to maintain their intellectual vitality and participation in the advancement of knowledge by being given time for research or for closely related scholarly activities; and
6. Research workers in Research Institutes and Industrial Laboratories should collaborate with Academic Institutions in the training and education of advanced students in Physics. »

(Dubrovnik, 1969)

Symbols

« The General Assembly recommends :
that authors be encouraged to adopt the SI units for data in Physics journals as recommended by the SUN Commission, the Conférence générale des poids et mesures and the International Organization for Standardization and by other international unions closely related to Physics. Editors are urged to use persuasion rather than stronger measures to secure the cooperation of authors in the choice of symbols for physical quantities and of units, but should require that standard symbols for units be used except when the names of the units are written out in full. »

(Dubrovnik, 1969)

EXECUTIVE COMMITTEE

(to hold office until the 1972 General Assembly)

President : Prof. Robert F. BACHER (1966)

Office of the Provost
California Institute of Technology
Pasadena, California 91109, U.S.A.

Past-President : Prof. D.I. BLOKHINTSEV (1960)

Academy of Sciences of the U.S.S.R.
Leninskii prospekt 14
Moscow B-71, U.S.S.R.

First Vice-President : Prof. H. MAIER-LEIBNITZ (1969)

Institut Max von Laue – Paul Langevin
Cedex 156
Grenoble–Gare 38, FRANCE.

Vice-Presidents : Prof. G. BERNARDINI (1966)

Scuola Normale Superiore
Pisa, ITALY.

Dr. S. BHAGAVANTAM (1966)

Ministry of Defence
Room 132-B
South Block
New Delhi 11, INDIA.

Dr. Walter BOAS (1966)

47, Wills Street
Kew, Victoria 3101, AUSTRALIA.

Prof. W. DEKEYSER (1966)

Laboratorium voor Kristallografie,
Krijgslaan 105,
Ghent, BELGIUM.

Prof. Alfred KASTLER (1969)

Laboratoire de Physique
École Normale Supérieure
24, rue Lhomond
Paris Ve, FRANCE.

Prof. L. PAL (1969)
Central Research Institute for Physics
Hungarian Academy of Sciences
Postfach 49
Budapest 114, HUNGARY.

Prof. S. ROZENTAL (1966)
Niels Bohr Institutet
Blegdamsvej 17
Copenhagen DK-2100, DENMARK.

Prof. V. WEISSKOPF (1969)
Department of Physics
Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Cambridge, Mass. 02139 U.S.A.

Secretary-General : Prof. C.C. BUTLER (1963)
Department of Physics
Imperial College
Prince Consort Road
London S.W. 7, ENGLAND.
Tel. : 01-589-5111

Associate Secretary-General : Prof. Larkin KERWIN (1963)
Vice-Rector
Université Laval
Québec 10, P.Q., CANADA.
Tél. : 418-656-2131

Telex : Prof. Butler – Impcol London 261503

Prof. Kerwin – BibuLaval Quebec 0113560

LIST of NATIONAL COMMITTEES (38)

Units = number of subscription units :

at present each unit : U.S. \$250.

starting January 1st, 1971 : U.S. \$300.

Votes = number of votes at the General Assembly.

Units	Votes	Name of Country	Address
2	2	Argentina	Dr. Carlos M. VARSAVSKY, Presidente, Asociacion Fisica Argentina, Instituto Argentino de Radioastronomia, Casilla de Correo No. 5, Villa Elisa (Pcia. de Bs. As), Buenos Aires.
6	3	Australia	Dr. J.S. DRYDEN, Chairman, Australian National Committee, Division of Applied Physics, C.S.I.R.O., University Grounds — City Road, Chippendale, N.S.W. 2008.
1	1	Austria	Austrian Society of Physics, Lenau-gasse 10, A-1082 Wien.
4	3	Belgium	M. NEVE de MEVERGNIES, Laboratoire du Centre d'Études de l'Énergie nucléaire, Mol-Donk.
1	1	Bolivia	Dr. Oscar SAAVEDRA, Laboratorio de Fisica Cosmica, Universidad Mayor de San Andrés, La Paz.
2	2	Brazil	Dr. A.M. COUCEIRO, Brazilian Committee for Physics, Conselho Nacional de Pesquisas, Avenida Marechal Camara 350, Rio de Janeiro G.B.
1	1	Bulgaria	IUPAP National Committee, The Academy of Sciences of Bulgaria, 1, Street of 7 November, Sofia.

8	4	Canada	Dr I.M. TEMPLETON Division de Physique pure, Conseil national de Recherches, Ottawa 7.
1	1	China	Dr. Y.K. TAI, President, The Physical Society of the Republic of China, P.O. Box No. 6030, Taipei, Taiwan.
1	1	Cuba	Sr. Giraldo Acevedo FANEGO, Director de Relaciones Internacionales, Academia de Ciencias de Cuba, Capitolio Nacional, La Havana.
3	2	Czechoslovakia	Prof. Dr. M. VALOUCH, Jednota cs. matematiku a fyziku, Spalena 26, Nove Mesto, Praha 1.
3	2	Denmark	Prof. S. ROZENTAL, Niels Bohr Institutet, 15 Blegdamsvej, Copenhagen.
1	1	Finland	Mr. L. LAITINEN, Vakaustoimisto, Mariank. 14, Helsinki 17.
12	5	France	Prof. R. LENNUIER, Laboratoires des Recherches physiques, Tour 22, 9, Quai St-Bernard, Paris Ve.
4	3	East Germany	Dr. A. BUCHNER, Physikalische Gesellschaft in der Deutschen Demokratischen Republik, Am Kupfergraben 7, Berlin W. 8.
12	5	West Germany	D. K.H. RIEWE, Deutsche Physikalische Gesellschaft E.V., Heraeusstrasse 12-14, Postfach 169, 645 Hanau/Main.
15	5	Great Britain	Dr. D.C. MARTIN, C.B.E., The Royal Society, 6 Carlton House Terrace, London S.W. 1.

4	3	Holland	Dr. H.J.M. LEBESQUE, Technical Physics University, Lorentzweg 1, Delft.
2	2	Hungary	Prof. G. TURCHANYI, Orvosi Fizikai Intezet, Puskin u. 9, Budapest VIII.
4	3	India	Dr. S. BHAGAVANTAM, The Ministry of Defence, South Block, New Delhi 11, Room 132-B.
1	1	Ireland	Dr. C.P. O'TOOLE, secretary, Irish National Committee for Physics, Royal Irish Academy, 19, Dawson Street, Dublin 2.
2	2	Israel	Dr. A.J. GREENFIELD, secretary, Physics Society of Israel, Department of Physics, Bar-Ilan University, Ramat Gan.
12	5	Italy	Dr. P. CALDIROLA, Istituto di Scienze Fisiche, Università degli Studi di Milano, Via Celoria 16, Milano.
8	4	Japan	Prof. Isao IMAI, Department of Physics, Faculty of Science, The University of Tokyo, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo 113.
2	2	Mexico	Prof. M.S. VALLARTA, Comision Nacional de Energia Nuclear, Insurgentes 1079.3, Mexico 18 D.F.
1	1	Norway	Prof. Kjell HERLOFSEN, Manager, Det Norske Videnskaps-Akademi, Drammensveien 78, Oslo 2.
1	1	Pakistan	Dr. M.R. SIDDIQI, President, Pakistan Academy of Sciences, 77-E. Satellite Town, Rawalpindi, West Pakistan.

4	3	Poland	Prof. Mr. Józef WERLE, secretary, Polish National Committee, Institute of Physics, Hoza 69, Warszawa .
3	2	România	Prof. I. AGARBICEANU, Academia Republicii Socialiste România, Calea Victoriei Nr. 125, Bucuresti .
1	1	South Africa	South African Council for Scientific and Industrial Research, The Head, Science Co-operation Division, P.O. Box 395, Pretoria .
1	1	South Korea	Dr. Sook-II KWUN, Public Relation Secretary, Korean Physical Society, c/o Department of Physics, Seoul National University, Seoul .
4	3	Spain	Dr Lorenzo PLAZA, Instituto de Optica, Serrano 121, Madrid .
8	4	Sweden	Prof. L. HULDT, Division of Physics, Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm 70 .
2	2	Switzerland	Prof. P. HUBER, Institute of Physics, Klingelbergstrasse 82, Basle .
1	1	United Arab Republic	The Director, Supreme Council for Scientific Research, Department of Scientific Societies, 101, Kasr El-Einy Street, Cairo .
18	5	United States of America	Dr. Hugh ODISHAW, Division of Physical Sciences, National Academy of Sciences, 2101, Constitution Avenue, Washington, D.C. 20418 .
12	5	U.S.S.R.	Dr. B.A. LESHKOVSTEV, Secretary, National Committee of Soviet Physicists, Academy of Sciences of the U.S.S.R., Leninskii prospekt 14, Moscow B-71 .
1	1	Yugoslavia	Prof. A. MILOJEVIC, Instituut za Fiziku, Postfach 550, Belgrade .

SPECIALIZED COMMISSIONS

During the course of its history, the Union has established a number of expert committees or commissions. The purpose of these committees varies considerably. For example, one of the important ones, called Symbols, Units and Nomenclature (SUN), meets regularly and prepares recommendations on various symbols and units, as its title suggests, which are submitted for approval by the General Assembly. Several of the special committees confine their work to the organization of international conferences, for example, in magnetism, cosmic rays and various other topics.

The General Assembly of the Union appoints the members of the commissions including the chairmen and secretaries. Commissions are expected to make nominations which must be sent to the Secretary-General a few months before each General Assembly.

The 1931 General Assembly decided that the President and the Secretary-General should be *ex officio* members of all Union commissions.

The normal period of service for a member of a commission is six years. Exceptions to this rule can be made, particularly for secretaries of commissions.

The 1960 General Assembly decided that commissions should be limited to six or seven members. In addition, some corresponding or associate members can be appointed. They are to be regarded as advisers to commissions. They will receive all the appropriate commission papers and may attend meetings in the place of an absent member.

It is essential that secretaries of commissions should send copies of all the commission papers to the Secretary-General of the Union.

A Commission usually meets during an international conference held under the auspice of the commission. Some commissions, for example the SUN Commission and the Publications Commission, may need to hold special meetings from time to time.

Commissions are granted a travel allowance from Union funds for these meetings. However, it is usually necessary for members of commissions to seek additional travel grants in their respective countries in order that an adequate number of meetings may be held.

At present, there are 16 specialized commissions. The membership of these commissions is given below. The date after each name is the year of the person's appointment to his class of membership. A summary of the activities of each Commission was deposited with the Secretary-General at the Dubrovnik General Assembly. Highlights are to be found in Appendix II of the Minutes of this meeting. Inquiries concerning the work of commissions should be addressed to the appropriate chairmen or secretaries.

1 – FINANCIAL COMMISSION

Prof. Robert F. BACHER (1966) Office of the Provost, California Institute of Technology, **Pasadena**, California 91109.

Prof. F. DEKEYSER (1966) Laboratorium voor Kristallografie, Krijgslaan 105, **Ghent**, BELGIUM.

2 – COMMISSION for SYMBOLS, UNITS and NOMENCLATURE (S.U.N.) (1931)

Chairman : Prof. Erik RUDBERG (1954) K Vetenskapsakademien, **104 05 Stockholm 50**, SWEDEN.

Secretary : Prof. Dr. U. STILLE (1954) Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt, Bundesallee 100, **D-33 Braunschweig**, WEST GERMANY.

Members : J. deBoer, Holland (1948) H.C. Wolfe, United States (1957) J. Rossel, Switzerland (1959) J. Terrien, France (1966) E. Djakov, Bulgaria (1969) M.L. McGlashen, United Kingdom (1969)

Corresponding Members : L. Rosenfeld, Denmark (1963) I.I. Novikov, U.S.S.R. (1966) D. Ilkovic, Czechoslovakia (1969) K. Shimoda, Japan (1969) L. Villena, Spain (1969) G. Volkoff, Canada (1969).

3 – COMMISSION on THERMODYNAMICS and STATISTICAL MECHANICS (1945)

Chairman : Prof. H. FRÖHLICH, F.R.S. (1963) Department of Theoretical Physics, The Chadwick Laboratory, P.O. Box 147, **Liverpool**, ENGLAND.

Secretary : Prof. Dr. P. MAZUR (1966) Instituut-Lorentz voor Theoretische Natuurkunde, Nieuwsteeg 18, **Leiden**, NETHERLANDS.

Members : R. Kubo, Japan (1963) L. Waldman, West Germany (1966) E. Montroll, United States (1966) C. Block, France (1966) A. Abrikosov, U.S.S.R. (1969) D. Betts, Canada (1969)

Corresponding members : N. Trappeniers, Holland (1966) A. Dacev, Bulgaria (1966) H. Wergeland, Norway (1966)

4 – COMMISSION on COSMIC RAYS (1947)

Chairman : Prof. J.G. WILSON (1963) Department of Physics, The University of Leeds, **Leeds LS2 9JT, ENGLAND.**

Secretary : Prof. M.G.K. MENON (1963) Director, Tata Institute of Fundamental Research, Homi Bhabha Road, Colaba, **Bombay 5, INDIA.**

Members : P. Meyer, United States (1966) S.N. Vernov, U.S.S.R. (1969) B. Peters, Denmark (1969) S. Somogyi, Hungary (1969) J. Nishimura, Japan (1969)

Corresponding members : E. Bagge, West Germany (1969) (Miss) R. Gall, Mexico (1969) C. Castagnoli, Italy (1969) J. Gierula, Poland (1969).

5 – COMMISSION on VERY LOW TEMPERATURE (1949)

Chairman : Prof. J. BARDEEN (1963) Department of Physics, University of Illinois, **Urbana, Illinois 61801, U.S.A.**

Secretary : Prof. T. SUGAWARA (1966) Institute for Solid State Physics, University of Tokyo, 7-22-1, Roppongi, Minatoku, **Tokyo 106, JAPAN.**

Members : N.E. Alekseevskii (1966) Institute for Physical Problems, Academy of Sciences of the USSR, Vorobyevskoye Shosse 2, **Moscow B-334, U.S.S.R.**

W. Buckel (1966) Physikalisches Institut der Tech. Hochschule, **Karlsruhe, WEST GERMANY.**

J.L. Olsen (1966) Eidg. Technische Hochschule, Laboratorium für Festkörperphysik, Gloriastrasse 35, **Zürich 8006, SWITZERLAND.**

S. Safrata (1966) Nuclear Research Institute, Czechoslovak Academy of Sciences, **Rez**, CZECHOSLOVAKIA.

K.W. Takonis (1966) Kamerlingh Onnes Laboratory, University of Leiden, **Leiden**, NETHERLANDS.

B. Dreyfus (1969) Université de Grenoble, **Grenoble**, FRANCE.

Corresponding Members : A.H. Cooke (1969) Clarendon Laboratory, **Oxford**, ENGLAND.

O.V. Lounasmaa (1969) Technical University of Helsinki, **Otaniemi** (Helsinki), FINLAND.

A.K. Sreedhar (1969) Solid State Physics Laboratory, Lucknow Road, **Delhi**, INDIA.

6 – COMMISSION ON PUBLICATIONS (1949)

Chairman : Dr. H.C. WOLFE (1966) American Institute of Physics, 335 East, 45th Street, **New York**, New York 10017, U.S.A.

Secretary : Prof. J. van den HANDEL (1966) Kamerlingh Onnes Laboratory, Nieuwsteeg 18, **Leiden**, NETHERLANDS.

Members : S. Pasternack (1966) Brookhaven National Laboratory, **Upton, L.I.**, New York 11973, U.S.A.

J. Weysenhoff (1966) 15 Slowackiego, m. 9, **Krakow**, POLAND.

B.R. Coles (1969) Physics Department, Imperial College, Prince Consort Road, **London S.W. 7**, ENGLAND.

J. Friedel (1969) Service de Physique des Solides, Bâtiment 210, Faculté des Sciences, **Orsay 91**, FRANCE.

E.M. Lifshits (1969) Vorobyovskoe shosse 2, **Moscow B-334**, U.S.S.R.

M. Matyas (1969) Institute of Solid State Physics, Czechoslovak Academy of Sciences, Cukrovarnicka 10, **Praha 6**, CZECHOSLOVAKIA.

Corresponding Members : K. Kinoshita (1966) Faculty of Science, Gakushuin University, Mejiro, **Tokyo**, JAPAN.

L. Villena (1966) Avenida de la Habana 147, **Madrid 16**, SPAIN.

E. Bretnütz (1969) Physikalische Berichte Budesallee 100, **33 Braunschweig**, WEST GERMANY.

M. Mladjenovic (1969) Institut za Nuklearne Nauke « B. Kidric », **Beograd**, Vinca, YUGOSLAVIA.

P. Papali (1969) Società Italiana di Fisica, via L. degli Andalò n. 2, **40124 Bologna**, ITALY.

C.I. Pedersen (1969) Institute of Physics and Physical Society, 1 Lowther Gardens, Prince Consort Road, **London S.W. 7**, ENGLAND.

7 – ACOUSTICS COMMISSION (1951)

Chairman : Prof. Dr. I. MALECKI (1966) Directeur du Dépt de la Politique scientifique et de la Promotion des Sciences fondamentales, UNESCO, Place de Fontenoy, **Paris 75**, FRANCE.

Secretary : Dr. D. SETTE (1966) Istituto di Fisica della Facolta Ingegneria, Piazzale delle Science 5, Universita di Roma, **Roma 00100**, ITALIA.

Members : Y. Saneyoshi, Japan (1966) E. Zwicker, West Germany (1966) I. Hirsch, U.S.A. (1969) J. Mattei, France (1969) A. Rimskii-Korsakov, U.S.S.R. (1969) F. Tarnoczy, Hungary (1969).

Corresponding members : F. Ingerslev, Denmark (1951) J. Frenkiel, Belgium (1963) F. Kolmer, Czechoslovakia (1966) D.W. Robinson, United Kingdom (1966) J.L. Fuchs, Argentina (1969) A. Lara, Spain (1969).

Observers from IUBS, IUPS, IUTAM.

8 – SEMICONDUCTORS COMMISSION (1957)

Chairman : Prof. E.W.J. MITCHELL (1963) J.J. Thompson Physical Laboratory, Whiteknights Park, **Reading**, Berks., ENGLAND.

Secretary : Prof. J. BOK (1966) Laboratoire de Physique, École Normale Supérieure, 24, rue Lhomond, **Paris Ve**, FRANCE.

Members : V.S. Vavilov, U.S.S.R. (1966) H. Welker, West Germany (1966) J. Auth, East Germany (1969) E. Kane, U.S.A. (1969) H. Kawamura, Japan (1969) J. Tauks, Czechoslovakia (1969).

Corresponding Members : H.Y. Fan, U.S.A. (1969) R. Grigorevici, Romania (1969) G.C. Jain, India (1969).

9 – MAGNETISM COMMISSION (1957)

Chairman : Dr. W.C. MARSHALL (1966) Atomic Energy Research Establishment, **Harwell**, Didcot, Berks., ENGLAND.

Secretary : Dr. G.T. RADO (1966) Naval Research Laboratory, **Washington**, D.C. 20390 U.S.A.

Members : A. Blandin, France (1969) S. Chikazumi, Japan (1969) C.J. Gorter, Holland (1969) E. Kneller, West Germany (1969) † L.V. Kirenski U.S.S.R. (1969).

Corresponding Members : L. Valenta, Czechoslovakia (1963) W. Andra, East Germany (1969) C. Herring, U.S.A. (1969) R. Kubo, Japan (1969) R. Pauthenèt, France (1969).

10 – SOLID STATE COMMISSION (1960)

Chairman : Dr. Walter BOAS (1963) 47 Wills Street, Kew, **Victoria 3101**, AUSTRALIA.

Secretary : Prof. E.F. BERTAUT (1966) Laboratoire d'Électrostatique et de Physique du métal, Rue des Martyrs, Cedex no 166, **Grenoble-Gare 38**, FRANCE.

Members : L.P. Gorkov, Moscow (1966) W.J. Merz, Zurich (1966) (Ferroelectricity) T. Nagamiya, Osaka (1966) A. Seeger, Stuttgart (1966) G. Szigeti, Budapest (1966) (Luminescence) J.M. Cowley, Arizona, USA (1969) (IUCr).

Corresponding Members : G. Chiarotti, Rome (1966) A. Guinier, Paris (1966) J.S. Koehler, Illinois, U.S.A. (1966) R. Blinc,

Ljubliana (1969) S.C. Jain, India (1969) R. Kaishev, Sofia (1969)

11 – COMMISSION on PARTICLES and FIELDS (1957)

Chairman : Prof. A.A. LOGUNOV (1969) Institute of High Energy Physics, **Serpukhov**, U.S.S.R.

Secretary : Prof. Robert L. WALKER (1966) California Institute of Technology, Lauritsen Laboratory, **Pasadena**, California 91109, U.S.A.

Members : T.G. Pickavance (1963) Science Research Council, Rutherford High Energy Laboratory, **Chilton**, Didcot, Berks., ENGLAND.

V.P. Dzhelepov (1966) Laboratory of Nuclear Problems, Joint Institute for Nuclear Research, Head Post Office, Box No. 79, **Moscow**, U.S.S.R.

K. Lanius (1966) Forschungsstelle für Physik hoher Energien, DAW, Platanenallee 6, **1615 Zeuthen/Berlin**, D.D.R.

S. Suwa (1966) Institute for Nuclear Study, University of Tokyo, Midori-Cho, Tanashi-Shi, **Tokyo**, JAPAN.

G. Salvini (1969) Istituto di Fisica dell'Università, Piazzale delle Scienze 5, **Roma**, ITALY.

C.N. Yang (1969) Department of Physics, State University of New York at Stony Brook, **Stony Brook**, L.I., New York 11790 U.S.A.

Corresponding Members : L. Van Hove (1966) CERN, **1211 Genève 23**, SUISSE.

G. Ekspong (1969) The University of Stockholm, Institute of Physics, Vanadisvagen 9, **Stockholm**, SWEDEN.

H. Joos (1969) DESY, Notkestieg 1, **2 Hamburg 52**, FED. REP. of GERMANY.

A. Lagarrigue (1969) Laboratoire de l'Accélérateur linéaire, Faculté des Sciences, Bâtiment 200, **Orsay 91**, FRANCE.

Y. Ne'eman (1969) Department of Physics, University of Tel-Aviv, 155 Herzl Street, **Tel-Aviv**, ISRAEL.

J. Pniewski (1969) Institut Fizyki Doswiadczalnej, ul. Hoza 69, **Warszawa**, POLAND.

B.M. Udgaonkar (1969), Tata Institute of Fundamental Research, Colaba, **Bombay 5**, INDIA.

12 – NUCLEAR PHYSICS COMMISSION (1960)

Chairman : Prof. R.E. BELL (1966) Foster Radiation Laboratory, McGill University, **Montreal 2**, CANADA.

Secretary : Prof. J. TEILLAC (1963) Institut du Radium, 11, rue Pierre et Marie Curie, **Paris 75**, FRANCE.

Membres : G.R. Bishop (1966) Department of Natural Philosophy, University of Glasgow, **Glasgow**, GREAT BRITAIN.

S.G. Cohen (1966) Physics Department, Hebrew University of Jerusalem, **Jerusalem**, ISRAEL.

E.M. Frank (1967) Academy of Sciences of the USSR, Leninskii prospekt 14, **Moscow B-71**, U.S.S.R.

T. Lauritsen (1966) Kellogg Radiation Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, 1201 East, California Boulevard, **Pasadena**, California 91109, U.S.A.

R. Remanna (1966) Atomic Energy Establishment — Trombay, Apollo Pier Road, **Bombay 1**, INDIA.

H. Schopper (1966) Institut for Expt. I. Kernphysik der Universitat, Postfach 3640 — Karlsruhe, **Karlsruhe 75**, WEST GERMANY.

Corresponding Members : E. Baumgartner (1969) Physikalische Anstalt Universitat Basel, Klingelbergstrasse 82, **Basel 4000**, SWITZERLAND.

J. Fowler (1966) Oak Ridge National Laboratory, P.O. Box X, **Oak Ridge**, Tennessee 37830, U.S.A.

R. Ricci (1969) Istituto di Fisica dell'Universita di Padova, **Padova**, ITALY.

M. Sakai (1969) Institute of Nuclear Study, Midori-cho 3-2-1, Tanashi, **Tokyo**, JAPAN.

I. Slaus (1969) Institut « R. Boskovic », **Zagreb**, YUGOSLAVIA.

S. Szalay (1966) Institut of Nuclear Research, Hungarian Academy of Sciences, 18/c Bem t \grave{e} r — Pf. 51, **Debrecen 1**, HUNGARY.

13 – ATOMIC MASSES and RELATED CONSTANTS COMMISSION (1960)

Chairman : Dr. A.H. WAPSTRA (1960) Institute for Nuclear Physics Research, Oosterringdijk 18, **Amsterdam O**, NETHERLANDS.

Secretary : Dr. E.R. COHEN (1966) Science Center — Aerospace and Systems Group, North American Rockwell Corporation, 1049 Camino dos Rios, **Thousand Oaks**, California 91360, U.S.A.

Members : W.H. Johnson, Jr., U.S.A. (1966) I.P. Selinov, U.S.S.R. (1966) H.H. Staub, Switzerland (1966) J. Terrien, France (1966) J.H. Bjerregaard, Denmark (1969) J.H. Sanders, United Kingdom (1969).

Corresponding members : W.W. Buechner, U.S.A. (1960) H. Duckworth, Canada (1960) U. Stille, West Germany (1960) J. Mattauch, West Germany (1966) K. Ogata, Japan (1966).

14 – COMMISSION on PHYSICS EDUCATION (1960)

Chairman : Prof. Hans H. STAUB (1966) Physik-Institut der Universität, Schönberggasse 9, **Zürich 8001**, SWITZERLAND.

Secretary : Dr. William C. KELLY (1966) National Research Council, 2101 Constitution Avenue, N.W., **Washington, D.C.** 20418, U.S.A.

Members : A.S. Akhmatov (1963) Novoslobodskaja 62, ap. 402, Physical Laboratory, Stankin, **Moscow A-55**, U.S.S.R.

W. Schaffer (1966) Department of Physics, University of Cape Town, Rondebosch, **Cape Town**, SOUTH AFRICA.

Michel-Y. Bernard (1969) Conservatoire national des Arts et M \acute{e} tiers, 292, rue St-Martin, **Paris 3e**, FRANCE.

Laxman S. Kothari (1969) 5, University Road, **Delhi**, INDIA.

W. Kroebel (1969) Institute for Applied Physics, University of Kiel, New University House 34, **Kiel 23**, GERMANY.

John L. Lewis (1969) Malvern College, **Malvern**, Worcestershire, ENGLAND.

Jozef Werle (1969) Department of Mathematics and Physics, Warsaw University, **Warsaw**, POLAND.

Corresponding Members : P. Fleury (1960) Institut d'Optique théorique et appliquée, 3, boulevard Pasteur, **Paris 15e**, FRANCE.

D. Sette (1960) Istituto di Fisica, Facolta di Ingegneria, Citta Universitaria, Piazzale delle Scienze 5, **Roma 00100**, ITALY.

M. Valouch (1960) Archangelska 2, **Praha 10**, Vrsovice, CZECHOSLOVAKIA.

H.B.G. Casimir (1966) V.N. Philips Gloelampenfabriken, Philips Industries, **Eindhoven**, NETHERLANDS.

A. Harashima (1969) International Christian University, Mitaka, **Tokyo**, JAPAN.

E. Nagy (1969) Institute for Experimental Physics, Eötvös University, Museum Körüt 6-8, **Budapest VIII**, HUNGARY.

15 – ATOMIC and MOLECULAR PHYSICS and SPECTROSCOPY COMMISSION (1966)

Chairman : Prof. A. KASTLER (1966) Laboratoire de Physique, École Normale Supérieure, 24 rue Lhomond, **Paris 5e**, FRANCE.

Secretary : Prof. W.L. FITE (1966) Department of Physics, University of Pittsburgh, **Pittsburgh**, Pennsylvania, 15213, U.S.A.

Members : Lewis M. Branscomb (1966) Director, National Bureau of Standards, **Washington, D.C. 20234**, U.S.A.

N.V. Fedorenko (1966) A.F. Ioffe Physico-Technical Institute, Academy of Sciences of the U.S.S.R., **Leningrad K-21**, U.S.S.R.

W.C. Price (1966) Physics Department, King's College, Strand, **London W.C.**, ENGLAND.

M.J. Seaton (1966) Department of Physics, University College London, Gower Street, **London W.C. 1**, ENGLAND.

A. Walsh (1969) Division of Chemical Physics, Commonwealth Scientific and Research Organization, Clayton, **Victoria**, AUSTRALIA.

H.L. Welsh (1969) University of Toronto, **Toronto**, CANADA.

Corresponding Members : N. Cassini, (Italy 1969) E.G. Hertz, D.D.R. (1969) G. Herzberg, Canada (1966) I. Kovacs, Hungary (1969) P.E. Noornan, Holland (1969) T. Skalinski, Poland (1969) K. Takayanagi, Japan (1969) H. Van Regemorter, France (1969).

16 - PLASMA PHYSICS COMMISSION (1969)

Chairman : Prof. L.A. ARTSIMOVICH (1966) I.V. Kurchatov Institute of Atomic Energy, **Moscow**, U.S.S.R.

Secretary : Prof. S.C. BROWN (1966) Research Laboratory of Electronics, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, **Cambridge**, Mass. 02139, U.S.A.

Members : H. Alfvén (1966) Division of Plasma Physics, The Royal Institute of Technology, **Stockholm 70**, SWEDEN.

Heinz Maecker (1966) Forschungslaboratorium der Siemens-Schuckert-Werke, **Munich**, WEST GERMANY.

K. Husimi (1969) Institute of Plasma Physics, Nagoya University, **Nagoya**, JAPAN.

R.S. Pease (1969) Culham Laboratory, U.K. Atomic Energy Authority, **Culham**, Abingdon, Berkshire, ENGLAND.

I. Popescu (1969) Institutul de Fizica, Academia Republicii Socialiste România, Calea Victoriei 114, **Bucuresti**, ROMÂNIA.

Richard F. Post (1966) Lawrence Radiation Laboratory, University of California — L-386, P.O. Box 809, **Livermore**, California 94550, U.S.A.

Corresponding Members : P.L. Bhatnagar, India (1969) B. Brunelli (1969) C. M. Braams Holland (1969) J.L. Delcroix, France (1969) L. Pekárek, Czechoslovakia (1969) L. Rothhardt, Jena, East Germany (1969) E.,S. Weibel, Switzerland (1969).

17 – INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION for OPTICS (1948)

The statutes of IUPAP provide for affiliated commissions which are almost independent of the parent union. At present, there is only one such commission — the International Commission for Optics, which was founded in 1948.

Seventeen countries are members of the Commission for Optics. They are : Australia, Austria, Belgium, Canada, Czechoslovakia, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Netherlands, Poland, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and U.S.A.

The membership of the Executive Committee is presently as follows :

President : H.H. HOPKINS, New Department of Applied Physics Sciences, University of Reading, Whiteknights Park, **Reading**, Berkshire, ENGLAND.

Vice-Presidents : L.E. Howlett (Canada), H. Kubota (Japan), T. Skalinski (Poland).

Secretary-Treasurer : J.-Ch. VIÉNOT, Laboratoire d'Optique, Faculté des Sciences, Université de Besançon, La Bouloie, **Besançon 25**, FRANCE.

IUPAP DELEGATES to MISCELLANEOUS COMMISSIONS

18 – INTERNATIONAL COUNCIL of SCIENTIFIC UNIONS (I.C.S.U.) :

Prof. Robert F. BACHER, U.S.A. (1969)

**19 – SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE on OCEANIC RESEARCH
(S.C.O.R.) :**

Sir Edward BULLARD, England (1966)

**20 – SPECIAL COMMISSION for SPACE RESEARCH
(COSPAR) :**

Dr. S. BHAGAVANTAM, India (1966)

**21 – UPPER MANTLE PROJECT :
(International Geophysical Commission) :**

Prof. S.K. RUNCORN, United Kingdom (1966)

**22 – INTER-UNION COMMISSION on SOLAR
TERRESTRIAL PHYSICS (IUCSTP) :**

Prof. S.N. VERNOV, U.S.S.R. (1966)

23 – ICSU – CODATA :

Prof. B. VODAR, France (1966)

24 – IUPAC – POLYMERS :

Prof. K. WOLF, Heidelberg (1969)

25 – ICSU – SPECTROSCOPY :

Dr. G. HERZBERG, Canada (1966)

Prof. A. KASTLER, France (1966)

Prof. W.C. PRICE, U.K. (1966)

26 – ICSU Abstracting Board :

Prof. H.W. KOCH, U.S.A. (1969)

27 – IUC – Crystal Growth :

Prof. H. DEKEYSER, Gent (1969)

28 – SCIENCE TEACHING COMMISSION :

Prof. H.H. STAUB, Switzerland (1969)

U. I. P. P. A.
RAPPORT GÉNÉRAL
1970

L'UNION INTERNATIONALE
DE PHYSIQUE PURE ET APPLIQUÉE

RENSEIGNEMENTS GÉNÉRAUX

ET

PROCÈS-VERBAL
de la XIII^e ASSEMBLÉE GÉNÉRALE
(DUBROVNIK, 1969)

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I – FONCTIONNEMENT DE L'UNION

L'histoire de l'Union internationale de Physique pure et appliquée est résumée dans huit publications antérieures (documents UIPPA 1, 2, 4, 5, 7, 8, 10 et 14).

L'Union est constituée par les comités nationaux de Physique ou associations de physiciens des divers pays adhérents. Ces comités délèguent des membres aux Assemblées générales de l'Union qui ont lieu tous les trois ans. L'Assemblée générale pourvoit à l'élection du bureau d'administration, à la nomination des diverses commissions spéciales et à la désignation de ses représentants auprès de plusieurs comités groupant les différentes unions scientifiques.

Les Assemblées générales antérieures ont eu lieu à Bruxelles (1923 et 1925), à Paris (1931 et 1947), à Londres (1934 et 1954), à Varsovie (1963), à Bâle (1966) et à Dubrovnik (1969). Le Comité exécutif se réunit une fois par année.

L'union est rattachée au Conseil international des Unions scientifiques (C.I.U.S.). Le Conseil est constitué en ce moment de 14 unions et d'une cinquantaine de délégués nationaux. Le Président du Conseil est le Professeur V.A. Ambartsumian (URSS), et le Secrétaire-général est le Professeur K. Chandrasekharan (Inde). Les bureaux administratifs se trouvent à Rome (7, via Cornelio Celso, Rome 00161, ITALIE).

L'Assemblée générale du C.I.U.S. est constituée par des représentants des unions scientifiques et des délégués nationaux. À l'avenir, cette assemblée se réunira tous les deux ans.

En 1946, le C.I.U.S. a conclu un accord avec l'Organisation des Nations-Unies pour l'Éducation, la Science et la Culture (UNESCO). Cet accord permet aux unions scientifiques d'obtenir,

par l'intermédiaire du C.I.U.S., des subventions à l'intention des congrès internationaux. Cette importante source de fonds a permis à l'UIPPA de subventionner près de soixante congrès pendant la période 1966-1969.

L'utilisation des subventions de l'UNESCO est soumise aux conditions suivantes:

- i) l'UNESCO doit être renseignée au sujet des conférences afin de pouvoir, le cas échéant, y déléguer un représentant;
- ii) l'UNESCO entend que son appui soit mentionné sur la couverture de toutes les publications faites par des organismes ayant bénéficié de subventions à cet effet. La formule suivante est recommandée: "Publié avec le concours financier de l'UNESCO";
- iii) l'UNESCO demande qu'on lui envoie dix exemplaires de tous les rapports issus d'une conférence.

Des conférences et des assemblées de commissions peuvent également être subventionnées par les fonds provenant des membres nationaux de l'UIPPA. Ces fonds servent aussi à faire face aux dépenses de l'administration.

La correspondance traitant des affaires générales de l'Union et de ses commissions doit être envoyée au Secrétaire-général. Cependant, la correspondance traitant des finances et du paiement des contributions des comités nationaux doit être envoyée au Secrétaire-général adjoint.

II – STATUTS DE L'UNION

(Votés par l'Assemblée générale de 1931 et modifiés par celles de 1948 et 1954 ; le texte du § 5 adopté en 1960 est indiqué en *italiques*).

I. Buts de l'Union et conditions d'admission

1. L'Union a pour but :

- (i) de créer et d'encourager une coopération internationale en physique ;
- (ii) de coordonner les efforts de préparation et de publication des extraits de mémoires et de tables de constantes de physique ;
- (iii) de réaliser une entente internationale sur les questions d'unités, d'étalonnage, de nomenclature et de notations ;
- (iv) d'aider la poursuite de recherches intéressantes.

Elle peut organiser des congrès internationaux.

Dans chaque pays, l'adhésion à l'Union peut être donnée soit par son Académie nationale, soit par son Conseil national de Recherches, soit par d'autres institutions similaires, soit par des sociétés scientifiques ou groupements de telles institutions ou sociétés, soit, à défaut de ceux-ci, par son Gouvernement.

Pour un même pays, des adhésions données séparément par plusieurs organisations distinctes ne peuvent être admises que sous la réserve d'une entente préalable entre ces organisations pour la répartition des cotisations et le partage des droits de vote.

Dans le mot pays sont compris les dominions, les protectorats diplomatiques, ainsi que les territoires ayant une activité scientifique indépendante.

II. Comités nationaux

2. Un comité national est constitué dans chacun des pays adhérents comme organisme de liaison avec l'Union. Il est créé sur

l'initiative soit de son Académie nationale, soit de son Conseil national de Recherches ou d'autres institutions ou groupements d'institutions nationales similaires, soit, à défaut de ceux-ci, de son Gouvernement.

3. Les comités nationaux ont pour fonction de faciliter et de coordonner, sur leurs territoires respectifs, l'étude des diverses branches de la Physique, envisagées principalement du point de vue international. Chaque comité national soit seul, soit de concert avec un ou plusieurs autres comités nationaux, a le droit de soumettre à l'Union des questions à discuter entrant dans la compétence de celle-ci.

Les comités nationaux désignent les délégués chargés de les représenter aux assemblées de l'Union.

Ils désignent un chef de délégation qui a qualité pour voter au nom de son comité sur les questions d'ordre administratif, ainsi qu'il est prévu aux articles 14 et 16.

III. Administration de l'Union

4. Les travaux sont dirigés par l'Assemblée générale des délégués.

5. *Le Comité exécutif de l'Union comprend : le Président, le précédent Président, le premier Vice-président, les Vice-présidents et le Secrétaire-général. À l'exception de l'ancien président, les membres du Comité sont élus par l'Assemblée générale ; ils demeurent en fonction jusqu'à la fin de l'Assemblée générale ordinaire qui suit celle de leur élection. Le premier Vice-président remplace le Président en cas d'absence de ce dernier.*

À l'exception du Secrétaire-général, les membres élus du Comité exécutif ne peuvent exercer une même fonction sans interruption pendant plus de deux périodes séparant les assemblées générales ordinaires.

Le comité exécutif peut pourvoir aux départs qui surviendraient dans son sein. Toute personne désignée dans ces conditions achève le mandat de celle qu'elle remplace.

Il existe, en outre, un *Bureau administratif* qui, sous la direction du Secrétaire-général de l'Union, expédie la correspondance, gère les ressources et assure la conservation des archives ainsi que la préparation et la distribution des publications approuvées par l'Assemblée générale.

IV. Commissions

6. L'Assemblée générale et, sous réserve d'approbation par l'Assemblée générale suivante, le Comité exécutif peuvent décider la création de commissions propres à l'Union de Physique et la participation à des *commissions mixtes*, communes à l'Union de Physique et à une ou plusieurs autres.

Parmi les commissions propres à l'Union, certaines, dites *commissions affiliées*, sont consacrées aux grands domaines de la Physique, d'autres, à objectif plus limité, sont dites *commissions spécialisées*.

Toutes les commissions doivent, par l'entremise de leur secrétaire, présenter à chaque Assemblée générale un rapport sur leurs travaux.

7. La constitution, les statuts, le fonctionnement et la situation financière des commissions *affiliées* sont soumis à l'approbation du Comité exécutif de l'Union qui doit veiller notamment à ce que leurs domaines d'action soient délimités au mieux.

Le Comité exécutif désigne un ou plusieurs de ses membres pour représenter l'Union au sein de chaque commission affiliée.

Les commissions affiliées peuvent, en plus des ressources qui leur sont affectées par l'Union, percevoir des cotisations spéciales et recevoir des dons d'autres sources.

8. Les membres des commissions *spécialisées* et les représentants de l'Union au sein des commissions mixtes sont élus par l'Assemblée générale, après examen des propositions du Comité exécutif de l'Union. Ils restent en fonction jusqu'à la fin de l'Assemblée générale suivante et sont rééligibles.

Les commissions spécialisées peuvent s'adjoindre des membres, sous réserve d'approbation du Comité exécutif.

La désignation des membres des commissions *affiliées* en plus des représentants du Comité exécutif de l'Union de Physique prévus à l'article 7, est fixée par leurs statuts particuliers.

Le fonctionnement des commissions *mixtes* est réglé par le Conseil international des Unions scientifiques.

V. Assemblées générales

9. L'Union se réunit en principe tous les trois ans en Assemblée générale ordinaire. Si l'époque et le lieu de cette réunion n'ont pas été arrêtés par l'Assemblée générale précédente, ils sont fixés par le Comité exécutif et communiqués, quatre mois à l'avance, aux organismes adhérents.

10. Dans des cas spéciaux, le Président peut, avec le consentement du Comité exécutif, convoquer une Assemblée extraordinaire ; il est tenu de la faire à la demande d'un tiers des voix des pays adhérents.

11. Tous les membres des comités nationaux peuvent assister aux réunions de l'Assemblée générale et prendre part aux discussions, mais seulement avec voix consultative.

Le Président de l'Union peut inviter des hommes de sciences, non délégués, à assister, à titre consultatif, aux séances de l'Assemblée générale.

Les membres non-délégués des commissions mentionnées à l'article 7 ont le droit d'assister, dans les mêmes conditions, aux séances de l'Assemblée générale où sont traitées les questions entrant dans leurs attributions.

12. L'ordre du jour d'une session est fixé par le Comité exécutif et communiqué au moins quatre mois avant l'ouverture de cette session. Toute question ne figurant pas à l'ordre du jour n'est prise en considération qu'avec l'assentiment préalable de la moitié au moins des voix des pays représentés à l'Assemblée générale.

VI. Congrès internationaux

13. Les congrès internationaux sont organisés par le Comité exécutif de l'Union.

VII. Budget et droit de vote

14. Le Comité exécutif prépare un budget de prévision pour chaque année de la période comprise entre deux sessions. Une Commission financière, nommée par l'Assemblée générale, est chargée de l'étude de ce budget et de la vérification des comptes de l'exercice précédent. Elle établit, sur ces deux questions, des rapports distincts qui sont soumis à l'Assemblée générale.

À la suite de cet examen financier, l'Assemblée générale fixe le taux de la part contributive unitaire (*).

Le montant de la cotisation est le produit du "taux de la part unitaire" par le nombre de "part contributives" du pays considéré. Ce nombre est fixé par le Comité exécutif, après examen des observations éventuelles du Comité national intéressé ; il peut, quand cela paraît opportun, être modifié par un accord entre le Comité exécutif et le Comité national intéressé.

Il est dans tous les cas soumis à la ratification de l'Assemblée générale qui suit sa fixation ou sa modification.

Le nombre de délégués officiels de chaque pays et celui des voix attribuées à chaque délégation sont fixés par le barème suivant :

Nombre de parts
contributives : 1, 2 ou 3, 4 à 6, 7 à 9, 10 et au-dessus

Nombre de délégués
officiels (et de voix) : 1, 2, 3, 4, 5

Dans chaque pays les organismes adhérents sont responsables du paiement des cotisations.

*Ce taux est fixé à \$300 dollars U.S. à partir du 1er janvier 1971.

15. Les recettes de tout ordre de l'Union provenant des contributions des divers pays sont consacrées :

- (i) à payer les frais de publications et les dépenses accessoires d'administration ;
- (ii) à atteindre les buts prévus à l'article 1.

Les ressources provenant de dons sont utilisées par l'Union en tenant compte des désirs exprimés par les donateurs.

Tout pays qui se retire de l'Union abandonne de ce fait ses droits à l'actif de l'association.

16. Dans les Assemblées générales, les résolutions concernant les questions d'ordre scientifique sont prises à la majorité des voix de tous les délégués présents.

Pour les questions d'ordre administratif et pour les questions mixtes, le vote a lieu par pays, le nombre de voix de chaque pays étant fixé à l'article 14.

S'il y a doute sur la catégorie dans laquelle doit être rangée une question à discuter, le Président décide.

Dans les commissions, les décisions sont prises à la majorité des voix des membres qui les composent et non par pays.

En toutes circonstances, s'il y a égalité de voix, celle du Président est prépondérante.

17. Pour les questions administratives figurant à l'ordre du jour, un pays qui n'est pas représenté peut envoyer par écrit son vote au Président. Pour être valable, ce vote doit être reçu avant le dépouillement du scrutin.

VIII. Règlements intérieurs

18. L'Assemblée générale peut édicter des règlements intérieurs concernant soit la conduite de ses travaux, soit les devoirs généraux qui incombent aux membres du Comité exécutif, soit en général, tous objets non prévus dans les statuts.

De même, chaque Commission peut élaborer des règlements pour la conduite de ses propres travaux. Aucun de ces règlements ne peut contenir de prescriptions contraires aux termes des présents statuts.

IX. Durée de l'Union et modifications aux statuts

19. La durée de l'Union n'est pas limitée.
20. Aucun changement ne pourra être apporté aux présents statuts sans l'approbation des deux tiers des voix de l'ensemble des pays adhérents.
21. En cas de dissolution de l'Union, votée par l'Assemblée générale à la majorité des deux tiers des voix de l'ensemble des pays adhérents, les fonds disponibles seront attribués par l'Assemblée à une ou plusieurs organisations scientifiques.
22. Le présent texte français servira exclusivement pour l'interprétation à donner aux articles des présents statuts.

III — Compte-rendu de la XIII^{ème} Assemblée Générale Dubrovnik, Yougoslavie, septembre 1969

Les délégués se réunirent dans la salle des Unions syndiquées dans la vieille cité de Dubrovnik les jeudi, vendredi et samedi, 11, 12 et 13 septembre 1969. Le Président, le Professeur D. I. Blokhintsev, présida toutes les séances.

Environ 120 délégués s'étaient inscrits à l'Assemblée générale. La liste, par pays membre, se trouve en Annexe V.

La Commission S.U.N. s'était réunie à Dubrovnik juste avant l'Assemblée générale.

Les arrangements pour les séances furent organisés par le Comité national de la Yougoslavie, sous la direction du Professeur Dr A. Milojevic. On avait réservé des salles confortables pour l'Assemblée dans la vieille ville pittoresque de Dubrovnik. Entre les séances, les délégués avaient le privilège d'entendre une excellente conférence donnée par le professeur N. Kurti du Clarendon Laboratory à Oxford, et aussi un concert de guitare remarquable donné par le docteur J. Jovicic de l'Université de Belgrade. On avait également fait des arrangements en vue de permettre aux délégués d'assister à un dîner et de faire une excursion à Kotar et à St-Stéphane. Un programme spécial pour les dames avait été également organisé.

PREMIÈRE SÉANCE, le jeudi 11 septembre 1969

Dix heures

Président : le professeur BLOKHINTSEV

I — Le Président du Comité national de la Yougoslavie, le professeur A. Milojevic, souhaita la bienvenue aux délégués. Tout en mentionnant que l'on célébrerait bientôt le 50^{ème} anniversaire de l'Union, il a fait remarquer que cette période coïncidait avec l'évolution de la Physique en Yougoslavie. Il a fait une courte revue des contributions que plusieurs scientifiques, tel que le professeur Boskovics de Dubrovnik même, avaient fait à la

Physique depuis plusieurs siècles, et il exprima la conviction que les délégués trouveraient beaucoup de choses intéressantes dans différents domaines lors de leur visite dans cette ville.

II – Le Président Blokhintsev remercia le professeur Milojevic de ses commentaires et des arrangements concernant le programme organisé de façon si profitable pour les délégués. Ensuite, le Secrétaire-général, le professeur C.-C. Butler, présenta le programme d'affaires que devait aborder l'Assemblée générale.

III – Nouveaux membres :

Le Secrétaire-général annonça la demande de Cuba de se joindre à l'Union. Cette demande avait reçu le consentement du Comité exécutif et, en accord avec les Statuts, on demandait maintenant que cette approbation soit ratifiée par l'Assemblée générale. Cuba détiendrait une part dans l'Union. L'Assemblée se prononça unanimement en faveur de l'admission de Cuba. Le Secrétaire-général soumit ensuite une demande d'admission venant de la Corée du Sud. Cette application était recommandée par le Comité exécutif. L'Assemblée vota unanimement l'admission de la Corée du Sud. Ce pays détiendra une part dans l'Union.

IV – Ordre du jour :

Le Secrétaire-général soumit l'ordre du jour pour approbation par les délégués qui l'acceptèrent unanimement. Il invita les Commissions et les délégués nationaux à soumettre les textes de résolutions qu'ils désiraient proposer afin qu'ils puissent être distribués aux délégués.

V – Rapport du Secrétaire-général :

Le Secrétaire-général soumit un rapport. Un grand nombre d'activités de routine mais importantes avaient été réalisées grâce surtout aux Commissions. Quatre réunions du Comité exécutif avaient eu lieu et le Secrétariat avait distribué de plus en plus de renseignements et de publicité traitant de l'Union (son livret de Renseignement généraux, son Bulletin de Nouvelles, son feuillet trimestriel, en plus d'articles dans l'*Australian Journal of Physics* et dans *Physics Today*). Il déclara que la situation financière de

L'Union était bonne, que ses états financiers avaient été vérifiés et seraient discutés plus tard. Le Secrétaire-général souligna l'importance des élections que l'on devait tenir lors de la troisième séance et expliqua la nature de la liste des candidats que l'on distribuait aux délégués. Il mentionna la possibilité qu'il y ait d'autres nominations au cours de l'Assemblée même et commenta la procédure qui serait suivie pour les votes.

VI – Rapports des Commissions :

Les diverses commissions internationales déposèrent des rapports de leurs activités depuis l'Assemblée générale de Bâle en 1966. Un résumé de ces rapports peut être consulté en Annexe II. Les résolutions présentées par les Commissions ont été différées à la deuxième séance de l'Assemblée. Les points particuliers soulevés par les commissions sont les suivants :

1. *Commission de la Finance* :
voir item X

2. *Commission S. U. N.* :

Le rapport fut présenté par le secrétaire, le professeur J. deBoer. Il mentionna l'adoption d'une nouvelle unité : le « Pascal » (newtons/m^2), et l'adoption de « K » comme symbole pour les degrés de température absolue. Il y eut un échange entre le professeur deBoer et le docteur Herzberg du Canada concernant l'opportunité de certaines recommandations de la Commission SUN telles que l'élimination de l'indice en cercle avant le symbole K pour la température absolue. Le professeur deBoer répondit que l'on avait consulté les meilleurs centres à ce sujet. Il déclara ensuite qu'ayant servi comme secrétaire de la Commission internationale depuis 1948, il avait remis sa démission. Les délégués à l'Assemblée applaudirent chaleureusement le professeur deBoer en témoignage de leur reconnaissance pour son dévouement efficace envers l'Union.

3. *Commission sur la Thermodynamique et la Mécanique statistique* :

Le rapport fut présenté par le docteur P. Mazur. En plus de commenter les congrès internationaux, le docteur Mazur dé-

clara que le président de la Commission, le docteur Kubo avait présenté sa démission.

4. *Commission sur les Rayons cosmiques :*

Le rapport fut présenté par le professeur Wilson. Traitant des congrès internationaux, il mentionna que la Commission tendait vers une politique visant à tenir une conférence majeure à tous les trois ans. La Commission était toujours d'avis qu'une conférence internationale de dix jours était nécessaire dans ce domaine particulier. Ce point de vue n'est cependant pas mentionné dans le rapport présenté. Il fit part de la tradition très utile suivant laquelle la Commission organisait une bibliothèque de rapports et de documents pertinents qui fonctionnait durant les dix jours que duraient les congrès internationaux.

5. *Commission des basses Températures :*

Le rapport fut présenté par le professeur Allen. Il mentionna que la Commission se proposait de geler son cycle de conférences à trois ans et espérait que ceci pourrait être synchronisé avec les cycles semblables de la Commission du Magnétisme et de la Commission des Semi-conducteurs. Il mentionna également la nature du Prix Fritz-London qui est administré par la Commission des très basses Températures. C'est le Prix international le plus prestigieux dans ce domaine et il est maintenant subventionné par la Compagnie I.B.M. Les délégués à l'Assemblée indiquèrent leur satisfaction au sujet de ce Prix auquel l'Union accorde son patronage.

6. *Commission des Publications :*

Le rapport fut présenté par le docteur Stickland. Mademoiselle Stickland souligna que, lors d'une assemblée des éditeurs des journaux de Physique, on avait décidé qu'il n'y avait pas lieu de créer une association spéciale d'éditeurs étant donné que la Commission internationale jouait pleinement le rôle d'une telle association.

7. *Commission sur l'Acoustique :*

Le rapport fut présenté par le docteur Malecki. Il souligna l'importance de la collaboration de la Commission sur l'Acousti-

que avec d'autres unions et d'autres associations étant donné que son domaine touchait les sphères biologiques et même sociologiques. La Commission croyait avoir un rôle important à jouer dans l'étude que l'on préparait sur le thème général de l'homme et son entourage. Il était maintenant reconnu que le bruit était une forme de pollution de l'entourage, et qu'il devait être contrôlé aussi rigoureusement que les autres types de pollution.

8. *Commission des Semi-conducteurs :*

Le rapport fut présenté par le Secrétaire, le docteur Mitchell, qui a voulu, pour l'information des délégués, définir l'étendue du domaine de la Commission des Semi-conducteurs. Celui-ci exclut des sujets tels que les halides alcalins, etc. (État solide); les problèmes mécaniques (État solide); le magnétisme (Magnétisme); mais comprend les problèmes des matériaux ayant des niveaux liés variant de quelques électron-volts à environ 0 électron-volt (excluant les métaux). Il mentionna que, contrairement à d'autres commissions, la Commission des Semi-conducteurs considérait que la séquence bi-annuelle était plus utile pour ces congrès internationaux. Le docteur Brattain terminait son mandat comme Président de la Commission et tous lui étaient très reconnaissants du travail qu'il avait accompli.

Le docteur Boas, de la Commission de l'État solide, a échangé des points de vue avec le docteur Mitchell sur la possibilité d'un patronage conjoint de certains congrès qui touchent à la fois les domaines des deux Commissions.

9. *Commission du Magnétisme :*

Le rapport fut présenté par le docteur Marshall. La Commission consentait à la synchronisation de son cycle tri-annuel avec celui de la Commission des très basses Températures.

10. *Commission de l'État solide :*

Le rapport fut présenté par le docteur Boas. Il expliqua la nature du travail de la Commission qui avait comme résultat la proposition d'un nombre relativement grand de congrès internationaux.

11. *Commission de la Physique nucléaire des hautes énergies :*

Le rapport fut présenté par le docteur Lanius. Il rappela la politique de la Commission qui voulait qu'il y ait une grande conférence internationale à tous les trois ans, accompagnée de plusieurs petites conférences spécialisées.

12. *Commission de la Physique nucléaire des basses énergies :*

Le rapport fut présenté par le professeur Huber. Il exprima les regrets de la Commission concernant le décès du docteur Amos deShalit, et présenta à l'Assemblée un court témoignage sur ce physicien distingué. (L'Assemblée se leva pour consacrer une minute de silence à la mémoire du docteur deShalit).

Le docteur Huber discuta la politique de conférence de la Commission qui cherchait à réduire le nombre de réunions internationales. Il souleva la question des visas qui, quoique de façon réduite, continuait à créer des problèmes. À titre d'exemple, il mentionna le refus d'un visa au professeur deShalit pour assister à un congrès international dans l'URSS. Des éléments d'action sont suggérés dans son rapport. La Commission déplorait également l'habitude des organisateurs de certaines conférences d'obliger les délégués à acheter les comptes-rendus.

13. *Commission des Masses atomiques :*

Le rapport fut présenté par le professeur Duckworth. Il mentionna l'amélioration dans les valeurs suivant les données minima basées sur ^{12}C qui ont été obtenues depuis 1966. Suivant le deuxième ajustement des valeurs initiales apparues en 1964-65, un troisième ajustement donnant les « étalons de masses atomiques 1969 » paraîtra bientôt dans la revue « Nuclear Data ». Au sujet des constantes fondamentales, la dernière revue critique avait eu lieu en 1963 avec quelques additions en 1965 et 1967. Il apparaît maintenant qu'il y avait des erreurs aussi grandes que 100 parties dans 10^6 dans les constantes aussi fondamentales que e , h , etc.

Il y eut ensuite un échange de vues entre le professeur Duckworth et le professeur Terrien (France) au sujet d'un che-

vauchement possible de la quatrième conférence internationale sur les masses atomiques et les constantes associées et une conférence proposée par le Bureau national des Étalons. On fit remarquer enfin que cette dernière chercherait à souligner aux jeunes physiciens que les mesures de précision impliquaient maintenant toujours les constantes fondamentales et étaient, par conséquent, d'intérêt renouvelé.

14. *Commission de l'Éducation :*

Le rapport fut présenté par le docteur Staub. Il mentionna le grand intérêt que le docteur deShalit avait manifesté pour le travail de la Commission de l'Éducation. Il avisa les délégués que la Commission présenterait une résolution concernant l'enseignement et la recherche.

15. *Commission de la Physique atomique et moléculaire et la Spectroscopie :*

Le rapport fut présenté par le docteur Herzberg. Il mentionna l'appui que donnait la Commission à la proposition de former une commission sur les plasmas.

VII – Commission internationale de l'Optique :

Le rapport fut présenté par le docteur Toraldo. Il expliqua la nature spéciale de la C.I.O. qui, comme Commission affiliée, avait maintenant des comités nationaux dans 17 pays. En effet, le seul pays où l'Optique représente une préoccupation majeure et qui n'est pas membre de la C.I.O. est l'URSS. Il déclara que l'état financier de la Commission était excellent et déposa un livret récemment préparé sur la nature et l'oeuvre de la C.I.O.

VIII – Commissions diverses :

Le Secrétaire-général décrit brièvement les activités des différentes commissions et des divers comités inter-unions. Un résumé des rapports reçus se trouve en Annexe II. En particulier, le Secrétaire-général fit remarquer :

1. *Commission conjointe sur la Radioactivité appliquée :*

Suivant une recommandation de l'UIPPA, le C. I. U. S. a maintenant aboli cette Commission conjointe.

2. *Comité scientifique sur la Recherche océanographique (SCOR)* :
Le rapport fut déposé.
3. *Commission spéciale pour la Recherche spatiale (COSPAR)* :
Aucun rapport n'a été reçu à date.
4. *Commission internationale de Géophysique (CIG)* :
Cette Commission a maintenant terminé son mandat. Cependant, un de ses comités, le « Upper Mantle Committee », continue ses activités et a déposé un rapport.
5. *Comité des Résumés scientifiques du CIUS* :
Le rapport n'a pas été reçu.
6. *Commission des Sciences atmosphériques* :
Aucun rapport n'a été reçu à date.
7. *Comité du CIUS sur les Données pour la Science et la Technologie (CODATA)* :
Le rapport fut déposé. Sir Gordon Sutherland ajouta que CODATA publierait bientôt une bibliographie des sources de données sur les substances pures. Quatre pays se sont joints aux six membres originaux de CODATA.
8. *Commission du CIUS sur la Spectroscopie* :
Aucun rapport n'a été présenté encore.
9. *Commission de l'UIPCA sur les Polymères* :
La Commission n'a pas présenté de rapport. Cependant, l'UIPCA est en train de se réorganiser et elle a accepté le docteur Wolf comme représentant de l'UIPPA auprès de cette Commission.
10. *Commission du CIUS sur la Physique solaire-terrestre* :
Le rapport fut déposé.

IX – Affaires du CIUS :

Le Président Blokhintsev fit rapport des relations entre l'UIPPA et le CIUS. Il était d'avis que lors de l'Assemblée générale du CIUS à Paris, on avait consacré beaucoup de temps à

la discussion des finances et relativement peu de temps à la discussion des affaires scientifiques. Sa requête au CIUS en vue d'une augmentation de la subvention accordée à l'Union, étant donné l'augmentation de l'activité en Physique depuis dix ans, a été reçue avec compréhension. (Remarque : en 1969, la subvention du CIUS à l'UIPPA a été portée de \$13,125. à \$16,125.).

Les délégués discutèrent brièvement différents aspects des relations avec le CIUS. Le professeur Robson (Canada) s'informa pour savoir si le CIUS se proposait de travailler dans le domaine des Symboles, des Unités et de la Nomenclature. Le Secrétaire-général répondit que la CIUS n'avait pas de Commission dans ce domaine, mais que la Commission SUN de l'Union collaborait avec d'autres unions telles que l'UIPCA directement, aussi bien qu'avec les autres organisations à l'extérieur du CIUS telles que la SIO.

DEUXIÈME SÉANCE, le vendredi 12 septembre 1969

Dix heures

Président : le professeur BLOKHINTSEV

X – Rapport de la Commission des Finances :

Le président de la Commission, Sir Gordon Sutherland, mentionna que le professeur deBoer et lui-même avaient examiné les rapports financiers de l'Union chaque année depuis 1966 et que le rapport triennal avait été distribué aux délégués. De façon générale, le professeur deBoer et lui-même trouvent que les finances de l'Union sont en bonne condition.

Situation financière :

Le Secrétaire-général adjoint résuma la situation financière de l'Union. Son budget de fonctionnement était d'environ \$55,000. par année alors que son capital de réserve avait été augmenté graduellement à \$45,000., soit un montant un peu inférieur au montant utilisé pour une année de fonctionnement. Depuis la dernière augmentation de la part dans l'Union en 1966, l'augmentation du coût de la vie a rongé considérablement la possibilité de l'Union de supporter à un niveau convenable les congrès

internationaux. Il rappela aux délégués que plusieurs commissions ont insisté dans leurs rapports sur le besoin d'une augmentation d'appui financier aux conférences internationales.

La recommandation du Comité exécutif de porter la valeur d'une part de \$250. à \$300. US a été soumise à tous les Comités nationaux. Une minorité seulement a exprimé des commentaires à la suite de cette proposition, mais cette minorité était décidément en faveur de l'augmentation. Le professeur Dobrotin de l'Union soviétique expliqua en détail les arrangements effectués dans son pays pour accueillir une conférence internationale. Il mentionna d'une part que le coût d'une telle conférence dépassait de beaucoup l'aide financière que l'Union pouvait accorder et d'autre part, qu'il était difficile pour plusieurs pays d'obtenir des espèces convertibles pour payer les frais toujours plus grands des nombreuses unions internationales. En conséquence, sa délégation n'appuierait pas cette résolution. Le professeur Blokhintsev demanda aux délégués d'indiquer officiellement leur avis au sujet de cette augmentation. Le total des mains levées indiqua que, des 86 votes présents, 8 étaient contre la résolution (URSS, Allemagne de l'Est) ; 18 se sont abstenus et 60 étaient en faveur. Étant donné cette indication, les délégués exprimèrent leur accord à l'effet qu'un vote formel n'était pas nécessaire, et le président Blokhintsev déclara la résolution acceptée, à savoir :

que la valeur d'une part dans l'Union sera augmentée de \$250.US à \$300.US à partir de 1971.

XI – Recommandations des Commissions :

Plusieurs commissions proposèrent des résolutions à l'Assemblée générale. Elles furent discutées lors de la deuxième séance et reprises ensuite en considération lors de la troisième séance. Le résumé des résultats de ces deux délibérations est indiqué ci-après :

a) Éducation en Physique :

On proposa une résolution concernant l'enseignement et la recherche. Cette résolution était basée sur celle adoptée par l'Union internationale des Sciences biologiques en 1967 et visait

à décourager la tendance à séparer l'enseignement et la recherche dans les universités. Sir Gordon Sutherland s'objecta à la clause traitant des directeurs d'étude des étudiants avancés. Il était d'avis que si l'on reconnaissait cette activité comme de l'enseignement officiel, on pourrait utiliser le fait pour dissocier davantage les directeurs de recherche de l'enseignement du premier cycle. Le docteur Havens, de la délégation des États-Unis, indiqua le besoin de reconnaître davantage le travail des physiciens qui préparaient des résumés et des revues et rendaient ainsi les résultats de leurs recherches avancées plus accessibles aux non spécialistes et aux étudiants. Lors de la troisième séance, les délégués adoptèrent à l'unanimité la résolution suivante :

Étant donné :

1. que les progrès rapides dans les domaines de la physique pure et appliquée accroissent non seulement la connaissance qu'a l'homme de son univers mais, par leurs applications, ont aussi des implications profondes pour le bien-être de l'humanité ;
2. que les découvertes en Physique, la plus fondamentale des sciences naturelles, influencent fortement toutes les sciences fondamentales et appliquées ainsi que les professions qui s'y rapportent ;
3. que l'enseignement de la Physique aux étudiants avancés, aux étudiants dans les domaines connexes scientifiques et professionnels, et à ceux qui deviendront partie d'une citoyenneté bien renseignée, ne peut être bien donné que par ceux qui sont eux-mêmes actifs à créer ou à utiliser de nouvelles connaissances ; et
4. que la recherche atteint son apogée lors de la communication de nouvelles connaissances à d'autres personnes et que les employeurs devraient reconnaître l'importance de l'évaluation et de la synthèse de connaissances existantes, ce qui exige souvent une capacité de perception et de créativité au moins aussi grande que pour la recherche primaire :

l'Union internationale de la Physique pure et appliquée adopte la résolution suivante :

1. la recherche et l'enseignement doivent être maintenus étroitement associés ;
2. toute tendance à la divergence entre les activités en vue de faire avancer et d'enseigner les connaissances doit être vigoureusement contrecarrée et l'on doit augmenter les efforts afin d'améliorer l'enseignement de la Physique ;
3. l'excellence dans l'enseignement et la dissémination de la connaissance relative à la Physique doivent être reconnues autant que pour la recherche. Conséquemment, toutes les agences et fondations accordant des subventions devraient également fournir un appui financier pour la préparation de revues critiques des développements courants et pour la compilation de données critiques ;
4. les chercheurs doués doivent également enseigner et on ne peut les exempter de l'enseignement que lors de circonstances spéciales et non pas afin de les récompenser de l'excellence de leurs travaux ;
5. on doit encourager les enseignants à entretenir leur vitalité intellectuelle et leur participation à l'avancement des connaissances en leur accordant du temps pour la recherche ou pour des activités académiques associées ; et
6. les chercheurs dans les Instituts de Recherche et dans les Laboratoires industriels devraient communiquer avec les organisations académiques en ce qui concerne l'éducation des étudiants avancés en Physique.

b) *Commission sur la Physique atomique et moléculaire et la Spectroscopie :*

Le docteur Gerhard Herzberg du Canada présenta une résolution touchant l'utilisation de la contrainte qu'imposent les éditeurs des journaux scientifiques et les directeurs de laboratoires en obligeant les auteurs de communications scientifiques à utiliser un système particulier d'unités ou de symboles. Commentant cette résolution, le professeur deBoer exprima sa crainte de voir l'Union

discuter des prérogatives des directeurs de laboratoires. Le professeur Kurti de la délégation du Royaume-Uni souhaita que l'Union ne devienne pas schizophrène, établissant d'une part des étalons et des normes et d'autre part regrettant que l'on cherche à les appliquer ! Le professeur deBoer insista sur le fait que la liberté académique des auteurs devrait impliquer une liberté correspondante pour les éditeurs. Il souligna de plus que les auteurs avaient le devoir de présenter leurs résultats de façon intelligible. Il était d'avis qu'avec le temps le problème serait résolu. Le docteur Wolfe de la délégation des États-Unis était d'accord que les éditeurs avaient aussi une responsabilité en vue de la compréhension des rapports publiés, et par conséquent devaient encourager l'uniformité. En particulier devaient-ils insister sur l'utilisation d'un système reconnu pour les symboles des unités. Le professeur Toraldo de la délégation de l'Italie fit remarquer que l'Union de Physique ne devrait pas insister sur quoi que ce soit. Cependant, elle devrait faire preuve d'unité sur certains principes. Il souhaitait que, dans le cas de la discussion présente, il en serait ainsi. Lors de la troisième séance, les délégués adoptèrent unanimement la résolution modifiée suivante :

“ que les auteurs soient encouragés à adopter les unités IS pour les données dans les journaux de Physique, tel que recommandé par la Commission S.U.N., la Conférence générale des poids et mesures, l'Organisation internationale pour la normalisation et par d'autres unions internationales associées à la Physique. On recommande aux éditeurs d'employer la persuasion plutôt que des mesures plus fortes pour obtenir la collaboration des auteurs sur le choix des symboles pour les quantités physiques et pour les unités, mais ils devraient exiger que les symboles recommandés pour les unités soient utilisés, sauf lorsque les noms des unités sont écrits au long ”.

XII – Résolutions présentées par le Comité exécutif et les Comités nationaux :

Le Comité exécutif et plusieurs des Comités nationaux ont proposé des résolutions à l'Assemblée générale. Celles-ci furent discutées de façon préliminaire et présentées par la suite à l'approbation des délégués lors de la troisième séance. Les résultats des deux délibérations sont résumés ainsi :

a) Comité exécutif :

Lien avec la Société européenne de Physique :

Le secrétaire-général, le professeur Butler, expliqua que la Société européenne de Physique désirait qu'un membre de l'UIPPA siège auprès de son Comité exécutif. Cette personne devrait elle-même être membre de la Société européenne. Le Comité exécutif recommanda que le délégué soit le professeur Butler et l'Assemblée générale endossa unanimement cette recommandation.

b) Comité exécutif :

Critères des congrès internationaux :

Le Secrétaire-général adjoint rapporta que, suivant des propositions venues de plusieurs commissions internationales, le Comité exécutif avait fait circuler les critères proposés pour l'évaluation des congrès internationaux. Ces critères tenaient compte de la valeur scientifique de la conférence, de son caractère international et de son organisation. Le docteur Havens de la délégation des États-Unis proposa comme amendement à la résolution l'addition d'une section suivant laquelle les congrès seraient désignés par catégories : les conférences plénières, les conférences thématiques, et les conférences hautement spécialisées. Les délégués discutèrent plusieurs points de phraséologie et leurs commentaires ayant été notés par le Secrétaire-général adjoint, on demanda au Comité exécutif de rédiger le texte final.

Lors de la troisième séance, la résolution telle qu'amendée fut acceptée à l'unanimité et se trouve à l'Annexe III du présent document.

c) Canada :

Concernant la Commission S.U.N. :

Le professeur Robson présenta une résolution recommandant que le C.I.U.S. crée une Commission des Symboles, Unités et de la Nomenclature. Le professeur deBoer de la

Commission S.U.N. de l'UIPPA déclara qu'il existait déjà un lien important entre cette Commission de l'Union et d'autres groupements dans ce domaine y compris plusieurs comme la SIO qui n'étaient pas reliés au C.I.U.S. Il craignait que l'organisation d'une commission supplémentaire compliquerait inutilement les choses. Le docteur Kurti de la délégation du Royaume-Uni fit remarquer que sa délégation appuierait la résolution si elle impliquait l'abolition de la Commission S.U.N. de l'UIPPA ainsi que l'abolition des autres commissions semblables dans d'autres unions afin d'avoir seulement une commission inter-unions. Cependant, si la résolution impliquait que la Commission de l'UIPPA demeurait, sa délégation s'y opposerait. Le professeur Robson déclara que l'intention de la résolution n'incluait pas l'abolition de la Commission S.U.N. de l'UIPPA. Lors de la troisième séance, la délégation canadienne demanda et obtint que sa résolution soit retirée.

d) **Pologne :**

Lien entre les commissions et les comités nationaux :

Le professeur Pal expliqua le besoin d'augmenter les efforts en vue de distribuer l'information venant du Comité exécutif et des commissions internationales aux physiciens en général et en particulier aux comités nationaux de l'UIPPA, de la SEP et de l'APS. Sa délégation proposait :

1. que l'UIPPA communique avec la SEP et l'APS au sujet d'un échange accru de renseignements et
2. que chaque commission internationale envoie des copies de sa correspondance et de ses documents à tous les comités nationaux.

Le professeur Kurti de la délégation du Royaume-Uni et le secrétaire-général Butler soulignèrent que ceci impliquerait beaucoup de difficulté pour les secrétariats des commissions internationales. Par contre, le professeur Auger de France insista sur le besoin qu'ont les administrateurs d'avoir

accès aux renseignements scientifiques donnant comme exemples l'UNESCO et l'OECD. L'Assemblée générale était d'accord qu'il existait un grand besoin de renseignements et d'une liaison plus grande entre les physiciens et les autres groupes, mais ne formula aucune résolution officielle.

e) **États-Unis :**

Noms des Commissions :

Le docteur Havens présenta une résolution proposant que l'on change le nom de la Commission internationale de la Physique nucléaire des basses énergies en celui de Commission internationale de la Physique nucléaire. On proposa également que le nom de la Commission internationale de la Physique nucléaire des hautes énergies devienne Commission internationale de la Physique des Particules et des Champs.

L'Assemblée générale adopta unanimement cette résolution.

XIII – Nouvelle Commission :

Le Secrétaire-général fit une courte revue de l'histoire de la Commission internationale sur la Physique atomique et moléculaire et la Spectroscopie. Constituée par l'Assemblée générale de Bâle en 1966, elle devait être modifiée au besoin après une période d'essai de trois ans. En 1966, la Commission avait été organisée avec trois divisions : la Spectroscopie, les Collisions atomiques, les Plasmas. Un de ses mandats était de communiquer avec les groupes organisant des conférences internationales sur les gaz ionisés afin de les inviter à collaborer avec l'UIPPA. Ceci a été fait et le comité d'organisation de ces congrès internationaux (qui reçoivent le patronage de l'UIPPA) a demandé à l'unanimité que l'Union forme une Commission des Plasmas. La Commission internationale sur la Physique atomique et moléculaire et la Spectroscopie, qui avait initié ces démarches, a étudié cette demande et l'endosse. Le Comité exécutif proposait maintenant à l'Assemblée générale de constituer une Commission internationale sur la Physique des Plasmas. L'Assemblée générale approuva unanimement cette proposition.

TROISIÈME SÉANCE, le samedi 13 septembre 1969

Dix heures

Président: le professeur BLOKHINTSEV

Avant de donner suite à l'ordre du jour, le président Blokhintsev invita plusieurs délégués à s'adresser à l'Assemblée générale.

Le professeur Dobrotin de la délégation soviétique commenta le décès récent du professeur POWELL qui découvrit le meson π . Il suggéra que l'Assemblée se lève pour une minute de silence en témoignage de son estime pour ce distingué savant.

Le professeur Allen présenta un témoignage éloquent à la mémoire du docteur Lewis WEIL, un membre de la Commission internationale des très basses Températures qui venait de décéder. L'Assemblée se leva pour une minute de silence à la mémoire de ce travailleur acharné.

Le professeur Auger de France souleva une question de privilège pour dire aux délégués qu'il assisterait bientôt à la réunion du Comité de l'UNESCO chargé de rencontrer les ministres des sciences de divers pays. Il se chargeait de voir à ce que le problème de l'association étroite enseignement-recherche discuté précédemment soit rapporté à ce Comité et que la résolution de l'UIPPA soit portée à son attention.

XIV – Congrès de 1970

Le Secrétaire-général présenta une liste des congrès internationaux auxquels le Comité exécutif recommandait qu'on accorde le patronage de l'Union. Afin d'orienter la discussion des délégués sur la résolution traitant des catégories de conférences (voir XIIb), les catégories suggérées avaient été indiquées sur la liste des conférences. Le Secrétaire-général fit ensuite des commentaires sur différents congrès proposés en donnant plus de détails au sujet de ceux qui n'avaient pas été recommandés par les Commissions internationales. Il fit aussi des commentaires sur la politique récente de l'Union en ce qui concerne les subventions accordées aux conférences, une liste de la distribution par commission ayant été distribuée aux délégués. Après une discussion sur des points

de détails, la liste des congrès telle que décrite en Annexe IV fut approuvée et ces congrès recevront le patronage de l'Union.

XV – Élections :

Le Secrétaire-général commenta la procédure à être suivie. Toutes les nominations pour les postes au Comité exécutif et aux Commissions internationales qui avaient été reçues durant l'été des commissions et des comités nationaux ont été incorporées dans une liste complète circulée aux délégués lors de leur arrivée à Dubrovnik. De cette liste, le Comité exécutif a préparé une liste de noms qu'il suggérait pour les divers postes, liste qui avait également été distribuée aux délégués. Bien que proposée officiellement par le Comité exécutif, cette liste pouvait être amendée par des propositions venant des délégués. De telles propositions furent émises et, comme résultat, les membres du Comité exécutif et des divers commissions internationales sont indiqués dans les pages centrales de ce document (IUPPA 16). Il n'y a pas eu de vote officiel.

Dans le cas de la Commission sur la Physique atomique et moléculaire et la Spectroscopie, seulement les membres de la Commission furent élus et il fut décidé de demander l'avis de la Commission au sujet du besoin de sub-divisions alors que la subdivision des Plasmas était maintenant devenue une Commission internationale.

Au cours de ces élections, on souligna en particulier le fait que le professeur Bacher devenait Président et que le professeur Maier-Leibnitz devenait premier Vice-président. On souligna également le fait que le professeur deBoer, qui avait rendu de très grands services à l'Union depuis au-delà de 20 ans, démissionnait comme secrétaire de la Commission internationale des Symboles, Unités et de la Nomenclature.

XVI – Résolutions des Commissions :

voir section XI.

XVII – Résolutions du Comité exécutif et des délégations nationales :

voir section XII.

XVIII – Assemblée générale de 1972 :

On informa les délégués que des invitations pour l'Assemblée générale de 1972 avaient été reçues de Washington, E.U. ; Madrid, Espagne ; Stockholm, Suède, et l'Allemagne de l'Est. Les délégués à l'Assemblée exprimèrent leur reconnaissance pour ces gracieuses invitations et demandèrent au Comité exécutif de faire un choix définitif lors de sa réunion de 1970.

XIX – Autres sujets :

Le docteur Gerhard Herzberg du Canada parla du travail accompli pour l'Union par le président Blokhintsev. Celui-ci s'était acquitté de ses tâches avec beaucoup de soin, de délicatesse et d'imagination et avait apporté beaucoup de dignité à sa position. Le docteur Herzberg mentionna également que trois des vice-présidents terminaient leur mandat : le professeur Danysz de la Pologne, le professeur Jauch de la Suisse, et Sir Gordon Sutherland du Royaume-Uni. Tous les trois avaient contribué grandement de leur temps et de leurs énergies pour les affaires de l'Union et avaient apporté une réelle contribution à la Physique. Il ajouta des remarques personnelles témoignant de l'extraordinaire travail du professeur deBoer pour la Commission S.U.N. depuis tant d'années.

XX – Ajournement de l'Assemblée :

Le président Blokhintsev s'adressa brièvement à l'Assemblée avant d'ajourner les séances. Copie de son discours se trouve à l'Annexe I. Au nom de tous les délégués, il remercia ensuite les organisateurs de la Yougoslavie et en particulier le professeur Milojevic et le docteur Milic qui s'étaient tant dévoués pendant l'Assemblée. Il exprima également sa reconnaissance personnelle à l'endroit des délégués pour leur participation aux discussions.

Le Président déclara alors la séance levée.

Annexe III

LES CONGRÈS INTERNATIONAUX

Les critères et les règlements qui suivent ont été approuvés pour essai lors de la XIII^{ème} Assemblée Générale de l'Union à Dubrovnik. Ils seront repris en considération par le Comité exécutif et tout changement dicté par l'expérience sera proposé à la XIV^{ème} Assemblée Générale.

1. Catégories

A. *Conférences générales*

Ces conférences couvriraient une revue complète, si les progrès dans la discipline donnée la justifie, du champ de Physique confié à une commission. Elle auraient normalement lieu à tous les trois ans et l'on pourrait s'attendre à une assistance variant entre 750 et 1500 personnes.

B. *Conférences particulières*

Lors de ces conférences, on traiterait de sous-sujets relatifs au champ d'intérêt de la Commission concernée (e.g. la spectroscopie nucléaire, les mécanismes de réactions nucléaires, la physique des ions lourds, dans le cas de la Commission de Physique nucléaire). Ces conférences auraient ordinairement lieu pendant l'année où on ne tiendrait pas de Conférence générale (catégorie A). On pourrait s'attendre à une assistance variant entre 300 et 600 personnes.

C. *Conférences spéciales*

Ces conférences traiteraient de sujets restreints et beaucoup plus spécialisés que dans les cas des conférences de catégorie B (e.g. les corrélations angulaires, les mesures de demi-vies, l'étude de résonances neutroniques, dans le cas de la Commission de Physique nucléaire). Ces conférences auraient lieu durant les années où on ne prévoit pas de conférences générales (catégorie A) et regrouperaient entre 50 et 200 personnes.

2. Critères

A. *Valeur scientifique*

- a) On devra clairement démontrer le besoin de la conférence proposée, i.e. que des progrès nouveaux et importants ont eu lieu depuis la dernière conférence de même catégorie ;
- b) les conférenciers invités et les communications acceptées pour discussion devront être d'un calibre des plus élevés ;
- c) on n'acceptera que les communications qui auront été prises en considération par un comité d'arbitres, ce qui assurera des communications d'un niveau comparable à celui des communications qui paraissent dans les journaux scientifiques réguliers. Si les communications invitées ou autres doivent être publiées, on devra fournir tous les efforts possibles afin qu'elles le soient dans un numéro spécial d'un journal scientifique régulier de façon à les rendre facilement disponibles à la communauté scientifique.

B. *Caractère international*

- a) Un comité international devra organiser le programme scientifique ;
- b) la participation devra être réellement internationale et ne pas constituer ce qui serait effectivement une conférence nationale à laquelle on aurait invité quelques physiciens de l'extérieur. Ces dernières conférences nationales sont nécessaires et des plus utiles, mais n'entrent pas dans le mandat de l'Union. Les organisateurs des conférences qui demandent le patronage de l'Union devront faire tout en leur possible pour assurer que l'assistance venant de l'extérieur du pays hôte ne soit pas inférieure à 30% mais de préférence supérieure à 50% ;
- c) les conférences "ouvertes" devront admettre les physiciens de tout pays membre de l'U.I.P.P.A. Par contre, la liste des invités à une conférence "sur invitation" devra inclure la possibilité de participation de physiciens

venant de tout pays membre de l'Union où l'on poursuit des recherches actives dans le domaine traité lors de la conférence ;

- d) l'U.I.P.P.A. n'accordera pas son patronage à une conférence si l'on refuse des visas à des participants pour raisons de nationalité ou de citoyenneté. Il est entendu que toute demande de patronage de l'Union implique que le pays hôte fera le nécessaire pour que chaque physicien recommandé par le Comité international (a) soit en mesure d'obtenir un visa et ce dans un temps convenable.

C. *Organisation*

- a) La conférence devra recevoir l'approbation de la Commission internationale appropriée de l'Union. De plus, les détails relatifs à l'organisation devront être soumis à cette Commission au mois d'avril de l'année précédant celle où la conférence doit avoir lieu ;
- b) il est impérieux que les dates précises, l'adresse de la conférence, le nom et l'adresse du Secrétaire ou de l'Organisateur principal de la conférence, etc. , soient fournis à la Commission qui pourra alors éviter des conflits de dates, etc. , s'il y a lieu ;
- c) la conférence proposée aurait avantage à recevoir l'approbation du Comité national de l'Union du pays hôte ;
- d) il est très utile à la Commission internationale d'avoir autant de détails que possible sur l'organisation et le budget de la conférence proposée.

3. Divers

Le Comité exécutif de l'Union se réunit à la fin de septembre de chaque année et détermine à cette occasion à quelles conférences internationales l'Union accordera son patronage et, s'il y a lieu, des octrois. Les Commissions doivent donc soumettre leurs recommandations au Secrétaire-général au plus tard le 15 août en ayant soin d'inclure tous les renseignements mentionnés

ci-haut (2-C : Organisation). Les recommandations de la Commission doivent être basées sur les critères définis en 2-A et 2-B, et doivent comprendre une classification quant à la catégorie (1). Ainsi donc, les organisateurs des conférences doivent soumettre leurs demandes aux Commissions internationales en avril afin de permettre à la Commission de se rencontrer (le plus souvent par correspondance) et d'étudier la demande. Pour ce qui concerne les conférences internationales qui ne sont pas du ressort des Commissions, on doit s'adresser directement au Secrétaire-général.

IV – QUELQUES RÉOLUTIONS ADOPTÉES LORS DES ASSEMBLÉES GÉNÉRALES

Congrès internationaux

« Pour que le patronage de l'Union soit accordé à une Conférence, ce qui implique, en principe, une subvention de l'Union déterminée selon les besoins et les possibilités, il est nécessaire :

1. que le Comité exécutif ait approuvé l'éventualité de ce patronage, compte tenu de l'intérêt actuel du sujet et des autres projets de colloques envisagés;
2. que les organisateurs du colloque aient pris, au préalable, l'engagement formel de soumettre, pour accord, au Président de l'Union de Physique, le programme scientifique précis, la date et le lieu des réunions et le choix des personnes appelées à présenter les principaux rapports, ce choix étant fait de manière à assurer à la Conférence une large participation internationale ».

(Londres, 1954)

Visas

« Étant donné que le déplacement libre de tous les hommes de science afin de participer aux congrès scientifiques internationaux est une des bases indispensables pour une saine coopération internationale, et étant donné en plus que cette question affecte non seulement l'Union internationale de Physique pure et appliquée mais toutes les unions scientifiques qui font partie du Conseil international des Unions scientifiques, l'Union internationale de Physique pure et appliquée demande au Conseil international des Unions scientifiques :

1. d'encourager ses membres nationaux à faire les démarches nécessaires auprès de leurs gouvernements respectifs pour que les hommes de science assistant aux congrès scientifiques internationaux puissent obtenir facilement des visas d'entrée et de sortie ;
2. de faire part de ce problème aux Nations-Unies avec une demande pour que l'on trouve les moyens nécessaires pour assurer

le déplacement libre des hommes de science qui assistent à des conférences et à des congrès internationaux scientifiques. »

(Varsovie, 1963)

Élections

« L'Assemblée discute ensuite la procédure que l'on pourrait suivre à l'avenir pour les nominations aux postes qui pourraient être vacants à l'Exécutif ainsi qu'aux commissions. Il fut décidé que toute suggestion devait être envoyée au Secrétaire-général par les comités nationaux bien avant la prochaine Assemblée. Toutes les propositions seront alors distribuées aux délégués dès leur arrivée à l'Assemblée. Le Comité exécutif aurait le droit d'ajouter des noms sur cette liste. Il devait cependant faire ces choix juste avant le début de l'assemblée et faire circuler un document aux délégués indiquant les suggestions du Comité exécutif. Ainsi, les délégués pourraient prendre en considération toutes les suggestions ainsi que les recommandations du Comité exécutif un ou deux jours avant d'être appelés à voter. On était d'accord que des noms supplémentaires pourraient être proposés par les membres de l'Assemblée juste avant le vote final. »

(Varsovie, 1963)

Jeunes scientifiques

« Étant donné qu'il est désirable de fournir une continuité dans la croissance des rencontres intimes internationales entre les physiciens, l'Assemblée générale de l'UIPPA considère qu'il est très désirable que les délégations aux grandes conférences internationales sous le patronage de l'UIPPA comprennent de jeunes physiciens en plus des savants des plus distingués dans le domaine particulier traité par la conférence. »

(Varsovie, 1963)

C.I.U.S.

« L'Assemblée générale de l'Union internationale de Physique pure et appliquée approuve en principe les propositions du Comité chargé de réorganiser le CIUS mais fait la recommandation suivante :

Afin de sauvegarder la nature scientifique impliquée dans le nom du CIUS, il est extrêmement désirable que le nombre de vote ne soit pas dépassé par le nombre de votes des membres nationaux à l'Assemblée générale du CIUS. On pourrait équilibrer ces blocs en augmentant le vote des unions et en donnant à chaque union générale plus de vote que chaque union spécialisée. On admet qu'au fur et à mesure que le nombre des unions et des nations donnant leur adhésion au CIUS augmentera, la procédure quant à la votation devra être modifiée. »

(Varsovie, 1963)

Communications scientifiques

« Toute communication scientifique, à l'exception peut-être de quelques lettres, devrait être publiée avec un résumé en anglais, en français ou en russe. Il est également désirable qu'elle soit publiée dans une deuxième langue ».

(Varsovie, 1963)

Publications

« L'Assemblée générale approuve :

1. le « Guide for the Preparation of Authors' Abstracts for Publication » tout en autorisant la Commission à effectuer quelques modifications afin d'effectuer un accord avec l'UNESCO ;
2. le « Guide for the Preparation of Scientific Papers for Publication » en autorisant la Commission à faire quelques modifications afin d'effectuer une entente avec l'UNESCO ;
3. la déclaration sur les références bibliographiques sur la deuxième page du rapport de la Commission ;
4. la déclaration suivante sur la publication des comptes-rendus des conférences :

L'assemblage d'une collection de textes de communications préparé d'avance pour les délégués à une conférence ne constitue pas une publication convenable du compte-rendu d'une conférence. Il est très souhaitable que les textes d'un

tel compte-rendu soient soumis à des arbitres scientifiques de la même façon que s'il s'agissait d'un journal scientifique réputé.

Lorsque les textes d'une conférence sont publiés ensemble plutôt que soumis séparément à des journaux appropriés, cet ensemble doit constituer un numéro régulier ou spécial d'un journal ou encore paraître dans un seul volume susceptible d'être largement distribué par un réseau bien établi.

Cependant, dans ce cas, l'on doit fournir la référence bibliographique.

Le compte-rendu publié doit être soumis aux services des résumés analytiques, et les secrétaires de conférences doivent assumer la responsabilité d'indiquer, à l'attention des journaux de résumés analytiques, l'existence de ces comptes-rendus.

L'Assemblée générale recommande :

5. l'adoption d'un seul critère pour l'utilisation des abréviations dans les titres de communications dans les journaux et, à cet effet, attire l'attention de l'OIS sur l'oeuvre du Comité Z-39 de l'American Standards Association. »

(Bâle, 1966)

Éducation en Physique

« Étant donné :

1. que les progrès rapides dans les domaines de la Physique pure et appliquée accroissent non seulement la connaissance qu'a l'homme de son univers mais, par leurs applications, ont aussi des implications profondes pour le bien-être de l'humanité ;
2. que les découvertes en Physique, la plus fondamentale des sciences naturelles, influencent fortement toutes les sciences fondamentales et appliquées ainsi que les professions qui s'y rapportent ;
3. que l'enseignement de la Physique aux étudiants avancés, aux étudiants dans les domaines connexes scientifiques et profes-

sionnels, et à ceux qui deviendront partie d'une citoyenneté bien renseignée, ne peut être bien donné que par ceux qui sont eux-mêmes actifs à créer ou à utiliser de nouvelles connaissances ; et

4. que la recherche atteint son apogée lors de la communication de nouvelles connaissances à d'autres personnes et que les employeurs devraient reconnaître l'importance de l'évaluation et de la synthèse de connaissances existantes, ce qui exige souvent une capacité de perception et de créativité au moins aussi grande que pour la recherche primaire :

l'Union internationale de la Physique pure et appliquée adopte la résolution suivante :

1. que la recherche et l'enseignement doivent être maintenus étroitement associés ;
2. que toute tendance à la divergence entre les activités en vue de faire avancer et d'enseigner les connaissances doit être vigoureusement contrecarrée, et que l'on doit augmenter les efforts afin d'améliorer l'enseignement de la Physique ;
3. que l'excellence dans l'enseignement et la dissémination de la connaissance relative à la Physique doit être reconnue autant que pour la recherche. Conséquemment, toutes les agences et fondations accordant des subventions devraient également fournir un appui financier pour la préparation de revues critiques des développements courants et pour la compilation de données critiques ;
4. que les chercheurs doués doivent également enseigner, et qu'on ne peut les exempter de l'enseignement que lors de circonstances spéciales et non pas afin de les récompenser de l'excellence de leurs travaux ;
5. qu'on doit encourager les enseignants à entretenir leur vitalité intellectuelle et leur participation à l'avancement des connaissances en leur accordant du temps pour la recherche ou pour des activités académiques associées ; et
6. que les chercheurs dans les Instituts de Recherche et dans les Laboratoires industriels devraient communiquer avec les orga-

nisations académiques en ce qui concerne l'éducation des étudiants avancés en Physique. »

(Dubrovnik, 1969)

Symboles

« Les délégués à l'Assemblée générale adoptèrent unanimement la résolution suivante :

que les auteurs soient encouragés à adopter les unités IS pour les données dans les journaux de Physique, tel que recommandé par la Commission S.U.N., la Conférence générale des Poids et Mesures, l'Organisation internationale pour la normalisation, et par d'autres unions internationales associées à la Physique. On recommande aux éditeurs d'employer la persuasion plutôt que des mesures plus fortes pour obtenir la collaboration des auteurs sur le choix des symboles pour les quantités physiques et pour les unités, mais ils devraient exiger que les symboles recommandés pour les unités soient utilisés, sauf lorsque les noms des unités sont écrits au long. »

(Dubrovnik, 1969)

ICSU Committee on Data for Science and Technology (CODATA)
(IUPAP representative : B. Vodar)

L'activité de CODATA s'est développée au cours de l'année écoulée. En particulier, on doit noter que CODATA a organisé la première Conférence Internationale sur la Production, la Collecte, l'Évaluation et la Dissémination des Données Numériques pour la Science et la Technologie, qui s'est tenue à Arnoldshain près de Francfort/Main en R.F.S., au mois de juillet 1968. Cette conférence, qui a réuni une centaine de participants de 14 pays différents, comportait des séances consacrées aux thèmes suivants:

- 1) Spectres infrarouges
- 2) Données thermodynamiques
- 3) Définitions
- 4) Indexation
- 5) Utilisation de la littérature scientifique
- 6) Formulaire de données numériques.

Il faut noter en particulier des exposés sur les importants programmes américains et soviétiques dans le domaine des données numériques, ainsi que dans divers pays, un intérêt pour ce domaine, où la mise en place de structures (tel que le Bureau National de Métrologie en France) pouvant servir à faciliter la coordination des efforts pour le développement des données numériques précises. La Conférence s'est terminée par une discussion (animée par Sir Gordon Sutherland) où ont été évoquées des vues d'avenir, dont la mise en place de Centre de Données Numériques, dont CODATA pourrait être le coordonnateur.

CODATA a tenu en 1968 sa réunion annuelle à Moscou et son Bureau s'est réuni à Francfort/Main où a été transféré son Secrétariat Central, placé sous la direction du Dr. Ch. Schäfer en remplacement du Dr. G. Waddington. Le Professeur Klemm est devenu Trésorier, en remplacement de Sir Gordon Sutherland qui l'a remplacé à la Vice-Présidence. La prochaine réunion du CODATA se tiendra fin juin à Rome.

Les pays suivants ont demandé à être affiliés au CODATA : Canada, Japon, Italie, Pologne.

Des représentants du CODATA ont participé à certaines des réunions organisées par l'UNESCO pour l'étude possible de l'Organisation d'un Système Mondial d'Information Scientifique, sans que les problèmes propres aux données numériques aient encore fait l'objet d'une discussion approfondie dans le cadre de cette étude.

Le groupe de travail sur l'usage des ordinateurs a poursuivi ses travaux et un nouveau groupe, sur les Constantes Fondamentales, a été constitué, avec le Dr. H.R. Cohen (U.S.A.) comme Président ; une très bonne liaison avec la Commission des Masses Atomiques et Constantes associées de l'U.I.P.P.A. est assurée par l'intermédiaire de membres communs, tels que le Dr Cohen et le Professeur Terrien. Signalons également la constitution d'un nouveau groupe sur les constantes clefs réunissant pour la première fois des experts de diverses disciplines scientifiques.

La préparation de l'index des recueils et projets des données numériques, est maintenant poursuivie à Francfort/Main pour le Secrétariat Central, après transfert des dossiers en provenance de Washington, et doit être achevée très prochainement.

July 1969.

INTERNATIONAL UNION OF PURE AND
APPLIED PHYSICS

JAN NILSSON
INSTITUTE OF THEORETICAL PHYSICS
GÖTEBORG, SWEDEN

I U P A P

GENERAL REPORT

1973

INTERNATIONAL UNION
OF PURE AND APPLIED PHYSICS

GENERAL INFORMATION

REPORT
ON THE XIVth GENERAL ASSEMBLY
WASHINGTON DC, 1972

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I — ADMINISTRATION

The history of the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics is described in eight previous publications (documents IUPAP 1, 2, 4, 5, 7, 8, 10 and 14).

Essentially, the Union is composed of the National Physics Committees or groups of physicists in the various countries adhering to the Union (see center pages). Delegates from these committees meet in the General Assemblies of the Union which are held every three years. The General Assembly appoints the members of the Executive Committee, and various special committees, and nominates representatives on various interunion committees.

General Assemblies were held in Brussels (1923 and 1925), Paris (1931 and 1947), London (1934 and 1954), Amsterdam (1948), Copenhagen (1951), Rome (1957), Ottawa (1960), Warsaw (1963), Basle (1966), Dubrovnik (1969), Washington DC (1972). The Executive Committee usually meets once each year.

The Physics Union adheres to the International Council of Scientific Unions (ICSU). This Council is at present composed of 17 unions and more than 60 national members. The President of ICSU is Prof. J. Coulomb (France), and the Secretary-General is Prof. F. A. Stafleu (Netherlands). The administrative office is in Paris (51, Bd de Montmorency, 75016 Paris, France).

The General Assembly of ICSU consists of union representatives, together with national delegates. In the future, the Assembly will meet in alternate years.

In 1946, ICSU concluded an agreement with the United Nations Economic, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) which enables the Union to receive, through ICSU, special financial grants specifically to support international conferences.

The use of funds from UNESCO for conference expenses is subject to the following conditions:

- i) UNESCO may wish to send a representative to the meeting;
- ii) UNESCO would like mention of its support in all relevant publications. The following wording is suggested: "Published with the financial support of UNESCO";
- iii) UNESCO would like to receive ten copies of all conference reports.

Conferences and meetings of commissions are also supported from funds derived from the national members of IUPAP. These funds are also used to meet the administration expenses of the Union.

Correspondence concerning financial and national matters should be sent to the Secretary-General.

Correspondence concerning the commissions and general publicity matters should be sent to the Associate Secretary-General.

II — STATUTES

(adopted by the General Assembly of 1931 and modified by those of 1948, 1954, and 1960. The 1960 modifications are in italics).

I. Aims of the Union and Conditions of Membership

1. The aims of the Union are:

- (i) the stimulation and promotion of international co-operation in Physics;
- (ii) the co-ordination of the work of preparing and publishing abstracts of papers and tables of physical constants;
- (iii) the promotion of international agreements on the use of symbols, units, nomenclature, and standards;
- (iv) the encouragement of interesting research.

The Union may organize international meetings.

Individual nations may join the Union through their National Academies, their National Research Councils, equivalent national societies or groups of societies, or, if suitable ones do not exist, through their Governments.

Membership of a given nation through several distinct organizations is not permitted, unless these several organizations have previously agreed to share Union dues and voting rights.

The word "nation" includes dominions, diplomatic protectorates, or other territories which have an independent scientific community.

II. National Committees

2. The body responsible for initiating its country's membership in the Union will set up a National Committee, which will maintain liaison with the Union.

3. The National Committees will, in their respective countries, encourage and co-ordinate study in various fields of Physics, with emphasis on international aspects. Every National Committee may, of itself or in collaboration with other National Committees, submit to the Union for discussion problems which are within its competence.

The National Committees elect their delegates to Union assemblies. They also elect a Delegation Head who votes on the delegation's behalf on questions of administration as laid down in Articles 14 and 16.

III. Administration of the Union

4. The work of the Union is directed by the General Assembly of delegates.

5. *The Executive Committee of the Union comprises: the President, the Past President, the first Vice-President, the Vice-Presidents, and the Secretary-General. With the exception of the Past-President, the members of the Executive Committee are elected by the General Assembly; they remain in office up to the end of the ordinary General Assembly following their election. The first Vice-President replaces the President if the latter is unable to officiate.*

With the exception of the Secretary-General, the elected members of the Executive Committee may not continually occupy the same office for more than two intervals between ordinary General Assemblies.

The Executive Committee may appoint members to vacancies which may occur in the Committee. Members named in this fashion will complete the term of the member whom they are replacing.

There is also set up an *administrative office* under the direction of the Secretary-General of the Union. This office deals with Union correspondence, administers Union funds, maintains archives, and organizes the preparation and distribution of those publications approved by the General Assembly.

IV. Commissions

6. The General Assembly and, subject to the approval of the next General Assembly, the Executive Committee may set up commissions pertinent to the work of the Union and may also decide to participate in joint commissions together with one or more other unions.

Union commissions include *affiliated commissions* whose activities concern certain wide fields of Physics, and *specialized commissions* which concern themselves with more specialized subjects.

Each commission must submit, through its Secretary, a report of its work to each General Assembly.

7. The constitution, statutes, activities, and financial statements of affiliated commissions must be submitted for approval to the Executive Committee of the Union. The latter has the particular responsibility of seeing that the commission's field of interest be well defined.

The Executive Committee delegates one or more of its members to represent the Union on each affiliated commission.

Affiliated commissions may, in addition to funds voted to them by the Union, collect special dues and receive grants from other sources.

8. The members of specialized commissions and the delegates of the Union to joint commissions are elected by the General Assembly which takes into consideration the suggestions of the Executive Committee. These members and delegates remain in office up to the end of the next General Assembly, and are eligible for re-election.

Specialized commissions may add members to their number subject to the approval of the Executive Committee.

The designation of members of affiliated commissions other than those delegates of the Executive Committee of the Union provided for under Article 7, is determined by the statutes of each commission.

Activities of joint commissions are governed by the International Council of Scientific Unions.

V. General Assemblies

9. Ordinary General Assemblies of the Union are held, in principle, every three years. If the date and site of a meeting have not been decided by the previous General Assembly, they are set by the Executive Committee and announced, at least four months in advance, to all members and affiliates.

10. In special cases, the President may, with the approval of the Executive Committee, convene an extraordinary General Assembly; he is obliged to do so at the request of one-third of the votes of member nations.

11. All members of National Committees may attend the meetings of the General Assembly and take part in the deliberations. However, they may not vote.

The President of the Union may invite scientists who are not delegates to attend meetings of the General Assembly as consultants.

Members of affiliated commissions mentioned in Article 7 who are not delegates to the General Assembly may nevertheless take part in meetings of the General Assembly when matters concerning their commission are discussed. However, they may not vote.

12. The Agenda of Meetings is determined by the Executive Committee and issued at least four months before the opening of the Meeting. Subjects not on the Agenda may not be debated at the Assembly without the consent of half of the votes of nations represented at the Assembly.

VI. International Congresses

13. International Congresses are organized by the Executive Committee of the Union.

VII. Budget and Voting Rights

14. The Executive Committee will draft a budget estimate for each year for the period between sessions of the General Assembly. A financial commission, set up by the General Assembly, is appointed to examine each year the financial statement of the preceding year, and to study the draft budget for the next. It prepares separate reports on these two matters for submission to the General Assembly.

Following consideration of these reports, the General Assembly sets the value of one share of Union dues.* Members' annual dues are then determined by the number of shares of each country. This number is determined by the Executive Committee which takes into account the suggestions of the country's National Committee, and may subsequently be modified by agreement between the Executive Committee and the said National Committee.

The establishment or modification of the number of shares assigned to a country must be ratified by the next General Assembly.

The number of official delegates (and votes) is fixed according to the following scale:

Number of shares:	1,	2 or 3,	4 to 6,	7 to 9,	10 and more
Number of official delegates (and votes):	1,	2,	3,	4,	5

The Academy or other group responsible for a country's membership in IUPAP is also responsible for the payment of annual dues.

15. All dues which the Union receives from its member countries must be used:

- (i) to pay for the cost of publications and incidental administrative expenses;
- (ii) to carry out the aims outlined in Article 1.

Gifts received by the Union must be used in accordance with the wishes of the donors.

*One share was fixed at U.S. \$300. from January 1st 1971.

Any country withdrawing from the Union forfeits its rights to Union assets.

16. In the course of General Assemblies, motions concerning scientific questions are carried by a majority of votes of all delegates present.

Motions concerning the administration of the Union or motions of a mixed nature will be carried by a majority of votes cast by heads of National Delegations according to Article 14.

Any doubts as to the category of the motion will be decided by the President.

At the meetings of commissions, motions are decided by majority votes of delegates and not by countries.

In all cases of tied votes, the President will cast the deciding vote.

17. A member country whose delegation will not attend a given General Assembly but wishes to vote on an appropriate matter appearing on the Agenda may send its vote in writing to the President. To be valid, it must be received before the votes on that motion be counted.

VIII. By-Laws

18. The General Assembly may pass by-laws regulating the conduct of its work, the duties incumbent on the members of the Executive Committee, or, in general, anything not provided by these statutes. Each commission may also set up bylaws governing its own activities. Such by-laws may not however contravene the Union's statutes.

IX. Deration of the Union and Modification of its Statutes

19. The life of the Union is not limited.

20. No change may be made in the present statutes without the approval of two-thirds of the votes of member countries.

21. In the event of the dissolution of the Union by a vote of the General Assembly receiving a majority of two-thirds of the votes of the member countries, its assets will be allocated by the General Assembly to one or more scientific organizations.

22. In the case of discussion as to the interpretation of the articles of the Statutes, the French text will be used exclusively.

APPENDIX A

Procedure for the Appointment of Commission Members by the General Assembly

These articles are in conformity with the Statutes. However, they are not themselves statutes but rules of procedure only. They may be adopted or changed by each General Assembly.

1. Each Commission (other than the Finance Commission) will consist of:

Chairman
Secretary
5 to 10 members.

2. Commissions will advise the Executive Committee on the appropriate size for their work. The Executive will make recommendations to each Assembly which will fix Commission sizes before elections take place.

3. Chairmen of Commissions

Chairmen will be appointed for 3 years, normally after 3 (or exceptionally after 6) years as secretary or as an ordinary member of their Commission. In exceptional circumstances, a Chairman may become an ordinary member of the Commission for 3 years after his period as Chairman.

4. Secretaries of Commissions

Secretaries will be appointed for 3 years after 3 years' service on the Commission. Secretaries will be eligible for a second, and final, cycle of 3 years. For the SUN and Atomic Masses Commissions, Secretaries may be appointed after 6 years' service on their Commission.

5. *Commission members*

Commission members will be appointed for 3 years and will be eligible for one further term of 3 years.

Exceptions to this rule will be permitted for members of Commissions which have very specialized tasks and undoubtedly have a need for some of their members to serve longer than 6 years.

6. *National Distribution of Commission Membership*

The members of each Commission (excluding Chairman and Secretary) must all come from different countries adhering to IUPAP.

The work of a few Commission may be hindered by this rule. They may present their case to the Executive and, if approval is given, the Executive will make a recommendation to the General Assembly for ratification before the elections take place.

7. *Associate Members*

Some Commissions have established valuable links with several scientific unions and other international organizations. They may wish to ask these organizations to nominate experts in these fields to become associate members of IUPAP Commissions. (IUPAP will be invited to appoint physicists as associate members of Commissions established by other Unions.)

The maximum number of associate members of any one Commission will normally be four.

Associate members are not entitled to vote at Commission Meetings nor will they be eligible for IUPAP grants towards travelling and subsistence expenses.

8. The Executive recognizes that it may not be possible to implement all these rules concerning length of service straightaway in 1972.

When new Commissions are established, *ad hoc* arrangements will need to be made until a normal rotation of membership can be established.

9. *Election Procedure for Commission Members*

- 9.1. National Committees and Commissions will be invited to suggest names for membership (including the offices of Chairman and Secretary) of Commissions to the Secretary-General up to *four months* before the General Assembly. Each name submitted must be accompanied by brief details of the physicist's career and post currently held, and, for names submitted by Commissions, it is desirable that the support of the candidate's National Committee should be obtained. A special form will be provided for this purpose. The Secretary-General (or Associate Secretary-General) will circulate all the names received by the deadline to National Committees 3 months before the General Assembly.
- 9.2. The Executive Committee will consider all the suggested names (and may itself suggest names) and will subsequently prepare, as a basis for discussion at the Assembly, a list of names for members of the Commissions.

In preparing the lists of names for Commissions, the Executive will endeavour to ensure a satisfactory world-wide spread of Commission membership. The Executive will publish their proposed list of Commission members as early as possible but not later than the beginning of the General Assembly.
- 9.3. After the publication of the Executive Committee's list of recommended names, it may transpire that some person may be unwilling to serve either as Chairman, Secretary or member. In this event, or if comments are received from National Committees or Commissions, the Executive Committee will make suitable proposals, e.g. they may interchange the name of one of the proposed officers with that of a proposed member or even introduce a new name. The Executive Committee's final list of names will be issued early in the Assembly in time for general discussion.
- 9.4. After the general discussion, individual National Delegations attending the Assembly will be able to reintroduce names from

the list of suggested names and add them to the final Executive list by *an agreed deadline* and using appropriate nomination forms. Names not on the original list may only be introduced by leave of the General Assembly. At this stage, each proposal must be seconded by another delegation. If any candidate is not a member of the proposer's nation, then the seconder should be the candidate's own National Delegation.

- 9.5. In the event of unforeseen circumstances (e.g. unexpected withdrawals) modifying the list of nominees after the nomination *deadline* is passed, the Secretary-General, after consultation with members of the Executive, will add such names as are necessary to complete the list. The modified list will then be presented to the General Assembly for ratification.
- 9.6. If more names are included on the final ratified list than the number of vacancies to be filled on one or more Commission, then secret ballots will be held. The voting procedure will be the same as the one adopted for choosing Executive Committee members. Voting must be consistent with paragraph (6.).
- 9.7. The procedure for filling casual vacancies on Commission which occur between meetings of the General Assembly will be the same as for casual vacancies on the Executive Committee (Statute 5).

APPENDIX B

The Sizes of IUPAP Commissions for the period 1973—75

Each Commission shall consist of Chairman and Secretary together with ordinary members, all appointed by the General Assembly. The numbers of ordinary members to be as followed:

C. 2	SUN	10 members
C. 3	Thermodynamics and Statistical Mechanics	10 members
C. 4	Cosmic Rays	8 members
C. 5	Very Low Temperature	9 members
C. 6	Publications	10 members
C. 7	Acoustics	10 members
C. 8	Semiconductors	8 members
C. 9	Magnetism	10 members
C.10	Solid State Physics	10 members
C.11	Particles and Fields	10 members
C.12	Nuclear Physics	10 members
C.13	Atomic Masses and Fundamental Constants	8 members
C.14	Education	9 members
C.15	Atomic and Molecular Physics and Spectroscopy	10 members
C.16	Plasma Physics	10 members

III. — MINUTES of the XIVth GENERAL ASSEMBLY of IUPAP WASHINGTON, U.S.A., SEPTEMBER 20—24, 1972

The Assembly met in the Auditorium of the United States National Academy of Sciences on Wednesday, Friday and Sunday, September 20, 22 and 24. The President, Professor Robert BACHER, was in the Chair for all sessions.

113 delegates had registered for the meeting. The list, by country, is given in Appendix I.

Arrangements for the meeting were made by the National Academy of Sciences, the American Institute of Physics, and the American Physical Society, coordinated by the USA National Committee for IUPAP. Chairman of the Arrangements Committee was Dr. Lewis Branscomb; chairman of the Finance Committee was Dr. Wm. Koch; chairman of the Science Programme was Dr. Wm. Havens. The Academy staff was under the direction of Dr. Hugh Odishaw, assisted by Mr. Richard Dow and Mrs. Susan Perry.

Delegates were guests at a reception given by the Academy. The dinner was tendered by the State Department of the USA, while the IUPAP banquet was tendered by the Research Corporation.

About 300 physicists in addition to the delegates attended the lectures of the science programme. Visits were arranged for delegates to the National Bureau of Standards and the Goddard Space Flight Center (NASA).

An inviting Ladies' programme was arranged by Mrs. Robert Bacher and Mrs. Herbert Friedman.

The First and Second sessions
Wednesday, September 20th
10h30 and 13h30

A —

The delegates were welcomed to Washington and the National Academy by Dr. Philip Handler, president of the Academy. Dr. E. E. David expressed his gratification at the visit of the Union to the United States. Professor Bacher also welcomed the Assembly on behalf of the United States National Committee for IUPAP, and read a message of welcome from President Nixon.

1. *Introduction*

Professor Bacher opened the meeting and read telegrams of greetings and good wishes from Professors Artsimovich of the Plasma Commission; Ambartsumian, president of ICSU; and Blokhintsev, past-president of IUPAP.

2. *Minutes*

The minutes of the XIIIth General Assembly held in Dubrovnik in 1969 were approved as printed in the General Report of 1970.

3. *Agenda*

A draft agenda had been circulated. This was commented on by the Secretary-General, who explained in detail the proposed voting procedure for elections. He noted that a secretariat was available for those wishing to distribute resolutions, etc.

On motion by Canada, seconded, the draft agenda was approved by voice vote.

Professor Kurti of the UK suggested that of the two proposed dates for the last session, that of Sunday morning be selected.

This was agreed to by show of hands.

4. *Obituaries*

The Secretary-General noted the passing of Professor Paul Huber, a former Vice-president and host at the XIIth Assembly at Basle; of Professor N. V. Fedorenko of the Atomic and Molecular Physics

and Spectroscopy Commission; and of Professor L. V. Kirenski of the Magnetism Commission. The delegates stood for a minute's silence in memory of these colleagues.

5. *Election procedures*

The document "Paper I" concerning the election procedures for Executive and Commission membership was commented on by the Secretary-General and then discussed by the Assembly. Several queries were answered and then

On motion by the United Kingdom, seconded, articles 1—6 (concerning the Executive) were approved by voice vote.

It was noted by the Assembly that these articles are in conformity with the statutes. However, they are not themselves statutes but rules of procedure only. They may be adopted or changed by each General Assembly.

Discussion continued on articles concerning the Commissions. Motion for adoption was successfully amended on motion by Sweden concerning associates from various organizations.

A further amendment by the United Kingdom on article 7 concerning the presence of members from a host country on the Commission was defeated by 56 roll-call votes to 21.

An amendment by France to limit the number of associates on Commissions "normally" to four was approved by 58 roll-call votes to 17.

An amendment by Switzerland to delete mention of specific Commissions in rules was approved by voice vote.

On motion by Australia, seconded, articles 1—8 (concerning Commissions) were approved as amended by voice vote.

Discussion continued on article 9. Several suggested minor modifications were permitted without motion.

On motion by Canada, seconded, article 9 (concerning Commissions) was approved by voice vote.

The Secretary-General undertook to provide a new copy of the rules as amended for final review at a subsequent session (see fourth Session).

6. *Size of Commissions*

The document "Paper II" concerning the proposed sizes of Commissions was explained by the Secretary-General. The general motion for adoption was successfully amended by voice vote on proposal by the United Kingdom concerning the preliminary wording. Discussion followed on the advisability of having Commissions elect their own chairman and secretary but this idea was not supported.

An amendment by Poland to change the number of members in the Semiconductor Commission from 8 to 10 was defeated by voice vote (8 had been requested by the Commission).

On motion by Sweden, seconded, the document "Paper II" (concerning Commission sizes) was adopted as amended by unanimous voice vote.

This document as amended is given in Appendix B to the Statutes in this Document (IUPAP-17).

7. *Slate for Elections*

The document "Paper III" contained suggestions made for the membership of each Commission by National Committees and Commissions, and the slate nominated by the Executive according to the rules of procedure. This had been circulated in preliminary form in June, and, as a result of comments received, re-circulated in modified form just before the beginning of the Assembly. The Secretary-General reviewed the document, offering many explanations of points raised by delegates. Some delegates advised that they would be submitting further nominations according to the rules of procedure (see Item 17).

8. *Report of the Secretary-General*

The Secretary-General reported that the routine business of the Union had been executed as usual by the London and Quebec offices.

Most of the detailed work of the Union was done by the Commissions and their Conference committees. Particular attention had been paid to giving greater publicity to the Union. The Executive had held three meetings between Assemblies and had spent much time in preparing the 50th anniversary. It had carefully studied the proposed nominating and election procedures following adverse comments by delegates on the procedures used at the XIIIth Assembly.

9. *Reports of International Commissions*

These had been circulated and will be found in Appendix II of this Document.

The reports were also presented orally by a Commission member, who sometimes added information and replied to questions from the Assembly. In particular:

C. 2 — *SUN*

Dr. Rudberg

It was suggested that the Commission circulate its proposals to National Committees and Commissions for comment before adoption. It was stated that the opinion of Physics Journals editors was also very important for practical reasons.

— Session adjourned —

B —

Following the Wednesday meetings, a short ceremony took place in the Auditorium: the unveiling of a bust by the Danish sculptor Harald Isenstein in commemoration of the 50th anniversary of the awarding of the Nobel Prize to Niels BOHR.

Brief remarks were made by Professor Larkin Kerwin who told the story of how the bust came to be commissioned; by Professor S. Rozental who described some of the features of Bohr's work; and by Professor Aage Bohr who thanked the Union on behalf of his family. The ceremony was presided by Professor Bacher.

C —

A sumptuous reception was then tendered the delegates and their wives by the National Academy of Sciences in its Great Hall.

The Third Session

September 22nd

09h00

D —

President Bacher announced that the revised version of Papers I and II would be available for the Sunday session, when elections would be held.

The Secretary-General announced that Dr. Jan NILSSON of Sweden had agreed to stand as Associate Secretary-General.

9. *Reports of International Commissions (cont'd)*

C.5 — Low Temperatures

Dr. Sugawara

The Commission was faced with problems of coordination of meetings (e.g. IIR and IUPAP in Helsinki and Moscow in 1975). The Fritz London award needed a source of funds. Possibly each LT Conference should underwrite it.

C.6 — Publications

Dr. Wolfe

The Commission's apprehension of the "SLAC" plan for organizing subscriptions to preprints with consequent by-passing of the referee system and worsening of the flood of un-refereed literature was emphasized.

C.11 — Particles & Fields

Dr. Ne'eman

This report sparked a discussion of the problem and value of Conference publications. Strong views were expressed to the effect that

they were too costly, published too late to be useful, insufficiently refereed. Suggestions were made (some of which had been successfully tried, others of which had previously been made by IUPAP):

: that only 3–4 page résumés of papers be published, and these before the conference;

: that only invited papers be published subsequently;

: that conference proceedings be only published as a special issue of a regular journal, e.g. the physics journal of host country.

The Publications Commission was requested to study this very particular problem.

C.12 — Nuclear Physics

Dr. Bell

Here the need was underlined for guidelines from IUPAP concerning co-sponsorship of Conferences by different Commissions. There had recently been a lack of communication between C.11 and C.12, now corrected. The visa problem was also a cause of anxiety. This would be taken up again under Item 14.

C.15 — Atomic and Molecular Physics and Spectroscopy

Dr. Kastler

No written report was available at the moment but Dr. Kastler gave a detailed and thoughtful review of the evolution of the atomic and molecular physics sector. The breadth of the Commission's responsibility was considerable, and thus many meetings resulted. Already the Plasma Commission had been spun off and it itself was considering a further division. Similar problems associated with rapid evolution faced the European Physical Society, which had adopted a structure analogous to ours. New fields were developing rapidly, particular Fourier transform spectroscopy, Beam-foil spectroscopy and electron beam spectroscopy. Over 5000 simple spectra remained to be examined.

“We know practically nothing of spectra in highly-ionized heavy atoms”.

Tunable lasers for high-resolution spectroscopy were showing great promise.

C.16 — Plasma Physics

Dr. Brown

The Commission, recently formed, already saw the need for providing for further groups. It would suggest to the Executive a study of the need for a Quantum Electronics Commission in 1975.

Drs. Wilson, Wolfe, Bertaut, Sette, Bok, Rado, Wapstra, Staub, and Valerin also presented the reports of their respective Commissions, and answered questions. The texts of reports are given in Appendix II.

10. *Reports of Inter-Union activities*

Some reports had also been circulated, and were now simply tabled. They will be found in Appendix III. Some reports and additional information were presented orally. In particular:

I.1 — Committee on Data for Science and Technology (CODATA)

Dr. Vodar

Oral report. CODATA concerned itself with providing the condensed and easily available information that are data. It was now urgent to define needs, standards, and provide for exchange, a clearing house, conferences, and study of retrieval techniques. A list of eight ways in which IUPAP could assist more was presented. The "need for speed" held the risk of a careless data, and thus Commissions should oversee the quality of data presented at their conferences. The publications of CODATA, easily available from its secretariat, were not sufficiently known.

I.2 — International Council of Scientific Unions (ICSU)

See item 11.

I.3 — Special Committee on Problems of the Environment (SCOPE)

Tabled.

I.4 — Committee on Space Research (COSPAR)

To come.

I.5 — UPPER MANTLE

Tabled.

I.6 — Inter-Union Committee on Solar-Terrestrial Physics (IUCSTP)

Dr. Friedman

Oral report. This group existed for the organization and promotion of continuing work such as IGY. At the moment, the International Magnetostatic Study was under way. Greater participation by IUPAP was urged.

I.7 — IUPAC Commission on Macromolecules

Dr. Becker

This is the field of a IUPAC-IUPAP Commission. There was recently an increase of interest on the part of chemists in bringing physics techniques and theories to bear on the problems of macromolecules.

I.8 — ICSU Inter-Union Commission on Spectroscopy

Dr. Herzberg

This group had recently been inactive. This was in itself excellent, since the Commission existed to iron out difficulties and conflicts between IUPAP, IUPAC, and IUA Commissions with respect to nomenclature, etc.

I.9 — ICSU Abstracting Board

Dr. Koch

Tabled. Need for IUPAP support emphasized.

I.10 — Inter-Union Commission on Crystal Growth

Dr. Dekeyser

No activity. It was suggested that IUPAP discontinues this contact.

I.11 — Commission on Science Teaching

Tabled.

11. *Report on ICSU matters*
(deferred)

12. *Report of the Finance Commission*

The President reported that the Commission had received and examined the financial reports of the Associate Secretary-General each year, and were well satisfied with them.

However support from ICSU-UNESCO was gradually decreasing in relative importance as inter-union groups became more numerous.

13. *Recommendations of Commissions.*

Preliminary. No proposals were yet to hand.

— Session adjourned —

The Fourth Session

September 24th

09h00

5. *Election procedures* (continued)

As decided under item 5 discussed at Session I, the Secretary-General distributed the latest version of "Paper I" on election procedures, as amended by the Assembly at Session I. The Secretariat had since had to introduce further changes to make the whole coherent, and had also provided for one two unexpected contingencies. The whole was submitted for discussion and approval. Much discussion in fact took place. Motion for adoption was successfully amended on motion by Poland that reference to specific commissions be deleted from mention of general procedures (voice vote, only 1 objection).

On motion by the United Kingdom, seconded, articles 1—8 were adopted as amended by voice vote.

Discussion then took place on article 9. An amendment by the USA to the motion for adoption to the effect that names other than those on the original list be considered for nomination during the last

stage of the election procedure was defeated by a voice vote. Further suggestions concerning this matter found no formal support and the President declared that the wording would thus stand as presented. Minor suggestions concerning several words were accepted by the Assembly as part of the main motion.

On motion by Australia, seconded, article 9 was adopted by voice vote.

In summing up the discussion, the President had consigned to the minutes the point that the redraft of article 9 in general and 9.4 in particular had not been intended to change the sense of the first draft discussed at session I, and in fact did not. The rules of procedure as adopted are to be found in this document as Appendix A to the Statutes.

14. *Future Union policy*

(deferred)

15. *International Conferences*

(deferred)

16. *Election of Executive Committee*

- a) No further nominations having been received according to the rules of procedure, the President presented Professor Maier-Leibnitz for the office of President. The vote in favor was unanimous. Professor Maier-Leibnitz expressed his appreciation and his view that IUPAP was the "warmest" of the scientific organizations.
- b) No further nominations having been received according to the rules of procedure, the President presented Dr. Clifford Butler for the office of first Vice-President. The vote in favor was unanimous. Dr. Butler expressed his thanks.
- c) No further nominations having been received according to the rules of procedure, the President presented the slate of candidates for the offices of Vice-Presidents (8), Secretary-General, and

Associate Secretary-General. The voice vote was unanimously in favor. The list will be found in the center section of this Document.

17. *Election of Commissions*

- a) The President announced the selection of Dr. Gordon Sutherland, Dr. E. L. Andronikashvili and Dr. Erik Rudberg as tellers.
- b) No further nominations having been received according to the rules of procedure, the President presented separately to the Assembly the slate of candidates of each of the following Commissions:

C.1 — Finance

C.2 — SUN

C.3 — Thermodynamics and Statistical Mechanics

C.4 — Cosmic Rays

C.5 — Very Low Temperatures

C.6 — Publications

C.7 — Acoustics

C.8 — Semiconductors

C.10 — Solid State

C.11 — Particles and Fields

C.12 — Nuclear Physics

C.15 — Atomic and Molecular Physics and Spectroscopy

C.16 — Plasma Physics

A voice vote was taken in each case, all voice votes being un-animously in favor.

- c) The Secretary-General reported a modification in the slate of C.13: Atomic Masses and Fundamental Constants, where the names of Drs. Johnson and Terrien had been interchanged in their positions as member and secretary, at the request of Dr. Terrien and with the consent of Dr. Johnson. This was proposed by the Secretary-General in accordance with the new rules of procedure. By voice vote, the Assembly approved the modified slate.
- d) In the case of Commission 9: Magnetism, and Commission 14: Education, further nominations had been received on the pres-

cribed forms. In two cases, the name proposed was not included on the original list, and thus required the approval of the Assembly

On motion by Canada, seconded, it was agreed to retain the name of Dr. E. Ferreira of Brazil on the Education Commission ballot. Agreed by voice vote, one vote in opposition.

On motion of the Federal Republic of Germany, seconded, it was agreed to retain the name of Dr. Sexl of the German Democratic Republic on the Education Commission ballot. Agreed by unanimous voice vote.

Secret ballots were then cast, and the results compiled by the Tellers were announced by the President.

The complete lists of all Commissions thus elected will be found in the center section of this Document.

- e) A slate of candidates to fill positions on the various interunion Commissions had been circulated at the beginning of the Assembly. Two vacancies remained: COSPAR and IUCSTP. No objection was raised to the suggestion by the Cosmic Rays Commission that Dr. B. Peters be nominated for these offices. By unanimous voice vote, the slate was approved.

The list of members will be found in the center section of this Document.

11. *Report on ISCU Matters*

The President welcomed Dr. Bhagavantam, just arrived from the ICSU Helsinki meeting. The latter reported that there had been a very long, somewhat controversial agenda. New statutes had been approved, but they much resembled the old ones, except for the creation of a much smaller Executive Committee, with a larger General Committee to meet once a year for steering purposes.

Among the various resolutions adopted were those dealing with a magnetosphere study for 1976–78, an increase in National Members dues of 30% in 1972 and 40% in 1973, a reorganization of IUCSTP, a resolution on the free circulation of scientists, the 1973 Budget (providing for \$13,125 for IUPAP, a drop of \$1,000), and

the suggestion that the 1974 meeting be in Turkey. Dr. Bhagavantam had himself been named chairman of COSTED.

Dr. Kastler requested that the ICSU resolution on the free circulation of scientists be distributed to the Assembly. This was done, and it is given in Appendix IV.

14. *Future Union Policy*

- a) Possible Commission on Quantum Electronics.
Deferred to Item 18.
- b) Resolution on the People's Republic of China.
Deferred to Item 19.

15. *International Conferences for 1973*

The Secretary-General commented on the list which had been circulated to delegates. Decisions would be taken by the Executive Committee as usual. No further comments were received.

18. *Resolutions from Commissions*

- a) Dr. Brown of the Plasma Commission introduced a resolution to set up a group to study the advisability of creating a Commission on Quantum Electronics. A question as to whether such a Commission would participate in and thus dilute the Union's budget was answered in the affirmative.

On motion by the United States, seconded, it was agreed by unanimous voice vote to set up the study committee.

- b) The United Kingdom introduced the following resolution:
"The General Assembly mindful of the importance of reliable and readily accessible physical data urges specialized commissions and other bodies associated with IUPAP to pay attention to the compilation and evaluation of data and to include, whenever appropriate, such activities in their agenda and programmes. It also requests the IUPAP representative on CODATA to study other possible modes of action with a view to increasing data activities within the Union."

On motion by the United Kingdom, seconded, this resolution was carried by unanimous voice vote.

19. *Resolution from National Delegations*

A resolution by Sweden initiated discussion on the possibility of the People's Republic of China joining IUPAP. ICSU had urged that countries establish as many scientific contacts with China as possible. The resolution as presented read:

“Considering the importance for the work of IUPAP of having as national member the People's Republic of China, the XIVth General Assembly of IUPAP invites and authorizes, within the framework of the IUPAP statutes, its Executive Committee to take all measures which the Committee deems necessary to achieve this goal.”

On motion by Sweden, seconded by Denmark, this resolution was passed with no negative vote.

20. *Venue of the 1975 General Assembly*

This matter would be taken up by the Executive in 1973.

21. *Other Business*

- a) A statement by Canada intending to be a résumé of IUPAP practice in the matter of encouraging the free circulation of scientists was circulated. It is found in Appendix V. Delegates appeared to agree that it set out the situation fairly.
- b) The Israeli delegation raised for information the problem of “Russian Jewish scientists being denied visas for emigrating and subsequently being punished by being deprived of their jobs”. Specific cases were named.

The Soviet delegation replied through an interpreter that the scientists in question and others in general who so wished would be allowed to leave in due course, but must await the usual time for such applications to be processed.

Since some occupied senior positions affecting the morale of their laboratories, the knowledge that they wished to leave would affect morale if they were not replaced in these positions.

President Bacher closed the discussion, reminding the Assembly of IUPAP's long-established principles on the free circulation of scientists.

- c) Dr. Goldwasser raised for information three problems encountered by a recent High Energy Physics Conference:
 1. Some visas issued by the USA were delayed, and intervention with the State Department had been undertaken;
 2. Two Soviet Union theorists had accepted invitations but were unable to come at the last minute;
 3. Papers had been received from some non-invited Soviet scientists at a very late date, when arrangements had been concluded.

These matters all involved, or seemed to, the free circulation of scientists, and made the organization of international conferences difficult.

Dr. Tuchkevich pointed out that the late issuing of visas was often responsible for the late arrival of scientific papers. The two went together. Both visas and papers should be produced well before the conference. He would inquire into the matter of Russian delegates not being able to attend. Dr. Andronikashvili mentioned other cases, but considered that individual cases should not be raised in IUPAP.

President Bacher reiterated that IUPAP followed a well-established policy which was in agreement with ICSU.

22. *Adjournment*

- a) President Bacher delivered a much-applauded Presidential address. The text will be found in Appendix VI.
- b) A moving vote of thanks was presented by Professor Amaldi. He mentioned the arrangements made by the United States National Academy of Sciences — particularly the brilliant scientific programme — and the hospitality of Dr. Handler and his colleagues.

Many of them had worked very long and hard to ensure the acknowledged success of the Assembly and the 50th Birthday of IUPAP.

Professor Amaldi also paid tribute to the efforts of President Bacher throughout three vigorous years. Retiring Secretary-General Butler had for nine years given invaluable service to the Union. Retiring Vice-Presidents Boas, Dekeyser, Bernardini, Bhagavantam and Rozental had also been unstinting in their contributions. He mentioned the work of the Quebec Secretariat.

His vote of thanks was generously applauded.

The Assembly then adjourned.

E —

Ladies attending the Assembly were offered a most interesting programme organized by Mrs. Robert Bacher and Mrs. Herbert Friedman.

F —

The IUPAP Banquet, presided by President Bacher, saw the John T. Tate Award of the American Institute of Physics for contributions to international Physics presented by Professor H. Richard Crane, Chairman, to Professor Gilberto Bernardini. After-dinner remarks were made by Dr. H. Guyford Stever.

G —

A Dinner tendered by the Research Corporation was held at the State Department, and presided by Professor Frederick Seitz. After-dinner remarks were made by Dr. James S. Coles, President of the Research Corporation, and an address on the aesthetic values of science was delivered by Dr. Robert R. Wilson.

H—

The remarkable scientific programme which was greatly enjoyed and attended not only by the Assembly delegates but also by about 300 other visiting scientists presented the following distinguished speakers: E. Amaldi; J. Bardeen; A. Bohr; H. B. G. Casimir; W. Gentner; R. W. Gould; G. Herzberg; F. Hoyle; K. S. Thorne; G. Toraldo di Francia; V. F. Weisskopf; J. Tuzo Wilson.

Québec, November 1972.

APPENDIX I

ATTENDANCE AT XIV GENERAL ASSEMBLY OF IUPAP

I. Summary:

<i>Delegation</i>	<i>Number in Delegation</i>
Argentina	0
Australia	3
Austria	1
Belgium	1
Bolivia	3
Brazil	0
Bulgaria	0
Canada	5
Cuba	0
Czechoslovakia	1
Denmark	2
Arab Republic of Egypt	0
Finland	0
France	11
Federal Republic of Germany	7
German Democratic Republic	3
Hungary	1
India	5
Ireland	1
Israel	1
Italy	4
Japan	2
Republic of Korea	1
Mexico	0
Netherlands	1
New Zealand	1
Norway	0
Pakistan	0

Poland	2
Romania	0
South Africa	0
Spain	1
Sweden	3
Switzerland	3
Taiwan	5
United Kingdom	7
USA	24
USSR	3
Yugoslavia	2
<hr/>	
	Total 104

In addition, there were 6 IUPAP officials and 3 observers who were not part of a delegation who attended the General Assembly. This gave us a total of 113 who attended the IUPAP General Assembly sessions.

II. Names of Delegates and Observers

Australia

Dr. Walter Boas
Dr. John Stuart Dryden
Prof. H. Webster

Austria

Prof. Dr. Otto Hittmair

Belgium

Prof. W. Dekeyser

Bolivia

Lic. Carlos Aguirre
Ing. Ricardo Anda
*Ing. Gaston R. Mejia

*Chairman of delegation.

Canada

Dr. R. E. Bell
Dr. Gerhard Herzberg
Prof. Paul Lorrain
Dr. G. Volkoff
Dr. J. Tuzo Wilson

Czechoslovakia

Prof. Dr. Miroslav Trlifaj

Denmark

*Prof. Aage Bohr
Prof. S. Rozental

France

Prof. Jacques Badoz
Prof. Dr. E. F. Bertaut
Prof. Julien Bok
Dr. Bernard Briat
Prof. G. Delacote
Prof. B. Dreyfus
Prof. Pierre Lallemand
Madame H. Mathieu-Faraggi
Prof. Jean Charles Terrien
Prof. B. Vodar
Prof. M. Michel Voos

*Federal Republic of Germany
Delegates*

Prof. Dr. G. W. Becker
*Prof. Dr. Karl Ganzhorn
Prof. Dr. Hans Joos
Prof. Dr. W. Kroebel
Prof. Dr. H. Maier-Leibnitz
Dr. K.-H. Riewe

Observer

Prof. Wolfgang Gentner

German Democratic Republic

Prof. J. Auth
Dr. Herbert Friedrich
Prof. Dr. Karl Lanus

Hungary

Prof. L. Pal

India

Prof. F. C. Auluck
Prof. S. Bhagavantam

Prof. M. G. K. Menon
Prof. B. M. Udgaonkar
Dr. P. Venkateswarlu

Ireland

Prof. Declan M. Larkin

Israel

Prof. Yuval Ne'eman

Italy

Prof. Edoardo Amaldi
Prof. Bruno Brunelli
Prof. D. Sette
Prof. G. Toraldo Di Francia

Japan

Prof. Isao Imai
Prof. T. Sugawara

Republic of Korea

Dr. Chul C. Lee

Netherlands

Dr. H. F. P. Knaap

New Zealand

Dr. Ian G. Donaldson

Poland

Prof. Leonard Sosnowski
Prof. Joseph Werle

Spain

Prof. Luis Bru

*Chairman of delegation.

Sweden

Dr. Eric Dyring
Prof. Jan S. Nilsson
Prof. E. Rudberg

Switzerland

Prof. Dr. Heini Granicher
Prof. Dr. Andre Mercier
Prof. Hans H. Staub

Taiwan

Delegates

Dr. Ching-Tang Chen-Tsai
Prof. Chun-Shan Shen
Dr. Wei-Noon Wang
Dr. Ta-You Wu

Observer

Mr. Hsuen-Chang Pan

United Kingdom

Delegates

Prof. George R. Bishop
*Prof. Nicholas Kurti
Dr. R. S. Pease
Prof. W. C. Price
Prof. J. G. Wilson

Observers

Prof. L. F. Bates, F.R.S.
Sir Gordon Sutherland

USA

Delegates

Dr. D. Allan Bromley
*Prof. Sanborn C. Brown

Dr. Edwin L. Goldwasser
Dr. W. W. Havens, Jr.
Dr. Frederick Seitz

Alternate Delegates

Prof. Stanley S. Ballard
Dr. John Bardeen
Dr. Lewis M. Branscomb
Dr. Milan D. Fiske
Dr. Martin Greenspan
Dr. H. William Koch
Dr. Roman Smoluchowski

Observers

Dr. E. Richard Cohen
Dr. Hsu Y. Fan
Dr. Joseph L. Fowler
Dr. Conyers Herring
Dr. I. Hirsh
Dr. Walter H. Johnson, Jr.
Dr. William C. Kelly
Dr. Hugh Odishaw
Dr. Simon Pasternack
Dr. George T. Rado
Dr. F. Dow Smith
Dr. Hugh C. Wolfe

USSR

Dr. Elevation Andronikashvili
Dr. Vasilij D. Badakayev
*Dr. Vladimir M. Tuchkevich

Yugoslavia

*Prof. Aleksandar Milojevic
Dr. Milorad Mladjenovic

*Chairman of delegation.

III. IUPAP Officials

President: Prof. Robert F. Bacher (USA)

First Vice-President: *Prof. H. Maier-Leibnitz (FRG)

Vice-Presidents:

Prof. G. Bernardini (Italy)

*Dr. S. Bhagavantam (India)

*Dr. Walter Boas (Australia)

*Prof. Dr. W. Dekeyser (Belgium)

Prof. Alfred H. Kastler (France)

*Prof. L. Pal (Hungary)

*Prof. S. Rozental (Denmark)

Prof. Victor Weisskopf (USA)

Secretary-General: Dr. C. C. Butler (UK)

Assoc. Secretary-General: Prof. Larkin Kerwin (Canada)

IV. Observers not included in National Delegations

Prof. Donald D. Betts (Canada) — member of Commission on Thermodynamics and Statistical Mechanics

Prof. H. B. G. Casimir (Netherlands) — member of Commission on Physics Education

Dr. Herbert Friedman (USA) — Representative from IUCSTP

*Also listed above as delegates.

APPENDIX II

Reports by Commissions

Specialized Commissions:

1. Financial Commission
2. Commission for Symbols, Units and Nomenclature
3. Commission on Thermodynamics and Statistical Mechanics
4. Commission on Cosmic Rays
5. Commission on Very Low Temperature Physics
6. Commission on Publications
7. Commission on Acoustics
8. Commission on Semiconductors
9. Commission on Magnetism
10. Commission on Solid State Physics
11. Commission on Particles and Fields
12. Commission on Nuclear Physics
13. Commission on Atomic Masses and Fundamental Constants
14. Commission on Physics Education
15. Commission on Atomic and Molecular Physics and Spectroscopy
16. Commission on Plasma Physics

Affiliated Commission:

17. International Commission for optics

1. Financial Commission — No written report

2. Commission for Symbols, Units and Nomenclature (SUN)

The SUN Commission has the task to promote unification in the use of symbols for quantities and units and in the nomenclature and terminology used in physics publications and teaching.

The SUN Commission collaborates with various international organisations active in the same field, in particular with the IUPAC (especially IUPAC/STU), the Comité International des Poids et Mesures and its Comité Consultatif des Unités, the International Organisation for Standardisation (especially IEC/TC 24 and 25).

One of the main activities were advice to and cooperation with the above-mentioned international organisations, with the aim to giving a clear understanding and a widespread application of the International System of Units (SI), as established by the relevant bodies of Metre Convention, and to selecting units not belonging to the SI units and their decimal multiples or submultiples for usage together with the SI for an unlimited time or during a transitory period.

From special problems, as discussed and solved together with the above-mentioned international organisations, should be mentioned here the following.

In the field of computers and information processing the representation for SI and other units to be used in systems with limited character sets, especially recommendations regarding two different sets of representation and the principle conditions for their application — in this field a rather satisfactory compromise could be found.

The presentation of logarithmic quantities (e.g. loss, gain, level, frequency interval, decision content, information content) in the frame work of normal quantity calculus together with the belonging units for those dimensionless quantities — with this subject still remain not yet overcome discrepancies of point of view between IEC and the other organisations.

Acknowledging and establishing the distinction between the dimensional independence and the metrological independence of base units — dimensional independence being a property of the base units as the base of an algebraic structure in the sense of the theory of sets in connection with quantity calculus, whereas metrological independence means the degree of independence in experimentally realising base units in a National Standardising Laboratory.

Adaptation of nomenclature and symbolism in the special field of thermodynamic energetic functions between IUPAC and IUPAP.

In collaboration with interestee above-mentioned international organisations drafting a new chapter *Plasma Physics*, widely enlarging and rearranging the chapter *Solid State Physics* completely revising the Appendix *Systems of Quantities and Units in Electricity and Magnetism* of the IUPAP/SUN document, which is leading at the same time to a simplification as well as adaptation to the practical needs of today. Details are contained in documents submitted by the Commission to the XIVth General Assembly for approval.

The future work of the SUN Commission for the next two or three years is, in further close cooperation with other international organisations engaged in this field, accomplishing the adaptation of the concepts, nomenclature, and symbolism needed in pure and applied physics to the present situation with the aim to submit to the XVth General Assembly a completely revised new edition of the IUPAP/SUN document, if the XIVth General Assembly agrees to this intention.

SUN Commission has been represented at the meetings of corresponding commissions or committees of other international organisations active in an analogous field.

During the three year cycle 1969—1972 the SUN Commission answered many written questions from individuals in science and technology and met three times: 9 and 10 September 1970 at Dubrovnik, 19 and 20 August 1971 in Paris, and 29, 30 and 31 August 1972 in Paris.

3. Commission on Thermodynamics and Statistical Mechanics

During the period 1969—1972 the Thermodynamics and Statistical Mechanics Commission sponsored altogether four conferences. In chronological order these were:

1. The international conference on Thermodynamics held in Cardiff, 1—4 April 1970. This conference was sponsored in addition by IUPAC. It was attended by about 180 scientists and covered topics ranging from statistical thermodynamics to pedagogical aspects of thermodynamics.

2. International Conference on Statistical Mechanics held in Chicago, 29 March—2 April 1971. This meeting, one in the series of international conferences on Statistical Mechanics, held every two years, was attended by about 300 physicists active in the field. It provided a rather complete survey of the current activities and developments in Statistical Mechanics.

3. The third international conference “de la Physique Theorique a la Biologie” organised by the Institut de la Vie at Versailles, 21—26 June 1971. The admission to this conference was by invitation only. It was attended by approximately 80 theoretical physicists, chemists, biologists, physiologists and mathematicians, and was once more most successful in confronting the points of view of various disciplines relevant for biological problems.

4. The “100 years Boltzmann equation symposium” held in Vienna 4—8 September 1972. The program of the conference is set up in such a way as to give a survey of the historical developments, the recent progress and the unsolved problems in kinetic theory. The admission is by invitation.

The Commission met in Paris on April 19, 1971, to discuss changes in its membership, as well as sponsorship of future conferences.

During 1973 the Commission wishes to sponsor two meetings:

1. Fourth conference on Theoretical Physics and Biology at Versailles, 27 May—2 June, 1973. The admission to this conference will be by invitation only. No funds are required from IUPAP.

2. An international conference on Statistical Mechanics at Amsterdam in September 1973 on the occasion of the centenary of the Van der Waals equation. The organiser is Professor N. Trappeniers, Van der Waals Laboratorium, University of Amsterdam, Valckenierstraat 67, Amsterdam.

The Commission intends to meet during this conference.

List of conferences sponsored by the Thermodynamics and Statistical Mechanics Commission during the period 1969—1972.

1. International conference on Thermodynamics, Cardiff, 1—4 April 1970, cosponsored by IUPAC.

Organiser: Professor P. T. Landsberg, Cardiff.

Proceedings published: Thermodynamics, Cardiff, Butterworth's 1970.

Not subsidised by IUPAP.

2. International conference on Statistical Mechanics, Chicago, 29 March—2 April, 1971.

Organiser: Professor Stuart A. Rice, The James Franck Institute, University of Chicago.

Proceedings to appear: Chicago University Press.

IUPAP grant: \$ 5000.

3. Third Conference from Theoretical Physics to Biology, Versailles, 21—26 June 1971.

Organiser: Professor M. Marois, Institut de la Vie, 89 Bd. St. Michel, Paris 5e, France.

Proceedings: not yet published.

Proceedings of 2nd conference Versailles (30.6—5.7.69) published: Institut de la Vie, "From Theoretical Physics to Biology" Ed. du Centre National de Recherche Scientifique, 15 Quai Anatole France — Paris 7e.

4. Hundred Years Boltzmann-Equation Symposium, Vienna, 4—8 September 1972.

Organising Committee: Professor E. G. D. Cohen (New York)

Professor W. Thirring (Vienna)

Professor H. Wergeland (Trondheim).

IUPAP grant: \$ 1000.

4. Commission on Cosmic Rays

The main activities of the Cosmic Ray Commission during the cycle 1969—1972 concerned the organisation and evaluation of the 12th International Conference on cosmic rays held at Hobart. This meeting was arranged with some trepidation on the grounds that sooner rather than later the conference ought to go to Australia. In the event it was highly successful. The attendance was fully representative of cosmic ray physics throughout the world, the only area rather more poorly represented than usual being Europe; even from Europe, however, there was a quite adequate attendance.

The Conference developed further the scheme of pre-presentation of papers first attempted two years earlier at Budapest. As a result the publication of short versions of contributed papers was completed in six volumes at the outset of the conference and lecturers were able to direct their attention to stressing important features and making points of clarification. The conference took place in August 1971 and the remainder of the publications, which will be based upon invited papers and rapporteur papers, is not yet in my hands.

The Commission met during the conference and had before it its own resolution that the 13th conference should take place at Denver in 1973, and proceeded to allocate the 14th conference to Germany who expect to mount it in or near Munich.

The Commission does not expect to submit any resolutions for consideration at the Washington Assembly.

5. Commission on Very Low Temperature Physics

A. Conferences sponsored and Proceedings: The main purpose of the Commission is to help plan and sponsor a series of international conferences on low temperature physics (LT Conferences).

1. LT 12 (Kyoto), Conference on Transport on Solids. The twelfth of the LT series, LT 12, was held in Kyoto, Japan, 4—10 September 1970. The number of participants was about 1000. The Fritz London Award was presented to Dr. B. Josephson, Cambridge University, for his distinguished work in low temperature physics. Proceedings of this conference were published in one volume (895 pages) in 1971 by Keigaku Publishing Co., Tokyo (Japan), edited by E. Kanda. A satellite conference on Transport in Solids was held in connection with LT 12 and sponsored also by IUPAP. It was held in Sydney, Australia, 26—29 August 1970.

2. LT 13. This conference is to be held at the University of Colorado, Boulder, USA, 21—25 August 1972. The Chairman of the Organising Committee is Dr. R. H. Kropschot, National Bureau of Standards, Boulder, Colorado.

3. Conference on Sciences of Superconductivity. This international conference was held at the Stanford University, Stanford, USA, 26—29 August 1969. Proceedings were published in 1972 in one volume (808 pages) by North-Holland Publishing Co., edited by F. Chilton.

4. Conference on Quantum Crystals. This conference was held in Banff, Canada, 6—10 September 1971. It was sponsored by IUPAP with no financial support.

B. Future Conferences: The Commission favours going to a three-year cycle of LT Conferences after 1972. The next LT Conference, LT 14, will be held in 1975, probably in Europe. The site and the nature of this conference will be discussed at the Commission Meeting to be held in Boulder, August 1972.

C. Meetings of the Commission: A meeting of the Commission was held in Kyoto, 8 September 1970, in connection with LT 12. At this meeting the site for LT 13 and LT 14 and other problems were discussed. The University of California at La-Jolla was chosen for the site of LT 13 (1972).* As to the site for LT 14 (1975), invitations were received from Helsinki and Haifa, but the final decision has been postponed to the 1972 meeting. Discussions were also made on the prospect and financial problems of the helium conservation program in USA. The Commission decided to send to Secretary-General a statement suggesting international support for helium conservation. The next meeting is to be held in Boulder, 24 August 1972.

D. Cooperation with other organisations: The Commission has been keeping close relation with international bodies in related areas. At the 1970 Meeting in Kyoto, O. V. Lounasmaa was appointed as the liaison member with the Commission 1 of the International Institute for Refrigeration, IIR. The former liaison member was N. Kürti.

6. Commission on Publications

The Commission held one meeting during the 3 year period at the CNRS in Paris on 12 May 1972.

*Later, this was changed to the University of Colorado, USA, because of delays in construction of buildings at La Jolla and other factors.

1. The Commission made recommendations for membership during 1972—1975.

2. Journal Program of the European Physical Society: Dr. Coles reported that EPS has approved a list of journals for designation as Europhysics Journals, on the basis of criteria for international editorial boards, regular refereeing procedures, etc. They must accept papers in any of three languages and must provide an abstract in English for each paper. The only commercially published journals included so far are PHYSICA and THE PHILOSOPHICAL MAGAZINE. No “letters” journals are included as yet. It is planned to use the specialist divisions of EPS in monitoring the commercial “international” journals in specialised fields. No “review” journals have been included as yet. The CZECHOSLOVAK JOURNAL OF PHYSICS has dropped the Europhysics label. Although the Soviet Union participates in EPS, no Russian journals are in the Europhysics list.

A new Style Manual has been prepared and will soon be printed in EUROPHYSICS NEWS.

3. The Current Physics Information system of the American Institute of Physics:

Supplementing brochures which had been mailed to the members earlier, Dr. Wolfe distributed copies of an article by Dr. H. W. Koch from SCIENCE, Nov. 1971 and an article by Dr. A. Herschman from PHYSICS TODAY, Nov. 1971. AIP is now producing and marketing a set of four secondary services to supplement its primary journal publication program.

- a) CURRENT PHYSICS ADVANCE ABSTRACTS (CPAA):
a monthly publication in 3 sections, providing abstracts arranged by subject classification of articles accepted for publication in AIP journals.
- b) SEARCHABLE PHYSICS INFORMATION NOTICES (SPIN):
a magnetic tape with title, author, abstract, cited references indexing and bibliographic data, covering about 70 journals.

- c) **CURRENT PHYSICS TITLES (CPT)**: a monthly publication in three sections, photocomposed from the SPIN tape and arranged by subject classification, giving title, author and bibliographic data.
- d) **CURRENT PHYSICS MICROFORM (CPM)**: a monthly microfilm containing the complete text of all journal issues published by AIP during the preceding month. The reel and frame number for each article is included as part of the data in SPIN and CPT.

The list of selected journals in SPIN and CPT was discussed and it was moved, seconded and carried: that the Commission on Publications recommends to AIP that all journals selected as Europhysics journals by EPS be included in SPIN and CPT.

Note added by H. C. W. Unless the list grows in such a way as to complicate unduly the cooperative arrangements between AIP and the Institution of Electrical Engineers, the publishers of **PHYSICS ABSTRACTS**, AIP sees no difficulty in complying with this request. AIP does not include journals other than those it publishes in CPM but encourages their publishers to arrange for similar microform output and to provide reel and frame numbers for SPIN and CPT. Questions were raised about duplication of effort between AIP and IEE. Dr. Wolfe pointed out that much attention has been given to cooperation, with each marketing the products of the other, and with each supplying to the other the inputs it generates. **CURRENT PAPERS IN PHYSICS** is not sectionalised and does not seem to AIP to fill the role of CPT, so there is some competition between them at present but it is hoped that they may be combined before too long.

4. **Classification and Indexing of Physics Literature**: AIP and IEE (INSPEC) have been working for some years on bringing their classification schemes into accord and a working group of the ICSU Abstracting Board is coordinating the effort to obtain a common classification scheme for all physics secondary journals. The combined AIP/INSPEC scheme was submitted to ICSU/AB in March 1972. Mr. Bretnütz reported that *Physikalische Berichte* tries to follow the classification scheme used by INSPEC but that this seems to be

more difficult for the multidisciplinary abstracting journals, *Bulletin Signalitique* and *Referationyi Zhurnal*.

The EPS Style Manual recommends that authors classify their papers in accordance with the scheme used by INSPEC and referees are asked to specify their areas of competence according to the same scheme. Most of the journals published by AIP use the AIP classification and indexing scheme. Dr. Pasternack was asked whether *PHYSICAL REVIEW*, which does not now use it, will follow this scheme for indexing in 1973. He reported that studies are underway to compare 1971 indexes prepared both ways as a basis for decision. Mr. Pedersen reported that the journals of the Institute of Physics are indexed by the INSPEC staff under a contract.

5. **Composition and Printing Techniques:** Mr. Pedersen reported that the IOP journals use Monophoto composition, which they find cheaper and more flexible than Monotype although corrections are more expensive, and offset printing. Mr. Bretnütz reported that *Physikalische Berichte* is printed by offset, using typewriter composition for abstracts and computerised photocomposition for indexes. Dr. Wolfe reported that essentially all AIP journals are printed by offset. An increasing number use typewriter composition with some set by monotype or computerised photocomposition. Since the "head" of each article (title, author, abstract) and the "tail" (cited references) have to be keyboarded for the SPIN tape, plans are underway to print these parts by computerised photocomposition and combine them with the typewriter-composed (or monotype) text, avoiding duplication of keyboarding.

6. **Bibliographic References:** It was reported that ICSU/AB and UNISIST have a combined group working on a standard format for bibliographic references to facilitate information interchange.

Subcommittee 4 of Committee Z-39 of the American National Standards Institute is also developing such a standard.

7. **Journal Title Abbreviations:** The ICSU/AB has agreed to follow the title abbreviation list developed and maintained by Z-39.

8. **Coden:** The matter of using 5-letter codens (developed by ASTM) or the serial number coding scheme developed by Z-39/SC-20 to

designate journals has not been resolved in the US, so AIP does not print either on its journals, although codens are used internally in physics information activities. The IOP journals have agreed to carry the coden designations if they are requested to do so by INSPEC.

9. SI Units: Dr. Wolfe reported that the SUN Commission of IUPAP has cooperated with ISO/TC 12 in producing Draft International Standard 1000 "SI Units and Recommendations for the Use of their Multiples and of Certain Other Units". The use of SI units and their standard symbols for all data in physics journals is recommended.

10. Preprint Distribution: Many authors distribute preprints of their papers and this practice is accepted by the Commission. The only current organised preprint system is PREPRINTS IN PARTICLES AND FIELDS operated by SLAC (Stanford) and CERN. A weekly sheet lists preprints received by SLAC and CERN and, in many cases, by preprint libraries operated at high energy physics centers. An "anti-preprint" list is published about once a month, giving bibliographic references for published papers originally listed as preprints. An individual may obtain a Xerox copy of a preprint from his preprint library or may request one from the author.

Dr. Pasternack reported that SLAC proposes the distribution of preprints to subscribers at \$ 100 per year with a \$ 2 per page publication charge to authors. After discussion, it was moved, seconded and carried unanimously that:

The Commission feels that the printing and distribution of preprints on a subscription basis would constitute their unedited and unrefereed publication and, as such, would be a serious departure from normally accepted practices in physics publication.

Dr. Pasternack also reported a request that journal articles, which have been made available as preprints carrying report numbers, should carry footnotes saying something like "supersedes UCRL 2794". The Commission had no objection to this and felt that it might be helpful.

11. Financial Problems of Journals: Mr. Pedersen reported a 50% increase in two years in the number of pages published in IOP jour-

nals, bringing financial strains associated with increased staff, etc. The consensus was that few other journals had grown at this rate recently. Dr. Wolfe reported that there has been a drop off in acceptance of page charges in AIP journals, due to cutbacks in government support of research, etc. Quotas of pages that can be published without payment of page charges have been established and some papers are being delayed by as much as 14 months. AIP is not happy about this but finds it essential for economic stability.

7. Commission on Acoustics

During the term 1969—72 the activity of ICA has been closely followed by the three Scientific Unions: IUTAM, IUPS, IUBS and the Biophysics Union. The first three of them have named an official observer.

Meetings of the Commission. Four meetings of the Commission were held: 5—6 May 1970 in Budapest (Hungary); 18—20 August and 25 August 1971 in Budapest; 3—4 May 1972 in Paris. A joint meeting of ICA with representatives of Acoustical Societies was held on August 20, 1971 in Budapest. Moreover the Chairman and the Secretary of ICA have been present to the first (constitutional) meeting of the Federation of European Acoustical Societies (Paris, 5 May 1972).

The Seventh International Congress. The Seventh Congress held in Budapest (18—26 August 1971) has been the major activity of the Commission in the present term. It was the first congress organised by the Commission in which a large participation of Acousticians of Socialist Countries was possible: 435 out of a total attendance of 1,530. The Countries represented were 34. The scientific sessions included the presentation of 14 invited papers and 627 contributed papers. Round table discussions were organised on 10 important issues. The papers were delivered in English (64%), German (23%) and French (13%). The proceedings of the Conference have been published in 4 volumes of about 3000 pages total. During the Congress an exhibition of acoustical and electroacoustical apparatus and of books was held: Hungarian enterprises presented their products. Visits to factories and special demonstrations were organised.

In connection with the main congress two specialised symposia were held: the first was devoted to Speech, the other to Noise Prevention.

The major burden of the organisation of the congress was undertaken by the Hungarian Organising Committee led by Professor T. Tarnoczy, a member of ICA. The Commission has however dedicated to this organisation a great attention during the last two years before the meeting by assisting the Hungarian Committee.

The cost of the congress has been evaluated to 82,000 USA dollars. They were covered in a small part by the entire IUPAP contribution for ICA, activities in the three years, by the registration fees (38,000\$), and by the help of the Hungarian Government and enterprises. All participants received the proceedings. The excellent organisation of the large congress was due to the continuous and effective help of Hungarian Authorities and the enthusiastic effort of Hungarian Acousticians. The Hungarian Academy has also helped by taking care of the publication of the proceedings. A certain number of copies of these are in deposit at the Academy and can be purchased from the Academy distributor: Kulture, Budapest 62.

During the Congress two meetings of representatives of Acoustical Societies and Commissions were held: to the first all Acoustical Societies and Commissions were invited to exchange information and try to coordinate action. Only European Acoustical Societies were present at the second meeting; a group of Societies have proposed a draft statute of a Federation for organising cooperation among Societies and the Commission; it has been discussed in detail and a Steering Group has been charged with preparation for the constitution of the Federation of Acoustical Societies of Europe (FASE)

Organisation of the 8th and 9th ICA Congresses. The Commission is at present taking care of the organisation of the 8th ICA Congress. It will be held in London in July 1974. Although open to all sectors of Acoustics it will try to underline in particular the problems of "Environmental Acoustics". It will have satellite symposia on Microwave Acoustics, Underwater Acoustics and Transportation Noise. The Commission has also started the organisation of the 9th Congress which will be held in Madrid (Spain) in the summer of 1977 and will

be the first one organised by the Commission in a Spanish speaking country.

Meetings connected with the IUPAP Assembly. ICA has stimulated the organisation of meetings connected with the IUPAP Assembly in Washington. Through the collaboration of the Acoustical Society of American two of such meetings have been organised: a symposium on the "Atmospheric sound propagation" at NBS (September 27—29) and the Inter-noise 72 Conference in Washington (4—6 October).

Information and Coordination Service. The Commission decided in 1969 to organise a service for collecting information on acoustic meetings in different countries and for diffusing this information by sending periodic lists of events to Acoustical Societies, Acoustic Journals and other organisations interested in Acoustics. This service has been undertaken by Dr. Kolmer, a Commission corresponding member, with the help of the Czechoslovakian Academy. The same service is also collecting and distributing information on European Laboratories where research in Acoustics is carried on. A further action of this center refers to the diffusion of information on the organisation, status, activities of each national Acoustical Commission or Society. The request of this activity came out during the meeting with the representatives of Acoustical Societies organised by ICA during its 7th Congress in Budapest.

Cooperation with Acoustical Societies and help with the organisation of a European Federation. ICA has usually called meeting of representatives of National Societies and Commissions during its Congresses. In Budapest the meeting discussed the activities of ICA, how to improve the exchange of information and the coordination of activities of various Societies, the problems which are at present of particular importance for the development of Acoustics. We have already quoted same action which resulted from this meeting in the field of exchange of information. The meeting pointed out also the great importance that the problems of noise pollution has at present and gave support to ICA action in this direction.

Man and his environment. ICA has been considering for a long time the importance of the problems connected with the environment: it

has had some of its members collaborating with ISO subcommittees on noise and architectural acoustics. In the last two years it has increased its activity in this field and it is collaborating in the effort that the UN are conducting on the "Human Environment": as it is known the UN have been organising for a long time the Conference on the subject in Stockholm (June 1972).

ICA has asked to participate and one of its members (Dr. Mattei) has participated to a meeting organised by the European Economic Commission in Prague in May 1971 as a preparation of European Countries to the Stockholm Conference. In this meeting the problems of noise, considered as a part of air pollution, have been presented. ICSU has organised a special group, SCOPE, to study the problem of environment, and IUPAP has appointed as its representative in this group Dr. Lara of ICA. Dr. Lara has been charged by SCOPE to prepare a report on the noise problem and ICA has appointed a small group of experts to assist Lara prepare a draft of this report. Due to the SCOPE procedures the final report will be ready in January 1973.

ICA, however, in order not to lose the unique opportunity of the Stockholm Conference (a Governmental Conference) for addressing to the Governments and calling their attention to the importance of considering noise aspects in their decisions on planning and of issuing adequate regulations concerning noise as well as to the need of supporting research on noise problems, has sent directly to the Stockholm Conference a document calling for resolutions to be adopted.

Financial Matters. The activity of the Commission has increased in the last term as shown above. The financial problems have become more acute. The operation at the level described has been possible only because the members have agreed to participate in meetings with a very low contribution to their expenses, or, more frequently, with no contribution at all, and they have found elsewhere funds for the activities that ICA has asked to them to perform. The low budget of the Commission, although ICA has given larger contributions to members moving from other continents than the place of the meeting, discriminates against some members. From the other side the great interdisciplinary nature of Acoustics requires direct discussion of

problems in meetings and the participation in them of a large part of Commission Members.

Appendix to ICA report (1969—72)

The Commission has organised the 7th ICA Congress in Budapest (Hungary) 18—26 August 1971.

The Proceedings of the Congress have been published by "Akademiei Kiado" Budapest in four main volumes and one abstract volume.

The total number of pages is of 3006.

The proceedings were distributed to all participants.

Extra copies can be purchased from "Kulture", Budapest 62, an agency of the Hungarian Academy.

ICA has also sponsored the following two meetings:

- 1) Symposium on Atmospheric sound propagation at NBS (Gaithersburg) 27—29 September 1972.
- 2) Internoise — 72 Conference (Washington 4—6 October 1972).

8. Commission on Semiconductors

1. International Conferences on the Physics of Semiconductors (type A)

a) The 10th Conference was held at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, Massachusetts, USA, 17—21 August 1970. Attendance 700. The Commission members were very satisfied with the scientific program which achieved a very good balance of high quality papers over the whole semiconductor field. The proceedings were published in December 1970. Editors S. P. Keller, J. C. Hensel and St. Stern, Atomic Energy Commission, Washington D. C. 1970.

b) The 11th Conference will be held in Warsaw, Poland, 25—29 July 1972. An International Committee was set up to decide the scientific program and to select the papers. A full report of the conference will be given later.

2. Topical Conferences (type B)

—International Conference on Photoconductivity, Stanford, USA,

12—15 August 1969. Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Photoconductivity. Editors E. M. Pell, Pergamon Press 1971.

— Conference on Heterojunctions and Layer Structure, Budapest, Hungary. 11—17 October 1970. Editor G. Szigeti, Akademiai Kiado, Budapest 1971.

— International Symposium on Radiation Effects in Semiconductors, Albany, USA, July 1970. Editors James Corbett and George Watkins. Gordon and Breach Science Publishers, New York, NY (USA).

— International Conference on Radiation Damage and Defects in Semiconductors, Reading, UK, 19—21 July 1972.

International conferences on Amorphous and Liquefied Semiconductors.

This field was rapidly developing these last years and an International Committee was set up which recommended conferences on that subject on a two-year periodicity. The conferences held during the 1969—1972 period were:

— 3rd Conference on Amorphous and Liquid Semiconductors, Cambridge, UK, 24—27 September 1969. Proceedings of the International Conference of Amorphous and Liquid Semiconductors, Editor N. Mott, North Holland 1970.

— 4th Conference on Amorphous and Liquid Semiconductors, Ann Arbor, Michigan, USA, 8—13 August 1971. No proceedings have been published.

— The 5th Conference is planned for the summer of 1973 in Garmisch-Partenkirchen, (German Federal Republic).

3. *Meetings of the Commission*

The Commission met in Cambridge, USA on August 17th 1970. The minutes of this meeting were sent to the Secretary-General in October 1970.

The next meeting will be held in Warsaw in July 1972.

4. *Budget*

The allocation for the 1969—1972 period was originally \$ 8000; after a request from the Secretary of the Commission this allocation was

raised to \$12000, of which \$1000 are part of the allocation for the 1973—1975 period. The allocations to the meetings were the following:

Cambridge (USA) Conference	(1970) — \$ 5000
Albany meeting	(1970) — \$ 500
Budapest meeting	(1970) — \$ 1500
Warsaw meeting	(1972) — \$ 5000

9. Commission on Magnetism

1. *Summary*

During the period 1969—1972, as in the preceding three years, the activities of the Magnetism Commission centered around the triennial Commission Meeting and the triennial International Conference on Magnetism (ICM). Both of these events took place in 1970 in Grenoble, France, and are briefly described below. The Commission sponsored, in addition, two “satellite” conferences of the 1970 ICM and two other conferences. All of these conferences are listed in Appendix A, which includes information on publications and financial support. During this three-year period, as in earlier ones, the entirety of the IUPAP funds at the Commission’s disposal has been used to support the ICM.

2. *The 1970 Meeting of the Magnetism Commission*

The major part of the meeting was devoted to the then current 1970 Grenoble ICM (see Sec. III), to a report on preparations for the 1973 Moscow ICM, and to a lengthy discussion of the visa problem. Among the Commission’s other actions, the most important ones were its decision to hold the 1976 ICM in Amsterdam, Holland, and its recommendation that an international program committee should be organised formally in conjunction with all ICMs to be held in 1976 and thereafter.

3. *The 1970 International Conference on Magnetism*

The 1970 Grenoble ICM is generally considered to have been a great success, its 84 scientific sessions reflecting the continued vitality of the field of magnetism. Of the almost 1200 participants, about two-thirds came from 30 countries other than France. In addition to 48 invited papers, a total of 705 were submitted. The Program Committee accepted 476 (i.e. only about 68%) for presentation, and then included, with the authors' concurrence, 425 of these in the Conference Proceedings which were subsequently published in two volumes of the *Journal de Physique*.

4. *Additional Information*

Additional information on Secs. II and III is given in the Secretary's 15 June 1970 and 7 July 1971 reports to Dr. Butler, and further details may be found in the Minutes of the 1970 Meeting of the Magnetism Commission (distributed on 27 April 1971) and in the references of Appendix A of the present report.

APPENDIX

(to Magnetism Commission Report)

Recommendations of the Magnetism Commission During 1969— 1972 for IUPAP Sponsorship or Co-Sponsorship of Conferences

(List prepared on June 7, 1972)

Note: Conferences marked with an asterisk (*) have already been granted IUPAP Sponsorship or Co-Sponsorship by the Executive.

Category	Title of Conference	Place and Date	IUPAP Support	Published Proceedings	Remarks
A	International Conference on Magnetism*	Grenoble, France Sept. 14–19/70	\$ 5000	See Reference 1	
C	Density of Electronic Charge and Spin*	Aussois, France Sept. 7–12/70	None	None	“Satellite” of '70 Grenoble Conference
C	Fourth International Colloquium on Magnetic Thin Films*	Prague, Czechoslovakia Sept. 21–23/70	None	See Reference 2	“Satellite” of '70 Grenoble Conference
B	Fourth International Symposium on Magnetic Resonance*	Rehovot, Israel Aug. 24–31/71	None	See Reference 3	Also sponsored by IUPAC
C	Symposium on the Physics of Dense Matter*	Copenhagen, Denmark After Aug. 1972	None		Co-sponsored by IAU

Category	Title of Conference	Place and Date	IUPAP Support	Published Proceedings	Remarks
A	International Conference on Magnetism	Moscow, USSR Aug. 22–28/73	More than \$ 5000 requested		
C	Sagamore IV: Electronic Charge, Spin and Momentum Density	Minsk, USSR Aug. 12–17/73	None		“Satellite” of '73 Moscow Conference
C	Sixth International Colloquium on Magnetic Thin Films	? USSR ?	None		“Satellite” of '73 Moscow Conference
B	Fifth International Symposium on Magnetic Resonance	Bombay, India Jan. or Feb. 1974	None		

Reference 1: Journal de Physique, Colloque C1, Supplement to Nos. 2–3, Volume 32, February–March 1972, pages C1–1 to C1–1210.

Reference 2: Czechoslovak Journal of Physics, vol. B21, No. 4–5, pages 329–590, 1971.

Reference 3: Invited papers: Pure and Applied Chemistry (to be published). Contributed papers: Journal of Magnetic Resonance (to be published).

10. Commission on solid state physics

1. The Commission consists of 8 members (including the Chairman and the Secretary) and 6 corresponding members, specifically representative of ferroelectricity lattice defects, luminescence and crystal growths.

2. Except for two meetings of the Chairman and Secretary, no meeting of the Commission took place. All matters were dealt with by correspondence.

3. The following conferences sponsored by the Commission took place:

- Third Sagamore Conference on Charge, Spin and Momentum Densities, Aussois, France, 9—12 September 1970; co-sponsored by I.U.Cr.
- *Metastable Alloys, Brela, Yugoslavia, 28—30 September 1970.
- *Third International Conference on Crystal Growth, Marseille, France, 5—9 July 1971; co-sponsored by IUCr and IOCG (International Organization for Crystal Growth formerly called, Comite International de Croissance Cristalline — CICC).
- *Second International Conference on Light Scattering in Solids, Paris, France, 19—23 July 1971.
- Fourth International Symposium on Magnetic Resonance, Jerusalem, Israel, 24—31 August 1971.
- *Colour Centres in Ionic Crystals, Reading, UK, 13—17 September 1971.
- International Conference for Solid Surfaces, Boston, USA, 11—15 October 1971.
- International Conference on Thin Films, Venice, Italy, 15—19 May 1972.
- *Second International Conference on Vapour Growth and Epitaxy, Jerusalem, Israel, 22—25 May 1972; co-sponsored by IUCr and IOCG.
- *Second Symposium on Surface Physics, Enschede, The Netherlands, 22—23 June 1972.
- *International Conference on Band Structure in Solids, Exeter, UK, 3—5 July 1972.
- Seventh International Symposium on the Reactivity of Solids, Bristol, UK, 17—21 July 1972; co-sponsored by IUPAC.

4. The following conferences are to be held with IUPAP sponsorship before the fall of this year:

- *Second International Conference on Luminescence, Leningrad, USSR, 17—22 August 1972.

- *International Conference on the Applications of the Mossbauer effect, Ayeleth Hashahar, Israel, 28—31 August 1972.
- *Second International Conference on the Properties of Liquid Metals, Tokyo, Japan, 3—8 September 1972.
- First International Conference on Modulation Spectroscopy, Tucson, USA, 23—26 November 1972; recommended by the IUPAP Solid State Commission and Spectroscopy Commission.

5. General Remarks.

The number of conferences sponsored by IUPAP in the field of Solid State Physics has increased from 13 (1966—1969) to 16 (1969—1972) and there is no indication for a slowing down. The total number of participants has exceeded 5000.

Some of the conferences have repetitive character and are organized on a nearly self supporting basis (about 1/3). For the major part (2/3) financial support from IUPAP was required (indicated by an asterisk).

6. The problem of the optimum size of conferences has still produced a considerable correspondence. Although the idea of a big Solid State Conference is not systematically rejected, the Commission members favour the middle-sized conferences of 200 to 300 participants as particularly suitable in specialized Solid State topics. The idea of conferences and summer schools of the Gordon type has encountered nearly unanimous favour.

11. Commission on Particles and Fields

A. Commission Operations and Procedures: The Commission has one regular meeting per year, held in conjunction with one of the principal conferences which it sponsors. At these meetings, proposals for future conferences are discussed and decisions are made regarding recommendations for IUPAP sponsorship of these conferences. Also general questions concerning the formal and overall scheduling of conferences on different topics in particle physics and technology are discussed.

Although we prefer to make decisions after discussion at these annual meetings, problems of timing have sometimes made it necessary to reach agreement on certain proposed conferences by mail during the interval between our meetings.

Meetings of the Commission during the period 1969—1972 were held or will be held as follows:

1969 — September 16, in Liverpool, Great Britain, on the occasion of the IV International Symposium on Electron and Photon Interactions at High Energy.

1970 — August 27 and September 1, in Kiew, USSR, on the occasion of the XV International Conference on High Energy Physics.

1971 — August 25, in Ithaca, New York, on the occasion of the V International Symposium on Electron and Photon Interactions at High Energy.

1972 — September 8 (tentative date), in Chicago, Illinois, on the occasion of the XVI International Conference on High Energy Physics.

B. Conferences Sponsored by the Commission during the Period 1969—1972:

Conferences in 1969

1. Topical Conference on Weak Interactions, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland, January 1969. Category B. Financial Support: \$ 1000. Proceedings: published by CERN-Scientific Information Service, Geneva, Switzerland 1969.

2. VII International Conference on High Energy Accelerators. Yerevan, USSR, August 1969. Category B. Financial Support: \$ 2000. Proceedings: published by the Publishing House of the Academy of Sciences of Armenian SSR, Yerevan 1970; General Editor, A. I. Alikhanian.

3. Third International Conference on High Energy Collisions, Stony Brook, New York, USA, September 1969. Category B. Financial Support: \$ 1000.

Proceedings: "High Energy Collisions", Yang, Cole, Good, Hwa and Lee-Franzini. Publisher — Gordon and Breach, New York 1969.

4. IV International Symposium on Electron and Photon Interactions at High Energies. Liverpool, UK, September 1969. Category B. Financial Support: None.

Proceedings: published by the Daresbury Nuclear Physics Laboratory, Daresbury, UK, 1969. Editor — D. W. Braben.

5. III International Conference on High Energy Physics and Nuclear Structure. Columbia University, New York, USA, September 1969, Category B. Financial Support: None.

Proceedings: High Energy Physics and Nuclear Structure; Proceedings. Edited by Samuel Devons, Plenum Press, New York 1970.

Conferences in 1970

1. XV International Conference on High Energy Physics, Kiev, USSR, 26 August—4 September 1970. Category A. Financial Support: US \$ 4000.

Chairman of Organising Committee: N. N. Bogolubov, Joint Institute for Nuclear Research, Head Post Office, PO. Box 70, Moscow, USSR.

Proceedings: Not published.

2. International Conference on Instrumentation for High Energy Physics, Dubna, USSR, 8—12 September 1970. Category B. Financial Support: US \$ 1000.

Chairman of Organising Committee: V. P. Dzhelepov, Joint Institute for Nuclear Research, Head Post Office, PO. Box 70, Moscow, USSR.

Proceedings: published by the Joint Institute for Nuclear Research, Dubna, USSR, 1971. Editor: V. P. Dzhelepov.

Conferences in 1971

1. VIII International Conference on High Energy Accelerators, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland, 20—24 September 1971. Category B. Financial Support: US \$ 2000.

Organiser: K. Johnson, CERN, 1211 Geneva 23, Switzerland.

Proceedings: published by CERN-Scientific Information Service, Geneva, 1971. Editor: M. Hildred Blewett.

2. V International Conference on Electron and Photon Interactions at High Energies, Ithaca, New York, 23—27 August 1971. Category B. Financial Support: US \$ 1000.

Organiser: Professor Boyce D. McDaniel, Laboratory of Nuclear Studies, Cornell University, Ithaca, New York.

Proceedings: 1971 International Symposium on Electron and Photon Interactions at High Energies. Published by the Laboratory of Nuclear Studies, Cornell University, Ithaca, New York 1972. Editor: N. B. Mistry.

3. International Conference on Duality and Symmetry in Hadron Physics, Tel-Aviv, Israel, 5—7 April 1971. Category B. Financial Support: US \$ 1000.

Organiser: Professor Y. Ne'eman, Department of Physics and Astronomy, Tel-Aviv University, Ramat-Aviv, Tel-Aviv, Israel.

Proceedings: published by The Weizmann Science Press of Israel, 1971. Edited by E. Gotsman.

4. International Conference on High Energy Physics and Nuclear Structure, Dubna, USSR, 7—12 September 1971. Category B. Financial Support: US \$ 1000.

Organiser: Professor V. P. Dzhelepov, Laboratory of Nuclear Problems, Joint Institute for Nuclear Research, Head Post Office, PO. Box 79, Moscow, USSR.

Conferences in 1972

1. XVI International Conference on High Energy Physics, Chicago, Illinois, 6—13 September 1972. Location: University of Chicago and National Accelerator Laboratory, Batavia, Illinois. Category A. Financial Support: US \$ 3000.

Organisers: Professor Edwin L. Goldwasser, National Accelerator Laboratory, PO. Box 500, Batavia, Illinois 60510; Professor Robert

G. Sachs, The Enrico Fermi Institute, 5630 Ellis Avenue, Chicago, Illinois 60637.

2. IV International Conference on High Energy Collisions, Oxford, UK, 5—7 April 1972. Category B. Financial Support: None.

Organiser: G. Manning, Rutherford High Energy Laboratory, Oxford, Chilton, Didcot, Berkshire, UK.

3. 4th International Conference on Magnet Technology, Brookhaven, New York, 19—22 September 1972. Category B. Financial Support: None.

Organiser: Dr. J. P. Blewett, Brookhaven National Laboratory, Upton, New York 11973.

(This conference was not reviewed by the Commission on Particles and Fields.)

12. Commission on Nuclear physics

Membership

The membership remains as elected by the General Assembly, Dubrovnik, September 1969.

Chairman, Secretary, Members

R. E. Bell (Canada)

J. Teillac (France)

G. R. Bishop (UK)

S. G. Cohen (Israel)

I. M. Frank (USSR)

T. Lauritsen (USA)

R. Ramanna (India)

H. Schopper (W. Germany)

Corresponding Members

E. Baumgartner (Switzerland)

J. Fowler (USA)

R. Ricci (Italy)

M. Sakai (Japan)
I. Slaus (Yugoslavia)
S. Szalay (Hungary)

Commission Procedure

The Commission did not meet during the three-year period 1969—1972, and all business was conducted by mail. A systematic form of mail ballot was introduced for obtaining members' opinions on various questions.

No general conference on nuclear physics was held during 1969—1972 (which also explains why the Commission did not meet). The absence of a general conference ("Category A") was the result of a deliberate decision taken by the Commission early in 1970, prompted by the widespread feeling that large conferences on nuclear physics had been too frequent in the immediately preceding years (one in each of 1967, 1968, and 1969). This may be one of the few cases where a Commission has actively discouraged the holding of large conferences. A category A conference is now scheduled for Munich, August 28—September 1, 1973; see the end of this report.

On the other hand the Commission sponsored an unusually large number of category B conferences, in the three-year period. A list of them is found at the end of this report.

Overlapping Subject Matter in Conferences

In April, 1971, the Chairman of this Commission heard for the first time about a conference scheduled for September, 1971, by the Commission on Particles and Fields on the subject "High Energy Physics and Nuclear Structure". The planning of this conference was already complete and all participants were already decided upon. The program made it clear that this was a straightforward conference on nuclear physics studied by intermediate- and high-energy techniques. According to a resolution of this Commission meeting in Dubna in 1968 jointly with members of the Commission on Particles and Fields, such conferences should be handled jointly by the two Commissions.

After correspondence between the two Commissions, agreement was reached to keep in contact on such questions. The Commission on Particles and Fields has now proposed such a Conference for June, 1973, in Uppsala, Sweden, for joint sponsorship by the two Commissions. The proposed data is not the best for Nuclear Physics, but the procedure is an improvement over the preceding case, and the Chairman recommends that the new Commission ratify joint sponsorship of this conference. In future there should be full joint planning of such conferences, including the place and date.

This case has been raised here, not in order to blame anyone, but to point out the general necessity of joint planning of conferences in overlapping fields. This Commission recommended in its 1970—71 report that the Executive consider this problem and attempt to devise procedures to solve it.

Visa Problems

In 1969 at Dubrovnik, the late Chairman of this Commission, Professor Huber, reported to the General Assembly that a conference participant (and Commission member), the late Amos de-Shalit, had been excluded from the 1968 Dubna conference on what appeared to be political grounds. The present Chairman now has to report a similar case involving several participants in the Commission-sponsored conference on Nuclear Structure Study with Neutrons in Budapest, July 31 to August 5, 1972. The Executive of IUPAP has already made some investigations and has discussed the matter in an Executive meeting. It is to be hoped that the Executive will be able to recommend procedures that will enable all Commissions to avoid such problems for future meetings.

List of Conferences Sponsored

1970

Polarization Phenomena in Nuclear Reactions
Madison, Wisconsin, August 31—September 4
Category B (\$1000)

Angular Correlation in Nuclear Physics
Delft, Netherlands, August 17—21
Category B (\$1000)

Hyperfine Interactions Detected by Nuclear Radiation
Rehovoth, Israel, September 6—11
Category B (\$1000)

1971

Statistical Properties of Nuclei
Albany, New York, USA, August 23—27
Category B (\$1500)

1972

Few Particle Problems in the Nuclear Interaction
Los Angeles, California, USA, August 28—September 1
Category B (\$2000)

Nuclear Moments and Nuclear Structure
Osaka, Japan, September 4—8
Category B (\$1200)

Sixth International Cyclotron Conference
Vancouver, Canada, July 18—21
Category B (\$1800)

Nuclear Structure Study with Neutrons
Budapest, Hungary, July 31—August 5
Category B (\$1200)

Conferences Recommended by the Commission for Support

General Conference on Nuclear Physics
Munich, West Germany, August 27—September 1, 1973
Category A. Recommended grant, \$5000
(Already approved in principle; amount of grant to be approved)

Photonuclear Reactions and Applications
Asilomar, California, March 26—30, 1973
Category B. Recommended grant, \$1500

Reactions Between Complex Nuclei
Gatlinburg, USA. Late October, 1973
Category B. Recommended grant, \$1500

V Conference on High Energy Physics and Nuclear Structure
Uppsala, Sweden. June 4—9, 1973
Category B (Jointly with Particles and Fields Commission)
Grant to be decided by agreement, not over \$1000 from Nuclear
Phys

Proposal received for 1974

The Few Body Problem in Nuclear (and Particle?) Physics
Quebec, Canada, August 1974

This is referred to the new Commission with the Chairman's recommendation for immediate consultation with the Commission on Particles and Fields.

R. E. Bell, Chairman
September 21, 1972

13. Commission on Atomic Masses and Fundamental Constants

1. Change of Commission Name

In view of the changing scope of the Commission's activities, it has become clear that the fundamental constants are an increasingly important part of the Commission's activities. Accordingly, at its meeting in September 1971 the IUPAP Executive Committee authorised the change of the Commission name to its present form.

2. Activities

A. The Commission was one of the sponsors of the International Conference on Precision Measurements and Fundamental Constants held at the United States National Bureau of Standards in Gaithersburg, Maryland, during the week of 3—7 August 1970. The proceeding of this Conference has been published by the United States National Bureau of Standards (Special Publication 343 (543 pp) August 1971).

B. The 4th International Conference on Atomic Masses and Fundamental Constants sponsored by the Commission was held at the British National Physical Laboratory, Teddington, England, during the week of 6—10 September 1971. The Proceedings will be published by Plenum Press (London).

C. It has become increasingly evident that progress in precision (n, γ) and (p, γ) reaction energy determinations is hampered by a lack of uniformity and standards in the use of gamma ray calibration lines. This Commission, in conjunction with the Commission on Nuclear Physics, has therefore established a Task Group on gamma ray calibration energies. This Task Group, consisting of Dr. O. van der Leun (Netherlands), Dr. R. G. Helmer (US), and Dr. P. van Assche (Belgium), will consider the problems associated with the measurement of gamma ray energies and will attempt to establish appropriate standards in this area.

D. Professor A. H. Wapstra (Chairman of the Commission) and Dr. N. B. Gove (Oak Ridge National Laboratory) have completed the 1971 Atomic Mass Evaluation which has been published in four parts in Nuclear Data Tables, July 1971. This evaluation consisted of:

Part I. Atomic Mass Table

Part II. Nuclear-Reaction and Separation Energies

Part III. Evaluation of Input Values; Adjustment Procedures

Part IV. Systematics of Separation and Decay Energies

Part V, Nuclear Reaction Q Values will appear separately in the near future.

E. Dr. E. R. Cohen (Secretary of the Commission) and Dr. B. N. Taylor (US National Bureau of Standards) are in the process of a new evaluation of the fundamental constants. This evaluation, which will take into account the considerable amount of new material which has become available in the last three years, should be completed by September and will be published in an appropriate journal.

3. *Meeting*

The Commission has held two meetings since those reported in the previous report.

1. August 3, 1970, Washington, D. C.
2. September 5, 1971, Twickenham, England.

4. *Conferences*

Preliminary discussions have been held concerning the time and place of the 5th International Conference on Atomic Masses and Fundamental Constants. Possible locations suggested have been: Sydney, Australia; Paris; Leningrad; the Conference will be scheduled for either 1974 or 1975.

14. Commission on Physics Education

1. Meeting of the Commission

The Commission met in Rome 11—12 July 1969; in Eger, Hungary, 14—15 September 1970; and in Kiel, West Germany 25—26 June 1971. In addition to members and corresponding members of the Commission, representatives from UNESCO and other interested organisations attended. The minutes of those meetings have been circulated.

2. International Seminar on the Role of History of Physics in Physics Education (1970)

The Seminar was held 13—17 July 1970 at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. The purpose of the Seminar was to stimulate and extend cooperation among physicists, historians of science, and others interested in the humanistic teaching of physics. Twenty-two persons, representing twelve countries, took part. The proceedings of the Seminar and a special report entitled *Resources for the History of Physics* have been published (University Press of New England, 1972). The Commission considered the recommendation of the Seminar that a book or books on the history of physics be written

for teachers and advanced students, but was unable to implement it within available resources.

3. *International Congress on the Education of Teachers of Physics in Secondary Schools* (1970)

The Congress was held in Eger, Hungary, 11—17 September 1970, under the joint sponsorship of IUPAP and the Hungarian National Committee on Physics Teaching. The purpose of the Congress was to review problems connected with the education of secondary-school physics teachers in many countries and to develop recommendations to government groups and universities for improved pre-service education, motivation, and continuing education of teachers. Total attendance at the Congress was 144, including representatives of 25 countries. The proceedings of the Congress have been published (MIT Press, 1971).

4. *International Congress on Teaching Physics to Students in Physics-Related Sciences and Professions*

At its meeting on 25—26 June 1971 the Commission made plans for this Congress to be held in Kiel, West Germany, 20—26 July 1972, under the sponsorship of the Commission and the West German National Committee. Between 150 and 200 participants were expected, representing the physical and biological sciences, engineering, agricultural sciences, and the health professions. The Congress was intended to provide answers to several major questions: (1) What do the “consumers” of physics education want that they are not now getting? (2) What do physicists think they have to offer that is not presently being taken advantage of? and (3) How should physics courses for non-physicist scientists and professionals be organised? Professor M. Y. Bernard of France was named the chairman of the Program Committee, and Professor W. Kroebel of West Germany the chairman of the Organising Committee. A program was developed, speakers were invited, and two circulars were distributed. The early response indicated considerable world-wide interest in the Congress.

Regrettably the Organizing Committee was unable to obtain sufficient financial support to make the Congress a success and was forced to cancel it. Notification of cancellation was sent to prospective participants early in June 1972.

5. *Other Meetings*

Plans for other international congresses or seminars are not under consideration at this time. Since the membership of the Commission will be reconstituted at the General Assembly in 1972, it does not seem advisable to carry forward planning of meetings that will be the responsibility of new members.

6. *Cooperation with UNESCO*

Two writing projects — “A Source Book for the Teaching of Physics in Secondary Schools” and “New Trends in the Teaching of Physics” — were completed. Manuscripts were given to UNESCO by the editors and publication is imminent.

7. *Request to IUPAP*

The reconstituted Commission will undoubtedly want to meet early in the triennium 1972—1975 to plan new activities. The requirement for travel funds will depend upon the number of Commission members and their distribution. It is suggested that at least \$2000 be budgeted by IUPAP for Commission travel in 1972—73.

Conferences Sponsored 1969—1972

International Seminar on the Role of History of Physics in Physics Education, Cambridge, Massachusetts, USA, 13–17 July 1970.

History in the Teaching of Physics, University Press of New England, Hanover, New Hampshire, 1972.

Resources for the History of Physics, University Press of New England, Hanover, New Hampshire, 1972.

Planck's Original Papers in Quantum Theory, Taylor and Francis, Ltd, London, 1972.

International Congress on the Education of Teachers of Physics in Secondary Schools, Eger, Hungary, 11—17 September 1970.
Teaching Physics — An Insoluble Task? MIT Press, 1971.

15. Commission on Atomic and Molecular Physics and Spectroscopy

Only a few commission members were able to attend the Commission meeting held in Oxford, England on 23 July 1970 at the occasion of the Oxford conference on Atomic Physics. Most of the affairs concerning the commission were dealt with by correspondence. The International Conferences sponsored by IUPAP in the field of Commission XV were the followings in chronological order:

1970:

- a) The Second International Conference on Atomic Physics held in Oxford, United Kingdom, 21—24 July 1970, organized by Dr. WOODGATE. 200 participants from 17 countries took part in this conference where all aspects of atomic physics were discussed.
The abstracts of the papers were available at the conference.
- b) The International Conference on Precision Measurements and Fundamental Constants was held in Gaithersburg, Maryland, USA on 3—7 August 1970, organized by Dr. L. M. BRANSCOMB. This was the first conference devoted to the field of fundamental constants as a whole. It achieved broad representation of most of the current work and except for the regrettable absence of contributions from the USSR, achieved good international participation. 193 participants attended the conference, 154 from USA and 39 from other countries.
- c) An International Conference on “Applications of Holography” was held in Besançon, France, on 6—11 July 1970. It was organized by Professor J. VIENOT and financially supported by the International Commission of Optics. It had a very large attendance, more than 400 participants from 24 countries. The summary of the communications has been published by “Nou-

velle Revue d'Optique Appliquée" Edition Masson, Paris, in its March—April 1970 issue.

- d) IUPAP had given also its moral support, without financial contribution, to the 16th Congress AMPERE held in Bucarest, Rumania, 1—5 September 1970, organized by Professor I. URSU. The proceedings of this conference on "Magnetic resonance and related phenomena" have been published by the Academy of Romania.

1971:

- a) The seventh International Conference on Physics of Electronic and Atomic Collisions was held in Amsterdam, 26—30 July 1971, organized by Professor J. KISTEMAKER. The conference brought together 800 scientists from 26 nations. The invited talks and progress reports were on subjects of broad interest to scientists in the field of atomic and molecular physics. The proceedings have been published by North Holland Co.
- b) The Third International Conference on Vacuum Ultraviolet Radiation Physics was held in Tokyo, Japan on 30 August—2 September 1971, organized by Dr. ISHIGURO and Prof. FUJIOKA. The Conference covered essentially the entire range of vacuum ultraviolet from 2000 Å to a few Å.
204 participants attended the conference, among them 54 from abroad. More than 80 papers were presented. The booklet of abstracts was available at the conference.

1972:

- a) The International Conference on Inner Shell Ionization Phenomena was held at Atlanta, Georgia, USA 17—21 April 1972, organized by Dr. R. W. FINK, Professor of Chemistry. It was the first International meeting in this field of physics. Its interest was to bring together workers in the fields of Auger electron spectroscopy, X-ray spectroscopy, radioactive decay, atomic collisions, theoretical atomic physics and nuclear physics.

- b) The Third International Conference on Atomic Physics, held in Boulder, Colorado, USA, 7—12 August 1972, organized by Dr. S. T. SMITH from JILA.
- c) The 17th Congress AMPERE on Magnetic Resonance and Relaxation Phenomena held at Wihuri Laboratory, University of Turku, Finland 21—26 August 1972, organized by Professor V. HOVI. 300 participants from 30 countries attended the meeting, where could be noticed a strong participation from both USSR (21 participants) and USA (21 participants). 14 invited papers and 102 communications were presented. The Congress report will be published by North Holland Co.

16. Commission on Plasma Physics

This Commission was formed by the XIII General Assembly of IUPAP in September 1969. Unfortunately, because of the large number of verbal nominations given to the General Assembly for membership on this Commission, it was not until late March that the officers of the Commission had a validated list of members and corresponding members. This seven-month delay in determining who the members of the Commission were prevented the Commission from doing any work before June 1970.

Most of the Commission business has been carried out by mail, but the Commission had one formal meeting in connection with the Fourth Conference on Plasma Physics and Controlled Nuclear Fusion Research, which was held in Madison, Wisconsin, USA, on 22 June 1971. Present or represented were the following members and corresponding members: Professor H. Alfvén, represented by Dr. B. Lehnert, Sweden; Professor Sanborn C. Brown, Secretary, USA; Dr. K. Husimi, Japan; Professor Ioan-Iovitz Popescu, Romania; Dr. Richard F. Post, USA; Dr. C. M. Braams, The Netherlands; Dr. Bruno Brunelli, Italy; Dr. J. L. Delcroix, represented by Dr. C. J. Jablon, France; and Professor E. S. Weibel, Switzerland.

The area of plasma physics and ionized gases is a very comprehensive one, and as a result there are several other international organizations which have committees of various sorts in this area of

physics. One of the very useful functions performed by the IUPAP Commission is to serve as a liaison between these various other organizations. This is accomplished to a large extent by overlapping membership. For example, the International Atomic Energy Agency has set up an International Fusion Research Council. Dr. C. M. Braams, a corresponding member of the Commission on Plasma Physics of IUPAP, is Chairman of the IAEA Council. The European Physical Society has set up a Plasma Physics Division and Dr. B. Lehnert, who has been acting for Professor Alfvén on the IUPAP Commission, is the President of this Division. There is a self-perpetuating International Scientific Committee that runs the International Conferences on Phenomena in Ionized Gases. It has been the recommendation of this Commission that a member of this Committee be nominated to membership on the Plasma Physics Commission to provide close liaison with this International Scientific Committee.

Also in connection with the wide range of physical phenomena covered by the field of plasma physics, this Commission has recommended to the General Assembly that the Plasma Physics Commission be made up of not less than two members expert in plasma physics, two members expert in gas discharge physics, and two members expert in astrophysical plasma phenomena.

Conferences sponsored by the Commission during 1971 were the following:

- a) International Symposium on Plasma Physics in St. John's Newfoundland, 5—9 July 1971; Conference Organizer: Dr. M. P. Bachynski, RCA Laboratories, 1001 Lenoir, Montreal, P. Q., Canada.
- b) Seminars in Fundamental and Applied Laser Physics, Isfahan, Iran, 1—7 September 1971; Conference Organizer: Professor Ali Javan, Rm. 6-210, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, Massachusetts 02139, USA.
- c) Xth International Conference on Phenomena in Ionized Gases, Oxford, England, 13—18 September 1971; Conference Organizer: Dr. R. N. Franklin, Keble College, Oxford England.

No conferences were sponsored by the Commission during the year 1972. This can be explained principally by the fact that there are two major international conferences of interest to this Commission which meet on a regular basis: one, the Conference on Phenomena in Ionized Gases, and the other, the Controlled Thermonuclear Fusion Conference. The first meets every two years and the second meets every three years and both met in 1971.

Conferences scheduled for 1973 are the following:

- a) XIth International Conference on Ionization Phenomena in Gases, Prague, Czechoslovakia, September 1973; Conference Organizer: Dr. L. Pekarek, Czechoslovak Academy of Science, Vinicna Ul. 7, Praha 2, Czechoslovakia.
- b) Conference on Plasma Theory, Kiev, USSR, October 1973; Conference Organizer: Professor L. A. Artsimovich, I. V. Kurchatov Institute of Atomic Energy, Moscow, USSR.

17. International Commission for Optics

1. Bureau

Le bureau actuel a été élu lors de CIO 8 (Reading 1969). Il est constitué par: Prof. H. H. Hopkins (President), J. Ch. Viénot (Secr. Trés.), Prof. B. Havelka, Prof. Koreo Kinoshita, Dr. R. M. Scott, Dr. W. H. Steel (Vice-Présidents).

2. Status — réglementation

Le Bureau de la CIO a mis au point un projet de rénovation des Status de la CIO, celui-ci a été proposé au Secrétaire Général de IUPAP et devrait être normalement discuté lors de la réunion CIO 9 en octobre 1972 à Santa Monica.

La nécessité de réglementer l'organisation des Écoles d'Été a également amené à proposer une procédure qui leur est applicable. Enfin, le Bureau de la CIO a examiné les relations à mettre en place d'une part avec les différentes organisations s'occupant des Couches

Minces, d'autre part avec les groupes d'optique européens et la Société Européenne de Physique.

3. *Réunions*

Plusieurs conférences et symposia ont été organisés sous les auspices de la CIO.

- Symposium International sur les Applications de l'Holographie, Besançon (France): 6—11 Juillet 1970.
- Symposium sur les Performances visuelles dans l'observation à travers un instrument d'optique, Munich (Allemagne): 21—23 Juillet 1971.
- 3ème Conférence Int. sur la Physique du Rayonnement Ultra-Violet dans le Vide, Tokyo-Kyoto (Japon): 30 Août—2 Septembre 1971.
- Optique intégrée, Ondes Guidées, Matériaux et Systèmes, Las Vegas, Nevada (USA): 7—9 Février 1972.
- Réunion Internationale sur les Couches Minces, Venise (Italie): 15—19 Mai 1972.

4. *Communications — bulletin de liaison*

La CIO ne comportant pas de membres individuels, mais regroupant les Comités Nationaux d'Optique de différents pays, les liaisons se font lors des Assemblées Générales (tri-annuelles), lors des Congrès et Symposiums de la CIO. L'amorce d'un bulletin de liaison régulier a démarré (a) sous forme de circulaires: octobre 1969, puis janvier 1970; (b) ensuite, un bulletin de liaison («News-Letter») a été diffusé: février 1971 puis avril 1972. Ce bulletin a pour but de renseigner les différents pays membres sur les activités de l'année (cf. copies jointes).

5. *Glossaire multilingue*

La mise au point d'un glossaire multilingue d'optique se poursuit. Une documentation étendue a été réunie, tant du point de vue lexicologique que du point de vue correspondance des termes dans des disciplines voisines.

6. *Accroissement du nombre des pays membres de la CIO*

Plusieurs adhésions nouvelles doivent être prochainement ratifiées ou sont actuellement en cours. Il s'agit d'Israël, du Mexique et de la République Démocratique d'Allemagne. Il semble que la Commission pourra également bientôt compter l'U. R. S. S. parmi ses membres.

7. *Budget*

Le budget de la CIO reste à peu près stationnaire, les cotisations n'ayant pas été réajustées et les ressources extérieures étant in-

APPENDIX III

INTER-UNION ACTIVITIES

ICSU Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research (SCOR)

The increasing scientific and public interest in the oceans has been reflected in increased activity of the numerous international scientific organisations concerned and, in particular, by SCOR. The work of SCOR is carried out at meetings of its executive committee, at general meetings which are usually combined with oceanographic conferences, at meeting of working groups and by publications. A part of the work is biological, geological or chemical and of no direct interest to IUPAP; a substantial part, however, is concerned with the physical properties of sea water and sediments and with hydrodynamics, thermodynamics and instrumentation. All of this has a basis in physics.

During the period four volumes of *SCOR Proceedings* have been published, these give a detailed account of the meetings and of the work done and resolutions adopted. One general meeting was held. This took place in Tokyo and was a joint enterprise with IAPSO, IABO, and CMG. The proceedings have been published as a book, *The Ocean World* edited by M. Uda (Tokyo 1971). A number of smaller conferences have been held.

Much attention was given at the Tokyo meeting to considering the formation of a *Marine Sciences Union*. It was the almost unanimous view of those present that this was unnecessary and would be very difficult to achieve in view of the multiplicity of organisations whose agreement would be needed. Most people felt that it would be more satisfactory to strengthen SCOR. With this in view a revised constitution for SCOR was drafted; this is being considered by ICSU. A feature of this constitution is the introduction of a new class of

Invited Members. This is to enable SCOR to coopt eminent oceanographers even if they are nationals of countries that have not joined SCOR. Some such members have already been appointed.

The main technical work of SCOR is done through working groups which hold meetings and organise cooperative projects. The working groups of main interest to IUPAP are:

WG 10 Oceanographic tables and standards. This committee prepared tables giving the physical properties of sea water and is responsible for advising on the certification of standard sea water. Particular attention has been given to the equation of state and to the relation between electrical conductivity and salinity. The theory of motions in the ocean requires very accurate determinations of density as a function of temperature, pressure and salinity. The investigations promoted by the working group have produced a great improvement in the quality of the data available. The program is continuing.

WG 15 Photosynthetic radiant energy. This group is concerned with the methods of measurement of solar radiation in the sea that are relevant to biology.

WG 21 Continuous current velocity measurement. This group is engaged in a comparison at sea of the performance of the principal types of current meters. Its work has revealed a number of discrepancies which are being investigated.

WG 27 Tides of the open sea. This group is concerned with instrumentation for measuring tides in the deep sea and with the analysis of the results.

WG 28 Air-sea interaction. This group is concerned with the transfer of energy, momentum and water between ocean and atmosphere. It is involved in the oceanographic aspects of the Atlantic Tropical Experiment of GARP and in the Mid-Ocean Dynamics Experiment.

WG 34 Oceanographic basis of ocean monitoring and prediction systems. This group is concerned with the design of equipment for systematic monitoring of oceanic conditions, the planning of cooperative programs and the dynamical interpretation of the results.

Most of these group are joint enterprises with other international bodies. Their terms of reference will be found in volume 7 of the *SCOR Proceedings* and accounts of the work of each are usually to be found in each issue.

Concern has been expressed lest the development of international law to cover activities in the deep sea might seriously restrict many kinds of oceanographic research. Much time has been spent on the discussion of this matter. Whilst the discussions have not led to any real consensus on the best method of minimising interference, they have led to a wider appreciation of the difficulties and have probably had some effect on the positions adopted by governments.

The eleventh general meeting of SCOR will take place in Oban, Scotland, in September 1972.

Upper Mantle Project

The Upper Mantle Project officially ended in December 1970. A final symposium on the results of this international corporation was held in August 1971 in Moscow at the general assembly of the International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics; the proceedings have been published as a special issue of *Tectonophysics*. During the period of the Upper Mantle Project it is not an exaggeration to say that a revolution has taken place in the earth sciences, especially with the discovery of many quantitative determinations of the large horizontal displacements of the earth's crust which have occurred over the last 100 m. y. The verification of the once speculative theory of continental drift and its more recent complement, the theory of sea floor spreading and the formulation of the theory of plate tectonics, has given us a dynamic in place of a static model of the earth's interior. The study of the physics of the processes in the earth's interior which has caused these movements, creep, convection and heat transfer, is still in a rudimentary state and most interesting problems in solid state physics and hydrodynamics invite investigation.

ICSU Abstracting Board

Report by H. W. Koch

The Abstracting Board of ICSU has made considerable progress of direct interest to IUPAP during the 1969—1972 period. A so-called Input Plan has been developed and approved by the Board in 1970. According to this plan, the major abstracting and indexing services of the world, including Physics Abstracts and Chemical Abstracts Service, will share the responsibilities and substantial costs involved in inputting a World Abstracting and Indexing System. An important prerequisite to the operational feasibility of this plan is the standardisation of the classification and indexing schemes for the organisation of physics literature in this computerised system. The ICSU/AB Working Group in Physics has just completed the details and agreements for a Physics Classification Scheme that will soon be adopted by Physics Abstracts, Bulletin Signalatique, and Physikalische Berichte, as well as many of the primary journals of the American Institute of Physics and the European Physical Society. Such agreements are not only the results of ICSU/AB efforts, but also of the effective coordination supplied by such commission of ICSU as the Publications Commission of IUPAP. Both the Board and this Commission can be justly proud of their past contributions to the developments of science information systems of the near future.

The importance of continued IUPAP contributions should be emphasised. IUPAP is the principal mechanism for ensuring that appropriate consideration be given to the needs, capabilities, and interests of individual physicists, who, after all, are to be the main contributors to, and users of, the information systems in physics now being designed and developed. Because of the importance of IUPAP's role, I am delighted that a physicist active in the publications committee of the European Physical Society will be encouraged to participate in ICSU/AB after my term of involvement as IUPAP representative is completed. My own personal involvement with ICSU/AB will continue as a representative of the American Institute of Physics that became a member service of the Board in 1972.

The Executive Committee and the General Assembly may want to consider expanding formally the role of the Publications Commission so as to include in its terms of reference abstracting and indexing, together with primary publications. This expansion would be facilitated by making the IUPAP representative to ICSU/AB a member of the Publications Commission and by charging the Commission with the responsibility for nominating the IUPAP representative to the Board. Consideration may also want to be given to changing the name of the Publications Commission to the Science Information Commission.

APPENDIX IV

RESOLUTIONS ADOPTED BY THE 14th GENERAL ASSEMBLY OF ICSU

The 14th General Assembly of ICSU

I. FREE CIRCULATION of SCIENTISTS

recapitulates that the terms of reference of the Standing Committee on the Free Circulation of Scientists, as defined by the 10th General Assembly, are to assist the Executive Board to find solutions to various problems associated with the implementation of the resolution, according to which the declaration of "political non-discrimination", adopted by the 8th General Assembly, is reaffirmed, and moreover:

- : in holding ICSU meetings and meetings of ICSU scientific and special committees, the Council shall take all measures within its powers to ensure the fundamental right of participation, without any political discrimination, of the representatives of every member of ICSU concerned and of invited observers,
- : this policy be adopted also by the Unions adhering to ICSU for all their activities,
- : the ICSU National Members be invited to follow this policy;

noting with satisfaction that ICSU, in executing its declared policy of supporting free international collaboration among scientists, has been successful in most cases;

observes, however, with regret, that scientists are still today sometimes not allowed freely to attend the appropriate scientific meetings organized by the ICSU family either abroad or in their home countries;

notes that the obstacles encountered in recent years have fallen into the following categories:

1. The refusal of a visa to enter a certain country. Fatal delays in granting visas.
2. Refusal of permission to participate in an appropriate scientific meeting organized by the ICSU family in the country of the scientist in question.
3. Refusal of the permission to travel to scientific meetings organized by the ICSU family and held outside the country.

Excessive payment required for the permission to travel out of the country to such meetings.

fearing that the difficulties encountered by scientists from some countries, in gaining permission freely to travel to scientific meetings of the ICSU family in other countries or to participate in such appropriate meetings in their own country, might endanger the global character of ICSU and the Unions;

decides to remind the affiliated Unions and other organs of ICSU of their obligation to bring all instances, in which the free circulation of scientists has been restricted, to the notice of the ICSU Standing Committee on the Free Circulation of Scientists;

recommends that when consideration is being given to the selection of a place for an ICSU meeting, the Standing Committee in the Free Circulation of Scientists shall, on request, provide summary information in its possession on previous cases of restriction relatives to the proposed place of meeting;

II. MIGRATION of TALENT

observes that recently considerable communication has been received by the Standing Committee on the difficulties encountered by some scientists wishing to migrate from their country;

observes also that this form of "brain drain", that is, the migration of talent from developing countries to the industrialized ones is of

great concern to the developing as well as to developed countries, as illustrated among others by resolution 1.243 of the General Conference of Unesco at its 16th session, in 1970;

observing, moreover, that the prevention of migration of scientists from a country is an internal political question, outside the terms of reference of ICSU, but nevertheless a serious challenge to the world scientific community;

notes that this problem does not fall within the mandate of the Standing Committee on the Free Circulation of Scientists;

decides to ask the Executive Board to study how ICSU should approach this new problem, namely the factual impossibility of migrating from a country and to report to the 15th General Assembly.

APPENDIX V

September 23, 1972

MEMORANDUM

TO: Secretary-General

FROM: R. E. Bell

SUBJECT: Visa Problems

(This memo is written because I will be absent from the IUPAP General Assembly meeting of September 24 where visa problems will be discussed. The views here expressed are my own and have not been submitted to either the Canadian Delegation or the Nuclear Physics Commission. In what follows, "country" means "IUPAP member country.")

1. I believe that the free movement of scientists for international scientific purposes is the most important aim of IUPAP. We should continue to press for this aim even while realizing that success may never be complete.
2. It is not reasonable to expect a host country to declare in advance that any scientist will be admitted to any IUPAP-sponsored meeting. Countries will presumably always retain the right to exclude individuals on an individual basis, and IUPAP should explicitly recognize this right.
3. It does seem reasonable to ask a host country to declare in advance that individuals will not be excluded solely on grounds of national origin. To secure such an advance declaration even in a single instance would be an important forward step for IUPAP. It is most likely to be achieved when the host country is a medium-sized one, possessing a considerable degree of flexibility in foreign policy. I believe IUPAP should press for such declarations at every opportunity. An equivalent form of declaration, which might be easier to

secure, would state that the host country is willing to consider individual visa applications from the citizens of any country to attend IUPAP — sponsored meetings.

4. The test of the sincerity of such a police (declared or undeclared) would be the host country's willingness to allow substitutes from the same country for any scientists whose individual applications had not been allowed.

5. What if (as in fact is common) no such declaration is received from official sources in the host country? IUPAP has already adopted this policy for itself; it should behave as if the declaration had been made, and proceed with the planning of the conference on the basis of its own policy. If, as seems very unlikely, an advance declaration were made by the host country that it would *not* consider applications from citizens of all countries, then IUPAP sponsorship should be withdrawn. Recovery of any IUPAP funds already advanced to the conference should not be attempted.

6. What if there is no declaration, but at the last moment scientists are excluded on grounds of national origin? This is the commonest kind of case; often the facts are not established until after the conference is finished. What sanctions should be attempted, if any, against the host country? In general, I believe that any possible sanctions should be applied against the country and not against the scientists of that country. The only sanctions that occur to me are, assuming that the facts are well established,

- a) publicizing the occurrence in IUPAP publications and elsewhere, and
- b) extreme caution in sanction further IUPAP events in the offending country.

7. I believe that IUPAP actions about visa problems should be carried out primarily by the President, Secretary-General, and Executive, rather than by individual commissions. The reason is clear: to bring the full weight of the IUPAP to bear on each case.

I hope that the General Assembly will adopt a clear policy similar to that expressed above, and that the "Checklist" for conference sponsorship will make that policy very explicit.

APPENDIX VI

Presidential address by Professor Robert F. Bacher at the XIVth General Assembly, Washington, September 1972

During the past few days we have heard some fine papers presented before the Scientific Sessions of this 50th Anniversary General Assembly of our Union. There have been reviews by distinguished physicists of most of the main areas of physics and some of the areas in which physics impinges on other sciences. These talks have shown us the present status of these many fields and some idea of the most important areas of future growth. The accomplishments of the past fifty years are very impressive. An enormous, coherent body of knowledge has been put together with many interlocks in fundamental concepts as well as in quantitative observation and calculation.

It would be easy looking at these accomplishments of physics to be too satisfied. But in fact, some of the most basic areas of physics are understood very imperfectly. One might say that our understanding is exceeded only by our ignorance. Looking back at one large field over a period a bit longer than the fifty years of our Union, the introduction of the nuclear atom led to the Bohr theory and, almost fifty years ago, to the development of quantum mechanics. Meanwhile properties of nuclei, especially the radioactive ones, were being studied and isotopic species were being elucidated. The whole subject of nuclear physics blossomed out in the early thirties with the discovery of the positive electron and the neutron and the advent of nuclear accelerators. By 1940 after the discovery of fission, a sizable amount of knowledge about nuclei had been assembled and was increased by intensive efforts on the large scale release of nuclear energy during World War II. This itself was a happening that had been singled out many years before by Rutherford himself as being so much moonshine. But physicists have more than once underestimated nature both in predicting what will come to pass and how complex the real world is. I can recall a distinguished

theoretical physicist saying in the mid forties that if we just understood the nucleon-nucleon interaction up to 10 million electron volts a bit better, we would have the key to nuclear forces. It soon became clear that pions and probably other unstable particles created in much higher energy interactions were involved in nuclear forces. This provided the impetus for studying nucleon interactions at high energy and for the development of high energy accelerators. The last twenty years have been spent unraveling the various excited states and unstable particles which are created at much higher energy and which are intimately connected with an understanding of the subject. The richness of nature has always been underestimated and nuclear and particle physics are no exceptions.

In many areas, but especially in the understanding of the very small and the very large, physics has been in the forefront of our understanding of nature. Some people — apparently an increasing number at present — are content to accept the behavior of nature as they see it with their own eyes. But many others, including all scientists, have a yearning to know more about why nature is the way it is or how various observed phenomena are related. This yearning prods us to dig always deeper into the atom, the atomic nucleus, excited states of nucleons and unstable particles. This urge also drives physicists and astronomers to learn more about what exists in those vast reaches of space in which we play so small a part and which contain such a wide variety of unusual objects. Many of these objects were unknown or at least unrecognized relatively few years ago. Scientific work in these and other areas has greatly affected our realization of the scope and complexity of nature, while giving us some confidence that, in the extraordinary way in which some of these observations fit together, we have a significant understanding of some parts of nature. In turn this work has added greatly to our culture and affected some of the most basic ideas of our philosophy.

As our understanding has increased, the difficulty, complexity and cost of adding to this understanding has increased very greatly. Financial support in increasing amounts especially from public funds has been essential to the development of fundamental physics in almost every area. This, of course, has brought a greatly increased

scrutiny by those who authorize the expenditures, as well as those who look at them with the thought that they could be used "more practically" or more helpfully for society, in other ways.

The real increases in support for basic science came about, however, mainly for the reason that the applications of science were vital to our technology. Technology became of major importance to industry, to the military, to transportation, to communication, to health care, to agriculture and to a host of other developments that affect our everyday lives. Then came space exploration with its enormous costs and its dependence on very highly sophisticated instrumentation. Space missions gave a fine opportunity for exciting new scientific observations and indeed some people reached the conclusion that this was the reason for space programs. Actually most of the missions could hardly have been justified even in small part entirely on their scientific contributions. These space missions were explorations on a new and very grand scale — not scientific experiments. The technical developments in this area often used some of the most recently discovered scientific findings and this technology forged an even stronger connecting link between science and technology. Along with all of these links came greater support for fundamental science because it formed the base for technology and because some scientific work led directly to new technology as a part of its own development. Inevitable the great development of technology has had an enormous impact on our society. Not all of this has been beneficial. Much of it has led to an increase in the complexity of life. For example the great developments in communication and transportation which have increased both the amount of exchange and the speed of exchange of ideas and news throughout the world, have in some ways degraded our environment. It may happen that a technological development which saves endless toil may have some effects which must be curbed in order not to become a nuisance or even a danger to society. As a result there are some people today who damn technology thoroughly and science too because of its close connection.

Things have not always been this way. I recall a story about Hilbert who, commenting to a group of students on the then often discussed hostility between science and technology remarked that this could

not possibly be true because they have nothing at all to do with one another. Indeed the separation of science and technology has played some part in the development of our Union. From the first it was named a Union of Pure and Applied Physics but historically there has been much greater emphasis on pure physics than on applied physics. This was probably both correct and inevitable many years ago but it certainly does not represent the situation today. Pure physics and applied physics are so tied together that no attempt to consider them completely separately can be successful. In looking to the future we must be increasingly aware of this close connection whether the application of physics is to another branch of science or whether it is to technology. In the former application there will be an immediate enrichment of pure physics itself and in the development of technology there may be major effects on our society as well as increases in our capabilities in pure physics.

The involvement of technology in the problems of our society and in particular the blame attached by some people to technology as the origin of many of our difficulties, poses some major problems for the future. This blame has probably been enhanced by some well meaning scientists and engineers who contrariwise believe that most of the problems of present day society can be solved by technology itself. This has sometimes been referred to as the "technological fix". It is rather unlikely that very many of the present day problems of society can be fixed by technology alone. It will usually require the solution of many other economic, social and political problems in addition. To most physicists this appears to be a journey into unknown and often disliked territory. Indeed it is true that most scientists are untutored in these areas and should realize that their views are those of laymen not experts. But this does not change the basic fact that science-based technology may be necessary but surely not sufficient for the solution of many of society's pressing problems. Those who say "Let us turn the clock back and live with the simplicity which our forefathers enjoyed" underestimate the magnitude of our present day problems and the impossibility of society doing without many of the advances that are rooted in technology. We have no chance of supporting the world population today without

employing our technology and the difficulties in the near future will be much worse. Even many of those parts of presently utilized technology which are not absolutely essential for existence would be given up with the greatest reluctance if at all.

Recently a sociologist at Harvard, Irene Taviss, has questioned whether the negative attitude of people toward technology, which we hear about constantly, is a reality. She has conducted a pilot study and contends that "the anti-technology spirit that so many commentators assure us is rampant in the land is probably a myth". Of course, this is only a preliminary study in a small part of the United States and it may not be confirmed elsewhere. Whether the anti-technology and anti-science spirit is a myth or not, it is getting a lot of attention from people who like to attribute many of society's problems to the development and widespread use of technology.

Various writers including Sir Peter Medawar and Murray Gell-Mann have pointed out that anti-science and anti-technology comments are only part of the picture. These sentiments carry still further into anti-rationality and sometimes to a growth in pseudoscience and mysticism. The astronomers have bemoaned the fact that there are many more astrologers than astronomers. The increased attention given to astrology, palm reading and various forms of magic and superstition is an evidence that the anti-rationality of those who criticize the effects of technology on our society, while probably a minority view, is a potent one and this view is shared by a significant number of educated and presumably intelligent people, especially young people. It is true that inadequate attention has often been paid to the full impact of new technical developments on society. Too little consideration has often been given to the serious effects on our environment. Too little value has been placed on preservation of the quality of our environment.

Scientists have often pointed out that they cannot be responsible for unforeseeable uses of the technology that come from scientific discoveries. Such cases are not imaginary. The early use of radio telescopes as an interferometer did not anticipate the extraordinary success of the phase-lock system which was used. This system was further developed in the long distance telemetry of the space pro-

gram. Now it is possible to use a base line roughly the earth's diameter. This leads to very high resolution of radio sources and with a point source, to distance determination on earth to 10 or 20 centimeters. Not only does this lead to new and exciting results in radio astronomy but may permit the measurement of fault motion and continent drift as never before. This same development also has major possibilities for extremely accurate navigation and may have important military applications. None of this could have seemed credible at the beginning.

Another example is the laser. The discoveries of the maser and the laser came out of an investigation to see if stimulated emission could really be observed as predicted by Einstein. The first laser was operated only a little more than ten years ago. Now we have lasers used in eye surgery, in accurate surveying and for many other purposes. Powerful lasers emitting short bursts of radiation are being applied to thermonuclear reactions. Most recently we hear that they are being used to produce laser driven implosions with the aim of producing thermonuclear energy releases in small pellets. Where this will lead is not easy to predict today, but the utilization of thermonuclear energy in the future seems to be almost certain. The energy demands due to increasing population and increasing energy use per person, even if restrained, will not be able to be met indefinitely from other sources.

The problem is and will continue to be: How can the beneficial effects of science based technology be maximized and the bad effects be minimized? This depends principally on how the technology is utilized and what care is taken by society in its exploitations. The problem will not be solved by trying to turn the clock back for science and technology. We need our science and technology desperately to solve the inevitable problems of the future.

It seems to me that physicists are beginning to think much more about the nature of the technology-society interaction and will try to understand it better. In the introduction to a report of an extended study of this subject at Harvard, Emmanuel Mesthene has summarized some of the studies that were conducted to ascertain the "degree to which technological change determines social change".

He concludes that the technologies which are developed and applied depend on institutions and values prevalent in society at any given time but that technological innovation provides society with new capabilities and not all of its consequences can be foreseen. He refers to social changes as a second order effect of technological change and one might extend this to make it a third order effect of scientific change or discovery. These higher order effects are still significant. It is interesting that he rejects the idea that the technological developments determine the nature of society.

Others in the social sciences take a much more negative attitude toward all technology and are critical of Mesthene. They lose sight of the dependence that we have today on technological developments for the continued existence of our present day society. Rather, they take the wholly negative view that the impact of technology on society has such disagreeable results that technology and science too should be curbed and not developed further. While this is certainly a minority view, scientists would be wise to pay more attention to the applications of science in the future.

If we look at our Union this means that we should take applied science seriously. In the relations with other fields of science, we will gain by broadening and enriching pure physics. In recent years some of the exciting interdisciplinary new fields have grown up in Special Committees outside the Unions. Some of these Special Committees involve the subject matter of many Unions and have built up a body of knowledge of their own too. In our Union we have not always carried out our obligations in keeping in close communication with the work of these Committees. This has led to some cases in which research under some of our own Commissions is no longer fully representative of the subjects with which they are concerned. Some physicists find that the only way in which they can communicate with other physicists who work in new fields is to do so outside the Union. I am not proposing that fields of research covered by Special Committees should be allocated to one Union or another. Special Committees have often been able to get support for their work more easily just because they were set up around a particular project. Partly for this reason the trend for many years has been for much

of the interdisciplinary work to go on without very close ties to related work in the Unions. The result is that small areas of science become isolated from the more general fields of which they are a part. Some of this separation may be inevitable with the large number of new interdisciplinary fields that have sprung up. It would be helpful to our Union and to the Special Committees if we put a greater effort into the communication and liaison with related Special Committees. The use or application of physics to other sciences is increasingly important to science as a whole.

The applications to technology and in particular the effects that these may have on our society are much more difficult problems, and these are today imperfectly understood. We physicists need to understand these effects and their reaction back on science more clearly. We can't be responsible for all the unforeseen consequences of science and technology but we surely must be more sensitive and understanding of possible consequences. There will inevitably be vigorous arguments as to whether the net effect of a particular development is beneficial or injurious and criteria for judgement will vary. It is not an easy task. But it is one in which physicists have both an obligation to society and a considerable amount of self-interest as well. The first problem is to improve understanding. Physicists do have something to contribute in working with these problems because of their technical content. There are also many examples of the application of scientific methods achieving success outside the fields of science. But to understand some of these problems takes knowledge in other areas as well. Perhaps the first step is to recognize this and to try to correct it.

Some of the Unions representing the sciences are by nature connected to applications which affect society. In physics this is not often the case, although a large fraction of the work in solid state and semiconductors has a close relation to industrial use and much of the work in these areas is supported by industry. Very likely there will be closer ties to industrial use in the future. It is accordingly somewhat anomalous that the relations of our Union with international engineering organizations continue to be as tenuous as they are. We do not need to incorporate technology and engineering into IUPAP but we do need to keep closer ties with the organizations which

represent these areas. Once again, this is increasingly made necessary by the involvement of physics and applied physics in technology and engineering advances, and the reaction that society has to this connection. We must know more about the applications of science and be able to understand better than we do today both the positive and the negative reactions of society to technological developments. Perhaps in time physicists will be able to exert more influence on how science is applied to technology, and to help maximize some of the beneficial effects and minimize some of the harmful consequences. During these past fifty years and especially in the past twenty years we have seen a great increase in the international exchange of ideas in physics. Our Union has had a major part in this growth especially through its sponsorship of international conferences by the various Commissions. Ease and speed of travel have greatly increased the number of international contacts that the average physicist has. These contacts and the opportunity to exchange ideas in person inevitably lead to better international understanding and this is an important result of our Union's principal activity — sponsoring international conferences.

We have now reached the point where our Union may be able to take additional steps. With the building of large new facilities for research, it has become increasingly common for research groups to travel long distances to carry on an experiment. It has been found to be much more effective for a group going to another country to collaborate in the work with physicists from the host country or the host laboratory. This international collaboration usually results in extended periods of residence and close association of the collaborating scientists. I have spoken to many physicists who have participated in such collaborative efforts and each one has been enthusiastic, particularly about the increase in international understanding that results. I hope that in the future our Union can play as important a role in the fostering of international collaboration in research as it has in the promotion of international conferences. There is still far too much red tape involved in collaborative efforts and perhaps this is an area where we can help.

We think of our Union as being truly international and there have

been many efforts to make it so. There are, however, some major gaps in our membership and, in addition, we are poorly represented among the developing countries. We need to pursue every opportunity to fill the major gaps in our membership and to make efforts to have an active participation by the physicists from important and influential nations whose role in IUPAP has been small or completely absent.

For the developing nations it is not surprising that their interest in IUPAP has not been very great. Our main activities have been in sponsoring research conferences on the latest work on the forefront of the various fields of pure physics. This is not of primary interest to the developing nations and there is no reason why it should be. The developing nations *are* interested, however, in many aspects of technology as it applies to agriculture, health care, transportation, communication and certain areas of industry just to mention a few. To follow these needs effectively, education is essential, particularly in the fundamentals that underlie these developments. In most cases some understanding of the fundamentals of physics is essential. Our ties to developing nations should be centered much more around the education that is needed in the course of their development. This is probably not the same physics education that has evolved in the more fully developed nations. We should, however, be able to utilize our experience in physics education and, with a study of the needs of the developing nations, be able to produce some very tangible assistance. This will be an easy task and it may go slowly but it seems to me to be a real challenge for our Union and especially for our Commission on Physics Education.

Looking back over our history we see some remarkable achievements in promoting international communication and exchange in physics. This has clearly resulted in an increase in understanding among the world's physicists. As we look to the future, there are many more opportunities ahead for our Union and I have tried to indicate a few of these to you today. I am confident that our Union will be able to continue its good work of the past and to extend it in the future. We can all hope and expect that our contributions to international understanding among physicists will be a growing part of that more universal understanding that is essential for world peace.

IV — SOME RESOLUTIONS PASSED BY GENERAL ASSEMBLIES

International Conferences

“For the patronage of the Union to be granted to a Conference, which implies, in principle, a subsidy from the Union fixed according to needs and available funds, it is necessary:

1. that the Executive Committee should have approved this subsidy, taking into account the future interest of the subject and other subjects proposed for Conferences;
2. that the organizers of the Conference should have, beforehand, undertaken to submit to the President of the Union the precise date, scientific programme, place of meeting, and choice of people to be invited to present the principal papers. The choice of the speakers should be made in such a way as to ensure the greatest possible *international* participation at the Conference.”

(London, 1954)

Visas

“The International Union of Pure and Applied Physics, considering that free travel possibilities of all scientists for the participation in international scientific conferences form an indispensable basis for successful international co-operation, and considering further that this question not only touches the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics, but all scientific Unions, requests the International Council of Scientific Unions:

1. to encourage its national members to take appropriate steps with their respective governments for arranging facilities for granting exit and entry visas to all scientists attending international scientific conferences;

2. to bring the problem to the notice of the United Nations with the request that a way be found for the free movement of scientists attending scientific conferences and meetings.”

(Warsaw, 1963)

Young Scientists

“In view of the desirability of providing continuity in the growth of close international contacts between physicists, the General Assembly of IUPAP considers it highly desirable to include some younger scientists among delegations to large international conferences sponsored by IUPAP in addition to leading scientists in the particular field.”

(Warsaw, 1963)

ICSU

“The General Assembly of the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics approves in principle the proposals of the reorganizing committee of ICSU, but makes the following recommendation: In order to safeguard the scientific character implied in ICSU’s name, it is highly desirable to prevent the voting power of the unions being outbalanced by the voting power of the national members in the General Assembly of ICSU. Balance could be achieved by increasing the vote of the unions and by giving each general union more votes than each specialized union. It is realized that, as the number of unions and nations adhering to ICSU increases, the voting procedure will need modification.”

(Warsaw, 1963)

Scientific Papers

“Every scientific paper, with the possible exception of short letters,

should be published with a synopsis (or abstract) in English, French or Russian. It is desirable to print it also in a second language.”

(Warsaw, 1963)

Publications

“The General Assembly approves:

1. The Guide for the Preparation of Author's Abstracts for publication with authorization to make some modifications in order to achieve accord with UNESCO;
2. The Guide for the Preparation of Scientific Papers for Publication with authorization to make some modification in order to achieve accord with UNESCO;
3. The statement on Bibliographic References on the second page of the Commission report;
4. The following statement on publication of conference proceedings: The assembly of collections of preprints for the participants does not constitute satisfactory publication of the proceedings of a conference. It is highly desirable that conference proceedings should be refereed in the same way as journal articles. When the proceedings are published as a unit, rather than by separate submission of the papers to appropriate journals, publication should be in a regular or special issue of a journal or in a book which will be made widely available through established channels.

A paper may be included in the proceedings of a conference, even though it may have been published first as a journal article. In this case, the bibliographic reference should be given. The published proceedings should be covered by the abstracting services, and conference secretaries should assume responsibility for bringing them to the attention of the abstract journals.

The General Assembly recommends:

5. The adoption of a single standard for Journal Title Abbrevia-

tions and, to that effect, draws the attention of ISO to the work of Committee Z-29 of the American Standards Association.”

(Basle, 1966)

Physics Education

“Considering that:

1. advances in the rapidly growing fields of pure and applied Physics not only deepen mankind’s understanding of the universe, but through their applications have profound implications for human welfare and destiny;
2. discoveries in Physics, the most basic of the natural sciences, strongly affect all of the basic and applied sciences and the professions related to them;
3. the teaching of Physics to advanced students of physics, to students in related scientific and professional fields, and to those who will become part of an enlightened citizenry can only be done well by those who are themselves active in creating or in using new knowledge; and
4. research reaches its culmination in the communications of new knowledge to others, and employers should recognize the importance of evaluation and synthesis of existing knowledge which often require depth of insight and creativity at least as great as primary research:

the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics resolves that:

1. Research and education be carried on in the closest possible association;
2. Any tendencies toward divergence between the activities of advancing and of disseminating knowledge be vigorously counteracted and efforts to improve the teaching of Physics be encouraged;
3. Excellence in teaching and in the dissemination of knowledge about Physics should receive the same recognition as excellence in research. In this connexion, all sponsoring agencies and foundations

should give financial support for the preparation of critical reviews of current developments and for the compilation of critical data;

4. Talented research workers be expected to teach, and their exemption from teaching occur only in special circumstances and not as a reward for excellence;

5. Teachers be encouraged to maintain their intellectual vitality and participation in the advancement of knowledge by being given time for research or for closely related scholarly activities;

and

6. Research workers in Research Institutes and Industrial Laboratories should collaborate with Academic Institutions in the training and education of advanced students in Physics.”

(Dubrovnik, 1969)

Symbols

“ The General Assembly recommends:

that authors be encouraged to adapt the SI units for data in Physics journals as recommended by the SUN Commission, the Conférence générale des poids et mesures and the International Organization for Standardization and by other international unions closely related to Physics. Editors are urged to use persuasion rather than stronger measures to secure the cooperation of authors in the choice of symbols for physical quantities and of units, but should require that standard symbols for units be used except when the name of the units are written out in full.”

(Dubrovnik, 1969)

People's Republic of China

“Considering the importance for the work of IUPAP of having as national member the People's Republic of China, the XIVth General Assembly of IUPAP invites and authorizes, within the framework of

the IUPAP statutes, its Executive Committee to take all measures which the Committee deems necessary to achieve this goal.”

(Washington, 1972)

CODATA

“The General Assembly mindful of the importance of reliable and readily accessible physical data urges specialized commissions and other bodies associated with IUPAP to pay attention to the compilation and evaluation of data and to include, whenever appropriate, such activities in their agenda and programmes. It also requests the IUPAP representative on CODATA to study other possible modes of action with a view to increasing data activities within the Union.”

(Washington, 1972)

V — INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES

Each year, IUPAP sponsors from 20 to 25 international conferences and awards grants to some of them. Conference organizers desiring IUPAP's sponsorship should communicate with the appropriate international commission which will then make recommendations to the IUPAP Executive Committee. April of the year proceeding proposed conference is the target date by which requests should be made to commissions. The request should include the IUPAP checklist which may be obtained from commissions (it is reproduced at the end of this section) and other information as indicated in the following pages.

1. Categories

A. *General Conferences*

These would be designed to provide an overview of the entire field of interest to a Commission, and would normally occur at three-year intervals if advances in the field warrant. Attendance in the range of 750—1500 would be anticipated.

B. *Topical Conferences*

These would concentrate on broad sub-fields in the area of the particular Commission's interest (e.g. nuclear spectroscopy, nuclear reaction mechanisms, heavy ion physics in the case of the Nuclear Physics Commission). They would normally be scheduled in the years between the type A General Conferences, if the latter have been held. Attendance in the range of 300—600 would be anticipated.

C. *Special Conferences*

These would concentrate on much more restricted specialized topics than in the case of type B Conferences (e.g. angular correlations,

lifetime measurements, neutron resonance studies in the case of the Nuclear Physics Commission). These would be scheduled in the years between the type A General Conferences, if the latter are held. Attendance in the range of 50—200 would be anticipated.

2. Criteria

A. *Scientific Value*

- a) There should be a clearly demonstrated need for the proposed conference, i.e. new and important advances to be discussed since the last conference of a similar type took place;
- b) the invited speakers and the papers accepted for discussion should be of high caliber;
- c) the accepting of papers should be based on some sort of refereeing system which assures a level comparable with that of papers in the regular journals. If the proceedings of the Conference are published, every effort should be made to have them published as a special issue of a regular journal in order to make them widely and easily available to the scientific community.

B. *International Character*

- a) There should be an international committee advising on the scientific programme;
- b) the participation should be genuinely international, and not constitute effectively a national conference to which a few physicists from outside the country are invited. Such national conferences are necessary and valuable, but do not come within the mandate of IUPAP. Organizers of conferences seeking Union sponsorship should make every effort to ensure that the attendance from outside the host country be not less than 30 % and preferable be more than 50 %;
- c) open conferences should admit physicists of any IUPAP member country. For a "closed" conference, the invitation list should

include potential contributors from all IUPAP member countries which have active programmes in the field;

- d) IUPAP will not sponsor a conference if visas are refused for travel to it purely on grounds of nationality or citizenship. It is understood that request for sponsorship implies that the host country makes timely entrance possible for every scientist recommended for participation by the international committee (a).

C. *Organization*

- a) The Conference should have the approval of the relevant international Commission of IUPAP, and thus pertinent details should be submitted by the month of April of the year prior to that in which the conference is to be held;
- b) it is important that the precise dates, address of the Conference and name and address of the Conference Secretary or Chief Organizer be submitted to the Commission, which can sometimes then help to avoid conflicts of dates, etc.;
- c) the proposed Conference would benefit by having the approval of the National Committee for IUPAP of the most country;
- d) it is very helpful to the International Commission to have as much detail as possible about the organization and budget for the proposed Conference.

3. Other

The Union Executive meets in late September of each year, at which meeting sponsorship of conferences is decided and grants, if any, are made. Commissions should forward their recommendations to the Associate Secretary-General by July 1st, including all of the information mentioned above (2-C: Organization). The Commission's recommendations should be based on the criteria of 2-A and 2-B, and should include a classification as to category (1). Therefore, organizers of Conferences should apply to Commissions by April, in order to allow the Commission to meet (often by letter) and study the request. Re-

quests for sponsorship of conferences not falling within the domain of a Commission should be sent directly to the Associate Secretary-General.

4. Résumé of IUPAP Policy concerning the Free Circulation of Scientists

1. The free movement of scientists for international scientific purposes is one of the most important aims of IUPAP. The Union will continue to press in this aim even while realizing that success may never be complete.

2. In this respect, IUPAP adheres to the declarations of ICSU and has made this policy the object of repeated resolutions.

3. While one might not always expect a host country to declare in advance that *any* scientist will be admitted to any IUPAP sponsored meeting, it does seem reasonable to ask as a minimum commitment that the host country declares in advance that individuals will not be excluded solely on grounds of national origin.

The check-list which IUPAP requires from Commissions before sponsoring an international conference requests this minimum commitment.

4. The test of the sincerity of such a commitment (declared or undeclared) would be the host country's willingness to allow substitutes from the same country for any scientist whose individual application had not been allowed for reasons concerning themselves rather than their nationality.

5. If no commitment is received from official sources in the host country, IUPAP will often behave as if the declaration had been made and proceed with the planning of the conference on the basis of its own policy. In this it will be guided by recent experience in the host country concerned.

If, following this, scientists are in fact excluded from the host country on grounds of national origin, this fact is publicized in IUPAP documents, reported to the ICSU committee on the free circulation

of scientists, and extreme caution is used in considering further IUPAP events in this particular country.

6. If rather than refusing individual scientists a host country, subsequent to a conference being granted IUPAP sponsorship, issue a declaration that it will not grant visas to citizens of a particular country, then IUPAP sponsorship would normally be withdrawn.

IUPAP recognizes that scientists do not in general approve of restrictive visa problems and therefore seeks to obtain redress by correction of the situation and not by any penalizing effective or implied of the scientists in the offending country.

5. Checklist

INTERNATIONAL UNION of PURE and APPLIED PHYSICS

CHECK LIST (see IUPAP Document 17)

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES

Name of Commission:

1. Title of Conference:

Location: Date:

Organizer or Secretary: name:

address:

.....

.....

Category of Conference:

A — General Conference:

B — Topical Conference:

C — Special Conference:

2. *Scientific Value:*

: Is there a clearly demonstrated need?

: Date of last conference on subject:

: Will refereeing system assure papers of high caliber?

: Are there sufficient distinguished guest speakers?

: Approximate number:

: Examples:

.....

3. *International Character:*

: Is there an international committee advising on the scientific programme?

Name of two members:
.....

: Will participation be sufficiently international (not less than 30 %, preferably more than 50 %)?

: Will the conference be open (must admit physicists of any IUPAP member country)?

: Will the conference be by invitation (should include potential contributors from all IUPAP member countries having active programmes in field)?

: Does host country guarantee visas will not be refused on grounds of nationality or citizenship?

(Very important: see IUPAP Document 17)

4. *Organization:*

: Has this conference the approval of the Commission?

: Has this conference the support of the National Committee of the host country?

: Are there any conflicts of dates with other conferences on similar subjects?

: Is financial support requested? Amount: \$.....

: Probable total budget: \$.... Is there a registration fee? \$....

Date: per:

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(39)

LIST OF NATIONAL COMMITTEES (39)

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Votes: Number of votes at the General Assembly

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4	3	Belgium	M. Nève de MÉVERGNIES, Laboratoire du Centre d'Études de l'Énergie nucléaire, 2400 Mol-Donk, BELGIQUE.
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2	2	Brazil	Dr. A. M. COUCEIRO, Conselho Nacional de Pesquisas, Avenida Marechal Camara 350, Rio de Janeiro G. B., BRAZIL

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| 8 | 4 | Canada | Dr I. M. TEMPLETON, Division de Physique pure, Groupe de Physique des Métaux, Conseil national de Recherches, Ottawa K1A OR6, CANADA. |
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| 3 | 2 | Czechoslovakia | Dr. J. FISCHER, Institute of Physics, CSAV, Na Slovance 2, 180 40 Prague 8, CZECHOSLOVAKIA. |
| 3 | 2 | Denmark | Prof. S. ROZENTAL, Niels Bohr Institutet, 15, Blegdamsvej, Copenhagen DK-2100, DENMARK. |
| 1 | 1 | Arab Republic of Egypt | Dr. S. R. HADDARA, Academy of Scientific Research and Technology, 101 Kasr El-Eini Street, Cairo, (ARAB REPUBLIC OF EGYPT). |
| 1 | 1 | Finland | Mr. L. LAITINEN, Vakaustoisisto, Mariank 14, Helsinki, FINLAND. |
| 12 | 5 | France | M. J. BADOZ, Laboratoire d'Optique physique, École supérieure de Physique et de Chimie industrielles, 10, rue Vauquelin, Paris 75, FRANCE. |
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| 2 | 2 | Israel | Prof. A. SHAPIRA, Faculty of Physics, The Weizmann Institute of Science, Rehovot , ISRAEL. |
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Nacional de Energia Nuclear, In-
surgentes 1079.3, Mexico 18 D. F. ,
MEXICO. |
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P. O. Box 56, Dunedin , NEW
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ger, Det Norske Videnskaps-Aka-
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Satellite Town, Rawalpindi , WEST
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of Physics, Hoza 69, Warszawa ,
POLAND. |
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for Atomic Physics, P. O. Box 35,
Bucharest , ROMANIA. |
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AFRICA. |
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2	2	Switzerland	Prof. H. H. STAUB, Physik-Institut der Universität, Schönberggasse 9, Zürich 8001, SWITZERLAND.
1	1	<u>Taiwan</u>	Dr. Y. K. TAI, President — The Physical Society, P. O. Box 2330, Taipei, TAIWAN.
18	5	United States of America	Mr. R. Y. DOW, Division of Physical Sciences, National Academy of Sciences, 2101 Constitution Avenue N. W., Washington, D C. 20418, USA.
12	5	USSR	Dr. B. A. LESHKOVSTEV, Academy of Sciences of the USSR, Lenskii prospekt 14, Moscow B-71, USSR.
1	1	Yugoslavia	Prof. J. MOSER, Faculty of Science, University of Skopje, P. P. 105, 910 00 Skopje, YUGOSLAVIE.

SPECIALIZED COMMISSIONS

During the course of its history, the Union has established a number of expert committees or commissions. The purpose of these committees varies considerably. For example, one of the important ones, called Symbols, Units and Nomenclature (SUN), meets regularly and prepares recommendations on various symbols and units, as its title suggests, which are submitted for approval by the General Assembly. Several of the special committees confine their work to the organization of international conferences, for example, in magnetism, cosmic rays and various other topics.

The General Assembly of the Union appoints the members of the commissions including the chairmen and secretaries. Commissions are expected to make nominations which must be sent to the Secretary-General a few months before each General Assembly.

The 1931 General Assembly decided that the President and the Secretary-General should be *ex officio* members of all Union commissions.

The normal period of service for a member of a commission is six years. Exceptions to this rule can be made, particularly for secretaries of commissions.

The 1960 General Assembly decided that commissions should be limited to six or seven members. In addition, some corresponding or associate members can be appointed. They are to be regarded as advisers to commissions. They will receive all the appropriate commission papers and may attend meetings in the place of an absent member.

It is essential that secretaries of commissions should send copies of all the commission papers to the Secretary-General of the Union.

A Commission usually meets during an international conference held under the auspice of the commission. Some commissions, for example the SUN Commission and the Publications Commission, may need to hold special meetings from time to time.

Commissions are granted a travel allowance from Union funds for these meetings. However, it is usually necessary for members of commissions to seek additional travel grants in their respective countries in order that an adequate number of meetings may be held.

At present, there are 16 specialized commissions. The membership of these commissions is given below. The date after each name is the year of the person's appointment to his class of membership. A summary of the activities of each Commission was deposited with the Secretary-General at the Dubrovnik General Assembly. Highlights are to be found in Appendix II of the Minutes of this meeting. Inquiries concerning the work of commissions should be addressed to the appropriate chairmen or secretaries.

1 — FINANCIAL COMMISSION

Prof. H. MAIER-LEIBNITZ, Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, Kennedyallee 40, **5300 Bonn-Bad Godesberg 1**, BRD.

Prof. L. PAL, Central Research Institute, Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Postfach 49, **Budapest 114**, HUNGARY.

2 — COMMISSION for SYMBOLS, UNITS, NOMENCLATURE (S.U.N.) (1931)

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Prof. E. RUDBERG (1954), The Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, **S-10405 Stockholm 50**, SWEDEN.

Secretary:

Prof. Dr. U. STILLE (1954), Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt, Bundesallee 100, **D-33 Braunschweig**, BRD.

Members:

A. BRAY (1972), Istituto di Metrologia, "G. Colonnetti", Strada delle Cacce 73, **Torino**, ITALIA.

J. de BOER (1948), Instituut voor Theoretische Fysica, Universiteit van Amsterdam, Valckenierstraat 65, **Amsterdam-O**, NETHERLANDS.

R. G. CHAMBERS (1972), H. H. Wills Physics Laboratories, University of Bristol, Royal Fort — Tundall Avenue, **Bristol BS8 1TL**, ENGLAND.

E. DJAKOV (1969), Institute of Electronics, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Blvd. "Lenin" no 152, **Sofia**, BULGARIA.

D. ILKOVIC (1969), Katedra Fyziky, Elektrotechnickej, Fakulty SVST, **Bratislava** — Frana Krala 25, CZECHOSLOVAKIA.

I. I. NUVIKOV (1966), Chkalova 41/2, **Moscow**, USSR.

L. ROSENFELD (1963), † Nordita, Blegdamsvej 17, **D1-2100 Copenhagen**, DENMARK.

J. ROSSEL (1959), Institut de Physique, Université de Neuchâtel, Appart. Chantemerle 3, **Neuchâtel Ch-2000**, SUISSE.

L. VILLENA (1969), Serrano 121, **Madrid 6**, SPAIN.

H. C. WOLFE (1957), American Institute of Physics, 335 East, 45th Street, **New York**, N.Y. 10017, USA.

Associates:

IUPAC:

M. L. McGLASHAN, Chemistry Department, Exeter University, **Exeter**, Devonshire, UNITED KINGDOM.

BIPM:

J. TERRIEN, Bureau international des Poids & Mesures, Pavillon de Breteuil, **Sèvres F-92**, FRANCE.

3 — COMMISSION on THERMODYNAMICS and STATISTICAL MECHANICS (1945)

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Secretary:

Prof. P. MAZUR (1966), Instituut-Lorentz voor Theoretische Natuurkunde, Nieuwsteeg 18, **Leiden**, NETHERLANDS.

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G. BOATO (1972), Istituto di Fisica dell'Università, Viale Benedetto XV, 5, **Genova, ITALIA.**

H. R. CALLEN (1972), Department of Physics, University of Pennsylvania, **Philadelphia, Penn. USA.**

H. HAKEN (1972), Tech. Universität Stuttgart, Azenbergstrasse 12, **D-7 Stuttgart, BRD.**

C. HEMMER (1972), Institute of Physics, Norges Tekniske Høgskole, **Trondheim, NORWAY.**

B. JANCOVICI (1972), Lab. de Physique théorique, Bâtiment 211, Université de Paris, **91 Orsay, FRANCE.**

C. G. KUPER (1972), Technion-Israel Inst. of Tech., Department of Physics, Kuryat Hatechion, Nave Sheanan, **Haifa, ISRAEL.**

P. T. LANDSBERG (1972), Dept. of Applied Maths. and Math. Physics, University College, P.O. Box 78, **Cardiff CF1 1XL, WALES.**

H. MORI (1972), Department of Physics, Faculty of Science, Kyushu University, Hakozaki-cho, **Fukunka, JAPAN.**

P. SZEPEFALUSY (1972), Inst. for Theoretical Physics, Roland Eotvos University, Puskin utco 5-7, **Budapest VIII, HUNGARY.**

4 — COMMISSION on COSMIC RAYS (1947)

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Senorita R. GALL, National University, **Mexico City**, MEXICO.

J. GIERULA, Institute of Nuclear Physics, Laboratory of Cosmic Rays, ul. Radzikowskiego 152, **Krakow 23**, POLAND.

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A. H. COOKE (1972), Clarendon Laboratory, **Oxford**, ENGLAND.

B. DREYFUS (1969), Centre de Recherches sur les très basses températures, CNRS, Boîte postale 166, **Grenoble 38042**, FRANCE.

W. J. HUISKAMP (1972), Kamerlingh Onnes Laboratorium, University of Leiden, Nieuwsteeg 18, **Leiden**, NETHERLANDS.

W. KLOSE (1972), Dept. of Theoretical Solid State Physics, Universität, **D-66 Saarbrücken**, BRD.

A. K. SREEDHAR (1969), Solid State Physics Laboratory, Lucknow Road, **Delhi**, INDIA.

I. M. TEMPLETON (1972), Metal Physics Group, Physics Division, National Research Council, **Ottawa, K1A OR6**, CANADA.

M. TINKHAM (1972), Physics Department, Harvard University, **Cambridge, Mass 02138** USA.

6 — COMMISSION on PUBLICATIONS (1949)

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J. HAMILTON (1972), Nordita, Blegd^aemsvej 17, **Copenhagen DK-2100, DENMARK.**

R. HEARING (1972), Department of Physics, Simon Fraser University, **Vancouver, CANADA.**

K. KINOSITA (1966), Department of Physics, Gakushuin University, 1-5 Mejiro — Toshima-ku, **Tokyo, JAPAN.**

J. KVASNICA (1972), Faculty of Maths. and Physics, Charles University, Ke Karlovu 3, Praha, **CZECHOSLOVAKIA.**

E. M. LIFSHITS (1969), Vorobyovskoe shosse 2, **Moscow B-334, USSR.**

A. W. K. METZNER (1972), Publications Division, American Institute of Physics, 335 East 45th Street, **New York, N.Y. 10017, USA.**

N. R. NILSSON (1972), Physics Department, University of Uppsala, Box 530, **S-571 21 Uppsala 1, SWEDEN.**

P. PAPALI (1969), "Il Nuovo Cimento", c/o Società Italiana di Fisica, via L. degli Andalò 2, **Bologna 40124, ITALIA.**

Associate:

From ICSU-AB: J. ZIMAN, Physics Department, Bristol University, **Bristol, UNITED KINGDOM.**

7 — COMMISSION ON ACOUSTICS (1951)

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J. IGARASHI (1972), Inst. of Space and Aeronautical Science, University of Tokyo, 4—16 Sakudairai — Nerima, **Tokyo**, JAPAN.

F. KOLMER (1966), Res. Inst. of Sound and Picture, Provaznicka 8, **Praha 1**, CZECHOSLOVAKIA.

A. LARA (1969), Centro de Investigaciones Físicas, Serrano 144, **Madrid 6**, ESPANA.

A. RIMSKII-KORSAKOV (1969), Acoustical Institute, ul. Shvernika 4, **Moscow**, USSR.

E. A. G. SHAW (1972), Physics Division, National Research Council, **Ottawa K1A OR6, CANADA.**

F. TARNOCZY (1969), Acoustics Research Group, Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Puskin u. 5—7, **Budapest VIII, HUNGARY.**

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From IUTAM: M. G. LIGHTHILL, Imperial College, Prince Consort Road, **London SW7, ENGLAND.**

IUPAB: Pending.

IUBS: Vacant.

IUPS: S. IURATO, Cattedra di Istologia ed Embriologia generale dell'Università di Bari, Istituto di Anatomia Umana Policlinico, **Bari, ITALY.**

8 — COMMISSION ON SEMICONDUCTORS (1957)

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Prof. V. M. TUCHKEVICH (1972), Institute of Technical Physics, Politechnicheskaya 26, **Leningrad, USSR.**

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C. HILSUM (1972), Physics and Electronics Department, Royal Radar Establishment, **Malvern**, Worcestershire, ENGLAND.

E. O. KANE (1969), Bell Telephone Laboratories, P. O. Box 261, Room 1D-242, **Murray Hill**, N. J. 07974, USA.

H. KAWAMURA (1969), Department of Physics, Osaka University, Toyonaka, **Osaka**, JAPAN.

O. MADELUNG (1972), Institute for Theoretical Physics (II), University Marburg, Mainzer Gasse 33, **D-3550 Marburg/Lahn**, BRD.

A. MANY (1972), Section V, Racah Institute of Physics, The Hebrew University, **Jerusalem**, ISRAEL.

9 — COMMISSION ON MAGNETISM (1957)

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A. BLANDIN (1969), Laboratoire de Physique des Solides, Université Paris-Sud, Bâtiment 510, **Orsay 91**, FRANCE.

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J. KANAMORI (1972), Department of Physics, Faculty of Sciences, Osaka University, Toyonaka, **Osaka 560**, JAPAN.

W. LOW (1972), Microwave Division, The Racah Inst. of Physics, Danciger "B" Bldg., The Hebrew University, **Jerusalem**, ISRAEL.

L. PAL (1972), Hungarian Academy of Science, Central Research Institute for Physics, P. O. B. 49, **Budapest 114**, HUNGARY.

R. STREET (1972), Physics Department, Monash University, Clayton, **Victoria 3168**, AUSTRALIA.

E. A. TUROV (1972), Institute of Physics of Metals, Sofia Kovalenskaya str. 18, **Sverdlovsk K-66**, USSR.

E. R. WOHLFARTH (1972), Department of Mathematics, Imperial College, Prince Consort Road, **London S. W. 7**, ENGLAND.

W. ZINN (1972), Kernforschungsanlage Jülich GMBH, Institut 4: Magnetimus, **517 Jülich**, BRD.

10 — COMMISSION ON SOLID STATE PHYSICS (1960)

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R. BLINC (1969), Institute "J. Stefan", **Ljubljana** (Jamova 39), **YUGOSLAVIA.**

J. A. E. DIEHL (1972), The Max-Planck Inst. for Metals Research, Seestrasse 95, **D-7 Stuttgart, BRD.**

H. EHRENREICH (1972), Div. of Eng. and Applied Physics, Harvard University, **Cambridge, Mass., USA.**

F. FUMI (1972), Istituto Nazionale de Fisica Nucleare, Università di Genova, Viale Benedetto XV, **Genova, ITALIA.**

S. C. JAIN (1969), Solid State Physics Laboratory, Ministry of Defence, Lucknow Road — **Delhi 7, INDIA.**

L. V. KELDYSH (1972), Fizika-Tehnicsezskij Insztitut, Academy of Sciences of the USSR, Politechnicheskaja ul. 26, **Leningrad K-21, USSR.**

A. KELLER (1972), H. H. Wills Physics Laboratories, University of Bristol, Royal Fort, Tyndall Avenue **Bristol BS8 1TL, ENGLAND.**

G. K. WHITE (1972), National Standards Laboratory, University Grounds, **Chippendale, NSW 2008, AUSTRALIA.**

Associate:

From IUCr: J. M. COWLEY (1969), Dept. of Physics, Arizona State University, **Tempe, Arizona 85281, USA.**

11 — COMMISSION on PARTICLES and FIELDS (1957)

Chairman:

Prof. C. N. YANG (1969), Inst. for Theoretical Physics, State University of New York at Stony Brook, **Stony Brook, N.Y. 11790, USA.**

Secretary:

Prof. G. SALVINI (1969), Istituto Fisica Università, Piazzale delle Scienze 5, **Rome 00185, ITALIA.**

Members:

G. EKSPONG (1969), Institute of Physics, The University of Stockholm, Vanadisvägen 9, **S-113 46 Stockholm, SWEDEN.**

E. L. GOLDWASSER (1972), National Accelerator Laboratory, P.O. Box 500, **Batavia, Ill. 60510, USA.**

B. P. GREGORY (1972), Lab. de Physique nucléaire des hautes énergies, École Polytechnique, 17 rue Descartes, **Paris Ve, FRANCE.**

H. JOOS (1969), Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron DESY, University of Hamburg, Notkestieg 1, **D-2 Hamburg 52, BRD.**

A. A. LOGUNOV (1969), Institute of High Energy Physics, **Serpukhov, USSR.**

Y. NE'EMAN (1969), Department of Physics, Tel-Aviv University, Ramat-Aviv, **Tel-Aviv, ISRAEL.**

P. PNIEWSKI (1969), Institute of Experimental Physics, University of Warsaw, Hoza 69, **Warszawa, POLAND.**

G. TAKEDA (1972), Department of Physics, Tohoku University, Katahira-cho, **Sendai, JAPAN.**

A. N. TAVHELIDZE (1972), Joint Institute for Nuclear Research, Head Post Office, P.O. Box 79, **Moscow, USSR.**

B. M. UDGAONKAR (1968), Tata Institute of Fundamental Research, Homi Bhabha Road, Colaba, **Bombay 5, INDIA.**

12 — COMMISSION on NUCLEAR PHYSICS (1960)

Chairman:

Madame H. FARAGGI-MATHIEU (1972), Département de Physique nucléaire, Commissariat de l'Energie atomique, 53 rue Fontaine-Grelot, **Bourg-la-Reine F-92**, FRANCE.

Secretary:

Prof. J. L. FOWLER (1966), Physics Division, Oak Ridge National Laboratory, P.O. Box X, **Oak Ridge**, Tenn. 37830, USA.

Members:

F. AJZENBERG-SELOVE (1972), Department of Physics, University of Pennsylvania, **Philadelphia**, Penn. 19104, USA.

E. BAUMGARTNER (1969), Physikalisches Institut der Universität, Klingelbergstrasse 82, **Basel 4000**, SWITZERLAND.

E. M. FRANK (1967), Academy of Sciences of the USSR, Leninskii prospekt 14, **Moscow B-71**, USSR.

B. MOTTELSON (1972), NORDITA, Blegdamsvej 17, **Copenhagen DK-2100**, DENMARK.

T. MAYER-KUCKUK (1972), Radiation and Nuclear Physics Inst., Faculty of Math. and Natural Sciences, University Bonn, Nullallee 14—16, **D-53 Bonn**, BRD.

M. PETRASCU (1972), Institute for Atomic Physics, P.O. Box 35, **Bucharest**, ROMANIA.

R. A. RICCI (1969), Istituto di Fisica G. Galilei, University of Padua, Via Marzolo 8, **Padova 35100**, ITALIA.

M. SAKAI (1969), Institute for Nuclear Study, University of Tokyo, Midori-cho 3-2-1 — Tanashi-shi, **Tokyo**, JAPAN.

I. ULEHLA (1972), Department of Theoretical Physics, Faculty of Math. and Physics, Charles University, V luhu 14, **Praha 14**, CZECHOSLOVAKIA.

J. C. WILLMOTT (1972), Physics Department, Schuster Laboratory, The University, **Manchester M13 9PL**, ENGLAND.

13 — COMMISSION on ATOMIC MASSES and FUNDAMENTAL CONSTANTS (1960)

Chairman:

Dr. E. R. COHEN (1966), Science Center, Aerospace and Systems Group, North American Rockwell Corp., 1049 Camino dos Rios, **Thousand Oaks**, Calif. 91360, USA.

Secretary:

Dr. W. H. JOHNSON (1966), School of Physics, University of Minnesota, **Minneapolis**, Minn. 55455, USA.

Members:

R. C. BARBER (1972), Department of Physics, University of Manitoba, **Winnipeg**, CANADA.

V. I. GOLDANSKY (1972), Inst. of Chemical Physics, Academy of Sciences of the USSR, Vorobyevskoe shosse 2b, **Moscow B-334**, USSR.

K. OGATA (1966), 1-1 Machikaneyama-cho, Toyonaka-shi, **Osaka-fu**, JAPAN.

J. H. SANDERS (1969), Clarendon Laboratory, Oxford University, **Oxford** UNITED KINGDOM.

H. H. STAUB (1966), Physik-Institut der Universität, Schonberggasse 9, **Zurich 8001**, SWITZERLAND.

U. STILLE (1960), Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt, Bundesallee 100, **D-33 Braunschweig**, BRD.

J. TERRIEN (1966), Bureau int. des Poids et Mesures, Pavillon de Breteuil, **Sèvres F-92**, FRANCE.

A. H. WAPSTRA (1960), Institute for Nuclear Physics Research, Oosterringdijk 18, Postbus 4395, **Amsterdam 1006**, NETHERLANDS.

14 — COMMISSION on PHYSICS EDUCATION (1960)

Chairman:

Dr. W. C. KELLY (1966), National Research Council, 2101 Constitution Avenue N.W., **Washington**, D.C. 20418, USA.

Secretary:

Prof. J. L. LEWIS (1969), Science Department, Malvern College, **Malvern**, Worcestershire, ENGLAND.

Members:

G. DELACOTE (1972), École normale supérieure, 24, rue Lhomond, **Paris 75**, FRANCE.

E. FERREIRA (1972), Dept. Physics-Pontificia, Universidade Católica, **Rio de Janeiro**, BRASIL.

A. P. FRENCH (1972), Department of Physics, Room 20-C-224, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, **Cambridge**, Mass. 02139, USA.

A. HARASHIMA (1969), International Christian University, **Mitaka**, **Tokyo**, JAPAN.

L. S. KOTHARI (1969), 5 University Road, **Delhi**, INDIA.

W. KROEBEL (1969), Department of Applied Physics, University of Kiel, Neue Universität Haus 34, Olshausenstrasse, D-23 Kiel, BRD.

A. N. MATVEYEV (1972), Physics Department, Moscow State University, Moscow, USSR.

E. NAGY (1969), Institute for Solid State Physics, Eötvös University, Muzeum krt. 6-8, Budapest VIII, HUNGARY.

J. WERLE (1969), Dept. of Mathematics and Physics, Warsaw University, Warsaw, POLAND.

15 — COMMISSION on ATOMIC & MOLECULAR PHYSICS and SPECTROSCOPY (1966)

Chairman:

Dr. L. M. BRANSCOMB (1966), Chief Scientist and Vice-President, IBM Corporate Headquarters, Armonk, N.Y., USA.

Secretary:

Prof. H. L. WELSH (1969), Physics Department, University of Toronto, Toronto 181, CANADA.

Members:

J. BROSSEL (1972), Laboratoire de Physique, École normale supérieure, 24 rue Lhomond, Paris 75, FRANCE.

A. GOZZINI (1972), University of Pisa, Via Nazario Sauro 22, Pisa, ITALIA.

J. B. HASTED (1972), Physics Department, Birkbeck College, Malet Street, London WC1C 7HU, ENGLAND.

J. H. HERTZ (1969), Zentralinstitut für Optik und Spektroskopi, Rudower Chaussee 5, DDR-1199 Berlin-Adlershof, DDR.

R. N. ILIIN (1972), Physico-Technical Institute, Polytechnical str. 26, **Leningrad K-21**, USSR.

I. KOVACS (1969), Department of Atomic Physics, Polytechnical University, XI. Budafoki ut 8, **Budapest 112**, HUNGARY.

G. zu PUTLITZ (1972), I. Phys. Institut University, Philosophenweg 12, **D-69 Heidelberg**, BRD.

T. SKALINSKI (1969), Institute of Physics, Polish Academy of Sciences, Al. Lotnikow 32/46, **Warszawa**, POLAND.

K. TAKAYANAGI (1969), Institute of Space and Aeronautical Sc., University of Tokyo, Komaba — Meguro-ku, **Tokyo**, JAPAN.

A. WALSH (1969), Division of Chemical Physics, David Rivett Laboratory, C.S.I.R.O., P.O. Box 160, Clayton, **Victoria 3168**, AUSTRALIA.

16 — COMMISSION on PLASMA PHYSICS (1969)

Chairman:

Prof. S. C. BROWN (1966), Department of Physics, Room 20A-125, Massachusetts Inst. of Technology, **Cambridge, Mass. 02139**, USA.

Secretary:

Dr. R. S. PEASE (1969), Culham Laboratory, **Culham**, Abingdon, Berkshire, ENGLAND.

Members:

C. M. BRAAMS (1969), FOM-Instituut voor plasma-fysica, **Rijnhuizen-Jutphaas**, NETHERLANDS.

B. BRUNELLI (1969), Laboratori Gas Ionizzati, CNEN, **Frascati**, ITALIA.

J. L. DELCROIX (1969), Division de Physique des Plasmas, Université de Paris-Sud, **90 Orsay**, FRANCE.

G. ECKER (1972), Division of Theoretical Physics, Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Buschey Str., **D-463 Bochum-Querenburg**, BRD.

M. B. GOTTLIEB (1972), Plasma Physics Laboratory, Forrestal Research Center, P. O. Box 451, **Princeton**, N. J. 08540, USA.

J. KRACIK (1972), Department of Physics, Fac. El. eng. Czech. Techn. Univ., Ceskomalinski 17, **Praha 6**, CZECHOSLOVAKIA.

I. POPESCU (1969), Institute of Physics, **Bucharest**, ROMANIA.

L. ROTHHARDT (1969), Deutsche Akademie der Wissenschaften, Zentralinstitut für Elektronenphysik, Institutsteil VI — Magnetoplasmadynamik, Fröbelstieg 3, **DDR-69 Jena**, DDR.

R. Z. SAGDEEV (1972), Institute of High Temperatures, USSR Academy of Sciences, Leninsky Prospect 14, **Moscow B-71**, USSR.

E. S. WEIBEL (1969), Centre de Recherche en Physique des Plasmas, Avenue des Bains 21, **Lausanne 1007**, SUISSE.

Associate:

From the International Scient. Committee on Ionized Gases: R. F. FRANKLIN, Clarendon Laboratory, Oxford University, **Oxford**, UNITED KINGDOM.

IUPAP DELEGATES to INTER-UNION COMMISSIONS

I.1 — International Council of Scientific Unions (ICSU)

H. MAIER-LEIBNITZ (1972), Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, Kennedyallee 40, **5300 Bonn-Bad Godesberg 1**, BRD.

I.2 — Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research (SCOR)

Sir E. BULLARD (1966), Department of Geodesy and Geophysics, Madingley Road, **Cambridge**, UNITED KINGDOM.

I.3 — Special Commission for Space Research (COSPAR)

B. PETERS (1972), Danish Space Research Institute, Lundtoftevej 7, **Lyngby 2800**, DENMARK.

I.4 — Inter-Union Commission on Solar Terrestrial Physics (IUCSTP)

B. PETERS (1972), Danish Space Research Institute, Lundtoftevej 7, **Lyngby 2800**, DENMARK.

I.5 — ICSU — CODATA

N. KURTI (1972), Department of Physics, Parks Road, Oxford University, **Oxford, OXI 3PU**, UNITED KINGDOM.

I.6 — IUPAC — Polymers

G. W. BECKER (1972), Bundesanstalt für Materialprüfung, Unter den Eichen 87, **D-1 Berlin 45**, BRD.

I.7 — ICSU — Abstracting Board

J. ZIMAN (1972), Physics Department, Bristol University, **Bristol**, UNITED KINGDOM.

I.8 — Committee on the Teaching of Sciences (ICSU)

H. H. STAUB (1969), Institut de Physique, Université de Zurich, Schonberggasse 9, **Zurich 8001**, SUISSE.

I.9 — European Physical Society

C. C. BUTLER (1972), Nuffield Lodge, Regents Park, **London NW1 4RS**, ENGLAND.

I.10 — **SCOPE**

A. LARA (1972), Centro de Investigaciones Fisicas, Serrano 144, **Madrid 6**, ESPANA.

I.11 — **ICO**

T. SKALINSKI (1972), Institute of Physics, Polish Academy of Sciences, Al. Lotnikow 32/46, **Warszawa**, POLAND.

I.12 — **ICSU — Spectroscopy Committee**

G. HERZBERG (1966), Division de Physique pure, Conseil national de Recherches, **Ottawa 7**, CANADA.

A. KASTLER (1966), Laboratoire de Physique, École normale supérieure, 24, rue Lhomond, **Paris 75**, FRANCE.

W. C. PRICE (1966), Physics Department, King's College, Strand, **London W. C. 2**, UNITED KINGDOM.

I.13 — **Bureau International des Poids et Mesures**

J. deBOER, Instituut voor Theoretische Fysica, Universiteit van Amsterdam, Valckenierstraat 65, **Amsterdam-O**, NETHERLANDS.

I.14 — **IUPAC Units Committee**

U. STILLE, Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt, Bundesallee 100, **D-33 Braunschweig**, BRD.

I.15 — **Committee on Science and Technology in Developing Countries (COSTED)**

S. BHAGAVANTAM, Indian Institute of Science, **Bangalore 560012**, INDIA.

L'UNION INTERNATIONALE DE LA PHYSIQUE
PURE ET APPLIQUÉE

I U P A P

RAPPORT GÉNÉRAL

1973

UNION INTERNATIONALE DE LA PHYSIQUE
PURE ET APPLIQUÉE

INFORMATION GÉNÉRALE

RAPPORT DE LA XIV^{ème}
ASSEMBLÉE GÉNÉRALE
WASHINGTON DC, 1972

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I — FONCTIONNEMENT DE L'UNION

L'histoire de l'Union internationale de Physique pure et appliquée est résumée dans huit publications antérieures (documents IUPAP 1, 2, 4, 5, 7, 8, 10 et 14).

L'Union est constituée par les comités nationaux de Physique ou associations de physiciens des divers pays adhérents. Ces comités délèguent des membres aux Assemblées générales de l'Union qui ont lieu tous les trois ans. L'Assemblée générale pourvoit à l'élection du bureau d'administration, à la nomination des diverses commissions spéciales et à la désignation de ses représentants auprès de plusieurs comités groupant les différentes unions scientifiques.

Les Assemblées générales antérieures ont eu lieu à Bruxelles (1923 et 1925), à Paris (1931 et 1947), à Londres (1934 et 1954), à Varsovie (1963), à Bâle (1969), à Dubrovnik (1969), et à Washington, D.C. (1972). Le Comité exécutif se réunit une fois par année.

L'union est rattachée au Conseil international des Unions scientifiques (C.I.U.S.). Le Conseil est constitué en ce moment de 17 unions et d'une soixantaine de délégués nationaux. Le Président du Conseil est le Professeur J. Coulomb (France) et le Secrétaire-général est le Professeur F. A. Stafleu (Pays-Bas). Les bureaux administratifs se trouvent à Paris (51, Bd de Montmorency, 75016 Paris, France).

L'Assemblée générale du C.I.U.S. est constituée par des représentants des unions scientifiques et des délégués nationaux. A l'avenir, cette assemblée se réunira tous les deux ans.

En 1946, le C.I.U.S. a conclu un accord avec l'Organisation des Nations-Unies pour l'Éducation, la Science et la Culture (UNESCO). Cet accord permet aux unions scientifiques d'obtenir, par l'intermédiaire du C.I.U.S., des subventions à l'intention des congrès internationaux.

L'utilisation des subventions de l'UNESCO est soumise aux conditions suivantes:

- i) l'UNESCO doit être renseignée au sujet des conférences afin de pouvoir, le cas échéant, y déléguer un représentant;
- ii) l'UNESCO entend que son appui soit mentionné sur la couverture de toutes les publications faites par des organismes ayant bénéficié de subventions à cet effet. La formule suivante est recommandée: "Publié avec le concours financier de l'UNESCO";
- iii) l'UNESCO demande qu'on lui envoie dix exemplaires de tous les rapports issus d'une conférence.

Des conférences et des assemblées de commissions peuvent également être subventionnées par les fonds provenant des membres nationaux de l'IUPAP. Ces fonds servent aussi à faire face aux dépenses de l'administration.

La correspondance traitant des questions financières et nationales doit être envoyée au Secrétaire-général. Cependant, la correspondance traitant les commissions et la publicité générale doit être envoyée au Secrétairegénéral adjoint.

II — STATUTS DE L'UNION

(Votés par l'Assemblée générale de 1931 et modifiés par celles de 1948 et 1954; le texte du § 5 adopté en 1960 est indiqué en *italiques*).

I. Buts de l'Union et conditions d'admission

1. L'Union a pour but:

- (i) de créer et d'encourager une coopération internationale en physique;
- (ii) de coordonner les efforts de préparation et de publication des extraits de mémoires et de tables de constantes de physique;
- (iii) de réaliser une entente internationale sur les questions d'unités, d'étalonnage, de nomenclature et de notations;
- (iv) d'aider la poursuite de recherches intéressantes.

Elle peut organiser des congrès internationaux.

Dans chaque pays, l'adhésion à l'Union peut être donnée soit par son Académie nationale, soit par son Conseil national de Recherches, soit par d'autres institutions similaires, soit par des sociétés scientifiques ou groupements de telles institutions ou sociétés, soit, à défaut de ceux-ci, par son Gouvernement.

Pour un même pays, des adhésions données séparément par plusieurs organisations distinctes ne peuvent être admises que sous la réserve d'une entente préalable entre ces organisations pour la répartition des cotisations et le partage des droits de vote.

Dans le mot pays sont compris les dominions, les protectorats diplomatiques, ainsi que les territoires ayant une activité scientifique indépendante.

II. Comités nationaux

2. Un comité national est constitué dans chacun des pays adhérents comme organisme de liaison avec l'Union. Il est créé sur l'initiative soit de son Académie nationale, soit de son Conseil national de Recherches ou d'autres institutions ou groupements d'institutions nationales similaires, soit, à défaut de ceux-ci, de son Gouvernement.

3. Les comités nationaux ont pour fonction de faciliter et de coordonner, sur leurs territoires respectifs, l'étude des diverses branches de la Physique, envisagées principalement du point de vue international. Chaque comité national soit seul, soit de concert avec un ou plusieurs autres comités nationaux, a le droit de soumettre à l'Union des questions à discuter entrant dans la compétence de celle-ci.

Les comités nationaux désignent les délégués chargés de les représenter aux assemblées de l'Union.

Ils désignent un chef de délégation qui a qualité pour voter au nom de son comité sur les questions d'ordre administratif, ainsi qu'il est prévu aux articles 14 et 16.

III. Administration de l'Union

4. Les travaux sont dirigés par l'Assemblée générale des délégués.

5. *Comité exécutif de l'Union comprend: le Président, le précédent Président, le premier Vice-président, les Vice-présidents et le Secrétaire-général. A l'exception de l'ancien président, les membres du Comité sont élus par l'Assemblée générale; ils demeurent en fonction jusqu'à la fin de l'Assemblée générale ordinaire qui suit celle de leur élection. Le premier Vice-président remplace le Président en cas d'absence de ce dernier.*

A l'exception du Secrétaire-général, les membres élus du Comité exécutif ne peuvent exercer une même fonction sans interruption pendant plus de deux périodes séparant les assemblées générales ordinaires.

Le comité exécutif peut pourvoir aux départs qui surviendraient dans son sein. Toute personne désignée dans ces conditions achève le mandat de celle qu'elle remplace.

Il existe, en outre, un *Bureau administratif* qui, sous la direction du Secrétaire-général de l'Union, expédie la correspondance, gère les ressources et assure la conservation des archives ainsi que la préparation et la distribution des publications approuvées par l'Assemblée générale.

IV. Commissions

6. L'Assemblée générale et, sous réserve d'approbation par l'Assemblée générale suivante, le Comité exécutif peuvent décider la création de commissions propres à l'Union de Physique et la participation à des *commissions mixtes*, communes à l'Union de Physique et à une ou plusieurs autres.

Parmi les commissions propres à l'Union, certaines, dites *commissions affiliées*, sont consacrées aux grands domaines de la Physique, d'autres, à objectif plus limité, sont dites *commissions spécialisées*.

Toutes les commissions doivent, par l'entremise de leur secrétaire, présenter à chaque Assemblée générale un rapport sur leurs travaux.

7. La constitution, les statuts, le fonctionnement et la situation financière des commissions *affiliées* sont soumis à l'approbation du Comité exécutif de l'Union qui doit veiller notamment à ce que leurs domaines d'action soient délimités au mieux.

Le Comité exécutif désigne un ou plusieurs de ses membres pour représenter l'Union au sein de chaque commission affiliée.

Les commissions affiliées peuvent, en plus des ressources qui leur sont affectées par l'Union, percevoir des cotisations spéciales et recevoir des dons d'autres sources.

8. Les membres des commissions *spécialisées* et les représentants de l'Union au sein des commissions mixtes sont élus par l'Assemblée

générale, après examen des propositions du Comité exécutif de l'Union. Ils restent en fonction jusqu'à la fin de l'Assemblée générale suivante et sont rééligibles.

Les commissions spécialisées peuvent s'adjoindre des membres, sous réserve d'approbation du Comité exécutif.

La désignation des membres des commissions *affiliées* en plus des représentants du Comité exécutif de l'Union de Physique prévus à l'article 7, est fixée par leurs statuts particuliers.

Le fonctionnement des commissions *mixtes* est réglé par le Conseil international des Unions scientifiques.

V. Assemblées générales

9. L'Union se réunit en principe tous les trois ans en Assemblée générale ordinaire. Si l'époque et le lieu de cette réunion n'ont pas été arrêtés par l'Assemblée générale précédente, ils sont fixés par le Comité exécutif et communiqués, quatre mois à l'avance, aux organismes adhérents.

10. Dans des cas spéciaux, le Président peut, avec le consentement du Comité exécutif, convoquer une Assemblée extraordinaire; il est tenu de la faire à la demande d'un tiers des voix des pays adhérents.

11. Tous les membres des comités nationaux peuvent assister aux réunions de l'Assemblée générale et prendre part aux discussions, mais seulement avec voix consultative.

Le Président de l'Union peut inviter des hommes de sciences, non délégués, à assister, à titre consultatif, aux séances de l'Assemblée générale.

Les membres non-délégués des commissions mentionnées à l'article 7 ont le droit d'assister, dans les mêmes conditions, aux séances de l'Assemblée générale où sont traitées les questions entrant dans leurs attributions.

12. L'ordre du jour d'une session est fixé par le Comité exécutif et communiqué au moins quatre mois avant l'ouverture de cette session. Toute question ne figurant pas à l'ordre du jour n'est prise en considération qu'avec l'assentiment préalable de la moitié au moins des voix des pays représentés à l'Assemblée générale.

VI. Congrès internationaux

13. Les congrès internationaux sont organisés par le Comité exécutif de l'Union.

VII. Budget et droit de vote

14. Le Comité exécutif prépare un budget de prévision pour chaque année de la période comprise entre deux sessions. Une Commission financière, nommée par l'Assemblée générale, est chargée de l'étude de ce budget et de la vérification des comptes de l'exercice précédent. Elle établit, sur ces deux questions, des rapports distincts qui sont soumis à l'Assemblée générale.

A la suite de cet examen financier, l'Assemblée générale fixe le taux de la part contributive unitaire (*).

Le montant de la cotisation est le produit du "taux de la part unitaire" par le nombre de "part contributives" du pays considéré. Ce nombre est fixé par le Comité exécutif, après examen des observations éventuelles du Comité national intéressé; il peut, quand cela paraît opportun, être modifié par un accord entre le Comité exécutif et le Comité national intéressé.

Il est dans tous les cas soumis à la ratification de l'Assemblée générale qui suit sa fixation ou sa modification.

Le nombre de délégués officiels de chaque pays et celui des voix attribuées à chaque délégation sont fixés par le barème suivant:

Nombre de parts
contributives: 1, 2 ou 3, 4 à 6, 7 à 9, 10 et au-dessus

*Ce taux est fixé à \$300 dollars U.S. à partir du 1er janvier 1971.

Nombre de délégués
officiels (et de voix): 1, 2, 3, 4, 5

Dans chaque pays les organismes adhérents sont responsables du paiement des cotisations.

15. Les recettes de tout ordre de l'Union provenant des contributions des divers pays sont consacrées:

- (i) à payer les frais de publications et les dépenses accessoires d'administration;
- (ii) à atteindre les buts prévus à l'article 1.

Les ressources provenant de dons sont utilisées par l'Union en tenant compte des désirs exprimés par les donateurs.

Tout pays qui se retire de l'Union abandonne de ce fait ses droits à l'actif de l'association.

16. Dans les Assemblées générales, les résolutions concernant les questions d'ordre scientifique sont prises à la majorité des voix de tous les délégués présents.

Pour les questions d'ordre administratif et pour les questions mixtes, le vote a lieu par pays, le nombre de voix de chaque pays étant fixé à l'article 14.

S'il y a doute sur la catégorie dans laquelle doit être rangée une question à discuter, le Président décide.

Dans les commissions, les décisions sont prises à la majorité des voix des membres qui les composent et non par pays.

En toutes circonstances, s'il y a égalité de voix, celle du Président est prépondérante.

17. Pour les questions administratives figurant à l'ordre du jour, un pays qui n'est pas représenté peut envoyer par écrit son vote au Président. Pour être valable, ce vote doit être reçu avant le dépouillement du scrutin.

VIII. Règlements intérieurs

18. L'Assemblée générale peut édicter des règlements intérieurs concernant soit la conduite de ses travaux, soit les devoirs généraux qui incombent aux membres du Comité exécutif, soit en général, tous objets non prévus dans les statuts.

De même, chaque Commission peut élaborer des règlements pour la conduite de ses propres travaux. Aucun de ces règlements ne peut contenir de prescriptions contraires aux termes des présents statuts.

IX. Durée de l'Union et modifications aux statuts

19. La durée de l'Union n'est pas limitée.

20. Aucun changement ne pourra être apporté aux présents statuts sans l'approbation des deux tiers des voix de l'ensemble des pays adhérents.

21. En cas de dissolution de l'Union, votée par l'Assemblée générale à la majorité des deux tiers des voix de l'ensemble des pays adhérents, les fonds disponibles seront attribués par l'Assemblée à une ou plusieurs organisations scientifiques.

22. Le présent texte français servira exclusivement pour l'interprétation à donner aux articles des présents statuts.

ANNEXE A

Procédure de Nomination des Membres des Commissions par l'Assemblée Générale

Ces articles sont conformes aux Statuts. Cependant, ils ne sont pas status eux-mêmes, mais seulement règles de procédure. Ils peuvent être adoptés ou changés par chaque Assemblée Générale.

1. Chaque Commission (sauf la Commission des Finances) consistera de:

Président
Secrétaire
5 à 10 membres.

2. Les Commissions aviseront le Comité Exécutif du nombre de Membres approprié pour leurs travaux: L'exécutif fera des recommandations à chaque Assemblée qui fixera le nombre de Membres des Commissions avant que les élections aient lieu.

3. Présidents des Commissions

Les présidents seront élus pour 3 ans, normalement après 3 (ou exceptionnellement 6) ans en tant que secrétaire ou membre ordinaire de leur Commission. Dans des circonstances exceptionnelles, un Président peut devenir un membre ordinaire de la Commission pour 3 ans après sa période en tant que Président.

4. Secrétaires des Commissions

Les Secrétaires seront élus pour 3 ans, après 3 ans de service dans la Commission. Les Secrétaires seront éligibles pour un second et final cycle de 3 ans. Pour SUN et "Atomic Masses Commissions", les Secrétaires pourront être élus après 6 ans de service dans leur Commission.

5. *Membres des Commissions*

Les membres des Commissions seront élus pour 3 ans et seront éligibles pour un autre terme de 3 ans.

Des exceptions à cette règle sont permises pour les Membres des Commissions qui ont des taches très spécialisées et indubitablement ont besoin des services de leurs Membres pour plus que 6 ans.

6. *Variété de Nationalités des Membres d'une Commission*

Les Membres de chaque Commission (à l'exception du Président et du Secrétaire) doivent tous venir de pays différents adhérents à l'IUPAP.

Le travail de quelques Commissions peut être entravé par cette règle. Elles doivent présenter leur cas à l'Exécutif et, si l'approbation est donnée, l'Exécutif fera une recommandation à L'Assemblée Générale pour la ratification avant que les élections aient lieu.

7. *Membres Associés*

Quelques Commissions ont établi des liaisons valables avec plusieurs unions scientifiques et d'autres organisations internationales. Elles peuvent désirer demander à ces organisations de nommer des experts dans ces domaines pour devenir membres associés des Commissions IUPAP. (IUPAP sera invitée à nommer des physiciens comme membres associés des Commissions établies par d'autres Unions.)

Le nombre maximum de membres associés de n'importe quelle Commission doit être normalement de quatre.

Les membres associés ne sont pas autorisés à voter aux Réunions des Commissions, pas plus qu'ils sont éligibles au soutien financier de l'IUPAP concernant voyages et dépenses de subsistance.

8. L'Exécutif reconnaît qu'il ne peut pas être possible d'appliquer toutes ces règles concernant la durée de service immédiatement en 1972.

Quand de nouvelles Commissions sont établies, des arrangements *ad hoc* auront besoin d'être effectués jusqu'à ce qu'un roulement normal des Membres puisse être établi.

9. *Procédure d'élection pour les Membres des Commissions*

9.1. Les Comités Nationaux et les Commissions seront invités à suggérer des noms de membres au Secrétaire Général (y compris pour les positions de Président et de Secrétaire) pour les Commissions à partir de quatre mois avant l'Assemblée Générale. Chaque nom proposé doit être accompagné de brefs détails de la carrière du physicien et des postes précédemment tenus, et, pour les noms proposés par les Commissions, il est souhaitable que le support du Comité National du candidat puisse être obtenu. Un formulaire spécial va être délivré dans ce but. Le Secrétaire Général (ou le Secrétaire Général Associé) fera circuler tous les noms reçus avant la date limite dans les Comités Nationaux, 3 mois avant l'Assemblée Générale.

9.2. Le Comité Exécutif considèrera tous les noms suggérés (et suggèrera lui-même des noms) et préparera par conséquent une liste des noms pour les membres des Commissions, liste qui servira de base de discussion à l'Assemblée.

En préparant les listes des noms pour les Commissions, l'Exécutif s'efforcera d'obtenir une satisfaisante propagation mondiale des candidatures à la Commission. L'Exécutif publiera sa proposition de liste des membres des Commissions aussitôt que possible mais avant le commencement de l'Assemblée Générale.

9.3. Après la publication de la liste des noms recommandés par le Comité Exécutif il peut apparaître qu'une personne ne veuille pas servir en tant que Président, Secrétaire ou membre. Dans ce cas, ou si des conseils sont reçus des Comités Nationaux ou Commissions, le Comité Exécutif fera des propositions convenables, par exemple il peut changer le nom d'un des proposés avec un des membres proposés ou même introduire un nouveau nom. La liste finale de noms du Comité Exécutif sera publiée très tôt à l'Assemblée, à temps pour la discussion générale.

- 9.4. Après la discussion générale, les délégations nationales individuelles participant à l'Assemblée auront la possibilité de réintroduire des noms sur la liste des noms suggérés et de les ajouter à la liste finale de l'Exécutif jusqu'à une date limite convenue et en utilisant des formulaires de nomination appropriés. Les noms ne figurant pas sur la liste originale peuvent seulement être introduits avec l'accord de l'Assemblée Générale. A ce stade, chaque proposition doit être secondée par une autre délégation. Si un candidat n'est pas de la même nationalité que le proposant, le candidat devra être alors proposé par sa propre délégation nationale.
- 9.5. Dans le cas de circonstances imprévues (par exemple un retrait de candidature) modifiant la liste des élus après que la limite finale soit passée, le Secrétaire Générale, après consultation avec les membres de l'Exécutif, ajoutera autant de noms qu'il est nécessaire pour compléter la liste. La liste modifiée sera présentée à l'Assemblée Générale pour ratification.
- 9.6. Si plus de noms sont inclus à la liste finale ratifiée que le nombre de places vacantes pour une ou plusieurs Commissions le permet, alors des votes secrets seront tenus. La procédure de vote sera la même que celle adoptée pour le choix des membres du Comité Exécutif. Les votes doivent être conformes au paragraphe (6).
- 9.7. La procédure pour remplir des vacances occasionnelles qui surviendraient dans la Commission entre des réunions de l'Assemblée Générale sera la même que pour des vacances occasionnelles dans le Comité Exécutif (statut 5).

ANNEXE B

Nombres de Membres pour les Commissions IUPAP pour la période 1973—75

Chaque Commission consiste d'un Président et un Secrétaire ainsi que des membres ordinaires, tous élus par l'Assemblée Générale. Le nombre des membres ordinaires est le suivant:

C. 2	SUN	10 membres
C. 3	Thermodynamics and Statistical Mechanics	10 membres
C. 4	Cosmic Rays	8 membres
C. 5	Very Low Temperature	9 membres
C. 6	Publications	10 membres
C. 7	Acoustics	10 membres
C. 8	Semiconductors	8 membres
C. 9	Magnetism	10 membres
C.10	Solid State Physics	10 membres
C.11	Particles and Fields	10 membres
C.12	Nuclear Physics	10 membres
C.13	Atomic Masses and Fundamental Constants	8 membres
C.14	Education	9 membres
C.15	Atomic and Molecular Physics and Spectroscopy	10 membres
C.16	Plasma Physics	10 membres